

Nader Ale Ebrahim's Academic Impact and Collaboration

Nader Ale Ebrahim^{1,2}

¹ Research and Technology Department, Alzahra University, Vanak, Tehran, Iran

² Research Visibility and Impact Center (RVnIC), Tehran, Iran.

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7091-4439> email: alebrahim@gmail.com

Abstract

By the end of 2023, [Nader Ale Ebrahim](#) achieved a significant milestone in his academic career, marked by an impressive growth in citations and scholarly impact. His work garnered 2,009 citations from 1,884 documents, reflecting a 31.6% increase in citations and a 31.7% increase in citing documents compared to the previous year (The list extracted from [SCOPUS](#) on January 11th, 2024). The number of his publications rose to 55, a 14.6% increase. Notably, his h-index reached 18, indicating a consistent quality and influence in his research. A remarkable 74.4% of his collaborations were international, highlighting his global research connections. Further, 51.3% of his documents ranked in the top citation percentiles, with 58.6% published in the top 25% journals, underscoring the relevance and esteem of his work in the academic community. His Field-Weighted Citation Impact stood at 2.19, demonstrating a significant above-average influence in his field. These achievements emphasize the growing visibility and impact of his research contributions.

Keywords: Research Tools, Research Impact, Research Visibility, Bibliometrics, University Rankings, Technology Management, Virtual R&D teams.

Introduction:

This paper serves as an expression of gratitude and admiration for the scholarly community that has engaged with and cited my research work over the years. Reflecting on this journey, I particularly focus on the period following the publication of my 2023 paper, "[A Milestone in Nader Ale Ebrahim's Academic Career](#)." This work not only marked a significant milestone in my

academic trajectory but also illustrated the growing interest and impact of my contributions in the realm of research visibility and impact. The increasing citations and collaborative endeavors highlight a vibrant academic dialogue and underscore the collective pursuit of knowledge advancement. Herein, I aim to acknowledge and appreciate every reader and scholar who has interacted with my work, contributing to the rich tapestry of academic discourse and collaboration that defines my career.

About Nader Ale Ebrahim

[Nader Ale Ebrahim](#) currently works as a freelance consultant specializing in "Research Visibility and Impact." He also serves as an adjunct lecturer at Alzahra University. His current research interests are university rankings, open access, research visibility, research tools, and bibliometrics. Dr. Nader offers valuable assistance and guidance to researchers, helping them effectively disseminate and promote their research work to maximize its visibility and impact. He firmly believes that the research cycle extends beyond publications alone. Thus, he encourages proactive efforts in the dissemination of research outputs. Nader is widely recognized as the creator of the "[Research Tools](#)" Box, and his teaching materials, available at "https://figshare.com/authors/Nader_Ale_Ebrahim/100797", have garnered over 580,000 views. Due to his expertise, he has been invited by numerous universities and research centers to conduct webinars and workshops, further empowering researchers in their scholarly endeavors.

References (articles cited my papers)

1. Abad-Segura, E., & González-Zamar, M. D. (2019). Effects of financial education and financial literacy on creative entrepreneurship: A worldwide research [Article]. *Education Sciences*, 9(3), Article 238. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci9030238>
2. Abad-Segura, E., & González-Zamar, M. D. (2021). Sustainable economic development in higher education institutions: A global analysis within the SDGs framework [Article]. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 294, Article 126133. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.126133>
3. Abbate, S., Centobelli, P., & Cerchione, R. (2023). The digital and sustainable transition of the agri-food sector [Article]. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 187, Article 122222. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2022.122222>
4. Abdelkader, E. M., Moselhi, O., Marzouk, M., & Zayed, T. (2021). Integrative Evolutionary-Based Method for Modeling and Optimizing Budget Assignment of Bridge Maintenance Priorities [Article].

Journal of Construction Engineering and Management, 147(9), Article 04021100.
[https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)CO.1943-7862.0002113](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)CO.1943-7862.0002113)

5. Abdelmageed, S., & Zayed, T. (2020). A study of literature in modular integrated construction - Critical review and future directions [Review]. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 277, Article 124044. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.124044>
6. Abdulaali, H. S., Usman, I. M. S., Korandeh, M. E., Alqawzai, S., & Alkhafaji, S. (2023). Applicability of green building rating tools in minimizing construction waste within the Iraqi building projects.
7. Abdulla, H., Zamorano, M., Rodríguez, M. L., El Shahawy, A., Hosny, S., Martín-Pascual, J., & El-Shatoury, S. (2023). An overview of agro-food industry wastewater treatment: a bibliometric analysis and literature review [Review]. *Applied Water Science*, 13(2), Article 47. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13201-022-01857-3>
8. Abeydeera, L. H. U. W., Mesthrige, J. W., & Samarasinghalage, T. I. (2019). Global research on carbon emissions: A scientometric review [Review]. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 11(14), Article 3972. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11143972>
9. Abi Saad, E., & Agogué, M. (2023). Creativity in virtual teams: Systematic review, synthesis and research agenda [Article]. *Creativity and Innovation Management*, 32(1), 117-140. <https://doi.org/10.1111/caim.12540>
10. Abideen, D., Yunusa-Kaltungo, A., Manu, P., & Cheung, C. (2021). Digitalization of construction life cycle: A systematic review of building and reliability information modelling (BRIM).
11. Aboelmaged, M., & Mouakket, S. (2020). Influencing models and determinants in big data analytics research: A bibliometric analysis [Article]. *Information Processing and Management*, 57(4), Article 102234. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ipm.2020.102234>
12. Absatar, A., & Alishayeva, B. (2023). “Bird in a Cage”: Traditions and Customs That Restrict Women’s Rights in the Kazakh Context as a Research Topic [Article]. *Ethics in Progress*, 14(2), 38-49. <https://doi.org/10.14746/eip.2023.2.3>
13. Aburishah, K., Owais, W., Al-Dahiyat, A., Bawaneh, A., & AlQudah, L. (2022). Mapping and visualisation of audit quality research trends [Article]. *International Journal of Economics and Business Research*, 25(1), 29-49. <https://doi.org/10.1504/ijebr.2023.127351>
14. AbuShihab, K., Obaideen, K., Alameddine, M., Alkurd, R. A. F., Khraiweh, H. M., Mohammad, Y., Abdelrahim, D. N., Madkour, M. I., & Faris, M. A. I. E. (2023). Reflection on Ramadan Fasting Research Related to Sustainable Development Goal 3 (Good Health and Well-Being): A Bibliometric Analysis [Article]. *Journal of Religion and Health*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10943-023-01955-9>
15. Acampora, A., Lucchetti, M. C., Merli, R., & Ali, F. (2022). The theoretical development and research methodology in green hotels research: A systematic literature review [Article]. *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Management*, 51, 512-528. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhtm.2022.05.007>
16. Adah, C. A., Aghimien, D. O., & Oshodi, O. (2023). Work–life balance in the construction industry: a bibliometric and narrative review [Article]. *Engineering, Construction and Architectural Management*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ECAM-02-2023-0150>
17. Adaku, E., Ankrah, N. A., & Ndekugri, I. E. (2021). Design for occupational safety and health: A theoretical framework for organisational capability [Article]. *Safety Science*, 133, Article 105005. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssci.2020.105005>
18. Adaku, E., Ankrah, N. A., & Ndekugri, I. E. (2022). Prevention through design: conceptual models for the assessment of a principal designer’s skills, knowledge and experience [Article]. *Journal of Engineering, Design and Technology*, 20(3), 595-623. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JEDT-07-2020-0278>

19. Adam, A., Ras, R., Bhattu, A. S., Raman, A., & Perera, M. (2017). "Researching the Research" in Prostate Cancer: A Comparative Bibliometric Analysis of the Top 100 Cited Articles in the Field of Prostate Cancer [Article]. *Current Urology*, 11(1), 26-35. <https://doi.org/10.1159/000447191>
20. Adán, L., García-Angulo, A., Gómez-Ruano, M. A., Sainz de Baranda, P., & Ortega-Toro, E. (2020). Bibliometric analysis of scientific production in female football [Article]. *Journal of Sport and Health Research*, 12(3), 302-317. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85104416307&partnerID=40&md5=fef77ad748fd551e9e31e4df4e42b247>
21. Adebayo, S. O., & Saini, M. (2023). A scientometric study for scientific research publication on gender inequality [Article]. *Quality and Quantity*, 57(6), 5107-5135. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11135-022-01604-5>
22. Adegioriola, M. I., Lai, J. H. K., Chan, E. H., & Amos, D. (2021). Heritage building maintenance management (HBMM): A bibliometric-qualitative analysis of literature [Review]. *Journal of Building Engineering*, 42, Article 102416. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.job.2021.102416>
23. Adegioriola, M. I., Yung, E. H. K., Lai, J. H. K., Chan, E. H. W., & Yevu, S. K. (2023). Understanding the influencing factors of heritage building maintenance management: findings from developed and developing regions [Article]. *Building Research and Information*, 51(5), 605-624. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09613218.2023.2167698>
24. Adnan, A., & Romli, R. (2022). A Comparative Evaluation on Methods of Teaching Computer Programming. In *Lecture Notes on Data Engineering and Communications Technologies* (Vol. 127, pp. 571-582): Springer Science and Business Media Deutschland GmbH.
25. Adriaanse, L., & Rensleigh, C. (2018). Research e-visibility: Using academia.Edu for knowledge sharing.
26. Adriaanse, L. S., & Rensleigh, C. (2020). Enhancing the e-visibility status of environmental science researchers at the university of South Africa.
27. Adriano, B., Cotto, N. M., Chauhan, N., Jaggi, M., Chauhan, S. C., & Yallapu, M. M. (2021). Milk exosomes: Nature's abundant nanoplatfrom for theranostic applications [Article]. *Bioactive Materials*, 6(8), 2479-2490. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bioactmat.2021.01.009>
28. Afful-Dadzie, E., & Afful-Dadzie, A. (2017). Liberation of public data: Exploring central themes in open government data and freedom of information research [Article]. *International Journal of Information Management*, 37(6), 664-672. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijinfomgt.2017.05.009>
29. Agarwal, N. K., & Islam, A. (2018). Ascertainning the place of library & information science in knowledge management research [Article]. *Proceedings of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, 55(1), 1-9. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pra2.2018.14505501002>
30. Agarwal, N. K., & Islam, M. A. (2020). Looking for knowledge management in library and information science research [Article]. *Global Knowledge, Memory and Communication*, 69(8-9), 697-716. <https://doi.org/10.1108/GKMC-01-2020-0001>
31. Agarwal, S., Kant, R., & Shankar, R. (2019). Humanitarian supply chain management frameworks: A critical literature review and framework for future development [Review]. *Benchmarking*, 26(6), 1749-1780. <https://doi.org/10.1108/BIJ-08-2018-0245>
32. Ageel, M. (2022). Pandemic Critical Care Research during the COVID-19 (2020-2022): A Bibliometric Analysis Using VOSviewer [Review]. *BioMed Research International*, 2022, Article 8564649. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2022/8564649>
33. Aggarwal, V., & Kapoor, M. (2018). Innovation growth from knowledge transfer in international strategic alliances [Review]. *Journal of Strategy and Management*, 11(4), 483-496. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JSMA-06-2018-0054>
34. Aghimien, D., Aigbavboa, C. O., Oke, A. E., Edwards, D., Thwala, W. D., & Roberts, C. J. (2022). Dynamic capabilities for digitalisation in the AECO sector – a scientometric review [Review].

- Engineering, Construction and Architectural Management, 29(4), 1585-1608.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/ECAM-12-2020-1012>
35. Aghimien, D. O., Aigbavboa, C. O., Oke, A. E., & Thwala, W. D. (2020). Mapping out research focus for robotics and automation research in construction-related studies: A bibliometric approach [Review]. *Journal of Engineering, Design and Technology*, 18(5), 1063-1079.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/JEDT-09-2019-0237>
 36. Aghimien, E. I., Aghimien, L. M., Petinrin, O. O., & Aghimien, D. O. (2020). High-performance computing for computational modelling in built environment-related studies – a scientometric review [Review]. *Journal of Engineering, Design and Technology*, 19(5), 1138-1157.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/JEDT-07-2020-0294>
 37. Aghimien, E. I., Li, D. H. W., & Tsang, E. K. W. (2022). Bioclimatic architecture and its energy-saving potentials: a review and future directions [Review]. *Engineering, Construction and Architectural Management*, 29(2), 961-988. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ECAM-11-2020-0928>
 38. Aguado-López, E., Becerril-García, A., Arriola, M. L., & Martínez-Domínguez, N. D. (2014). Ibero-America in mainstream science (Thomson Reuters/Scopus): A fragmented region [Article]. *Interiencia*, 39(8), 570-579. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84907208431&partnerID=40&md5=0637f7fe8db93dd85c2ddb30cc37d501>
 39. Ahmad, I., Ahmed, G., Shah, S. A. A., & Ahmed, E. (2020). A decade of big data literature: analysis of trends in light of bibliometrics [Article]. *Journal of Supercomputing*, 76(5), 3555-3571.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11227-018-2714-x>
 40. Ahmad, K. S., Naqvi, S. N., & Jaffri, S. B. (2021). Systematic review elucidating the generations and classifications of solar cells contributing towards environmental sustainability integration [Review]. *Reviews in Inorganic Chemistry*, 41(1), 21-39. <https://doi.org/10.1515/revic-2020-0009>
 41. Ahmad, N., Haleem, A., & Syed, A. A. (2014). Study of reasons for enterprise systems adoption among Indian organizations [Article]. *Journal of Enterprise Information Management*, 27(6), 696-718. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JEIM-02-2013-0006>
 42. Ahmad, N., & Mehmood, R. (2015). Enterprise systems: Are we ready for future sustainable cities [Article]. *Supply Chain Management*, 20(3), 264-283. <https://doi.org/10.1108/SCM-11-2014-0370>
 43. Ahmad, W., Ahmad, A., Ostrowski, K. A., Aslam, F., & Joyklad, P. (2021). A scientometric review of waste material utilization in concrete for sustainable construction [Article]. *Case Studies in Construction Materials*, 15, Article e00683. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cscm.2021.e00683>
 44. Ahmad, W., Ahmad, A., Ostrowski, K. A., Aslam, F., Joyklad, P., & Zajdel, P. (2021). Sustainable approach of using sugarcane bagasse ash in cement-based composites: A systematic review [Article]. *Case Studies in Construction Materials*, 15, Article e00698.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cscm.2021.e00698>
 45. Ahmad, W., Khan, M., & Smarzewski, P. (2021). Effect of short fiber reinforcements on fracture performance of cement-based materials: A systematic review approach [Article]. *Materials*, 14(7), Article 1745. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma14071745>
 46. Ahmed, S., & Taha, Z. (2011). Virtual R&D teams: A potential growth of education-industry collaboration [Article]. *Academic Leadership*, 9(4).
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84857544625&partnerID=40&md5=67cac74e85b0fd2ef11c6cda805c92fb>
 47. Ahmi, A., Elbardan, H., & Raja Mohd Ali, R. H. (2019). Bibliometric analysis of published literature on industry 4.0.
 48. Ahmi, A., & Mohd Nasir, M. H. (2019). Examining the trend of the research on extensible business reporting language (xbrl): A bibliometric review [Article]. *International Journal of Innovation*,

Creativity and Change, 5(2), Article 1145. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85081654893&partnerID=40&md5=ca1cc10a512ddcdc9a6a9c5114dd5057>

49. Ahn, B. S. (2023). Solving multi-attribute decision making problems with incomplete weights: A dual approach [Article]. *Journal of the Operational Research Society*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01605682.2023.2217212>
50. Akakandelwa, A. (2016). The diffusion of the concept of knowledge management among african scholars: A bibliometrics perspective. In *Managing Knowledge Resources and Records in Modern Organizations* (pp. 124-148). IGI Global. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-5225-1965-2.ch008>
51. Akakandelwa, A. (2020). The diffusion of the concept of knowledge management among African scholars: A bibliometrics perspective. In *African Studies: Breakthroughs in Research and Practice* (pp. 399-423). IGI Global. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-7998-3019-1.ch022>
52. Akbar, I., Arisaktiwardhana, D., & Naomi, P. (2020). How does indonesian scientific production on renewable energy successfully support the policy design? A journey towards sustainable energy transition [Article]. *Problemy Ekorozwoju*, 15(2), 41-52. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85090750833&partnerID=40&md5=f3b590ca1f4a09788135c32aa44b7b90>
53. Akbar, P. N. G., & Edelenbos, J. (2021). Positioning place-making as a social process: A systematic literature review [Article]. *Cogent Social Sciences*, 7(1), Article 1905920. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311886.2021.1905920>
54. Akbari, A., & Shahrokhi, M. (2023). Open-access vs. paywalled journals in translation and interpreting studies: is it the time to abolish stumbling blocks? [Article]. *Onomazein*(60), 54-69. <https://doi.org/10.7764/onomazein.60.04>
55. Akhmedova, M. G., Galchenko, N. A., Lutskovskaia, L. Y., Minkin, M. R., Ibragimov, G. I., Kryukova, N. I., & Sizova, Z. M. (2023). Uncovering patterns and trends in online teaching and learning for STEM education [Review]. *Contemporary Educational Technology*, 15(3), Article ep444. <https://doi.org/10.30935/cedtech/13363>
56. Akidi, J. O., Osedo, O. A., & Chukwueke, C. (2021). Maintaining Publishing Standards and Global Visibility: Essential Tips for Nigerian Library and Information Professionals [Article]. *Library Philosophy and Practice*, 2021, 1-16. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85108786614&partnerID=40&md5=82b3d9406d8e9ce444582a91df34323f>
57. Akim, É. K., & Mergulhão, R. C. (2015). Overview of the intellectual production of performance measurement in public management [Article]. *Revista de Administracao Publica*, 49(2), 337-366. <https://doi.org/10.1590/0034-7612126126>
58. Akinlolu, M., Haupt, T. C., Edwards, D. J., & Simpeh, F. (2022). A bibliometric review of the status and emerging research trends in construction safety management technologies [Article]. *International Journal of Construction Management*, 22(14), 2699-2711. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15623599.2020.1819584>
59. Akomea-Frimpong, I., Jin, X., Osei-Kyei, R., & Kukah, A. S. (2023). Public–private partnerships for sustainable infrastructure development in Ghana: a systematic review and recommendations [Article]. *Smart and Sustainable Built Environment*, 12(2), 237-257. <https://doi.org/10.1108/SASBE-07-2021-0111>
60. Akomea-Frimpong, I., Jin, X., Osei-Kyei, R., & Pariafsai, F. (2023). Critical managerial measures on financial risks of sustainable public–private partnership projects: a PRISMA review [Review]. *Journal of Financial Management of Property and Construction*, 28(3), 398-422. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JFMPC-12-2021-0070>

61. Akyol, A., & Kocyigit, B. F. (2021). Publication activity in the field of Sjögren's syndrome: a ten-year Web of Science based analysis [Article]. *Rheumatology International*, 41(4), 763-769. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00296-020-04714-1>
62. Al Risi, N. M. (2021). The characteristics of intellectual output in the field of big data in Oman from 2010 to 2020.
63. Al Rousan, R., Khasawneh, N., & Sujood. (2023). Mapping 30 years of tourism and hospitality research in the Arab world: a review based on bibliometric analysis [Review]. *Tourism Review*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/TR-04-2023-0201>
64. Alajmi, B., & Alhaji, T. (2018). Mapping the field of knowledge management: Bibliometric and content analysis of journal of information & knowledge management for the period from 2002-2016 [Article]. *Journal of Information and Knowledge Management*, 17(3), Article 1850027. <https://doi.org/10.1142/S0219649218500272>
65. Alarabi, K., Alsalihi, N. R., Almarashdi, H. S., Zakarneh, B., & Annamalai, N. (2023). The Role of Computer Simulations (CSs) and Artificial Intelligence on Student Learning: Moderating the Impact of the Learning Environment [Article]. *Przestrzen Społeczna*, 23(3), 103-122. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85178266885&partnerID=40&md5=69c2c448711b7a1184e0d066d3d3f9f0>
66. Al-Ashmori, A., Basri, S. B., Dominic, P. D. D., Capretz, L. F., Muneer, A., Balogun, A. O., Gilal, A. R., & Ali, R. F. (2022). Classifications of Sustainable Factors in Blockchain Adoption: A Literature Review and Bibliometric Analysis [Review]. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 14(9), Article 5176. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14095176>
67. Alcayde, A., Montoya, F. G., Baños, R., Perea-Moreno, A. J., & Manzano-Agugliaro, F. (2018). Analysis of research topics and scientific collaborations in renewable energy using community detection [Article]. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 10(12), Article 4510. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su10124510>
68. Alchokr, R., Joshi, S. V., Saake, G., Leich, T., & Krüger, J. (2023). Investigating the Relation Between Authors' Academic Age and Their Citations. In O. Alonso, H. Cousijn, G. Silvello, S. Marchesin, M. Marrero, & C. Teixeira Lopes (Eds.), (Vol. 14241 LNCS, pp. 106-113): Springer Science and Business Media Deutschland GmbH.
69. Aldag, R. R. J., & Kuzuhara, L. W. (2015). *Creating high performance teams: Applied strategies and tools for managers and team members* [Book]. Taylor and Francis. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203109380>
70. Aldea, C., Draghici, A., & Dragoi, G. (2012). New perspectives of virtual teams' collaboration. In (Vol. 248 CCIS, pp. 176-185).
71. Aldea, C. C., & Draghici, A. (2012). Comparison study of some collaborative tools use in virtual teams.
72. Aldeen, K. N. (2021). 40-YEAR BIBLIOMETRIC ANALYSIS OF WAQF: ITS CURRENT STATUS AND DEVELOPMENT, AND PATHS FOR FUTURE RESEARCH [Article]. *Journal of Islamic Monetary Economics and Finance*, 7(1), 181-200. <https://doi.org/10.21098/jimf.v7i1.1308>
73. Ale Ebrahim, S., Ashtari, A., Zamani Pedram, M., & Ale Ebrahim, N. (2019). Publication Trends in Drug Delivery and Magnetic Nanoparticles [Review]. *Nanoscale Research Letters*, 14, Article 164. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s11671-019-2994-y>
74. Alexis Parra-Orobio, B., Soto-Paz, J., Ricardo Oviedo-Ocaña, E., Vali, S. A., & Sánchez, A. (2023). Advances, trends and challenges in the use of biochar as an improvement strategy in the anaerobic digestion of organic waste: a systematic analysis [Review]. *Bioengineered*, 14(1), Article 2252191. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21655979.2023.2252191>

75. Alfandari, R., & Taylor, B. J. (2022). Systematic Bibliographic Database Searching for Literature Reviews: Case Study on Child Protection Decision-Making [Review]. *British Journal of Social Work*, 52(1), 518-535. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bjsw/bcab013>
76. Alghazi, S. S., Wong, S. Y., Kamsin, A., Yadegaridehkordi, E., & Shuib, L. (2020). Towards sustainable mobile learning: A brief review of the factors influencing acceptance of the use of mobile phones as learning tools [Article]. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 12(24), 1-19, Article 10527. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su122410527>
77. Al-Haideri, A., Noor, A. S. M., & Al-Hadi, I. A. A. Q. (2022). Adoption of Cloud-Based E-Government Services: A Bibliometric Analysis and Research Agenda. In M. Al-Emran, M. A. Al-Sharafi, M. N. Al-Kabi, & K. Shaalan (Eds.), (Vol. 322, pp. 747-755): Springer Science and Business Media Deutschland GmbH.
78. Alhammadi, S. A. (2022). Identification and Categorisation of Safety Improvement Practices in the Construction Industry: Review Study [Article]. *International Review of Civil Engineering*, 13(1), 53-66. <https://doi.org/10.15866/irece.v13i1.21199>
79. Alhawary, F. A. (2012). Factors affecting virtual team works collaboration: A case study in the Jordanian royal medical services [Article]. *Journal of Information and Knowledge Management*, 11(3), Article 1250020. <https://doi.org/10.1142/S0219649212500207>
80. Alhjouj, A., Bonoli, A., & Zamorano, M. (2022). A Critical Perspective and Inclusive Analysis of Sustainable Road Infrastructure Literature [Review]. *Applied Sciences (Switzerland)*, 12(24), Article 12996. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app122412996>
81. Al-Hoorie, A. H., & Vitta, J. P. (2019). The seven sins of L2 research: A review of 30 journals' statistical quality and their CiteScore, SJR, SNIP, JCR Impact Factors [Article]. *Language Teaching Research*, 23(6), 727-744. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1362168818767191>
82. Alhousary, T., Underwood, J., & Xanthidis, D. (2017). ICT developments and utilization in the Omani banking sector [Article]. *WSEAS Transactions on Business and Economics*, 14, 409-416. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85040764261&partnerID=40&md5=50a4c2b53c96266a40e9a713c2256721>
83. Ali, A. S., Zaaba, Z. F., & Singh, M. M. (2023). Privacy during epidemic of COVID-19: a bibliometric analysis [Article]. *Bulletin of Electrical Engineering and Informatics*, 12(1), 587-596. <https://doi.org/10.11591/eei.v12i1.4460>
84. Ali, K. N., Alhajlah, H. H., & Kassem, M. A. (2022). Collaboration and Risk in Building Information Modelling (BIM): A Systematic Literature Review [Article]. *Buildings*, 12(5), Article 571. <https://doi.org/10.3390/buildings12050571>
85. Ali, M. Y., & Richardson, J. (2019). Google Scholar Citation metrics of Pakistani LIS scholars: an overview [Article]. *Global Knowledge, Memory and Communication*, 68(4-5), 392-412. <https://doi.org/10.1108/GKMC-03-2018-0025>
86. Alice Chen, M. R., Hwang, G. J., Majumdar, R., Toyokawa, Y., & Ogata, H. (2023). Research trends in the use of E-books in English as a foreign language (EFL) education from 2011 to 2020: a bibliometric and content analysis [Review]. *Interactive Learning Environments*, 31(4), 2411-2427. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10494820.2021.1888755>
87. Alimohammadi, V., Seyyed Ebrahimi, S. A., Kashanian, F., Lalegani, Z., Habibi-Rezaei, M., & Hamawandi, B. (2022). Hydrophobic Magnetite Nanoparticles for Bioseparation: Green Synthesis, Functionalization, and Characterization [Article]. *Magnetochemistry*, 8(11), Article 143. <https://doi.org/10.3390/magnetochemistry8110143>
88. Al-Jenaibi, B. (2011). Public relation practitioners, independency, and teamwork in the UAE organizations. In *Handbook of Research on Business Social Networking: Organizational, Managerial,*

and Technological Dimensions (pp. 964-980). IGI Global. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-61350-168-9.ch050>

89. Alkadhim, H. A., Amin, M. N., Ahmad, W., Khan, K., Al-Hashem, M. N., Houda, S., Azab, M., & Baki, Z. A. (2022). Knowledge Mapping of the Literature on Fiber-Reinforced Geopolymers: A Scientometric Review [Review]. *Polymers*, 14(22), Article 5008. <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym14225008>
90. Alkaissy, M., Arashpour, M., Ashuri, B., Bai, Y., & Hosseini, R. (2020). Safety management in construction: 20 years of risk modeling [Article]. *Safety Science*, 129, Article 104805. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssci.2020.104805>
91. All, A., Castellar, E. N. P., & Van Looy, J. (2021). Digital Game-Based Learning effectiveness assessment: Reflections on study design [Article]. *Computers and Education*, 167, Article 104160. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2021.104160>
92. Al-Lawati, A., & Barbosa, L. (2019). A Framework for Intelligent Policy Decision Making Based on a Government Data Hub. In D. A. Alexandrov, Y. Kabanov, O. Koltsova, I. Musabirov, A. V. Boukhanovsky, & A. V. Chugunov (Eds.), (Vol. 1038 CCIS, pp. 92-106): Springer.
93. Al-Lawati, E. H., Abdul Kohar, U. H., & Shahrin Suleiman, E. (2022). Entrepreneurial culture in educational institutions: A scoping review [Review]. *Cogent Business and Management*, 9(1), Article 1997237. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311975.2021.1997237>
94. Al-Lawati, E. H., Kohar, U. H. A., & Suleiman, E. S. B. (2021). Entrepreneurship studies in the sultanate of Oman: A scoping review of 20 years publications [Review]. *Estudios de Economia Aplicada*, 39(10). <https://doi.org/10.25115/eea.v39i10.5974>
95. Allen, R. M. (2021). When peril responds to plague: predatory journal engagement with COVID-19 [Article]. *Library Hi Tech*, 39(3), 746-760. <https://doi.org/10.1108/LHT-01-2021-0011>
96. Allen, V. (2013). All for One [Editorial]. *Journal of Obstetrics and Gynaecology Canada*, 35(5), 403-404. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1701-2163\(15\)30929-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1701-2163(15)30929-4)
97. Allen, V. (2013). Tous pour un [Article]. *Journal of Obstetrics and Gynaecology Canada*, 35(5), 405-407. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1701-2163\(15\)30930-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1701-2163(15)30930-0)
98. Allison, B. B., Shuffler, M. L., & Wallace, A. M. (2015). The successful facilitation of virtual team meetings. In *The Cambridge Handbook of Meeting Science* (pp. 680-705). Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781107589735.029>
99. Almalki, A. (2022). Common Risk Factors in Construction Sector – A Review [Article]. *International Review of Civil Engineering*, 13(6), 455-465. <https://doi.org/10.15866/irece.v13i6.21744>
100. Almulhim, A. F. (2023). Knowledge Management Practices and Firm Performance: The Moderating Role of Resource Commitment [Article]. *WSEAS Transactions on Business and Economics*, 20, 1647-1658, Article 146. <https://doi.org/10.37394/23207.2023.20.146>
101. Alnashwan, Y. A., Khan, M. A., Kashif, H., Mohiuddin, S. S., Siddique, N., Alessa, A. M., Alotaibi, A. A., Al-Jindan, F. A., Moizuddin, K., Waris, A., & Menezes, R. G. (2023). Exploring the current status and trends of research on Langerhans Cell Sarcoma: A bibliometric analysis [Review]. *Electronic Journal of General Medicine*, 20(5), Article em514. <https://doi.org/10.29333/ejgm/13314>
102. Alosaimi, M. A., Umar, I. N., & Rabu, S. N. A. (2023). THE MODERATION EFFECT OF TEACHERS' EXPERIENCE AND BIOGRAPHY ON THEIR INTENTION TO USE THE GAMIFICATION IN ONLINE LEARNING ACTIVITIES [Article]. *Journal of Theoretical and Applied Information Technology*, 101(11), 4459-4471. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85166428068&partnerID=40&md5=9c2ce2676bd4edaf9c73a80bdd35f267>

103. Alsadi, J., Antony, J., Mezher, T., Jayaraman, R., & Maalouf, M. (2023). Lean and Industry 4.0: A bibliometric analysis, opportunities for future research directions [Article]. *Quality Management Journal*, 30(1), 41-63. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10686967.2022.2144785>
104. Al-Saeed, Y., Edwards, D. J., & Scaysbrook, S. (2020). Automating construction manufacturing procedures using BIM digital objects (BDOs): Case study of knowledge transfer partnership project in UK [Article]. *Construction Innovation*, 20(3), 345-377. <https://doi.org/10.1108/CI-12-2019-0141>
105. Alsharif, A. H., Salleh, N. Z. M., & Baharun, R. (2020). Research trends of neuromarketing: A bibliometric analysis [Article]. *Journal of Theoretical and Applied Information Technology*, 98(15), 2948-2962. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85092513784&partnerID=40&md5=4cffc223bf572872be44aa3a4f5673b3>
106. Alstete, J. W., Beutell, N. J., & Meyer, J. P. (2018). *EVALUATING SCHOLARSHIP AND RESEARCH IMPACT: History, Practices, and Policy Development* [Book]. Emerald Group Publishing Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.1108/9781787563872>
107. Al-Suqri, M. N., & Gillani, M. (2022). A Comparative Analysis of Information and Artificial Intelligence Toward National Security [Review]. *IEEE Access*, 10, 64420-64434. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2022.3183642>
108. Altarturi, H. H. M., Saadoon, M., & Anuar, N. B. (2020). Cyber parental control: A bibliometric study [Article]. *Children and Youth Services Review*, 116, Article 105134. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chilyouth.2020.105134>
109. Altuwaim, A., AlTasan, A., & Almohsen, A. (2023). Success Criteria for Applying Construction Technologies in Residential Projects [Article]. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 15(8), Article 6854. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15086854>
110. Alvarez, G. R., Vanz, S. A. S., & Barbosa, M. C. (2017). Scientometric indicators for Brazilian research on High Energy Physics, 1983-2013 [Article]. *Anais da Academia Brasileira de Ciencias*, 89(3), 2525-2543. <https://doi.org/10.1590/0001-3765201720160620>
111. Alvarez, N., Velluti, F., Guidali, F., Serra, G., Gabriela Kramer, M., Ellena, J., Facchin, G., Scarone, L., & Torre, M. H. (2020). New BI and TRI-Thiazole copper (II) complexes in the search of new cytotoxic drugs against breast cancer cells [Article]. *Inorganica Chimica Acta*, 508, Article 119622. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ica.2020.119622>
112. Alvarez-Sández, D., Velázquez-Victorica, K., Mungaray-Moctezuma, A., & López-Guerrero, A. (2023). Administrative Processes Efficiency Measurement in Higher Education Institutions: A Scoping Review [Review]. *Education Sciences*, 13(9), Article 855. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci13090855>
113. Alves, I., Analide, C., & Vaz, F. (2022). The Relationship Between Financial Execution in R&D and Scientific Production. In S. R. Gonzalez, J. M. Machado, A. Gonzalez-Briones, J. Wikarek, R. Loukanova, G. Katranas, & R. Casado-Vara (Eds.), (Vol. 332, pp. 171-181): Springer Science and Business Media Deutschland GmbH.
114. Alves, R. F., Vieira Neto, J., de Mattos Nascimento, D. L., de Andrade, F. E., Tortorella, G. L., & Garza-Reyes, J. A. (2022). Lean accounting: a structured literature review [Article]. *TQM Journal*, 34(6), 1547-1571. <https://doi.org/10.1108/TQM-06-2021-0185>
115. Alyousef, R., Ahmad, W., Ahmad, A., Aslam, F., Joyklad, P., & Alabduljabbar, H. (2021). Potential use of recycled plastic and rubber aggregate in cementitious materials for sustainable construction: A review [Review]. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 329, Article 129736. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.129736>
116. Amin, M. N., Ahmad, W., Khan, K., & Ahmad, A. (2022). Steel Fiber-Reinforced Concrete: A Systematic Review of the Research Progress and Knowledge Mapping [Review]. *Materials*, 15(17), Article 6155. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma15176155>

117. Amin, M. N., Ahmad, W., Khan, K., & Sayed, M. M. (2022). Mapping Research Knowledge on Rice Husk Ash Application in Concrete: A Scientometric Review [Review]. *Materials*, 15(10), Article 3431. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma15103431>
118. Amin, M. N., Khan, K., Nazar, S., & Deifalla, A. F. (2023). Application of waste recycle tire steel fibers as a construction material in concrete [Review]. *Reviews on Advanced Materials Science*, 62(1), Article 20220319. <https://doi.org/10.1515/rams-2022-0319>
119. Ampah, J. D., Yusuf, A. A., Afrane, S., Jin, C., & Liu, H. (2021). Reviewing two decades of cleaner alternative marine fuels: Towards IMO's decarbonization of the maritime transport sector [Article]. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 320, Article 128871. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.128871>
120. Anagnos, T., Lyman-Holt, A. L., & Brophy, S. P. (2015). Virtual peer teams: Connecting students with the online work environment.
121. Anand, A., & Dumazert, J. P. (2022). Knowledge sharing in organization: Reviewing the foundations of the field and current themes using bibliometrics [Article]. *Knowledge and Process Management*, 29(3), 270-283. <https://doi.org/10.1002/kpm.1720>
122. Anderson, J. R., Jacobsen, S., Walters, M., Bundgaard, L., Diendorfer, A., Hackl, M., Clarke, E. J., James, V., & Peffers, M. J. (2022). Small non-coding RNA landscape of extracellular vesicles from a post-traumatic model of equine osteoarthritis [Article]. *Frontiers in Veterinary Science*, 9, Article 901269. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fvets.2022.901269>
123. Andreucci-Annunziata, P., Mellado, A., & Vega-Muñoz, A. (2022). Telesupervision in Psychotherapy: A Bibliometric and Systematic Review [Review]. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(23), Article 16366. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph192316366>
124. Andreucci-Annunziata, P., Riedemann, A., Cortés, S., Mellado, A., del Río, M. T., & Vega-Muñoz, A. (2023). Conceptualizations and instructional strategies on critical thinking in higher education: A systematic review of systematic reviews [Review]. *Frontiers in Education*, 8, Article 1141686. <https://doi.org/10.3389/educ.2023.1141686>
125. Andriollo, E., Caimo, A., Secco, L., & Pisani, E. (2021). Collaborations in environmental initiatives for an effective “adaptive governance” of social–ecological systems: What existing literature suggests [Review]. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 13(15), Article 8276. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13158276>
126. Annarelli, A., Battistella, C., & Nonino, F. (2017). Web-application development projects by online communities Which practices favour innovation? [Article]. *Industrial Management and Data Systems*, 117(1), 166-197. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IMDS-10-2015-0440>
127. Anoye, A. B., & Kouamé, J. S. (2018). Leadership challenges in virtual team environment [Article]. *International Journal of Scientific and Technology Research*, 7(7), 160-167. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85059866275&partnerID=40&md5=9aa772bf1b45ababa589b34c04547019>
128. Antwi, K. (2023). Review on research trends in biomass resources and biofuel potential: A bibliometric analysis [Article]. *Nativa*, 11(2), 212-219. <https://doi.org/10.31413/NAT.V11I2.15821>
129. Ardanuy, J. (2017). Using the web of science for the study of lesser disciplines in humanities: The case of folklore [Article]. *Investigacion Bibliotecologica*, 31(73), 111-129. <https://doi.org/10.22201/iibi.24488321xe.2017.73.57849>
130. Arifin, Z., Said, M., & Said, L. R. (2023). Improving Task Performance through Virtual Team Communication [Article]. *International Journal of Industrial Engineering and Production Research*, 34(2). <https://doi.org/10.22068/ijiepr.34.2.1>

131. Armoed, Z. (2021). The Covid-19 Pandemic: Online Teaching and Learning at Higher Education Institutes.
132. Arora, S., Warne, D. P., & Dahiya, M. (2023). Theory and concept of strategic human resources management. In *Strategic Human Resource Management in the Hospitality Industry: A Digitalized Economic Paradigm* (pp. 208-231). IGI Global. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-6684-7494-5.ch011>
133. Arsova, S., Genovese, A., & Ketikidis, P. H. (2022). Implementing circular economy in a regional context: A systematic literature review and a research agenda [Article]. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 368, Article 133117. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.133117>
134. Asadi, N., Guaragni, F., Johannknecht, F., Saidani, M., Scholle, P., Borg, J., & Panasiuk, D. (2017). Success factors of an ipd based approach in a remote multidisciplinary team environment - Reflections on a case study.
135. Asghar, I., Egaji, O. A., & Griffiths, M. (2021). An overview of the digital solutions for helping people with aphasia through bibliometric analysis [Review]. *eNeurologicalSci*, 22, Article 100311. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ensci.2021.100311>
136. Assaf, M., Hussein, M., Abdelkhalek, S., & Zayed, T. (2023). A Multi-Criteria Decision-Making Model for Selecting the Best Project Delivery Systems for Offsite Construction Projects [Article]. *Buildings*, 13(2), Article 571. <https://doi.org/10.3390/buildings13020571>
137. Assaf, M., Hussein, M., Alsulami, B. T., & Zayed, T. (2022). A Mixed Review of Cash Flow Modeling: Potential of Blockchain for Modular Construction [Review]. *Buildings*, 12(12), Article 2054. <https://doi.org/10.3390/buildings12122054>
138. Assapun, S., & Thummaphan, P. (2023). Assessing the Effectiveness of Board Game-based Learning for Enhancing Problem-Solving Competency of Lower Secondary Students [Article]. *International Journal of Instruction*, 16(2), 511-532. <https://doi.org/10.29333/iji.2023.16228a>
139. Astatke, M., Weng, C., & Chen, S. (2023). A literature review of the effects of social networking sites on secondary school students' academic achievement [Review]. *Interactive Learning Environments*, 31(4), 2153-2169. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10494820.2021.1875002>
140. Atieno, A. V., Onyancha, O. B., & Kwanya, T. (2022). Trends, patterns and determinants of research productivity at the Technical University of Kenya [Article]. *Information Development*, 38(1), 97-113. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0266666920983400>
141. Aulawi, H., Suseno, N. S., & Abdullah, K. H. (2023). TRENDS IN E-COMMERCE AND SOCIAL MEDIA RESEARCH IN ASIA: FIVE YEARS OF SCIENTOMETRIC AND CONTENT ANALYSIS [Article]. *Journal of Applied Engineering and Technological Science*, 5(1), 58-72. <https://doi.org/10.37385/jaets.v5i1.2420>
142. Avaristo, J. A. D. C., & Ubeda, C. L. (2022). Analysis of the development of competences in a Brazilian master of public administration [Article]. *Teaching Public Administration*, 40(1), 25-41. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0144739421993889>
143. Aydin, S., Kosarenko, N. N., Khlusyanov, O. V., Malakhovskaya, V. V., & Kameneva, G. N. (2022). University students' memories of their secondary science education experiences [Article]. *Frontiers in Education*, 7, Article 1016919. <https://doi.org/10.3389/feduc.2022.1016919>
144. Ayele, W. Y., & Juell-Skielse, G. (2020). A Process Model for Generating and Evaluating Ideas: The Use of Machine Learning and Visual Analytics to Support Idea Mining. In A. Ko, E. Francesconi, G. Kotsis, I. Khalil, & A. M. Tjoa (Eds.), (Vol. 12394 LNCS, pp. 189-203): Springer Science and Business Media Deutschland GmbH.
145. Ayodele, F. O., Yao, L., & Haron, H. (2019). Promoting Ethics and Integrity in Management Academic Research: Retraction Initiative [Review]. *Science and Engineering Ethics*, 25(2), 357-382. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11948-017-9941-z>

146. Ayub, M., Othman, M. H. D., Kadir, S. H. S. A., Ali, A., Khan, I. U., Yusop, M. Z. M., Matsuura, T., Ismail, A. F., Rahman, M. A., & Jaafar, J. (2021). Research and development journey and future trends of hollow fiber membranes for purification applications (1970–2020): A bibliometric analysis [Article]. *Membranes*, 11(8), Article 600. <https://doi.org/10.3390/membranes11080600>
147. Azan, W., & Li, Y. (2022). Blockchain-based Traceability: A bibliometric and lexicometric analysis for knowledge graph.
148. Aziz, E., Mustapha, H., & Jamila, E. A. (2020). A bibliometric study of the recent advances in open innovation concept.
149. Aziz, S., Nazir, M. R., Nazir, M. I., & Gazali, S. (2023). Crowdfunding A bibliometric analysis and future research Agenda [Review]. *Heliyon*, 9(12), Article e22981. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e22981>
150. Azman, M. N. A., Permana, S. A., Jana, P., & Al-Muhsin, M. A. (2022). The Online Publishing Strategies in Improving the Higher Education Institution Ranking: A Case Study of PGRI University of Yogyakarta [Article]. *Pegem Egitim ve Ogretim Dergisi*, 12(1), 193-198. <https://doi.org/10.47750/pegegog.12.01.19>
151. Azmi, N. N., & Hussain, A. (2021). A Bibliometric Analysis of Dropbox on Scopus Publication [Article]. *Webology*, 18(SpecialIssue), 54-78. <https://doi.org/10.14704/WEB/V18SI02/WEB18012>
152. Baarimah, A. O., Alaloul, W. S., Liew, M. S., Al-Aidrous, A. H. M. H., Alawag, A. M., & Musarat, M. A. (2021). Integration of Building Information Modeling (BIM) and Value Engineering in Construction Projects: A Bibliometric Analysis.
153. Baarimah, A. O., Alaloul, W. S., Liew, M. S., Alawag, A. M., Musarat, M. A., & Alzubi, K. M. (2021). Current State of Post-Disaster Reconstruction Projects: A Bibliometric Analysis.
154. Baarimah, A. O., Alaloul, W. S., Liew, M. S., Kartika, W., Al-Sharafi, M. A., Musarat, M. A., Alawag, A. M., & Qureshi, A. H. (2022). A bibliometric analysis and review of building information modelling for post-disaster reconstruction [Review]. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 14(1), Article 393. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14010393>
155. Babamiri, M., Heidarimoghadam, R., Ghasemi, F., Tapak, L., & Morteza pour, A. (2021). Ergonomics 4.0: A bibliometric review of Human Factors research in Industrial Revolution 4.0 (IR 4.0) [Article]. *Work*, 70(1), 321-334. <https://doi.org/10.3233/WOR-213576>
156. Bacigalupo, S. A., Dixon, L. K., Gubbins, S., Kucharski, A. J., & Drewe, J. A. (2020). Towards a unified generic framework to define and observe contacts between livestock and wildlife: A systematic review [Review]. *PeerJ*, 8, Article 10221. <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.10221>
157. Badassa, B. B., Sun, B., & Qiao, L. (2020). Sustainable transport infrastructure and economic returns: A bibliometric and visualization analysis [Article]. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 12(5), Article 2033. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12052033>
158. Bador, E. M., Abdel-Magid, I. M., Ahmad, S., & Akhter, M. (2020). Bibliometric Analysis of Wastewater Literature Published in Web of Science 2019 to 2020 [Article]. *Library Philosophy and Practice*, 2020, 1-21. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85098230019&partnerID=40&md5=893c4fa22596f0c5c3146f04dff70c9f>
159. Baek, E., Haines, S., Fares, O. H., Huang, Z., Hong, Y., & Lee, S. H. M. (2022). Defining digital fashion: Reshaping the field via a systematic review [Article]. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 137, Article 107407. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2022.107407>
160. Baggio, R., Micera, R., & Del Chiappa, G. (2020). Smart tourism destinations: a critical reflection [Article]. *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Technology*, 11(3), 407-423. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JHTT-01-2019-0011>

161. Bagni, G., Godinho Filho, M., Thürer, M., & Stevenson, M. (2021). Systematic review and discussion of production control systems that emerged between 1999 and 2018 [Article]. *Production Planning and Control*, 32(7), 511-525. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09537287.2020.1742398>
162. Bahel, V. (2023). Instructional Quality Guideline for VR-based Learning Platform.
163. Bahri, S., Adnyana, I. K., Hasan, M. F., Ray, H. R. D., & Paramitha, S. T. (2022). Science Mapping for Nutrition Education in Sports Recovery Research: A Bibliometric Analysis [Article]. *International Journal of Education in Mathematics, Science and Technology*, 10(4), 795-811. <https://doi.org/10.46328/ijemst.2620>
164. Bahtiar, Ibrahim, & Maimun. (2022). ANALYSIS OF STUDENTS' SCIENTIFIC LITERACY SKILL IN TERMS OF GENDER USING SCIENCE TEACHING MATERIALS DISCOVERY MODEL ASSISTED BY PhET SIMULATION [Article]. *Jurnal Pendidikan IPA Indonesia*, 11(3), 371-386. <https://doi.org/10.15294/jpii.v11i3.37279>
165. Bai, X., Pan, H., Hou, J., Guo, T., Lee, I., & Xia, F. (2020). Quantifying Success in Science: An Overview [Article]. *IEEE Access*, 8, 123200-123214, Article 9134748. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2020.3007709>
166. Bandara, T., & Wijewardene, L. (2023). Global Research Effort on Hilsa shad (*Tenulosa ilisha*)—Insights from Scientometrics [Article]. *Thalassas*, 39(2), 981-996. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41208-023-00552-7>
167. Banker, D. V., Garg, S., & Maggon, M. (2023). Virtual Leadership: Bibliometrics, Framework-Based Systematic Review, and Future Agenda [Review]. *South Asian Journal of Business and Management Cases*, 12(3), 300-332. <https://doi.org/10.1177/22779779231206500>
168. Barani, M., Bilal, M., Rahdar, A., Arshad, R., Kumar, A., Hamishekar, H., & Kyzas, G. Z. (2021). Nanodiagnosis and nanotreatment of colorectal cancer: an overview [Review]. *Journal of Nanoparticle Research*, 23(1), Article 18. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11051-020-05129-6>
169. Barraza, N., Alvarado Barrios, G., Peng, J., Lamata, L., Solano, E., & Albarrán-Arriagada, F. (2022). Analog quantum approximate optimization algorithm [Article]. *Quantum Science and Technology*, 7(4), Article 045035. <https://doi.org/10.1088/2058-9565/ac91f0>
170. Barros, D., & Teixeira, A. A. C. (2021). A PORTRAIT OF DEVELOPMENT ECONOMICS IN THE LAST SIXTY YEARS [Article]. *Journal of Economic Development*, 46(2), 69-118. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85111396670&partnerID=40&md5=d9b3b435c1dfd5955beaea64e9523f29>
171. Barrot, J. S. (2017). Research impact and productivity of Southeast Asian countries in language and linguistics [Article]. *Scientometrics*, 110(1), 1-15. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-016-2163-3>
172. Barth, J., & Muehlfeld, K. (2022). Thinking out of the box—by thinking in other boxes: a systematic review of interventions in early entrepreneurship vs. STEM education research [Article]. *Management Review Quarterly*, 72(2), 347-383. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11301-021-00248-3>
173. Bartolacci, F., Bellucci, M., Corsi, K., & Soverchia, M. (2022). A Systematic Literature Review of Theories Underpinning Sustainability Reporting in Non-financial Disclosure. In *SIDREA Series in Accounting and Business Administration* (Vol. Part F28, pp. 87-113): Springer Nature.
174. Basaran, M. A., Dogan, S., & Kantarci, K. (2020). On modeling of responses generated by travel 2.0 implementation: fuzzy rule-based systems [Article]. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 32(4), 1503-1522. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJCHM-03-2019-0279>
175. Bassiri Abyaneh, A., Allan, A., Pieters, J., Somenahalli, S., & Soltani, A. (2023). Applying the AURIN Walkability Index at the Metropolitan and Local Levels by Sex and Age in Australia. In *Urban Book Series* (Vol. Part F270, pp. 283-303): Springer Science and Business Media Deutschland GmbH.

176. Bastanchury-López, M. T., & De-Pablos-Heredero, C. (2022). A Bibliometric Analysis on Smart Cities Related to Land Use [Review]. *Land*, 11(12), Article 2132. <https://doi.org/10.3390/land11122132>
177. Bastida, R., Gupta, H., & Wingreen, S. C. (2013). A comparative study of the effect of blogs and email on virtual team performance.
178. Bataineh, M., Ashiq, M., Ul Haq, I., & ur Rehman, S. (2020). Mentorship in Education: A bibliometric analysis of 100 top-cited articles [Article]. *Library Philosophy and Practice*, 2020, 1-25. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85098171110&partnerID=40&md5=981ce65acb9d2fd67bc6d11871c9e078>
179. Batırlık, S. N., Gencer, Y. G., & Akkucuk, U. (2022). Global Virtual Team Leadership Scale (GVTLS) Development in Multinational Companies [Article]. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 14(2), Article 1038. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14021038>
180. Batra, S. (2023). Use of PLS-SEM Approach in the Construction Management Research.
181. Battistella, C., Annarelli, A., & Nonino, F. (2015). Exploring the impact of organizational and working models, incentives and collaboration strategies on innovation development in online communities of practices.
182. Bawack, R. E., Wamba, S. F., Carillo, K. D. A., & Akter, S. (2022). Artificial intelligence in E-Commerce: a bibliometric study and literature review [Article]. *Electronic Markets*, 32(1), 297-338. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12525-022-00537-z>
183. Bawaneh, A. K., & Malkawi, E. (2023). STEM FACULTY MEMBERS' PERSPECTIVES AND CHALLENGES TOWARDS DISTANCE LEARNING AND VIRTUAL CLASSES DURING COVID-19 OUTBREAK [Article]. *Turkish Online Journal of Distance Education*, 24(1), 246-261. <https://doi.org/10.17718/tojde.958068>
184. Behl, A., Chavan, M., Dutta, P., & Sheorey, P. A. (2020). Benchmarking publication metrics for Indian business researchers: Exploring the role of collaboration [Review]. *Benchmarking*, 27(2), 571-591. <https://doi.org/10.1108/BIJ-04-2019-0184>
185. Behzadi, P., & GajdÁCs, M. (2020). Dos and don'ts of a successfully peer-reviewed publication: From A–Z [Article]. *European Journal of Microbiology and Immunology*, 10(3), 125-130. <https://doi.org/10.1556/1886.2020.00023>
186. Belbaly, N. (2018). A transactive memory systems perspective on virtual team creativity.
187. Benton, D. C., Benton, A. D., González-Jurado, M. A., & Del Pulgar, M. G. (2019). Comparing the Scholarship Contributions of Five Disciplines to the Occupational Licensure Literature Indexed in Web of Science™ [Article]. *Journal of Nursing Regulation*, 10(3), 4-13. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2155-8256\(19\)30142-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2155-8256(19)30142-5)
188. Bergerot, B. (2022). The Citizen Science Paradox [Review]. *Land*, 11(8), Article 1151. <https://doi.org/10.3390/land11081151>
189. Bernardová, D., Kašparová, K., Fink, M., Ivanová, K., & Arkhangelska, T. (2020). Construction and Significance of Corporate Social Responsibility Indices—from Results to the Essence [Article]. *Organizacija*, 53(3), 212-226. <https://doi.org/10.2478/orga-2020-0014>
190. Bernini, F., Giuliani, M., & La Rosa, F. (2023). Measuring greenwashing: A systematic methodological literature review [Article]. *Business Ethics, the Environment and Responsibility*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/beer.12631>
191. Bersani, M. M., Marconi, F., Tamburri, D. A., Nodari, A., & Jamshidi, P. (2019). Verifying big data topologies by-design: a semi-automated approach [Article]. *Journal of Big Data*, 6(1), Article 40. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40537-019-0199-y>
192. Bester, M. S., & Bester, L. M. (2021). Coping strategies for a collarless workforce: An employee experience guide. In *Agile Coping in the Digital Workplace: Emerging Issues for Research and*

Practice (pp. 205-229). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-70228-1_11

193. Bettoni, M., Maerker, M., Bosino, A., Schillaci, C., & Vogel, S. (2022). Bibliometric Analysis of Soil and Landscape Stability, Sensitivity and Resistivity [Article]. *Land*, 11(8), Article 1328. <https://doi.org/10.3390/land11081328>
194. Bhagyalaxmi, D., & Babu, B. S. (2023). Bibliographic Analysis on Image Classification using Transfer Learning [Article]. *International Journal of Intelligent Systems and Applications in Engineering*, 11(2), 104-111. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85160836498&partnerID=40&md5=68b413bd3fbc7fbf99aced28149e0e5b>
195. Bhandal, R., Meriton, R., Kavanagh, R. E., & Brown, A. (2022). The application of digital twin technology in operations and supply chain management: a bibliometric review [Review]. *Supply Chain Management*, 27(2), 182-206. <https://doi.org/10.1108/SCM-01-2021-0053>
196. Bhardwaj, P., & Kalro, A. D. (2024). Consumer well-being—A systematic literature review and research agenda using TCCM framework [Review]. *International Journal of Consumer Studies*, 48(1), Article e12991. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ijcs.12991>
197. Bharti, N., Leonard, M., & Singh, S. (2016). Review and Comparison of the Search Effectiveness and User Interface of Three Major Online Chemical Databases [Review]. *Journal of Chemical Education*, 93(5), 852-863. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jchemed.5b00601>
198. Bhat, S. K., Pande, N., & Ahuja, V. (2017). Employee profile configurator: A tool to improve effectiveness of a virtual team [Article]. *International Journal of Networking and Virtual Organisations*, 17(4), 392-409. <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJNVO.2017.088459>
199. Bhat, S. K., Pande, N., & Ahuja, V. (2017). Virtual Team Effectiveness: An Empirical Study Using SEM.
200. Bhoomaiah, D., Pandian, K., Kantharajan, G., Agarwal, S., Hemalatha, M., Rajendran, K. V., & Srinivasa Rao, C. (2022). Mapping the research impact of collaboration and networking of ICAR fisheries research institutes in India: A scientometric study [Article]. *Indian Journal of Fisheries*, 69(1), 1-21. <https://doi.org/10.21077/ijf.2022.69.1.113025-01>
201. Bhuia, M. S., Chowdhury, R., Sonia, F. A., Kamli, H., Shaikh, A., El-Nashar, H. A. S., El-Shazly, M., & Islam, M. T. (2023). Anticancer Potential of the Plant-Derived Saponin Gracillin: A Comprehensive Review of Mechanistic Approaches [Review]. *Chemistry and Biodiversity*, 20(9), Article e202300847. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cbdv.202300847>
202. Bian, J., Abdelrahman, S., Shi, J., & Del Fiore, G. (2019). Automatic identification of recent high impact clinical articles in PubMed to support clinical decision making using time-agnostic features [Article]. *Journal of Biomedical Informatics*, 89, 1-10. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbi.2018.11.010>
203. Biddau, F., Brondi, S., & Cottone, P. F. (2022). Unpacking the Psychosocial Dimension of Decarbonization between Change and Stability: A Systematic Review in the Social Science Literature [Review]. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 14(9), Article 5308. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14095308>
204. Bidwe, R. V., Mishra, S., Patil, S., Shaw, K., Vora, D. R., Kotecha, K., & Zope, B. (2022). Deep Learning Approaches for Video Compression: A Bibliometric Analysis [Review]. *Big Data and Cognitive Computing*, 6(2), Article 44. <https://doi.org/10.3390/bdcc6020044>
205. Biemans, W. (2023). The impact of digital tools on sales-marketing interactions and perceptions [Article]. *Industrial Marketing Management*, 115, 395-407. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indmarman.2023.10.015>
206. Bilad, A., Zaim, M., & Zaim, F. (2022). Industry 4.0 tools in the industrial sector: A Systematic Literature Review.

207. Bilbao-Terol, A., & Bilbao-Terol, C. (2024). The Choquet integral supported by a hedonic approach for modelling preferences in hotel selection [Article]. *Omega (United Kingdom)*, 122, Article 102971. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.omega.2023.102971>
208. Bilgiç, M., & Işın, A. (2023). Embarking on a journey: a bibliometric analysis of the relative age effect in sport science [Article]. *German Journal of Exercise and Sport Research*, 53(3), 325-332. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12662-021-00792-w>
209. Bircan, T., & Salah, A. A. A. (2022). A Bibliometric Analysis of the Use of Artificial Intelligence Technologies for Social Sciences [Article]. *Mathematics*, 10(23), Article 4398. <https://doi.org/10.3390/math10234398>
210. Bodell, S., & Levins, K. (2012). Virtual teamworking and collaboration in occupational therapy: A paradox [Article]. *British Journal of Occupational Therapy*, 75(12), 574-576. <https://doi.org/10.4276/030802212X13548955545657>
211. Böhme, U., & Tesch, S. (2017). Mehr Zitationen erhalten [Article]. *Nachrichten aus der Chemie*, 65(12), 1223-1227. <https://doi.org/10.1002/nadc.20174067630>
212. Bolisani, E., & Scarso, E. (2019). The times they are (Not?) A-changing: Recent trends of knowledge management literature [Article]. *Electronic Journal of Knowledge Management*, 17(1), 89-99. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85079166872&partnerID=40&md5=b6316d83292579c95587960d733e08b1>
213. Bolisani, E., Scarso, E., & Kassaneh, T. C. (2023). The Pervasive Identity of Knowledge Management: Consolidation or Dilution? In *Knowledge Management and Organizational Learning* (Vol. 12, pp. 23-45): Springer Science and Business Media Deutschland GmbH.
214. Borrego, G., Moran, A. L., Palacio, R., & Rodriguez, O. M. (2016). Understanding architectural knowledge sharing in AGSD teams: An empirical study.
215. Botes, W. (2022). Pre-Service Teachers' Experiences on the Development of Educational Science Board Games [Article]. *European Journal of STEM Education*, 7(1), Article 02. <https://doi.org/10.20897/ejsteme/11784>
216. Bouillet, D. (2017). SPECIFICITIES OF THE SCIENCE OF EDUCATIONAL REHABILITATION IN CENTRAL AND EASTERN EUROPE [Article]. *Specialusis Ugdymas*, 2(37), 39-78. <https://doi.org/10.15388/SE.2017.5>
217. Bouillet, D., & Jokić, M. (2019). Characteristics of educational sciences research activity in European post-socialist countries in the period 1996 to 2013: Content analysis approach [Article]. *European Educational Research Journal*, 18(4), 407-425. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1474904119827462>
218. Boukacem-Zeghmouri, C., Bador, P., Lafouge, T., & Prost, H. (2016). Relationships between consumption, publication and impact in French universities in a value perspective: a bibliometric analysis [Article]. *Scientometrics*, 106(1), 263-280. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-015-1779-z>
219. Boukhelif, M., Hanine, M., & Kharmoum, N. (2023). A Decade of Intelligent Software Testing Research: A Bibliometric Analysis [Review]. *Electronics (Switzerland)*, 12(9), Article 2109. <https://doi.org/10.3390/electronics12092109>
220. Braun, J., & Missler-Behr, M. (2021). Product Development in the Automotive Industry in the Context of Industry 4.0 - A Bibliometric Analysis.
221. Brem, A., Nylund, P. A., & Roshani, S. (2023). Unpacking the complexities of crisis innovation: a comprehensive review of ecosystem-level responses to exogenous shocks [Review]. *Review of Managerial Science*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11846-023-00709-x>
222. Brem, A., Tidd, J., & Daim, T. (2019). Introduction - Managing innovation: Understanding international innovation [Editorial]. *Managing Innovation: Internationalization Of Innovation*, xv-xxxii. https://doi.org/10.1142/9781786346551_0001

223. Bremser, K., & Olivos-Rossini, M. (2017). Teaching in virtual environments to enhance intercultural understanding between Germans and Peruvians [Conference Paper]. *World Review of Entrepreneurship, Management and Sustainable Development*, 13(5-6), 635-646. <https://doi.org/10.1504/WREMSD.2017.086321>
224. Bryanov, K., & Vziatyshva, V. (2021). Determinants of individuals' belief in fake news: A scoping review determinants of belief in fake news [Article]. *PLoS ONE*, 16(6 June), Article e0253717. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0253717>
225. Brzezinski, M. (2015). Power laws in citation distributions: evidence from Scopus [Article]. *Scientometrics*, 103(1), 213-228. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-014-1524-z>
226. Bubphapant, J., & Brandão, A. (2024). Content marketing research: A review and research agenda [Review]. *International Journal of Consumer Studies*, 48(1), Article e12984. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ijcs.12984>
227. Burmaoglu, S., Saritas, O., Kıdak, L. B., & Berber, İ. C. (2017). Evolution of connected health: a network perspective [Article]. *Scientometrics*, 112(3), 1419-1438. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-017-2431-x>
228. Buturlina, O., Dovhal, S., Hryhorov, H., Lysokolenko, T., & Palahuta, V. (2021). Stem education in Ukraine in the context of sustainable development [Article]. *European Journal of Sustainable Development*, 10(1), 323-338. <https://doi.org/10.14207/ejsd.2021.v10n1p323>
229. Bwambale, B., Nyeko, M., Muhumuza, M., & Kervyn, M. (2020). Questioning knowledge foundation: What is the best way to integrate knowledge to achieve substantial disaster risk reduction? [Review]. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, 51, Article 101850. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdrr.2020.101850>
230. Bzhalava, L. (2015). The innovative performance of R&D outsourcing1 [Article]. *Journal of Innovation Management*, 3(4), 70-95. https://doi.org/10.24840/2183-0606_003.004_0006
231. Cabeza, L. F., Chàfer, M., & Mata, É. (2020). Comparative analysis of web of science and scopus on the energy efficiency and climate impact of buildings [Article]. *Energies*, 13(2), Article 409. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en13020409>
232. Cabral, C., & Dhar, R. L. (2021). Green competencies: insights and recommendations from a systematic literature review [Review]. *Benchmarking*, 28(1), 66-105. <https://doi.org/10.1108/BIJ-11-2019-0489>
233. Çağlayan Akay, E., Yılmaz Soydan, N. T., & Kocarık Gacar, B. (2022). Bibliometric analysis of the published literature on machine learning in economics and econometrics [Article]. *Social Network Analysis and Mining*, 12(1), Article 109. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13278-022-00916-6>
234. Čajka, A., & Novotný, J. (2022). Let us expand this Western project by admitting diversity and enhancing rigor: A systematic review of empirical research on alternative economies [Article]. *Ecological Economics*, 196, Article 107416. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2022.107416>
235. Calderón Peralvo, F., Cazorla Vanegas, P., & Avila-Ordóñez, E. (2022). A systematic review of COVID-19 transport policies and mitigation strategies around the globe [Article]. *Transportation Research Interdisciplinary Perspectives*, 15, Article 100653. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trip.2022.100653>
236. Camarasa, C., Nägeli, C., Ostermeyer, Y., Klippel, M., & Botzler, S. (2019). Diffusion of energy efficiency technologies in European residential buildings: A bibliometric analysis [Review]. *Energy and Buildings*, 202, Article 109339. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2019.109339>
237. Camilleri, M. A. (2019). Higher education marketing: Opportunities and challenges in the digital Era [Article]. *Academia (Greece)*, 2019(16-17), 4-28. <https://doi.org/10.26220/aca.3169>

238. Cammarano, A., Dello Iacono, S., Meglio, C., & Nicolais, L. (2023). Advances in Transdermal Drug Delivery Systems: A Bibliometric and Patent Analysis [Review]. *Pharmaceutics*, 15(12), Article 2762. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pharmaceutics15122762>
239. Campagna, L. M., & Fiorito, F. (2022). On the Impact of Climate Change on Building Energy Consumptions: A Meta-Analysis [Review]. *Energies*, 15(1), Article 354. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en15010354>
240. Campos-Andaur, P., Padilla-Lobo, K., Contreras-Barraza, N., Salazar-Sepúlveda, G., & Vega-Muñoz, A. (2022). The Wine Effects in Tourism Studies: Mapping the Research Referents [Article]. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 14(5), Article 2569. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14052569>
241. Canavesi, A., & Minelli, E. (2022). Servant Leadership: a Systematic Literature Review and Network Analysis [Article]. *Employee Responsibilities and Rights Journal*, 34(3), 267-289. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10672-021-09381-3>
242. Cancian, L. C., Dalmolin, R. S. D., & Caten, A. T. (2018). Bibliometric analysis for pattern exploration in worldwide digital soil mapping publications [Article]. *Anais da Academia Brasileira de Ciências*, 90(4), 3911-3923. <https://doi.org/10.1590/0001-3765201820180423>
243. Can-Güven, E. (2022). The current status and future needs of global bioaerosol research: a bibliometric analysis [Article]. *International Journal of Environmental Science and Technology*, 19(8), 7857-7868. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13762-021-03683-7>
244. Can-Güven, E., & Gedik, K. (2016). Global research activities on dioxins and dioxin-like compounds [Review]. *International Journal of Environment and Pollution*, 60(1-4), 12-33. <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJEP.2016.082116>
245. Cañibano, A., Chamakiotis, P., Rojahn, L., & Russell, E. (2022). Understanding Well-Being in Virtual Teams: A Comparative Case Study. In M. Themistocleous & M. Papadaki (Eds.), (Vol. 437 LNBIP, pp. 667-680): Springer Science and Business Media Deutschland GmbH.
246. Cano, E. V., Meneses, E. L., & Sanchiz, D. C. (2014). Bibliometric study of "Profesorado. Journal of curriculum and Teacher Education" (1997-2013) [Article]. *Profesorado*, 18(3), 191-212. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84920440946&partnerID=40&md5=72cacc1c96f3920030f96ffe83a67867>
247. Cao, Q., Png, B. T., Cai, Y., Cen, Y., & Xu, D. (2021). Interactive Virtual Reality Game for Online Learning of Science Subject in Primary Schools.
248. Cao, R., Cheung, C., Yunusa-Kaltungo, A., Manu, P., Liu, C., & Qiao, Q. (2023). The transmission of COVID-19 in construction: A systematic review of findings from statistical and modelling techniques. In *Construction Safety, Health and Well-being in the COVID-19 era* (pp. 15-27). CRC Press. <https://doi.org/10.1201/9781003278368-3>
249. Caputo, F., Soto-Acosta, P., Chiacchierini, C., Mazzoleni, A., & Passaro, P. (2021). Smashing local boundaries for sustain companies' innovativeness: The role of international R&D teams [Article]. *Journal of Business Research*, 128, 641-649. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2020.04.062>
250. Carotenuto, G., & Nicolais, F. (2023). One Secret for a High Citation Rate [Editorial]. *Publications*, 11(2), Article 23. <https://doi.org/10.3390/publications11020023>
251. Carroquino, J., Roda, V., Mustata, R., Yago, J., Valiño, L., Lozano, A., & Barreras, F. (2018). Combined production of electricity and hydrogen from solar energy and its use in the wine sector [Article]. *Renewable Energy*, 122, 251-263. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2018.01.106>
252. Carvalho, V. R., Costa, L. C. B., Baeta, B. E. L., & Peixoto, R. A. F. (2023). Lignin-Based Admixtures: A Scientometric Analysis and Qualitative Discussion Applied to Cement-Based Composites [Review]. *Polymers*, 15(5), Article 1254. <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym15051254>
253. Casanoves, M., Solé-Llussà, A., Haro, J., Gericke, N., & Valls, C. (2023). Assessment of the ability of game-based science learning to enhance genetic understanding [Article]. *Research in*

Science and Technological Education, 41(4), 1496-1518.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/02635143.2022.2044301>

254. Castaneda, D. I., & Cuellar, S. (2021). Knowledge sharing in business education [Review]. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 13(7), Article 3657. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13073657>
255. Castellano, S., Davidson, P., & Khelladi, I. (2017). Creativity techniques to enhance knowledge transfer within global virtual teams in the context of knowledge-intensive enterprises [Article]. *Journal of Technology Transfer*, 42(2), 253-266. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10961-016-9509-0>
256. Castillo, D., Vega-Muñoz, A., Salazar-Sepúlveda, G., Contreras-Barraza, N., & Torres-Alcayaga, M. (2023). Bibliometric Mapping of School Garden Studies: A Thematic Trends Analysis [Article]. *Horticulturae*, 9(3), Article 359. <https://doi.org/10.3390/horticulturae9030359>
257. Castillo, J. A., & Powell, M. A. (2019). Analysis scientific production from Ecuador and the impact of international collaboration in the period 2006-2015 [Article]. *Revista Espanola de Documentacion Cientifica*, 42(1), Article e225. <https://doi.org/10.3989/redc.2019.1.1567>
258. Castillo, J. A., & Powell, M. A. (2020). Research Impact and International Collaboration: A Study of Ecuadorian Science [Article]. *Journal of Hispanic Higher Education*, 19(3), 232-249. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1538192718779169>
259. Castillo, J. A., & Powell, M. A. (2020). Research Productivity and International Collaboration: A Study of Ecuadorian Science [Article]. *Journal of Hispanic Higher Education*, 19(4), 369-387. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1538192718792151>
260. Castro-Rodríguez, Á. M., Martínez-Ardila, H. E., & Camacho-Pico, J. A. (2020). Determining factors in the creation of University Spin-off [Article]. *Aibi, Revista de Investigacion Administracion e Ingenierias*, 8(2), 62-75. <https://doi.org/10.15649/2346030X.845>
261. Çavaş, B., Çapar, S., Çavaş, L., & Yahşi, Ö. (2021). Turkish STEM Teachers' Opinions about the Scientist-Teacher-Student Partnership [Article]. *Journal of Turkish Science Education*, 18(4), 622-637. <https://doi.org/10.36681/tused.2021.94>
262. Cavus, N. (2020). Evaluation of MoblrN M-learning system: Participants' attitudes and opinions [Article]. *World Journal on Educational Technology: Current Issues*, 12(3), 150-164. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85090675228&partnerID=40&md5=e4d243c7364a41eec506c6cb31be6d68>
263. Celdrán-Bernabeu, M. A., Mazón, J. N., Ivars-Baidal, J. A., & Fernando Vera-Rebollo, J. (2018). Smart Tourism. A study on systematic mapping [Review]. *Cuadernos de Turismo*(41), 107-138+655-658. <https://doi.org/10.6018/turismo.41.326971>
264. Cerchione, R., Centobelli, P., Oropallo, E., Magni, D., & Borin, E. (2023). Knowing what you don't know: a tertiary study on knowledge management [Article]. *Journal of Knowledge Management*, 27(9), 2548-2578. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JKM-07-2022-0589>
265. Cerqueira-Streit, J. A., Endo, G. Y., Guarnieri, P., & Batista, L. (2021). Sustainable Supply Chain Management in the Route for a Circular Economy: An Integrative Literature Review [Review]. *Logistics*, 5(4), Article 81. <https://doi.org/10.3390/logistics5040081>
266. Cerqueira-Streit, J. A., Guarnieri, P., de Oliveira, L. H., & Demajorovic, J. (2023). From Trash to Profit: How Packaging Waste Management Has Driven the Circular Economy—An Integrative Literature Review [Review]. *Logistics*, 7(3), Article 66. <https://doi.org/10.3390/logistics7030066>
267. Çevikbaş, M., & Işık, Z. (2021). An overarching review on delay analyses in construction projects [Article]. *Buildings*, 11(3), Article 109. <https://doi.org/10.3390/buildings11030109>
268. Chakraborty, D., Rana, N. P., Khorana, S., Singu, H. B., & Luthra, S. (2023). Big Data in Food: Systematic Literature Review and Future Directions [Review]. *Journal of Computer Information Systems*, 63(5), 1243-1263. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08874417.2022.2132428>

269. Chamakiotis, P. (2020). Virtual teams as creative and agile work environments. In *Agile Working and Well-Being in the Digital Age* (pp. 133-142). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-60283-3_10
270. Chamakiotis, P., & Panteli, N. (2016). Leading structurally dynamic virtual project teams.
271. Chamakiotis, P., & Panteli, N. (2016). The World is your office: Being creative in a global virtual organization. In *Analyzing Digital Discourse and Human Behavior in Modern Virtual Environments* (pp. 87-108). IGI Global. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-4666-9899-4.ch005>
272. Chamakiotis, P., Panteli, N., & Davison, R. M. (2021). Reimagining e-leadership for reconfigured virtual teams due to Covid-19 [Review]. *International Journal of Information Management*, 60, Article 102381. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijinfomgt.2021.102381>
273. Chan, A. P. C., Nwaogu, J. M., & Naslund, J. A. (2020). Mental Ill-Health Risk Factors in the Construction Industry: Systematic Review [Review]. *Journal of Construction Engineering and Management*, 146(3), Article 04020004. [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)CO.1943-7862.0001771](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)CO.1943-7862.0001771)
274. Chan, C., & Holosko, M. J. (2016). A Review of Information and Communication Technology Enhanced Social Work Interventions [Article]. *Research on Social Work Practice*, 26(1), 88-100. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1049731515578884>
275. Chan, J., Johns, F., & Moses, L. B. (2018). Academic metrics and positioning strategies. In *Metric Culture: Ontologies of Self-Tracking Practices* (pp. 177-195). Emerald Group Publishing Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.1108/978-1-78743-289-520181010>
276. Chang, C. C., & Yang, S. T. (2023). Interactive effects of scaffolding digital game-based learning and cognitive style on adult learners' emotion, cognitive load and learning performance [Article]. *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, 20(1), Article 16. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41239-023-00385-7>
277. Chang, R., Song, X., & Omrany, H. (2022). WHAT HINDERS THE TRANSITION TOWARDS SUSTAINABLE CONSTRUCTION IN CHINA? CRITICAL CHALLENGES AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS [Article]. *Journal of Green Building*, 17(4), 99-127. <https://doi.org/10.3992/jgb.17.4.99>
278. Charef, R., Alaka, H., & Emmitt, S. (2018). Beyond the third dimension of BIM: A systematic review of literature and assessment of professional views [Article]. *Journal of Building Engineering*, 19, 242-257. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jobe.2018.04.028>
279. Charef, R., Emmitt, S., Alaka, H., & Fouchal, F. (2019). Building Information Modelling adoption in the European Union: An overview [Article]. *Journal of Building Engineering*, 25, Article 100777. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jobe.2019.100777>
280. Charteris, J., Berman, J., & Page, A. (2021). Virtual team professional learning and development for practitioners in education [Article]. *Professional Development in Education*, 47(4), 638-650. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19415257.2021.1879215>
281. Chasanah, N., Gunawan, I., & Baroudi, B. (2023). International development project success: A literature review [Review]. *Journal of International Development*. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jid.3809>
282. Chatfield, A. T., Shlemon, V. N., Redublado, W., & Darbyshire, G. (2013). Creating value through virtual teams: A current literature review.
283. Chatfield, A. T., Shlemon, V. N., Redublado, W., & Darbyshire, G. (2014). Creating value through virtual teams: A current literature review [Article]. *Australasian Journal of Information Systems*, 18(3), 257-269. <https://doi.org/10.3127/ajis.v18i3.1104>
284. Chattopadhyay, A. (2014). Ethics of scientific publication: (Mal)-practices and Consequentialism.
285. Chaudhari, A. A., & Mulay, P. (2019). SCSi: Real-Time Data Analysis with Cassandra and Spark. In *Studies in Big Data* (Vol. 43, pp. 237-264): Springer Science and Business Media Deutschland GmbH.

286. Chaudhuri, N. B., & Dhar, D. (2023). Digitizing creativity evaluation in design education: a systematic literature review [Article]. *International Journal of Technology and Design Education*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10798-023-09846-6>
287. Chaudhuri, R., Chavan, G., Vadalkar, S., Vrontis, D., & Pereira, V. (2020). Two-decade bibliometric overview of publications in the *Journal of Knowledge Management* [Review]. *Journal of Knowledge Management*, 25(6), 1550-1574. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JKM-07-2020-0571>
288. Chawla, R. N., & Goyal, P. (2022). Emerging trends in digital transformation: a bibliometric analysis [Review]. *Benchmarking*, 29(4), 1069-1112. <https://doi.org/10.1108/BIJ-01-2021-0009>
289. Chellappa, V., Srivastava, V., & Salve, U. R. (2021). A systematic review of construction workers' health and safety research in India [Review]. *Journal of Engineering, Design and Technology*, 19(6), 1488-1504. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JEDT-08-2020-0345>
290. Chen, C. K., Huang, N. T. N., & Hwang, G. J. (2022). Findings and implications of flipped science learning research: A review of journal publications [Review]. *Interactive Learning Environments*, 30(5), 949-966. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10494820.2019.1690528>
291. Chen, C. Y., Huang, H. J., Lien, C. J., & Lu, Y. L. (2020). Effects of Multi-Genre Digital Game-Based Instruction on Students' Conceptual Understanding, Argumentation Skills, and Learning Experiences [Article]. *IEEE Access*, 8, 110643-110655, Article 9110562. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2020.3000659>
292. Chen, H., Feng, Y., Li, S., Zhang, Y., & Yang, X. (2019). Bibliometric analysis of theme evolution and future research trends of the type a personality [Review]. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 150, Article 109507. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2019.109507>
293. Chen, M. R. A., & Hwang, G. J. (2022). Effects of experiencing authentic contexts on English speaking performances, anxiety and motivation of EFL students with different cognitive styles [Article]. *Interactive Learning Environments*, 30(9), 1619-1639. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10494820.2020.1734626>
294. Chen, R., Yin, G., Zhao, W., Yan, K., Wu, S., Hao, D., & Liu, G. (2023). Topographic Correction of Optical Remote Sensing Images in Mountainous Areas: A systematic review [Article]. *IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Magazine*, 11(4), 125-145. <https://doi.org/10.1109/MGRS.2023.3311100>
295. Chen, S., Cui, T., & Qiu, J. (2022). Review of Studies Analyzing Interdisciplinary Dynamics [Article]. *Data Analysis and Knowledge Discovery*, 6(5), 1-9. <https://doi.org/10.11925/infotech.2096-3467.2021.0976>
296. Chen, W., Ahmed, M. M., Sofiah, W. I., Isa, N. A. M., Ebrahim, N. A., & Hai, T. (2021). A Bibliometric Statistical Analysis of the Fuzzy Inference System - Based Classifiers [Article]. *IEEE Access*, 9, 77811-77829, Article 9439531. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3082908>
297. Chen, W., Jin, R., Xu, Y., Wanatowski, D., Li, B., Yan, L., Pan, Z., & Yang, Y. (2019). Adopting recycled aggregates as sustainable construction materials: A review of the scientific literature [Review]. *Construction and Building Materials*, 218, 483-496. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2019.05.130>
298. Chen, W., Liu, W., Geng, Y., Brown, M. T., Gao, C., & Wu, R. (2017). Recent progress on emergy research: A bibliometric analysis [Review]. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 73, 1051-1060. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2017.02.041>
299. Chen, X., Chang-Richards, A. Y., Pelosi, A., Jia, Y., Shen, X., Siddiqui, M. K., & Yang, N. (2022). Implementation of technologies in the construction industry: a systematic review [Article]. *Engineering, Construction and Architectural Management*, 29(8), 3181-3209. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ECAM-02-2021-0172>

300. Chen, Y., Guo, Q., Qiao, C., & Wang, J. (2023). A systematic review of the application of eye-tracking technology in reading in science studies [Review]. *Research in Science and Technological Education*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02635143.2023.2285297>
301. Chen, Z., Lai, Z., Song, C., Zhang, X., & Cheng, J. C. P. (2023). Smart camera placement for building surveillance using OpenBIM and an efficient Bi-level optimization approach [Article]. *Journal of Building Engineering*, 77, Article 107257. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jobe.2023.107257>
302. Chen, Z., & Schintler, L. A. (2023). Rediscovering regional science: Positioning the field's evolving location in science and society [Article]. *Journal of Regional Science*, 63(3), 617-642. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jors.12634>
303. Cheng, M. T., Chou, W. C., Hsu, M. E., & Cheng, F. C. (2022). Blending educational gaming with physical experiments to engage high school students in inquiry-based learning [Article]. *Journal of Biological Education*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00219266.2022.2157861>
304. Cheng, S. C., Hwang, G. J., & Lai, C. L. (2022). Critical research advancements of flipped learning: a review of the top 100 highly cited papers [Review]. *Interactive Learning Environments*, 30(9), 1751-1767. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10494820.2020.1765395>
305. Cherednichenko, O., Matveiev, O., Yanholenko, O., & Maneva, R. (2021). Multi-agent modeling of project management processes in distributed teams.
306. Chiang, D. C. I., Antwi-Afari, M. F., Anwer, S., Mohandes, S. R., & Li, X. (2023). Occupational stress in the construction industry: a bibliometric-qualitative analysis of literature and future research directions [Review]. *International Journal of Building Pathology and Adaptation*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJBPA-08-2023-0114>
307. Chidozie, B. C., Ramos, A. L., & Ferreira, J. V. (2024). Simulation-Based Approaches to Enhance Operational Decision-Support in Healthcare 5.0: A Systematic Literature Review. In F. J. Silva, L. P. Ferreira, J. C. Sa, M. T. Pereira, & C. M. A. Pinto (Eds.), (pp. 671-678): Springer Science and Business Media Deutschland GmbH.
308. Chigariro, D., & Khumalo, N. B. (2018). Electronic records management research in ESARBICA: a bibliometric study [Article]. *Records Management Journal*, 28(2), 159-174. <https://doi.org/10.1108/RMJ-12-2016-0045>
309. Chihib, M., Salmerón-Manzano, E., Novas, N., & Manzano-Agugliaro, F. (2019). Bibliometric maps of BIM and BIM in universities: A comparative analysis [Article]. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 11(16), Article 4398. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11164398>
310. Chiroma, H., & Abawjy, J. H. (2023). *Computing Research Survival Manual: A practical handbook for beginners* [Book]. Institute of Physics Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1088/978-0-7503-5017-4>
311. Chistyakov, A. A., Zhdanov, S. P., Avdeeva, E. L., Dyadichenko, E. A., Kunitsyna, M. L., & Yagudina, R. I. (2023). Exploring the characteristics and effectiveness of project-based learning for science and STEAM education [Article]. *Eurasia Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology Education*, 19(5), Article em2256. <https://doi.org/10.29333/EJMSTE/13128>
312. Chivukula, K., & Pattanaik, L. N. (2023). PRIORITIZING LEAN TOOLS FOR INTEGRATION WITH INDUSTRY 4.0 TECHNOLOGIES USING A HYBRID FUZZY MOORA APPROACH [Article]. *International Journal of Industrial Engineering : Theory Applications and Practice*, 30(5), 1133-1149. <https://doi.org/10.23055/ijietap.2023.30.5.8883>
313. Choate, J., Aguilar-Roca, N., Beckett, E., Etherington, S., French, M., Gaganis, V., Haigh, C., Scott, D., Sweeney, T., & Zubek, J. (2021). International educators' attitudes, experiences, and recommendations after an abrupt transition to remote physiology laboratories [Article]. *Advances in Physiology Education*, 45(2), 310-321. <https://doi.org/10.1152/ADVAN.00241.2020>

314. Choudhary, H., & Bansal, N. (2022). Addressing Digital Divide through Digital Literacy Training Programs: A Systematic Literature Review [Article]. *Digital Education Review*(41), 224-248. <https://doi.org/10.1344/DER.2022.41.224-248>
315. Christwardana, M., & Khaerudini, D. S. (2022). The Scientometric Evaluation of The Research on Yeast Microbial Fuel Cells as A Promising Sustainable Energy Source [Article]. *Analytical and Bioanalytical Electrochemistry*, 14(8), 768-788. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85137562053&partnerID=40&md5=e27cbc34a250513de975b93f72f23c67>
316. Chugh, N. (2022). A Bibliometric Analysis of Anomaly Detection for IoT-Enabled Smart Cities. In A. Tomar, H. Malik, P. Kumar, & A. Iqbal (Eds.), (Vol. 915, pp. 297-308): Springer Science and Business Media Deutschland GmbH.
317. Çıki, K. D., & Tanrıverdi, H. (2023). Self-Determination Theory in the Field of Tourism: A Bibliometric Analysis [Review]. *Tourism*, 71(4), 769-781. <https://doi.org/10.37741/t.71.4.8>
318. Cinar, S., Pirasa, N., & Altun, E. (2022). The Effect of a STEM Education Workshop on Science Teachers' Instructional Practices [Article]. *Journal of Turkish Science Education*, 19(1), 349-369. <https://doi.org/10.36681/tused.2022.1125>
319. Civitillo, R., Festa, G., Priporas, C. V., & Rossi, M. (2022). Intellectual capital in nonprofit organizations: a focus on social capital as a marketing enabler [Article]. *International Marketing Review*, 39(5), 1052-1068. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IMR-01-2021-0029>
320. Clayson, P. E., Baldwin, S. A., & Larson, M. J. (2021). The open access advantage for studies of human electrophysiology: Impact on citations and Altmetrics [Article]. *International Journal of Psychophysiology*, 164, 103-111. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpsycho.2021.03.006>
321. Clements, R., Alizadeh, T., Kamruzzaman, L., Searle, G., & Legacy, C. (2023). A Systematic Literature Review of Infrastructure Governance: Cross-sectoral Lessons for Transformative Governance Approaches [Review]. *Journal of Planning Literature*, 38(1), 70-87. <https://doi.org/10.1177/08854122221112317>
322. Clements, R., Searle, G., & Alizadeh, T. (2023). Epistemic silences in settler-colonial infrastructure governance literature [Article]. *Geographical Research*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1745-5871.12601>
323. Çoban, N. A., Gedik, K., & Kaya, S. (2015). A case study on public noise annoyance in relation to research trends on noise pollution.
324. Cochrane, L., & Wilson, A. (2023). Nuancing the double and triple nexus: analyzing the potential for unintended, negative consequences [Article]. *Development Studies Research*, 10(1), Article 2181729. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21665095.2023.2181729>
325. Coimbra, D. R., Dominski, F. H., Brandt, R., Bevilacqua, G. G., Andreato, L. V., & Andrade, A. (2022). Twenty years of scientific production in sport and exercise psychology journals: A Bibliometric Analysis in Web of Science [Article]. *Revista de Psicologia del Deporte*, 31(1), 245-261. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85136459896&partnerID=40&md5=757bf42cc68d30a012adf7b7d80d8140>
326. Cole, M. L., Cox, J. D., & Stavros, J. M. (2019). Building collaboration in teams through emotional intelligence: Mediation by SOAR (strengths, opportunities, aspirations, and results) [Article]. *Journal of Management and Organization*, 25(2), 263-283. <https://doi.org/10.1017/jmo.2016.43>
327. Colombo, B., Gaiardelli, P., Dotti, S., & Caretto, F. (2022). Recycling technologies for fibre-reinforced plastic composite materials: A bibliometric analysis using a systematic approach [Review]. *Journal of Composite Materials*, 56(19), 3063-3080. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00219983221109877>

328. Conine, T. E. (2014). The Virtual Simulation: A Tool for Leadership Education in Global Corporations [Article]. *Global Business and Organizational Excellence*, 33(5), 17-28. <https://doi.org/10.1002/joe.21560>
329. Contreras-Barraza, N., Espinosa-Cristia, J. F., Salazar-Sepulveda, G., Vega-Muñoz, A., & Ariza-Montes, A. (2021). A Scientometric Systematic Review of Entrepreneurial Wellbeing Knowledge Production [Review]. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12, Article 641465. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.641465>
330. Cook, S. B., Cochrane, L., & Corbett, J. (2020). Searching through silos: Assessing the landscape of participatory mapping research using google scholar and web of science [Article]. *International Journal of E-Planning Research*, 9(4), 23-39. <https://doi.org/10.4018/IJEPR.2020100102>
331. Cordeiro, C. D., & Teodoro, V. D. (2022). How PISA is present in the scientific production: A bibliometric review. In *Critical Perspectives on PISA as a Means of Global Governance: Risks, Limitations, and Humanistic Alternatives* (pp. 25-47). Taylor and Francis Inc. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003255215-3>
332. Cordero, A. S., Melgar, S. G., & Márquez, J. M. A. (2019). Green building rating systems and the new framework level(s): A critical review of sustainability certification within Europe [Review]. *Energies*, 13(1), Article 66. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en13010066>
333. Cordero, A. S., Rodríguez, M. V., Melgar, S. G., & Márquez, J. M. A. (2021). Social criteria to develop an in use holistic urban sustainable assessment tool: UHU2SAT.
334. Corrales-Reyes, I. E., Villegas-Maestre, J. D., Vitón-Castillo, A. A., Tusell-Hormigó, D., Mamani-Benito, O. J., & Carranza-Esteban, R. F. (2022). Validity and reliability of an academic procrastination scale in Cuban dental students [Article]. *Revista Cubana de Medicina Militar*, 51(3), Article e02201826. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85138404237&partnerID=40&md5=de398c8fff4bf42b4572b122cc7aa9c0>
335. Corrêa, R. D. S., de Oliveira, U. R., Abdalla, M. M., & Fernandes, V. A. (2022). Systematic literature review on sustainable products: Impact on organizations, research opportunities and future perspectives [Review]. *Cleaner Waste Systems*, 1, Article 100003. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clwas.2022.100003>
336. Correia, G. R., Machado, J. C., Almeida, S. S., Santos, L. A. C., Costa, R. L., Calil, F. N., & de Melo e Silva-Neto, C. (2022). Scientific production on urban pruning waste: a scientometric analysis [Article]. *Revista Brasileira de Geografia Física*, 15(4), 1701-1714. <https://doi.org/10.26848/rbgf.v15.4.p1701-1714>
337. Costa, F. H. D. O., de Moraes, C. C., da Silva, A. L., Delai, I., Chaudhuri, A., & Pereira, C. R. (2022). Does resilience reduce food waste? Analysis of Brazilian supplier-retailer dyad [Article]. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 338, Article 130488. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.130488>
338. Costa Junior, E., Andrade, R. M. D. C., Rocha, L. S., Taramasco, C., & Ferreira, L. (2021). Computational Solutions for Human Falls Classification [Article]. *IEEE Access*, 9, 161590-161602. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3132796>
339. Costa Melo, D. I., Queiroz, G. A., Alves Junior, P. N., Sousa, T. B. D., Yushimito, W. F., & Pereira, J. (2023). Sustainable digital transformation in small and medium enterprises (SMEs): A review on performance [Review]. *Heliyon*, 9(3), Article e13908. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e13908>
340. Costa Melo, I., Alves Junior, P. N., Queiroz, G. A., Yushimito, W., & Pereira, J. (2023). Do We Consider Sustainability When We Measure Small and Medium Enterprises' (SMEs') Performance Passing through Digital Transformation? [Review]. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 15(6), Article 4917. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15064917>

341. Costa-Carrapiço, I., Raslan, R., & González, J. N. (2020). A systematic review of genetic algorithm-based multi-objective optimisation for building retrofitting strategies towards energy efficiency [Review]. *Energy and Buildings*, 210, Article 109690. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2019.109690>
342. Cotler, J., Yoder, R., Breimer, E., & Delbelso, D. (2012). Developing 21st century communicators.
343. Cox, C., Gopsill, J., & Hicks, B. (2021). Demystifying digital X.
344. Coy-Aceves, L. E., & Corona-Vasquez, B. (2022). Bibliometric analysis of artificial intelligence algorithms used for microbial fuel cell research [Article]. *Water Practice and Technology*, 17(10), 2071-2082. <https://doi.org/10.2166/wpt.2022.116>
345. Crammond, R., Omeihe, K. O., Murray, A., & Ledger, K. (2018). Managing knowledge through social media: Modelling an entrepreneurial approach for Scottish SMEs and beyond [Article]. *Baltic Journal of Management*, 13(3), 303-328. <https://doi.org/10.1108/BJM-05-2017-0133>
346. Cretu, D. M., & Morandau, F. (2022). Bullying and cyberbullying: a bibliometric analysis of three decades of research in education [Article]. *Educational Review*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00131911.2022.2034749>
347. Cuadrado-Ballesteros, B., Ríos, A. M., & Guillamón, M. D. (2023). Transparency in public administrations: a structured literature review [Review]. *Journal of Public Budgeting, Accounting and Financial Management*, 35(5), 537-567. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JPBAFM-10-2022-0158>
348. Cubillos, C., Roncagliolo, S., & Cabrera-Paniagua, D. (2023). Learning and Motivation When Using Multiple-Try in a Digital Game for Primary Students in Chile [Article]. *Education Sciences*, 13(11), Article 1119. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci13111119>
349. Cummings, C. L., Lin, S. H., & Trump, B. D. (2017). Public perceptions of climate geoengineering: A systematic review of the literature [Review]. *Climate Research*, 73(3), 247-264. <https://doi.org/10.3354/cr01475>
350. Cuschieri, S. (2022). *A Roadmap to Successful Scientific Publishing: The Dos, the Don'ts and the Must-Knows* [Book]. Springer International Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-99295-8>
351. Cutting, J., & Deterding, S. (2022). The task-attention theory of game learning: a theory and research agenda [Article]. *Human-Computer Interaction*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07370024.2022.2047971>
352. Cutting, J., & Iacovides, I. (2022). Learning by Doing: Intrinsic Integration Directs Attention to Increase Learning In Games [Article]. *Proceedings of the ACM on Human-Computer Interaction*, 6, Article 240. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3549503>
353. da Silva, D. J. C., Lopes, L. F. D., Santos Costa Vieira da Silva, L., da Silva, W. V., Teixeira, C. S., & Veiga, C. (2023). Relationship between ecosystem innovation and performance measurement models [Article]. *International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management*, 72(10), 2898-2918. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJPPM-06-2021-0349>
354. da Silva, J. B. N., Senna, P., Chousa, A., & Coelho, O. (2020). Data mining and operations research techniques in Supply Chain Risk Management: A bibliometric study [Review]. *Brazilian Journal of Operations and Production Management*, 17(3), Article e2020966. <https://doi.org/10.14488/BJOPM.2020.029>
355. Da Silva, V. P. J. (2022). Systematized asynchronous physical leisure activities during the COVID-19 pandemic [Article]. *Retos*, 46, 552-564. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85135554089&partnerID=40&md5=04ed4b1e304e0ededc68d50e847bd9d6>

356. Dahmani, N., Benhida, K., Belhadi, A., Kamble, S., Elfezazi, S., & Jauhar, S. K. (2021). Smart circular product design strategies towards eco-effective production systems: A lean eco-design industry 4.0 framework [Article]. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 320, Article 128847. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.128847>
357. Dairo, A., & Szűcs, K. (2021). Fuzzy Analytics Application in Digital and Consumer Marketing: A Literature Review. In A. Rocha, M. K. Peter, S. Loureiro, J. L. Reis, R. Cayolla, & Z. Bogdanovic (Eds.), (Vol. 205, pp. 135-144): Springer Science and Business Media Deutschland GmbH.
358. Dalidig, S. M. N. M. (2020). Effects of Game-Based Teaching on Students' Conceptual Understanding.
359. Damerow, J., & Wintergrün, D. (2019). The hitchhiker's guide to data in the history of science [Article]. *ISIS*, 110(3), 513-521. <https://doi.org/10.1086/705497>
360. Dan, H. K., Tung, H. T., Khanh, D. V., & Nguyen, H. (2023). Bibliometric Analysis of Research Trends on Quantum-Dot-Sensitized Solar Cells over Two Decades [Article]. *Energies*, 16(15), Article 5734. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en16155734>
361. Dana, L. P., Crocco, E., Culasso, F., & Giacosa, E. (2023). Mapping the field of digital entrepreneurship: a topic modeling approach [Article]. *International Entrepreneurship and Management Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11365-023-00926-6>
362. Dang, Z., Li, L., Peng, H., & Zhang, J. (2021). Impact of sudden global events on cross-field research cooperation [Article]. *Information (Switzerland)*, 12(1), 1-18, Article 26. <https://doi.org/10.3390/info12010026>
363. Darmawan, I., Lussak, A., Hidayat, D., Prihatma Bayu Putra, O., & Pangaribuan, C. H. (2023). Factors Affecting University Lecturers' Self-Efficacy, and Performance during the COVID-19 Pandemic.
364. Darroudi, M., Gholami, M., Rezayi, M., & Khazaei, M. (2021). An overview and bibliometric analysis on the colorectal cancer therapy by magnetic functionalized nanoparticles for the responsive and targeted drug delivery [Review]. *Journal of Nanobiotechnology*, 19(1), Article 399. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12951-021-01150-6>
365. Darroudi, M., Nazari, S. E., Kesharwani, P., Rezayi, M., Khazaei, M., & Sahebkar, A. (2022). Background of carbon nanotubes for drug delivery systems. In *Emerging Applications of Carbon Nanotubes in Drug and Gene Delivery* (pp. 1-35). Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-323-85199-2.00009-1>
366. Darroudi, M., & Ziarani, G. M. (2021). Chemical behavior of cysteine in organic synthesis [Review]. *Current Organic Synthesis*, 18(7), 624-638. <https://doi.org/10.2174/1570179418666210216141343>
367. Das, R., & Kodwani, A. D. (2018). Strategic human resource management: a power based critique [Article]. *Benchmarking*, 25(4), 1213-1231. <https://doi.org/10.1108/BIJ-09-2016-0143>
368. Dasanayaka, C. H., Gunarathne, N., Murphy, D. F., & Nagirikandalage, P. (2022). Triggers for and barriers to the adoption of environmental management practices by small and medium-sized enterprises: A critical review [Review]. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, 29(4), 749-764. <https://doi.org/10.1002/csr.2244>
369. Dash, S., Das, T., Patel, P., Panda, P. K., Suar, M., & Verma, S. K. (2022). Emerging trends in the nanomedicine applications of functionalized magnetic nanoparticles as novel therapies for acute and chronic diseases [Review]. *Journal of Nanobiotechnology*, 20(1), Article 393. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12951-022-01595-3>
370. Dash, S., & Kalamdhad, A. S. (2021). Science mapping approach to critical reviewing of published literature on water quality indexing [Review]. *Ecological Indicators*, 128, Article 107862. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2021.107862>

371. Davaei, M., Gunkel, M., Veglio, V., & Taras, V. (2022). The influence of cultural intelligence and emotional intelligence on conflict occurrence and performance in global virtual teams [Article]. *Journal of International Management*, 28(4), Article 100969. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.intman.2022.100969>
372. Dave, M., Singh, K., Kumar, A., & Kumar, S. (2019). Knowledge management measures: an empirical investigation of Indian cement industry [Article]. *Benchmarking*, 26(3), 734-752. <https://doi.org/10.1108/BIJ-10-2017-0290>
373. David, K., & Golan, C. (2017). The mediating effect of interpersonal trust on virtual team's collaboration [Article]. *International Journal of Knowledge Management*, 13(3), 20-37. <https://doi.org/10.4018/IJKM.2017070102>
374. Davidson, P. L. (2013). Why do many firms still miss the competitive advantage of virtual teams?
375. Davis, E. A., & Stephens, A. (2022). *Science and Engineering in Preschool Through Elementary Grades: The Brilliance of Children and the Strengths of Educators (2022)* [Book]. National Academies Press. <https://doi.org/10.17226/26215>
376. De Almeida, I. M., Jugend, D., Deus, R. M., & De Souza, F. B. (2021). Contributions of the Circular Economy to the Leather Life Cycle: A Theoretical Review and Integrative Framework Proposal [Review]. *Journal of the Society of Leather Technologists and Chemists*, 105(6), 274-289. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85134876190&partnerID=40&md5=e8ee7fa04a1abf7ec30ce667c29910c5>
377. De Bruyn, A. J. (2017). Exploring high-performance work processes in effective virtual teams [Article]. *African Journal of Economic and Management Studies*, 8(4), 398-409. <https://doi.org/10.1108/AJEMS-06-2016-0070>
378. de Bruyn, C., Ben Said, F., Meyer, N., & Soliman, M. (2023). Research in tourism sustainability: A comprehensive bibliometric analysis from 1990 to 2022 [Review]. *Heliyon*, 9(8), Article e18874. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e18874>
379. de Castro, A. B. C., Nodari, C. H., de Guimarães, J. C. F., El-Aouar, W. A., da Silva, A. W. P., & de Sousa, J. C. (2022). Knowledge Management: thematic configuration and emerging issues [Article]. *Ciencia da Informacao*, 51(2), 30-47. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85142632984&partnerID=40&md5=1ac51c16e13a179afca3c95a8de61516>
380. de Diego, E., & Almodóvar, P. (2022). Mapping research trends on strategic agility over the past 25 years: insights from a bibliometric approach [Article]. *European Journal of Management and Business Economics*, 31(2), 219-238. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EJMBE-05-2021-0160>
381. de Enrique Arnau, L., & Pinillos-Costa, M. J. (2023). Board of directors and business transformation: a bibliometric analysis [Article]. *European Journal of Management and Business Economics*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EJMBE-10-2022-0338>
382. de Faria Silva, R., Souza, A., Kaczam, F., Dalazen, L. L., da Silva, W. V., & da Veiga, C. P. (2022). Public-Private Partnerships and Value for Money [Article]. *Public Works Management and Policy*, 27(4), 347-370. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1087724X221108149>
383. de la Ballina, J., & Cachero, S. (2023). Teaching Marketing Research at the University Level—From Academic and Professional Perspectives [Article]. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 15(2), Article 1480. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15021480>
384. de la Sotta, T., Chang, V., Pizarro, B., Henriquez, H., Alvear, N., & Saavedra, J. M. (2023). Impact of attention mechanisms for organ segmentation in chest x-ray images over U-Net model [Article]. *Multimedia Tools and Applications*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11042-023-17220-w>
385. De la Torre Bayo, J. J., Martín Pascual, J., Torres Rojo, J. C., & Zamorano Toro, M. (2022). Waste to Energy from Municipal Wastewater Treatment Plants: A Science Mapping [Article]. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 14(24), Article 16871. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su142416871>

386. de la Torre Bayo, J. J., Martín-Lara, M. Á., Calero Hoces, M., Sánchez Castillo, P. M., Pula, H. J., & Zamorano, M. (2023). Management of Used COVID-19 Personal Protective Equipment: A Bibliometric Analysis and Literature Review [Review]. *Applied Sciences (Switzerland)*, 13(4), Article 2377. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app13042377>
387. de la Vega, R. C., Pinto, G. O., Ribeiro, F. F., & Spiegel, T. (2022). Pull processes in health care: a systematic literature review [Review]. *Gestao e Producao*, 29, Article e1921. <https://doi.org/10.1590/1806-9649-2022v29e1921>
388. de Lima, B. T., Devós Ganga, G. M., Filho, M. G., & de Santa-Eulalia, L. A. (2023). Blockchain capabilities for supply chain management [Article]. *European Journal of Industrial Engineering*, 17(5), 657-695. <https://doi.org/10.1504/EJIE.2023.133214>
389. De Menéndez, A. M. H., Morales-Menendez, R., & Orta, P. (2017). Virtual teams in engineering - Global practices.
390. de Moraes, C. C., de Oliveira Costa, F. H., Roberta Pereira, C., da Silva, A. L., & Delai, I. (2020). Retail food waste: mapping causes and reduction practices [Review]. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 256, Article 120124. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.120124>
391. de Oliveira, A. B., Rodrigues, R. S., & Matias, M. (2017). Journals scientific of Agrarian sciences: Analysis of the Brazilian titles indexed in the web of science and scopus [Article]. *Perspectivas em Ciencia da Informacao*, 22(2), 3-28. <https://doi.org/10.1590/1981-5344/2582>
392. de Oliveira, A. O., Oliveira, H. L. S., Gomes, C. F. S., & Ribeiro, P. C. C. (2019). Quantitative analysis of RFID' publications from 2006 to 2016 [Article]. *International Journal of Information Management*, 48, 185-192. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijinfomgt.2019.02.001>
393. de Oliveira Azevêdo, R., Rotela Junior, P., Chicco, G., Aquila, G., Souza Rocha, L. C., & Santana Peruchi, R. (2021). Identification and analysis of impact factors on the economic feasibility of wind energy investments [Review]. *International Journal of Energy Research*, 45(3), 3671-3697. <https://doi.org/10.1002/er.6109>
394. de Oliveira Azevêdo, R., Rotela, P., Jr., Souza Rocha, L. C., Chicco, G., Aquila, G., & Peruchi, R. S. (2020). Identification and analysis of impact factors on the economic feasibility of photovoltaic energy investments [Review]. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 12(17), Article 7173. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12177173>
395. de Oliveira, L. G., de Paiva, A. P., Balestrassi, P. P., Ferreira, J. R., da Costa, S. C., & da Silva Campos, P. H. (2019). Response surface methodology for advanced manufacturing technology optimization: theoretical fundamentals, practical guidelines, and survey literature review [Article]. *International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology*, 104(5-8), 1785-1837. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00170-019-03809-9>
396. de Oliveira, U. R., Espindola, L. S., da Silva, I. R., da Silva, I. N., & Rocha, H. M. (2018). A systematic literature review on green supply chain management: Research implications and future perspectives [Review]. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 187, 537-561. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.03.083>
397. de Oliveira, U. R., Gomes, T. S. M., de Oliveira, G. G., de Abreu, J. C. A., Oliveira, M. A., da Silva César, A., & Aprigliano Fernandes, V. (2022). Systematic Literature Review on Sustainable Consumption from the Perspective of Companies, People and Public Policies [Article]. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 14(21), Article 13771. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su142113771>
398. de Oliveira, U. R., Menezes, R. P., & Fernandes, V. A. (2023). A systematic literature review on corporate sustainability: contributions, barriers, innovations and future possibilities [Review]. *Environment, Development and Sustainability*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10668-023-02933-7>

399. de Oliveira, V. T., Teixeira, D., Rocchi, L., & Boggia, A. (2023). Trends in sustainability assessment supported by geographic information systems: A bibliometric approach [Review]. *Environmental Science and Policy*, 141, 117-125. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2023.01.003>
400. de Paulo, A. F., & Calvet, H. (2022). Evolution of scientific knowledge on the internet of things and smart homes [Article]. *Journal of Technology Management and Innovation*, 17(4), 3-13. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85148613394&partnerID=40&md5=10df58525c9a7a1c1be168f5d169dcd5>
401. de Souza, D. G. B., Dos Santos, E. A., Soma, N. Y., & da Silva, C. E. S. (2021). Mcdm-based r&d project selection: A systematic literature review [Review]. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 13(21), Article 11626. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su132111626>
402. de Souza, T. A., Alcântara, R. L. C., & Piato, É. L. (2017). Risk management in supply chains: Bibliometric analysis of intellectual production in the period from 2000 to 2015 [Article]. *Espacios*, 38(19), Article 16. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85018756788&partnerID=40&md5=874cb0fb4eec286da7589c344b64a0ab>
403. De Stefano, D., Fuccella, V., Vitale, M. P., & Zaccarin, S. (2023). Quality issues in co-authorship data of a national scientific community [Article]. *Network Science*, 11(1), 98-112. <https://doi.org/10.1017/nws.2022.40>
404. de Vasconcelos Silva, A. C. P., Spiegel, T., Scavarda, L. F., & da Cunha Reis, A. (2022). How to increase access to kidney transplantation: the analysis of a Brazilian public hospital through operations management [Article]. *International Journal of Services and Operations Management*, 41(4), 404-430. <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJSOM.2022.122927>
405. de Vries, J. R., van Bommel, S., & Peters, K. (2018). Trust at a distance-trust in online communication in environmental and global health research projects [Article]. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 10(11), Article 4005. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su10114005>
406. Debnath, R., Pettit, C., & Leao, S. Z. (2022). Geodesign Approaches to City Resilience Planning: A Systematic Review [Review]. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 14(2), Article 938. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14020938>
407. Dehghanbanadaki, H., Aazami, H., Ejtahed, H. S., Sohrabi, A., Raftar, S. K. A., Tarashi, S., Tabatabaei-Malazy, O., Bahramali, G., Siadat, S. D., Esfahani, E. N., & Razi, F. (2022). The global scientific publications on gut microbiota in type 2 diabetes; a bibliometric, Scientometric, and descriptive analysis [Article]. *Journal of Diabetes and Metabolic Disorders*, 21(1), 13-32. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40200-021-00920-1>
408. Del Giudice, M., Scuotto, V., Garcia-Perez, A., & Messeni Petruzzelli, A. (2019). Shifting Wealth II in Chinese economy. The effect of the horizontal technology spillover for SMEs for international growth [Article]. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 145, 307-316. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2018.03.013>
409. Delafenestre, R. (2019). New business models in supply chains: a bibliometric study [Review]. *International Journal of Retail and Distribution Management*, 47(12), 1283-1299. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJRDM-12-2018-0281>
410. Demo, G., Rezende Costa, A. C., Coura, K. V., de Fátima Oliveira, Á., & Júnior, S. G. (2021). Resilience at Work: Research Itineraries, a Critical Review of Measures and a Proposal for Measurement of the Construct for Organizational Diagnosis. In *Assessing Organizational Behaviors: A Critical Analysis of Measuring Instruments* (pp. 107-124). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-81311-6_5
411. Derbe, G., Li, Y., Wu, D., & Zhao, Q. (2020). Scientometric review of construction project schedule studies: Trends, gaps and potential research areas [Review]. *Journal of Civil Engineering and Management*, 26(4), 343-363. <https://doi.org/10.3846/jcem.2020.12317>

412. Deutz, D. B., Vlachos, E., Drongstrup, D., Dorch, B. F., & Wien, C. (2020). Effective publication strategies in clinical research [Article]. *PLoS ONE*, 15(1), Article e0228438. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0228438>
413. Deyanova, K., Brehmer, N., Lapidus, A., Tiberius, V., & Walsh, S. (2022). Hatching start-ups for sustainable growth: a bibliometric review on business incubators [Review]. *Review of Managerial Science*, 16(7), 2083-2109. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11846-022-00525-9>
414. Dhakate, N., Joshi, R., Ali, F., & Kumar, S. (2023). Current knowledge and future research directions of medical tourism: insights from a bibliometric analysis [Article]. *Asia Pacific Journal of Tourism Research*, 28(8), 889-906. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10941665.2023.2276848>
415. Dhawan, S. M., Gupta, B. M., & Gupta, R. (2018). Mapping global research output in big data during 2007-16 [Article]. *Emerging Science Journal*, 2(3), 117-129. <https://doi.org/10.28991/esj-2018-01135>
416. Dhillon, S. K., Ibrahim, R., & Selemat, A. (2019). Cybernetic diagnosis approach for publication productivity of Malaysian Research University.
417. Dhital, S., & Rupakheti, D. (2019). Bibliometric analysis of global research on air pollution and human health: 1998–2017 [Article]. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 26(13), 13103-13114. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-019-04482-x>
418. Di Vita, G., Pilato, M., Pecorino, B., Brun, F., & D'Amico, M. (2017). A review of the role of vegetal ecosystems in CO2 capture [Review]. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 9(10), Article 1840. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su9101840>
419. Diaz Gonzalez, A., & Dentchev, N. A. (2021). Ecosystems in support of social entrepreneurs: a literature review [Review]. *Social Enterprise Journal*, 17(3), 329-360. <https://doi.org/10.1108/SEJ-08-2020-0064>
420. Díaz, M., Teixidó, M., Gil, R. M., Cabeza, L. F., & Aras, L. M. (2022). A Comparative Analysis of Scopus and Web of Science (WoS) Literature on the Autism Crisis [Review]. *Review Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders*, 9(4), 618-634. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40489-021-00277-4>
421. Díaz-Restrepo, C. A., Hoyos, O., Arismendy-Quintero, D. E., & Duque, P. (2023). Financial Education in the Young Population: A Revision and Bibliometric Analysis [Article]. *Revista Colombiana de Educacion*(89), 148-180. <https://doi.org/10.17227/rce.num89-14201>
422. Diez-Martinez, I., & Peiro-Signes, A. (2022). Transitioning towards sustainability: The ‘what’, ‘why’ and ‘how’ of the integration of sustainable practices into business models [Article]. *Tec Empresarial*, 16(1), 44-86. <https://doi.org/10.18845/te.v16i1.6013>
423. Dimzov, S., Kokić, I. B., & Juric, M. (2020). Student research papers available under hrČak portal: The analysis of papers based on graduate theses from the dabar repository [Article]. *Vjesnik Bibliotekara Hrvatske*, 63(1-2), 31-64. <https://doi.org/10.30754/vbh.63.1-2.819>
424. Dincă, M., Luștea, A., Crașovan, M., Onițiu, A., & Berge, T. (2023). Students’ Perspectives on Team Dynamics in Project-Based Virtual Learning [Article]. *SAGE Open*, 13(1). <https://doi.org/10.1177/21582440221147269>
425. Dincer, C., & Dincer, B. (2023). Social Commerce and Purchase Intention: A Brief Look at the Last Decade by Bibliometrics [Article]. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 15(1), Article 846. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15010846>
426. Dissanayake, I., Zhang, J., & Gu, B. (2014). Virtual team performance in crowdsourcing contests: A social network perspective completed research paper [Conference Paper]. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85107713844&partnerID=40&md5=4c5bc81f4c6b5cd58475c58a03d5263c>

427. Dissanayake, I., Zhang, J., & Gu, B. (2015). Task Division for Team Success in Crowdsourcing Contests: Resource Allocation and Alignment Effects [Conference Paper]. *Journal of Management Information Systems*, 32(2), 8-39. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07421222.2015.1068604>
428. do Amaral, J. V. S., de Carvalho Miranda, R., Montevechi, J. A. B., dos Santos, C. H., & Gabriel, G. T. (2022). Metamodeling-based simulation optimization in manufacturing problems: a comparative study [Article]. *International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology*, 120(7-8), 5205-5224. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00170-022-09072-9>
429. do Amaral, J. V. S., dos Santos, C. H., Montevechi, J. A. B., & de Queiroz, A. R. (2023). Energy Digital Twin applications: A review [Review]. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 188, Article 113891. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2023.113891>
430. do Carmo, G., Felizardo, L. F., de Castro Alcântara, V., da Silva, C. A., & do Prado, J. W. (2023). The impact of Jürgen Habermas's scientific production: a scientometric review [Article]. *Scientometrics*, 128(3), 1853-1875. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-022-04625-x>
431. Do, Q., Ramudhin, A., Colicchia, C., Creazza, A., & Li, D. (2021). A systematic review of research on food loss and waste prevention and management for the circular economy [Review]. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 239, Article 108209. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpe.2021.108209>
432. Dodds, C. D., & Kiernan, M. D. (2019). Hidden Veterans: A Review of the Literature on Women Veterans in Contemporary Society [Article]. *Illness Crisis and Loss*, 27(4), 293-310. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1054137319834775>
433. Doekhie, K. D., Strating, M. M. H., Buljac-Samardzic, M., van de Bovenkamp, H. M., & Paauwe, J. (2018). The different perspectives of patients, informal caregivers and professionals on patient involvement in primary care teams. A qualitative study [Article]. *Health Expectations*, 21(6), 1171-1182. <https://doi.org/10.1111/hex.12824>
434. Dolšak, J. (2023). Determinants of energy efficient retrofits in residential sector: A comprehensive analysis [Article]. *Energy and Buildings*, 282, Article 112801. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2023.112801>
435. Dominko, M., & Verbič, M. (2019). Subjective well-being among the elderly: A bibliometric analysis [Article]. *Quality and Quantity*, 53(3), 1187-1207. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11135-018-0811-9>
436. Dong, X., Wei, X., Shu, F., Su, Q., Wang, J., Liu, N., & Qiu, J. (2022). A Bibliometric Analysis on Global Psychological and Behavioral Research Landscape on COVID-19 Pandemic [Article]. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(2), Article 879. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph19020879>
437. Donthu, N., Kumar, S., & Pattnaik, D. (2021). Intellectual structure and publication pattern in *International Journal of Advertising*: a bibliometric analysis during 1982–2019 [Article]. *International Journal of Advertising*, 40(2), 148-174. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02650487.2020.1756655>
438. Dornelles, A. Z., Boyd, E., Nunes, R. J., Asquith, M., Boonstra, W. J., Delabre, I., Michael Denney, J., Grimm, V., Jentsch, A., Nicholas, K. A., Schröter, M., Seppelt, R., Settele, J., Shackelford, N., Standish, R. J., Yengoh, G. T., & Oliver, T. H. (2020). Towards a bridging concept for undesirable resilience in social-ecological systems [Article]. *Global Sustainability*, 3, Article e20. <https://doi.org/10.1017/sus.2020.15>
439. Dorofeeva, A. A., & Nyurenberger, L. B. (2019). Trends in digitalization of education and training for industry 4.0 in the Russian Federation.
440. Dorofeeva, A. A., Ponomareva, E. Y., Shamaeva, N. P., & Nyurenberger, L. B. (2021). Implementation of the national project for staffing the digital economy.

441. Dou, P., Shen, H., Li, Z., & Guan, X. (2021). Time series remote sensing image classification framework using combination of deep learning and multiple classifiers system [Article]. *International Journal of Applied Earth Observation and Geoinformation*, 103, Article 102477. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jag.2021.102477>
442. Dou, Y., Xue, X., Wang, Y., Xue, W., & Huangfu, W. (2022). Evaluation of enterprise technology innovation capability in prefabricated construction in China [Article]. *Construction Innovation*, 22(4), 1059-1084. <https://doi.org/10.1108/CI-12-2020-0196>
443. Draghici, A., Aldea, C. C., & Draghici, G. (2013). Decision making process approach for choosing the adequate ICT tool in virtual teams [Article]. *International Journal of Human Capital and Information Technology Professionals*, 4(2), 56-71. <https://doi.org/10.4018/jhcitp.2013040105>
444. Drira, N., Kotti, M., Fakhfakh, M., Siarry, P., & Tlelo-Cuautle, E. (2019). Pseudo Expected Improvement Based-Optimization for CMOS Analog Circuit Design.
445. Drira, N., Kotti, M., Fakhfakh, M., Siarry, P., & Tlelo-Cuautle, E. (2020). Convergence rates of the efficient global optimization algorithm for improving the design of analog circuits [Article]. *Analog Integrated Circuits and Signal Processing*, 103(1), 143-162. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10470-020-01585-1>
446. Driscoll, D. A., Banks, S. C., Barton, P. S., Ikin, K., Lentini, P., Lindenmayer, D. B., Smith, A. L., Berry, L. E., Burns, E. L., Edworthy, A., Evans, M. J., Gibson, R., Heinsohn, R., Howland, B., Kay, G., Munro, N., Scheele, B. C., Stirnemann, I., Stojanovic, D., . . . Westgate, M. J. (2014). The trajectory of dispersal research in conservation biology. Systematic review [Review]. *PLoS ONE*, 9(4), Article e95053. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0095053>
447. Driskell, T., Funke, G., Tolston, M., Capiola, A., & Driskell, J. E. (2023). Fluid and Virtual Teams [Article]. *Small Group Research*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/10464964231216367>
448. Drivas, K., Balafoutis, A. T., & Rozakis, S. (2015). Research funding and academic output: evidence from the Agricultural University of Athens [Article]. *Prometheus: Critical Studies in Innovation*, 33(3), 235-256. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08109028.2016.1150575>
449. Drivas, K., & Kremmydas, D. (2020). The Matthew effect of a journal's ranking [Article]. *Research Policy*, 49(4), Article 103951. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2020.103951>
450. Drozd, A., Matusiak, K., Setkiewicz, Z., Ciarach, M., Janeczko, K., Sandt, C., Borondics, F., Horak, D., Babic, M., & Chwiej, J. (2020). FTIR microspectroscopy revealed biochemical changes in liver and kidneys as a result of exposure to low dose of iron oxide nanoparticles [Article]. *Spectrochimica Acta - Part A: Molecular and Biomolecular Spectroscopy*, 236, Article 118355. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.saa.2020.118355>
451. Du, H. S., Ke, X., Chu, S. K. W., & Chan, L. T. (2017). A bibliometric analysis of emergency management using information systems (2000-2016) [Review]. *Online Information Review*, 41(4), 454-470. <https://doi.org/10.1108/OIR-05-2017-0142>
452. Du, J., Zhang, J., Castro-Lacouture, D., & Hu, Y. (2023). Lean manufacturing applications in prefabricated construction projects [Review]. *Automation in Construction*, 150, Article 104790. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2023.104790>
453. Duan, Z., Huang, Q., & Zhang, Q. (2022). Life cycle assessment of mass timber construction: A review [Review]. *Building and Environment*, 221, Article 109320. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2022.109320>
454. Duc, M. (2021). Searching for over-research in large bibliometric databases. Exploratory proposals starting from an Arctic case study [Article]. *Annales de Geographie*, 2021(742), 71-98. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85123174968&partnerID=40&md5=559f3682183a328e1a03fae6bca10ec>

455. Duc, M. (2022). When over-researchedness is invisibilised in bibliographic databases: Insights from a case study about the Arctic region. In *Over Researched Places: Towards a Critical and Reflexive Approach* (pp. 111-132). Taylor and Francis. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003099291-9>
456. Dung, T. M., Nga, N. T., & Thanh, L. T. (2023). Interdisciplinary education in the context of protection of water resources: A case study in Vietnam [Article]. *Journal of Education and e-Learning Research*, 10(3), 569-577. <https://doi.org/10.20448/jeelr.v10i3.4986>
457. Duque-Urbe, V., Sarache, W., & Gutiérrez, E. V. (2019). Sustainable supply chain management practices and sustainable performance in hospitals: A systematic review and integrative framework [Review]. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 11(21), Article 5949. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11215949>
458. Dwekat, A., Seguí-Mas, E., Zaid, M. A. A., & Tormo-Carbó, G. (2022). Corporate governance and corporate social responsibility: mapping the most critical drivers in the board academic literature [Review]. *Meditari Accountancy Research*, 30(6), 1705-1739. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MEDAR-01-2021-1155>
459. Eaidgah, Y., Abdekhodae, A., Najmi, M., & Arab Maki, A. (2018). Holistic performance management of virtual teams in third-party logistics environments [Review]. *Team Performance Management*, 24(3-4), 186-202. <https://doi.org/10.1108/TPM-05-2017-0020>
460. Earl, C., Johnson, A., Yelapaala, K., & Good, T. (2011). Making Project Team Recommendations from Online Information Sources.
461. Ebrahim, N. A., Ahmed, S., Abdul Rashid, S. H., & Taha, Z. (2010). Virtual R&D teams: A potential growth of education-industry collaboration.
462. Ebrahim, N. A., Ahmed, S., Rashid, S. H. A., Wazed, M. A., & Taha, Z. (2012). Virtual collaborative R&D teams in Malaysia manufacturing SMEs. In (Vol. 433-440, pp. 1653-1659).
463. Ebrahim, N. A., Salehi, H., Embi, M. A., Danaee, M., Mohammadjafari, M., Zavvari, A., Shakiba, M., & Shahbazi-Moghadam, M. (2014). Equality of Google scholar with web of science citations: Case of Malaysian engineering highly cited papers [Article]. *Modern Applied Science*, 8(5), 63-69. <https://doi.org/10.5539/mas.v8n5p63>
464. Ebrahim, N. A., Salehi, H., Embi, M. A., Tanha, F. H., Gholizadeh, H., & Motahar, S. M. (2014). Visibility and citation impact [Article]. *International Education Studies*, 7(4), 120-125. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ies.v7n4p120>
465. Ebrahim, N. A., Salehi, H., Embi, M. A., Tanha, F. H., Gholizadeh, H., Motahar, S. M., & Ordi, A. (2013). Effective strategies for increasing citation frequency [Article]. *International Education Studies*, 6(11), 93-99. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ies.v6n11p93>
466. Ebrahim, S. A., Ashtari, A., Pedram, M. Z., Ebrahim, N. A., & Sanati-Nezhad, A. (2020). Publication trends in exosomes nanoparticles for cancer detection [Article]. *International Journal of Nanomedicine*, 15, 4453-4470. <https://doi.org/10.2147/IJN.S247210>
467. Ebrahim, S. A., Poshtan, J., Jamali, S. M., & Ebrahim, N. A. (2020). Quantitative and Qualitative Analysis of Time-Series Classification Using Deep Learning [Article]. *IEEE Access*, 8, 90202-90215, Article 9090138. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2020.2993538>
468. Ebrahimi, S., Dehghan, M., & Jowkar, A. (2017). Evaluation of predictive indicators of scientific impact to increase the citations of articles in scientific journals [Article]. *Iranian Journal of Information Processing Management*, 32(3), 661-693. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85020779807&partnerID=40&md5=f7ec352b24914232ac340d785da2674d>
469. Ebrahimi, S., Mehrad, J., Setareh, F., & Hosseinchari, M. (2016). Path analysis of the relationship between visibility and citation: the mediating roles of save, discussion, and recommendation metrics [Article]. *Scientometrics*, 109(3), 1497-1510. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-016-2130-z>

470. Ebrahimi, S., Setareh, F., & HosseinChari, M. (2016). Assessing the relationship between the alternative metrics of visibility and social bookmarking with citation index in PLOS altmetrics [Article]. *Iranian Journal of Information Processing Management*, 31(3), 845-864 and xvii. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84973885526&partnerID=40&md5=c77e410fae9c2a98d235f2bc598121f0>
471. Eduljee, N. B., Chakravarty, R., Croteau, K., & Murphy, L. (2022). Understanding Research Trends in HyFlex (hybrid flexible) Instruction Model: A Scientometric Approach [Article]. *International Journal of Instruction*, 15(4), 935-954. <https://doi.org/10.29333/iji.2022.15450a>
472. Eichler, G. M., & Schwarz, E. J. (2019). What sustainable development goals do social innovations address? A systematic review and content analysis of social innovation literature [Article]. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 11(2), Article 522. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11020522>
473. Eisenberg, J., & DiTomaso, N. (2021). Structural decisions about configuration, assignments, and geographical distribution in teams: Influences on team communications and trust [Article]. *Human Resource Management Review*, 31(2), Article 100739. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hrmr.2019.100739>
474. Eisenberg, J., Post, C., & DiTomaso, N. (2019). Team Dispersion and Performance: The Role of Team Communication and Transformational Leadership [Article]. *Small Group Research*, 50(3), 348-380. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1046496419827376>
475. Ekundayo, T. C., Orimoloye, I. R., Ololade, O. O., & Okoh, A. I. (2021). Prioritization of health emergency research and disaster preparedness: A systematic assessment of the coronavirus disease 2019 pandemic. In *Data Science for COVID-19: Volume 2: Societal and Medical Perspectives* (pp. 465-486). Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-323-90769-9.00033-5>
476. El Badawi El Najjar, R., Blanco, E., Pourroy, F., Prudhomme, G., & Maussang-Detaille, N. (2015). Proposal of a framework for characterizing virtual collectives in the engineering design field.
477. El Khaled, D., Novas, N., Gazquez, J. A., & Manzano-Agugliaro, F. (2018). Dielectric and bioimpedance research studies: A scientometric approach using the scopus database [Review]. *Publications*, 6(1), Article 6. <https://doi.org/10.3390/publications6010006>
478. Elaheh, F., Md Nor, M., Abbas, G. B., Nader, A. E., & Nasrin, M. (2018). Five decades of scientific development on "attachment theory": Trends and future landscape [Article]. *Pertanika Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*, 26(3), 2145-2160. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85054127169&partnerID=40&md5=39457bf5a95724366c86f70cdc0220d5>
479. Elaish, M. M., Hussein, M. H., & Hwang, G. J. (2023). Critical research trends of mobile technology-supported English language learning: A review of the top 100 highly cited articles [Article]. *Education and Information Technologies*, 28(5), 4849-4874. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-022-11352-6>
480. Elaish, M. M., Shuib, L., Ghani, N. A., Mujtaba, G., & Ebrahim, N. A. (2019). A bibliometric analysis of m-learning from topic inception to 2015 [Article]. *International Journal of Mobile Learning and Organisation*, 13(1), 91-112. <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJMLO.2019.096470>
481. Elaish, M. M., Shuib, L., Hwang, G. J., Ghani, N. A., Yadegaridehkordi, E., & Zainuddin, S. Z. (2023). Mobile English language learning: a systematic review of group size, duration, and assessment methods [Review]. *Computer Assisted Language Learning*, 36(3), 430-456. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09588221.2021.1931341>
482. El-Alfy, E. S. M., & Mohammed, S. A. (2020). A review of machine learning for big data analytics: bibliometric approach [Article]. *Technology Analysis and Strategic Management*, 32(8), 984-1005. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09537325.2020.1732912>

483. Eleonora, Z., Tetiana, R., Ihor, R., Nataliia, P., & Anastasiia, M. (2023). Analysis of digital marketing trends in 2022-2023 of the global fuel and energy complex (experience for Ukraine) [Article]. *Quality - Access to Success*, 24(192), 360-367. <https://doi.org/10.47750/QAS/24.192.43>
484. Elgaard Jensen, T., Kleberg Hansen, A. K., Ulijaszek, S., Munk, A. K., Madsen, A. K., Hillersdal, L., & Jespersen, A. P. (2019). Identifying notions of environment in obesity research using a mixed-methods approach [Review]. *Obesity Reviews*, 20(4), 621-630. <https://doi.org/10.1111/obr.12807>
485. ElKattan, A. G., Gavilan, D., Elsharnouby, M. H., & Mahran, A. F. A. (2023). Mapping sharing economy themes: science mapping, topic modeling, and research agenda [Article]. *Journal of Marketing Analytics*. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41270-023-00238-2>
486. Elliot, T., Almenar, J. B., Niza, S., Proença, V., & Rugani, B. (2019). Pathways to modelling ecosystem services within an urban metabolism framework [Review]. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 11(10), Article 2766. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11102766>
487. Elomari, Y., Norouzi, M., Marín-Genescà, M., Fernández, A., & Boer, D. (2022). Integration of Solar Photovoltaic Systems into Power Networks: A Scientific Evolution Analysis [Review]. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 14(15), Article 9249. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14159249>
488. ElSayary, A. (2021). Transdisciplinary STEAM Curriculum Design and Authentic Assessment in Online Learning: A Model of Cognitive, Psychomotor, and Affective Domains [Article]. *Journal of Turkish Science Education*, 18(3), 493-511. <https://doi.org/10.36681/tused.2021.86>
489. Elshaboury, N., Al-Sakkaf, A., Abdelkader, E. M., & Alfalah, G. (2022). Construction and Demolition Waste Management Research: A Science Mapping Analysis [Review]. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(8), Article 4496. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph19084496>
490. Emami, A., & Farzane, M. K. (2022). A bibliometric analysis of entrepreneurship research in Iran [Article]. *International Journal of Technological Learning, Innovation and Development*, 14(1-2), 134-152. <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJTLID.2022.121482>
491. Endrerud, O. E. V., & Liyanage, J. P. (2015). Collaborative Operating Environments in the Offshore Petroleum Sector: Solutions for Added Value in B2B Relationships. In W. B. Lee, B. Choi, L. Ma, & J. Mathew (Eds.), (pp. 253-263): Springer Science and Business Media Deutschland GmbH.
492. Ergu, D., & Peng, Y. (2014). A framework for SaaS software packages evaluation and selection with virtual team and BOCR of analytic network process [Article]. *Journal of Supercomputing*, 67(1), 219-238. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11227-013-0995-7>
493. Escuadra, C. J., Magallanes, K., Lee, S., & Chung, J. Y. (2023). Systematic analysis on school violence and bullying using data mining [Article]. *Children and Youth Services Review*, 150, Article 107020. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.childyouth.2023.107020>
494. Esparragoza, I. E., Farak, S. L., Ocampo, J. R., Segovia, J. N., Viganò, R., Duque-Rivera, J., & Rodriguez, C. A. (2015). Assessment of students' interactions in multinational collaborative design projects [Article]. *International Journal of Engineering Education*, 31(5), 1255-1269. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84940384671&partnerID=40&md5=bf7e052f5938416aa8a37d61a5be8997>
495. Espegren, Y., & Hugosson, M. (2023). HR analytics-as-practice: a systematic literature review [Article]. *Journal of Organizational Effectiveness*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JOEPP-11-2022-0345>
496. Esteves, S., Martinez-Perez, C., Alvarez-Peregrina, C., & Sánchez-Tena, M. Á. (2023). Citation Network Analysis on the Influence of Vision on Academic Performance [Article]. *Children*, 10(3), Article 591. <https://doi.org/10.3390/children10030591>
497. Etemadifard, S. M., Khaniki, H., Baghestan, A. G., & Akhtari-Zavare, M. (2018). Iran's social sciences issues in web of science (WoS): Who said what? [Article]. *Pertanika Journal of Social*

- Sciences and Humanities, 26(2), 1159-1174. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85049344875&partnerID=40&md5=2da02a5583d84b491fc231585810d679>
498. Ettlíe, J. E., Tucci, C., & Gianiodis, P. T. (2017). Trust, integrated information technology and new product success [Article]. *European Journal of Innovation Management*, 20(3), 406-427. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EJIM-12-2015-0128>
499. Eze, M. E., Okeji, C. C., & Bosah, G. E. (2019). Self-archiving options on social networks: a review of options [Article]. *Library Hi Tech News*, 36(1), 9-12. <https://doi.org/10.1108/LHTN-12-2017-0091>
500. Ezema, I. J., & Onyancha, O. B. (2017). Citation impact of health and medical journals in Africa: Does open accessibility matter? [Article]. *Electronic Library*, 35(5), 934-952. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EL-11-2016-0245>
501. Fabrizio, C. M., Kaczam, F., de Moura, G. L., da Silva, L. S. C. V., da Silva, W. V., & da Veiga, C. P. (2022). Competitive advantage and dynamic capability in small and medium-sized enterprises: a systematic literature review and future research directions [Review]. *Review of Managerial Science*, 16(3), 617-648. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11846-021-00459-8>
502. Fagan, J. C., & Willey, M. (2018). The discoverability of award-winning undergraduate research in history: Implications for academic libraries [Article]. *College and Undergraduate Libraries*, 25(2), 164-186. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10691316.2018.1456994>
503. Fagerholm, F., Sanchez Guinea, A., Borenstein, J., & Munch, J. (2014). Onboarding in open source projects [Article]. *IEEE Software*, 31(6), 54-61, Article 6879055. <https://doi.org/10.1109/MS.2014.107>
504. Fahimifar, S., Mousavi, K., Mozaffari, F., & Ausloos, M. (2023). Identification of the most important external features of highly cited scholarly papers through 3 (i.e., Ridge, Lasso, and Boruta) feature selection data mining methods: Identification of the most important external features of highly cited scholarly papers through 3 (i.e., Ridge, Lasso, and Boruta) feature selection data mining methods [Article]. *Quality and Quantity*, 57(4), 3685-3712. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11135-022-01480-z>
505. Fairclough, R., & Thelwall, M. (2015). National research impact indicators from Mendeley readers [Article]. *Journal of Informetrics*, 9(4), 845-859. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joi.2015.08.003>
506. Fajardo, L. M. S., Bom-Camargo, Y. I., Calderón, C. L. F., & Ramírez, V. H. M. (2021). Public Social Responsibility to contribute to the consolidation of the Sustainable Development Goals [Article]. *Juridicas CUC*, 17(1), 211-252. <https://doi.org/10.17981/juridcuc.17.1.2021.08>
507. Fan, T. T., Chen, Y. C., Wu, Y. J., Liang, H. H., Bai, Y., Ma, F. Q., Wang, H. C., Yang, Y. P., & Mo, Q. L. (2022). Knowledge Domain and Emerging Trends of Chinese Medicine in Management of Pediatric Asthma: A Scientometric Study [Article]. *Chinese Journal of Integrative Medicine*, 28(2), 162-167. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11655-021-3347-0>
508. Fang, B., Yu, J., Chen, Z., Osman, A. I., Farghali, M., Ihara, I., Hamza, E. H., Rooney, D. W., & Yap, P. S. (2023). Artificial intelligence for waste management in smart cities: a review [Review]. *Environmental Chemistry Letters*, 21(4), 1959-1989. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10311-023-01604-3>
509. Faqih, F., & Zayed, T. (2021). A comparative review of building component rating systems [Review]. *Journal of Building Engineering*, 33, Article 101588. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.job.2020.101588>
510. Faqih, F., Zayed, T., & Alfalah, G. (2022). Technology-based multi-tiered building diagnosis framework [Article]. *International Journal of Building Pathology and Adaptation*, 40(1), 101-133. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJBPA-10-2020-0088>

511. Faqih, F., Zayed, T., & Soliman, E. (2020). Factors and defects analysis of physical and environmental condition of buildings [Article]. *Journal of Building Pathology and Rehabilitation*, 5(1), Article 19. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41024-020-00084-0>
512. Faraz, A., Mounsef, J., Raza, A., & Willis, S. (2022). Child Safety and Protection in the Online Gaming Ecosystem [Article]. *IEEE Access*, 10, 115895-115913. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2022.3218415>
513. Farghadani, R., Rajarajeswaran, J., Mohd Hashim, N. B., Abdulla, M. A., & Muniandy, S. (2017). A novel β -diiminato manganese(III) complex as the promising anticancer agent induces G0/G1 cell cycle arrest and triggers apoptosis via mitochondrial-dependent pathways in MCF-7 and MDA-MB-231 human breast cancer cells [Article]. *RSC Advances*, 7(39), 24387-24398. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c7ra02478a>
514. Farmanbar, N., Mohseni, S., & Darroudi, M. (2022). Green synthesis of chitosan-coated magnetic nanoparticles for drug delivery of oxaliplatin and irinotecan against colorectal cancer cells [Article]. *Polymer Bulletin*, 79(12), 10595-10613. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00289-021-04066-1>
515. Farooq, R. (2022). A review of knowledge management research in the past three decades: a bibliometric analysis [Article]. *VINE Journal of Information and Knowledge Management Systems*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/VJIKMS-08-2021-0169>
516. Farooq, R. (2023). Mapping the field of knowledge management: a bibliometric analysis using R [Review]. *VINE Journal of Information and Knowledge Management Systems*, 53(6), 1178-1206. <https://doi.org/10.1108/VJIKMS-06-2021-0089>
517. Fatin, N. N., & Sudira, P. (2023). The integrated PjBL with STEM approach in the EV-green electric car project.
518. Fauzan, & Jahja, A. S. (2021). INTELLECTUAL DYNAMICS OF GOOD GOVERNANCE STUDIES: A BIBLIOMETRIC ANALYSIS [Article]. *Journal of Indonesian Economy and Business*, 36(2), 155-178. <https://doi.org/10.22146/jieb.v36i2.1411>
519. Fayad, A. A. S., Binti Mohd Ariff, A. H., Ooi, S. C., Ahmi, A., & Khatib, S. F. A. (2023). Towards concise reporting through integrated reporting: a bibliometric review [Review]. *Meditari Accountancy Research*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MEDAR-10-2021-1470>
520. Feliciano, D. (2019). A review on the contribution of crop diversification to Sustainable Development Goal 1 “No poverty” in different world regions [Review]. *Sustainable Development*, 27(4), 795-808. <https://doi.org/10.1002/sd.1923>
521. Felsberger, A., & Reiner, G. (2020). Sustainable industry 4.0 in production and operations management: A systematic literature review [Article]. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 12(19), 1-39, Article 7982. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12197982>
522. Fernandez, V., Guillot, C., & Marraud, L. (2014). What about skills, tactics and practices of remote workers? Evidence and analyses [Article]. *Revue Francaise de Gestion*, 238(1), 101-118. <https://doi.org/10.3166/rfg.238.101-118>
523. Fernández-Bedoya, V. H., Meneses-La-Riva, M. E., & Suvo-Vega, J. A. (2021). Ecotourism in Times of Covid-19: A Systematic Review from the Five Continents on How This Activity is Being Carried out and What Proposals They Have for the near Future [Review]. *Academic Journal of Interdisciplinary Studies*, 10(6), 1-10. <https://doi.org/10.36941/ajis-2021-0148>
524. Ferraz, R. M., da Veiga, C. P., da Veiga, C. R. P., Furquim, T. S. G., & da Silva, W. V. (2023). After-Sales Attributes in E-Commerce: A Systematic Literature Review and Future Research Agenda [Review]. *Journal of Theoretical and Applied Electronic Commerce Research*, 18(1), 475-500. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jtaer18010025>
525. Ferreira, A. M., Marchezini, V., Mendes, T. S. G., Trejo-Rangel, M. A., & Iwama, A. Y. (2023). A Systematic Review of Forensic Approaches to Disasters: Gaps and Challenges [Article].

International Journal of Disaster Risk Science, 14(5), 722-735. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13753-023-00515-9>

526. Ferreira, K. A., Toledo, M. L., & Rodrigues, L. F. (2021). Postponement practices in the Brazilian Southeast wine sector [Article]. *International Journal of Logistics Management*, 32(1), 6-23. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJLM-10-2019-0292>
527. Ferreira, P. G. S., Pinheiro De Lima, E., & Gouvêa Da Costa, S. E. (2012). Virtual team's performance measurement revisited.
528. Fetrati, M. A., Hansen, D., & Akhavan, P. (2022). How to manage creativity in organizations: Connecting the literature on organizational creativity through bibliometric research [Article]. *Technovation*, 115, Article 102473. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.technovation.2022.102473>
529. Figueroa-Rodríguez, K. A., Hernández-Rosas, F., Figueroa-Sandoval, B., Velasco-Velasco, J., & Rivera, N. A. (2019). What has been the focus of sugarcane research? A bibliometric overview [Review]. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 16(18), Article 3326. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph16183326>
530. Filippov, D. M., Kazak, A. N., Samokhvalov, D. V., & Shamaeva, N. P. (2020). Modeling the construction of an individual learning path.
531. Fitriastuti, L. I., Sujoko, S., Herawan, T., & Vemberi, Y. (2019). Knowledge management system usage and organization learning: Recent trends and open problems [Article]. *Journal of Advanced Research in Law and Economics*, 10(6), 1832-1849. [https://doi.org/10.14505/jarle.v10.6\(44\).26](https://doi.org/10.14505/jarle.v10.6(44).26)
532. Flores-Sosa, M., Leon-Castro, E., Mendoza-Carvajal, B., & Aviles-Ochoa, E. (2023). 45 Years of the Exchange Rate Study: A Bibliometric Analysis [Article]. *Review of Development Finance*, 13(1), 42-57. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85163303421&partnerID=40&md5=f27a9bf7015b0c8f6645022e3ac65978>
533. Flynn, R. M., Kleinknecht, E., Ricker, A. A., & Blumberg, F. C. (2021). A narrative review of methods used to examine digital gaming impacts on learning and cognition during middle childhood [Review]. *International Journal of Child-Computer Interaction*, 30, Article 100325. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijcci.2021.100325>
534. Fonseca, J. (2015). Beyond the impact factor: The scientific article and dissemination of knowledge in medicine [Editorial]. *Revista Portuguesa de Imunoalergologia*, 23(2), 67-69. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84948758985&partnerID=40&md5=df4ee476c8000539843d2d62fc84dcc7>
535. Francey, A., & Mettler, T. (2021). The effects of open government data: Some stylised facts [Article]. *Information Polity*, 26(3), 273-288. <https://doi.org/10.3233/IP-200281>
536. French, R. B., & Fagan, J. C. (2019). The Visibility of Authority Records, Researcher Identifiers, Academic Social Networking Profiles, and Related Faculty Publications in Search Engine Results [Article]. *Journal of Web Librarianship*, 13(2), 156-197. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19322909.2019.1591324>
537. Freschi, G., Menegatto, M., & Zamperini, A. (2023). How Can Psychology Contribute to Climate Change Governance? A Systematic Review [Review]. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 15(19), Article 14273. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su151914273>
538. Friedrich, R. (2017). The virtual team maturity model: Performance improvement of virtual teams [Book]. Springer Fachmedien Wiesbaden. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-658-19771-1>
539. Fu, H., Yu, B., Wang, H., Tong, H., Jiang, L., Zhang, Y., Meng, G., Sun, M., & Lin, J. (2022). Knowledge domain and hotspots concerning photosensitive hydrogels for tissue engineering applications: A bibliometric and visualized analysis (1996-2022) [Article]. *Frontiers in Bioengineering and Biotechnology*, 10, Article 1067111. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fbioe.2022.1067111>

540. Fu, J., Song, W., Hao, Z., Fan, M., & Li, Y. (2023). Research trends and hotspots of exosomes in respiratory diseases [Article]. *Medicine (United States)*, 102(39), E35381. <https://doi.org/10.1097/MD.00000000000035381>
541. Fung, H. W., Chien, W. T., Lam, S. K. K., & Ross, C. A. (2023). The Relationship Between Dissociation and Complex Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder: A Scoping Review [Article]. *Trauma, Violence, and Abuse*, 24(5), 2966-2982. <https://doi.org/10.1177/15248380221120835>
542. Furlong, C., Guthrie, L., De Silva, S., & Considine, R. (2015). Analysing the terminology of integration in the water management field [Article]. *Water Policy*, 17(1), 46-60. <https://doi.org/10.2166/wp.2014.185>
543. Furstenau, L. B., Leivas, P., Sott, M. K., Dohan, M. S., López-Robles, J. R., Cobo, M. J., Bragazzi, N. L., & Choo, K. K. R. (2023). Big data in healthcare: Conceptual network structure, key challenges and opportunities [Review]. *Digital Communications and Networks*, 9(4), 856-868. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dcan.2023.03.005>
544. Furstenau, L. B., Rabaioli, B., Sott, M. K., Cossul, D., Bender, M. S., Farina, E. M. J. M., Filho, F. N. B., Severo, P. P., Dohan, M. S., & Bragazzi, N. L. (2021). A bibliometric network analysis of coronavirus during the first eight months of COVID-19 in 2020 [Article]. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(3), 1-24, Article 952. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18030952>
545. Furstenau, L. B., Rodrigues, Y. P. R., Sott, M. K., Leivas, P., Dohan, M. S., López-Robles, J. R., Cobo, M. J., Bragazzi, N. L., & Choo, K. K. R. (2023). Internet of things: Conceptual network structure, main challenges and future directions [Review]. *Digital Communications and Networks*, 9(3), 677-687. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dcan.2022.04.027>
546. Galetsi, P., & Katsaliaki, K. (2020). Big data analytics in health: an overview and bibliometric study of research activity [Review]. *Health Information and Libraries Journal*, 37(1), 5-25. <https://doi.org/10.1111/hir.12286>
547. Galetsi, P., Katsaliaki, K., & Kumar, S. (2019). Values, challenges and future directions of big data analytics in healthcare: A systematic review [Review]. *Social Science and Medicine*, 241, Article 112533. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2019.112533>
548. Galli, C., & Guizzardi, S. (2020). Change in format, register and narration style in the biomedical literature: A 1948 example [Article]. *Publications*, 8(1), Article 10. <https://doi.org/10.3390/publications8010010>
549. Gallo, T., Cagnetti, C., Silvestri, C., & Ruggieri, A. (2021). Industry 4.0 tools in lean production: A systematic literature review.
550. Gamarra, M. P., & Giroto, M. (2022). Ethical behavior in leadership: a bibliometric review of the last three decades [Article]. *Ethics and Behavior*, 32(2), 124-146. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10508422.2020.1863799>
551. Gan, Y., Liu, J., Zhao, Y., Zhu, M., & Wang, G. (2024). Inverted U-Shaped relationship between team size and citation impact: Mediating role of responsibility diffusion [Article]. *Accountability in Research*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08989621.2023.2300255>
552. Gañán, P., Barajas, J., Zuluaga, R., Castro, C., Marín, D., Tercjak, A., & Builes, D. H. (2023). The Evolution and Future Trends of Unsaturated Polyester Biocomposites: A Bibliometric Analysis [Review]. *Polymers*, 15(13), Article 2970. <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym15132970>
553. Gandhi, A., Sensuse, D. I., & Suchayo, Y. G. (2019). Knowledge Sharing Model for Competitive Ecosystem on Gig Economy.
554. Gannon, W. J. F., Jones, D. R., & Dunnill, C. W. (2019). Enhanced lifetime cathode for alkaline electrolysis using standard commercial titanium nitride coatings [Article]. *Processes*, 7(2), Article 112. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pr7020112>

555. Gao, T., Chai, Y., & Liu, Y. (2017). A review of knowledge management and future research trend.
556. Gao, T., Tao, Y., Wang, Q., Liu, J., Du, Z., Xing, Y., Chen, F., & Mei, J. (2023). A bibliometric analysis of insomnia in adolescent [Article]. *Frontiers in Psychiatry*, 14, Article 1246808. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsy.2023.1246808>
557. Gao, W., Huang, J., Qiu, Q., Shrestha, A., Yuan, C., Anand, S., Wang, G., & Wang, G. (2023). Conservation and Management of Protected Areas in China and India: A Literature Review (1990–2021) [Review]. *Climate*, 11(1), Article 22. <https://doi.org/10.3390/cli11010022>
558. Gao, Y., Wu, Q., & Zhu, L. (2020). Merging the citations received by arXiv-deposited e-prints and their corresponding published journal articles: Problems and perspectives [Article]. *Information Processing and Management*, 57(5), Article 102267. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ipm.2020.102267>
559. Garbade, P. J. P., Onno Omta, S. W. F., & Fortuin, F. T. J. M. (2013). Exploring the characteristics of innovation alliances of dutch biotechnology SMEs and their policy implications [Article]. *Bio-based and Applied Economics*, 2(1), 91-111. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85017334618&partnerID=40&md5=45e7869e68e358852d127ad858ac13d8>
560. Garcia-Chitiva, M. D. P., & Correa, J. C. (2023). Soft skills centrality in graduate studies offerings [Article]. *Studies in Higher Education*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03075079.2023.2254799>
561. Garcia-Iruela, M., Fonseca, M. J., Hijon-Neira, R., & Chambel, T. (2020). Gamification and computer science students' activity [Article]. *IEEE Access*, 8, 96829-96836, Article 9099268. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2020.2997038>
562. García-Martínez, I., Gutiérrez Cáceres, R., Luque de la Rosa, A., & León, S. P. (2021). Analysing educational interventions with gifted students. Systematic review [Review]. *Children*, 8(5), Article 365. <https://doi.org/10.3390/children8050365>
563. Garousi, V., & Fernandes, J. M. (2016). Highly-cited papers in software engineering: The top-100 [Article]. *Information and Software Technology*, 71, 108-128. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.infsof.2015.11.003>
564. Garousi, V., & Fernandes, J. M. (2017). Quantity versus impact of software engineering papers: a quantitative study [Article]. *Scientometrics*, 112(2), 963-1006. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-017-2419-6>
565. Garousi, V., & Mäntylä, M. V. (2016). Citations, research topics and active countries in software engineering: A bibliometrics study [Review]. *Computer Science Review*, 19, 56-77. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cosrev.2015.12.002>
566. Garro Abarca, V. M., Palos-Sanchez, P. R., & Rus-Arias, E. (2020). Working in virtual teams: A systematic literature review and a bibliometric analysis [Review]. *IEEE Access*, 8, 168923-168940. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2020.3023546>
567. Garro-Abarca, V., Palos-Sanchez, P., & Aguayo-Camacho, M. (2021). Virtual Teams in Times of Pandemic: Factors That Influence Performance [Article]. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12, Article 624637. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.624637>
568. Gasparyan, A. Y., Nurmashev, B., Yessirkepov, M., Udovik, E. E., Baryshnikov, A. A., & Kitas, G. D. (2017). The journal impact factor: Moving toward an alternative and combined scientometric approach [Note]. *Journal of Korean Medical Science*, 32(2), 173-179. <https://doi.org/10.3346/jkms.2017.32.2.173>
569. Gaviria-Marin, M., Merigó, J. M., & Baier-Fuentes, H. (2019). Knowledge management: A global examination based on bibliometric analysis [Article]. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 140, 194-220. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2018.07.006>

570. Geisler, E. (2022). *Beyond Business Analytics: The Foundations of Behavioral Perspective Theory* [Book]. Springer International Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-43718-3>
571. Gelzer, E. R., Laforge, M. P., Becker, J. A., Hough, N. P., Lambert, M. S., Poulin, M. P., Thomas-Kuzilik, R., Verzuh, T. L., & Merkle, J. A. (2022). Getting cited early: influence of visibility strategies, structure, and focal system on early citation rates [Article]. *Journal of Wildlife Management*, 86(4), Article e22214. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jwmg.22214>
572. Gemente, G. B., da Silva, A. L., da Silva, E. M., & Costa, F. H. (2024). Pressures, power relationships and governance mechanisms: a multi-tier supply chain approach [Review]. *International Journal of Logistics Management*, 35(1), 1-28. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJLM-05-2021-0291>
573. Ghabban, F., Selamat, A., & Ibrahim, R. (2016). Factors affect scholarly publication productivity among academic staff at Taibah University [Article]. *International Journal of Control Theory and Applications*, 9(30), 185-194. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85004001475&partnerID=40&md5=a8042927ed4e533f43a8d5ba1dd651df>
574. Ghabban, F., Selamat, A., & Ibrahim, R. (2018). New model for encouraging academic staff in Saudi universities to use IT for knowledge sharing to improve scholarly publication performance [Article]. *Technology in Society*, 55, 92-99. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techsoc.2018.07.001>
575. Ghabban, F., Selamat, A., Ibrahim, R., Krejcar, O., Maresova, P., & Herrera-Viedma, E. (2019). The influence of personal and organizational factors on researchers' attitudes towards sustainable research productivity in Saudi universities [Article]. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 11(17), Article 4804. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11174804>
576. Ghaleb, H., Alhajlah, H. H., Bin Abdullah, A. A., Kassem, M. A., & Al-Sharafi, M. A. (2022). A Scientometric Analysis and Systematic Literature Review for Construction Project Complexity [Article]. *Buildings*, 12(4), Article 482. <https://doi.org/10.3390/buildings12040482>
577. Ghanbari Baghestan, A., Khaniki, H., Kalantari, A., Akhtari-Zavare, M., Farahmand, E., Tamam, E., Ebrahim, N. A., Sabani, H., & Danaee, M. (2019). A Crisis in “Open Access”: Should Communication Scholarly Outputs Take 77 Years to Become Open Access? [Article]. *SAGE Open*, 9(3). <https://doi.org/10.1177/2158244019871044>
578. Ghane, M. R., & Kumarsi, S. (2018). Four decades of scientific activity in Iran from the perspective of the conference proceedings, highly cited and hot papers, and open access papers, in the light of the law of economic, social, and cultural development plan of Iran [Article]. *Iranian Journal of Information Processing Management*, 34(1), 27-56. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85064215697&partnerID=40&md5=ef821298f263842bbad59d903c4b2910>
579. Ghani, N. A., Teo, P. C., Ho, T. C. F., Choo, L. S., Kelana, B. W. Y., Adam, S., & Ramliy, M. K. (2022). Bibliometric Analysis of Global Research Trends on Higher Education Internationalization Using Scopus Database: Towards Sustainability of Higher Education Institutions [Article]. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 14(14), Article 8810. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14148810>
580. Gheni, A. Y., Jabar, M. A., Jusoh, Y. Y., Mohd Ali, N., & Abdullah, R. H. (2016). Factors for communication technologies selection within virtual software teams.
581. Ghiringhelli, C., & Lazazzara, A. (2016). Perceived training needs for effective virtual teams: An exploratory study [Book Chapter]. *Lecture Notes in Information Systems and Organisation*, 19, 21-35. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-38974-5_3
582. Gholampour, S., Gholampour, B., & Noruzi, A. (2022). Highly Cited Papers in Sport Sciences: Identification and Conceptual Analysis [Article]. *International Journal of Information Science and Management*, 20(2), 305-324. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85123519463&partnerID=40&md5=c694edda21bfbe82f6099b65df542a6c>

583. Ghorbani, Z., Kargaran, S., Saberi, A., Haghghinasab, M., Jamali, S. M., & Ale Ebrahim, N. (2022). Trends and patterns in digital marketing research: bibliometric analysis [Article]. *Journal of Marketing Analytics*, 10(2), 158-172. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41270-021-00116-9>
584. Giannetta, N., Dionisi, S., Tonello, M., Di Simone, E., & Di Muzio, M. (2022). A Worldwide Bibliometric Analysis of Published Literature on Medication Errors [Article]. *Journal of Patient Safety*, 18(3), 201-209. <https://doi.org/10.1097/PTS.0000000000000894>
585. Gierczyk, M., & Hornby, G. (2023). Summer learning loss: review of research and implications for remediation of post-pandemic learning loss [Article]. *Preventing School Failure*, 67(3), 132-140. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1045988X.2023.2204823>
586. Giffoni, F., Salini, S., & Sirtori, E. (2018). Evaluating business support measures: The Bayesian Network approach [Article]. *Evaluation*, 24(2), 133-152. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1356389018767179>
587. Gil, R. M., Gutiérrez-Ujaque, D., & Teixidó, M. (2023). Analyzing the Metaverse: Computer Games, Blockchain, and 21st-Century Challenge [Article]. *International Journal of Human-Computer Interaction*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10447318.2023.2290380>
588. Gill, J., Okere, I., HaddadPajouh, H., & Dehghantanha, A. (2018). Mobile forensics: A bibliometric analysis. In *Advances in Information Security* (Vol. 70, pp. 297-310): Springer New York LLC.
589. Gilli, K., Veglio, V., Gunkel, M., & Taras, V. (2022). In search of the Holy Grail in global virtual teams: The mediating role of satisfaction on performance outcomes [Article]. *Journal of Business Research*, 146, 325-337. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2022.03.056>
590. Gil-Marín, M., Vega-Muñoz, A., Contreras-Barraza, N., Salazar-Sepúlveda, G., Vera-Ruiz, S., & Losada, A. V. (2022). Sustainability Accounting Studies: A Metasynthesis [Review]. *Sustainability* (Switzerland), 14(15), Article 9533. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14159533>
591. Glazkova, A., & Morozov, D. (2023). Multi-task fine-tuning for generating keyphrases in a scientific domain.
592. Glazkova, A. V., & Morozov, D. A. (2023). Applying Transformer-Based Text Summarization for Keyphrase Generation [Article]. *Lobachevskii Journal of Mathematics*, 44(1), 123-136. <https://doi.org/10.1134/S1995080223010134>
593. Gökmen, A. (2012). Virtual business operations, e-commerce & its significance and the case of Turkey: Current situation and its potential [Article]. *Electronic Commerce Research*, 12(1), 31-51. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10660-011-9084-2>
594. Goksu, I., Ozkaya, E., & Gunduz, A. (2022). The content analysis and bibliometric mapping of CALL journal [Article]. *Computer Assisted Language Learning*, 35(8), 2018-2048. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09588221.2020.1857409>
595. Goldberg, J., & Howe, S. (2015). Virtual capstone design teams: Preparing for global innovation [Conference Paper]. *International Journal of Engineering Education*, 31(6), 1773-1779. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84959262465&partnerID=40&md5=646b08861dae760e080534402d794315>
596. Gomez, M. J., RUIPEREZ-Valiente, J. A., & Clemente, F. J. G. C. (2023). A Systematic Literature Review of Game-Based Assessment Studies: Trends and Challenges [Article]. *IEEE Transactions on Learning Technologies*, 16(4), 500-515. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TLT.2022.3226661>
597. Gómez, S. A. (2020). Games and Gamification in the Classroom. In *Lecture Notes in Educational Technology* (pp. 101-115): Springer.
598. Gómez-Berbís, J. M., Colomo-Palacios, R., López-Cuadrado, J. L., González-Carrasco, I., & García-Crespo, A. (2011). SEAN: Multi-ontology semantic annotation for highly accurate closed domains [Article]. *International Journal of Physical Sciences*, 6(6), 1440-1451.

<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-79957955344&partnerID=40&md5=85c52289c3b2f06cd332216b4e1d6a15>

599. Gómez-Molina, S., Cano, L. D., Bran-Piedrahita, L., Valencia-Arias, A., & Martínez-Herrera, E. (2019). Research trends in urban health: Results from a bibliometric analysis [Article]. *Revista Geografica Venezolana*, 60(1), 74-91. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85071836543&partnerID=40&md5=953a3f608282db8d189c52d1d9b8da49>
600. Gómez-Trueba Santamaría, P., Arahetes García, A., & García Domonte, A. (2023). Scientometric Analysis of the Relationship between Expenditure on Defence and Economic Growth: Current Situation and Future Perspectives [Article]. *Defence and Peace Economics*, 34(8), 1071-1090. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10242694.2022.2091191>
601. Gonçalves, A. F. A., Dos Santos, J. A., França, L. C. J., Campoe, O. C., Altoé, T. F., & Scolforo, J. R. S. (2021). Use of the process-based models in forest research: A bibliometric review [Review]. *Cerne*, 27(1), Article e-102769. <https://doi.org/10.1590/01047760202127012769>
602. González, M. J. P., Guzmán, M. F., & Chaviano, O. G. (2015). Criteria, classifications and tendencies of bibliometric indicators in the evaluation of the science [Article]. *Revista Cubana de Informacion en Ciencias de la Salud*, 26(3), 290-309. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84939641534&partnerID=40&md5=4b1046fbfc339b5eadb261e79edac3c8>
603. Gonzalez Ronquillo, M., & Angeles Hernandez, J. C. (2017). Antibiotic and synthetic growth promoters in animal diets: Review of impact and analytical methods [Article]. *Food Control*, 72, 255-267. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodcont.2016.03.001>
604. Gonzalez-Alcaide, G., Palacios-Fernandez, S., & Ramos-Rincon, J. M. (2021). Thematic research clusters in very old populations (≥ 80 years): a bibliometric approach [Article]. *BMC Geriatrics*, 21(1), Article 266. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12877-021-02209-7>
605. González-Valiente, C. L., Santos, M. L., & Arencibia-Jorge, R. (2019). Evolution of the Socio-cognitive Structure of Knowledge Management (1986-2015): An Author Co-citation Analysis [Article]. *Journal of Data and Information Science*, 4(2), 36-55. <https://doi.org/10.2478/jdis-2019-0008>
606. González-Zamar, M. D., & Abad-Segura, E. (2021). Emotional creativity in art education: An exploratory analysis and research trends [Article]. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(12), Article 6209. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18126209>
607. González-Zamar, M. D., & Abad-Segura, E. (2021). Visual arts in the university educational ecosystem: Analysis of schools of knowledge [Article]. *Education Sciences*, 11(4), Article 184. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci11040184>
608. Gordillo, A., Barra, E., López-Pernas, S., & Quemada, J. (2021). Development of teacher digital competence in the area of e-safety through educational video games [Article]. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 13(15), Article 8485. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13158485>
609. Gordillo, A., Barra, E., & Quemada, J. (2021). SGAME: An Authoring Tool to Easily Create Educational Video Games by Integrating SCORM-Compliant Learning Objects [Article]. *IEEE Access*, 9, 126414-126430. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3111513>
610. Gordillo, A., Lopez-Fernandez, D., & Tovar, E. (2022). Comparing the Effectiveness of Video-Based Learning and Game-Based Learning Using Teacher-Authored Video Games for Online Software Engineering Education [Article]. *IEEE Transactions on Education*, 65(4), 524-532. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TE.2022.3142688>
611. Gordon, A. (2018). International virtual teams in higher education [Review]. *Tripodos*, 42, 39-58. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85055140527&partnerID=40&md5=dc228606cec3565bab7d522ad51688c9>

612. Goswami, A. K., & Agrawal, R. K. (2018). A reflection on knowledge sharing research: patterns and trends [Article]. *VINE Journal of Information and Knowledge Management Systems*, 48(3), 352-372. <https://doi.org/10.1108/VJIKMS-08-2017-0049>
613. Goswami, A. K., & Agrawal, R. K. (2020). Building intellectual structure of knowledge sharing [Article]. *VINE Journal of Information and Knowledge Management Systems*, 50(1), 136-162. <https://doi.org/10.1108/VJIKMS-03-2019-0036>
614. Gradeci, K., Labonnote, N., Sivertsen, E., & Time, B. (2019). The use of insurance data in the analysis of Surface Water Flood events – A systematic review [Article]. *Journal of Hydrology*, 568, 194-206. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2018.10.060>
615. Gradeci, K., Labonnote, N., Time, B., & Köhler, J. (2017). Mould growth criteria and design avoidance approaches in wood-based materials – A systematic review [Review]. *Construction and Building Materials*, 150, 77-88. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2017.05.204>
616. Graham, P., Nikolova, N., & Sankaran, S. (2020). Tension between Leadership Archetypes: Systematic Review to Inform Construction Research and Practice [Review]. *Journal of Management in Engineering*, 36(1), Article 03119002. [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)ME.1943-5479.0000722](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)ME.1943-5479.0000722)
617. Grančay, M. (2021). What you publish matters: A novel way of measuring research sophistication [Article]. *Journal of Scientometric Research*, 10(1), 47-54. <https://doi.org/10.5530/JSCIRES.10.1.6>
618. Gressgård, L. J. (2011). Virtual team collaboration and innovation in organizations [Article]. *Team Performance Management*, 17(1), 102-119. <https://doi.org/10.1108/13527591111114738>
619. Groff, M. L., Offringa, M., Emdin, A., Mahood, Q., Parkin, P. C., & Cohen, E. (2020). Publication trends of pediatric and adult randomized controlled trials in general medical journals, 2005–2018: A citation analysis [Article]. *Children*, 7(12), Article 293. <https://doi.org/10.3390/children7120293>
620. Gu, M., Ahmad, W., Alaboud, T. M., Zia, A., Akmal, U., Awad, Y. A., & Alabduljabbar, H. (2022). Scientometric Analysis and Research Mapping Knowledge of Coconut Fibers in Concrete [Review]. *Materials*, 15(16), Article 5639. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma15165639>
621. Gu, Z., Meng, F., & Farrukh, M. (2021). Mapping the Research on Knowledge Transfer: A Scientometrics Approach [Article]. *IEEE Access*, 9, 34647-34659, Article 9360736. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3061576>
622. Guan, X., Sun, C., Hwang, G. J., Xue, K., & Wang, Z. (2022). Applying game-based learning in primary education: a systematic review of journal publications from 2010 to 2020 [Review]. *Interactive Learning Environments*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10494820.2022.2091611>
623. Guan, Y., Qiu, Y., Xu, F., & Fang, J. (2022). Effect of Game Teaching Assisted by Deep Reinforcement Learning on Children's Physical Health and Cognitive Ability [Article]. *Mobile Information Systems*, 2022, Article 6150261. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2022/6150261>
624. Guerra Fernandes, J. A., Marques, C. S., Silva, R., & Martins, H. (2022). Ethnic entrepreneurship: A bibliometric review and future research agenda [Article]. *Strategic Change*, 31(4), 397-413. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jsc.2516>
625. Guerrero-Baena, M. D., Gómez-Limón, J. A., & Fuet Cardozo, J. V. (2014). Are multi-criteria decision making techniques useful for solving corporate finance problems? A bibliometric analysis [Article]. *Revista de Metodos Cuantitativos para la Economia y la Empresa*, 17(1), 60-79. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84902296867&partnerID=40&md5=502d282d53021302082ec5735007c9ed>
626. Guido, G., Haghshenas, S. S., Vitale, A., Astarita, V., & Geem, Z. W. (2023). A Quantitative and Qualitative Review of the Role of Intelligent Transportation Systems in Road Safety Studies through Three Decades [Article]. *Journal of Soft Computing in Civil Engineering*, 7(4), 93-109. <https://doi.org/10.22115/SCCE.2023.382320.1597>

627. Gülbün, H., & Yildirim, N. (2021). A QUALITATIVE BIBLIOMETRIC ANALYSIS ON DATA MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES AND ROADMAPS AS A CRITICAL TECHNOLOGY MANAGEMENT TOPIC IN DIGITALIZATION.
628. Gulzar, A., Ahmed, S., Khan, M. A., & Siddique, N. (2022). Bibliometric analysis of mobile learning research from 1984 to 2020 [Article]. *International Journal of Mobile Learning and Organisation*, 16(4), 429-446. <https://doi.org/10.1504/ijmlo.2022.125963>
629. Guo, F., Li, W., Jiang, P., Chen, F., & Liu, Y. (2022). Deep Learning Approach for Damage Classification Based on Acoustic Emission Data in Composite Materials [Article]. *Materials*, 15(12), Article 4270. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma15124270>
630. Guo, F., Li, W., Jiang, P., Chen, F., & Yang, C. (2023). Deep Learning for Time Series-Based Acoustic Emission Damage Classification in Composite Materials [Article]. *Russian Journal of Nondestructive Testing*, 59(6), 665-676. <https://doi.org/10.1134/S1061830923600314>
631. Guo, K. (2022). A systematic review of research on immigrant parenting of young children in the 21st century (2000–2020) [Article]. *Journal of Family Theory and Review*, 14(4), 620-643. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jftr.12485>
632. Gupta, O., & Joshi, P. (2023). Applications of IoT in Retail: A Systematic Review.
633. Gupta, R. K., Ucler, C., & Bernard, A. (2018). Extension of the Virtual Customer Inspection for Distant Collaboration in NPD.
634. Gupta, S., & Pathak, G. S. (2017). Understanding the dimensions of virtual teams: A study of professional students in India [Article]. *International Journal of Web-Based Learning and Teaching Technologies*, 12(2), 55-68. <https://doi.org/10.4018/IJWLTT.2017040104>
635. Gupta, S., & Pathak, G. S. (2018). Virtual team experiences in an emerging economy: a qualitative study [Article]. *Journal of Organizational Change Management*, 31(4), 778-794. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JOCM-04-2017-0108>
636. Guraya, S. Y., & Guraya, S. S. (2017). The confounding factors leading to plagiarism in academic writing and some suggested remedies: A systematic review [Review]. *Journal of the Pakistan Medical Association*, 67(5), 767-772. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85017210282&partnerID=40&md5=e181de4cb4140c527a05f3ef22096147>
637. Gürşen, A. E. (2022). Intellectual Influencer as a New Ambassador in Digital Marketing Communication [Article]. *Central European Journal of Communication*, 15(3), 464-482. [https://doi.org/10.51480/1899-5101.15.3\(32\).7](https://doi.org/10.51480/1899-5101.15.3(32).7)
638. Gusenbauer, M. (2019). Google Scholar to overshadow them all? Comparing the sizes of 12 academic search engines and bibliographic databases [Article]. *Scientometrics*, 118(1), 177-214. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-018-2958-5>
639. Gusenbauer, M. (2022). Search where you will find most: Comparing the disciplinary coverage of 56 bibliographic databases [Article]. *Scientometrics*, 127(5), 2683-2745. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-022-04289-7>
640. Gustafson, C. M., Roffers-Agarwal, J., & Gammill, L. S. (2022). Chick cranial neural crest cells release extracellular vesicles critical for their migration [Article]. *Journal of Cell Science*, 135(12). <https://doi.org/10.1242/jcs.260272>
641. Gustavo Siqueira Ferreira, P., Pinheiro de Lima, E., & Gouvea da Costa, S. E. (2012). Developing a methodology for assessing virtual teams' performance perception [Article]. *International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management*, 61(7), 710-729. <https://doi.org/10.1108/17410401211263827>
642. Gutiérrez, M., Calatayud, P., & Tomás, J. M. (2018). Motives to practice exercise in old age and successful aging: A latent class analysis [Article]. *Archives of Gerontology and Geriatrics*, 77, 44-50. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.archger.2018.04.003>

643. Gutiérrez-Rebollar, L. A., & Tuero del Prado, C. C. (2023). ANALYSIS OF SCIENTIFIC PRODUCTION IN AQUATIC EXERCISE AIMED AT THE ELDERLY [Article]. *Journal of Sport and Health Research*, 15(1), 197-214. <https://doi.org/10.58727/jshr.91281>
644. Guy, I., Ronen, I., Kravi, E., & Barnea, M. (2016). Increasing activity in enterprise online communities using content recommendation [Article]. *ACM Transactions on Computer-Human Interaction*, 23(4), Article 22. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2910581>
645. Habibi, A., Mousavi, M., Jamali, S. M., & Ale Ebrahim, N. (2022). A bibliometric study of medical tourism [Article]. *Anatolia*, 33(3), 415-425. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13032917.2021.1954042>
646. Hadi, A., Cheung, F., Adjei, S., & Dulaimi, A. (2023). Evaluation of Lean Off-Site Construction Literature through the Lens of Industry 4.0 and 5.0 [Review]. *Journal of Construction Engineering and Management*, 149(12), Article 03123007. <https://doi.org/10.1061/JCEMD4.COENG-13622>
647. Haghshenas, S. S., Guido, G., Vitale, A., & Ghoushchi, S. J. (2022). Quantitative and Qualitative Analysis of Internet of Things (IoT) in Smart Cities and its Applications.
648. Haider, L. J., Boonstra, W. J., Peterson, G. D., & Schlüter, M. (2018). Traps and Sustainable Development in Rural Areas: A Review [Article]. *World Development*, 101, 311-321. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.worlddev.2017.05.038>
649. Hakim, A. R., Romadhon, Sulistyowati, P., Windari, S., & Sholihah. (2023). Amazing culture: Game of local wisdom based on unity engine.
650. Halevi, G., Moed, H., & Bar-Ilan, J. (2017). Suitability of Google Scholar as a source of scientific information and as a source of data for scientific evaluation—Review of the Literature [Review]. *Journal of Informetrics*, 11(3), 823-834. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joi.2017.06.005>
651. Halford, A. J., Burrell, A. G., Yizengaw, E., Bothmer, V., Carter, B. A., Raymond, J. C., Maute, A., Samara, M., Maruyama, N., & Alves, L. R. (2022). Thoughts from a past AGU SPA fellows committee [Article]. *Frontiers in Astronomy and Space Sciences*, 9, Article 1054343. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fspas.2022.1054343>
652. Hall, C. M., & Ram, Y. (2017). Walk on: Conclusions and the future. In *The Routledge International Handbook of Walking* (pp. 403-411). Taylor and Francis. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315638461>
653. Hall, O. P., Jr., & Ko, K. D. (2017). Management education collaboration networks. In *Business Education and Ethics: Concepts, Methodologies, Tools, and Applications* (Vol. 3-3, pp. 1160-1177). IGI Global. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-5225-3153-1.ch059>
654. Hama, K., & Matsubara, T. (2023). Multi-Modal Entity Alignment Using Uncertainty Quantification for Modality Importance [Article]. *IEEE Access*, 11, 28479-28489. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2023.3259987>
655. Hammond, P., Opoku, M. O., Kwakwa, P. A., & Amissah, E. (2023). Predictive models of going concerns and business failure [Article]. *Cogent Business and Management*, 10(2), Article 2226481. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311975.2023.2226481>
656. Han, Q., Fan, L., & Wan, H. (2019). Recent development of metal alloy nanostructures for electrochemical hydrogen generation [Short Survey]. *International Journal of Electrochemical Science*, 14, 11549-11549. <https://doi.org/10.20964/2019.12.21>
657. Han, S. J., & Beyerlein, M. (2016). Framing the Effects of Multinational Cultural Diversity on Virtual Team Processes [Review]. *Small Group Research*, 47(4), 351-383. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1046496416653480>
658. Han, S. J., Chae, C., Macko, P., Park, W., & Beyerlein, M. (2017). How virtual team leaders cope with creativity challenges [Article]. *European Journal of Training and Development*, 41(3), 261-276. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EJTD-10-2016-0073>

659. Han, S. J., Liao-Hing, C., & Beyerlein, M. (2016). Facilitating multicultural student team engagement in higher education: A model for digital learning environments. In *Handbook of Research on Transformative Digital Content and Learning Technologies* (pp. 184-210). IGI Global. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-5225-2000-9.ch011>
660. Han, Y., Jeong, J., Ko, M. H., Lee, S., & Kim, J. (2018). Analysis of global competitiveness of engineering modeling and simulation technology for next-manufacturing innovation: Using quantitative analysis of patents and papers [Article]. *ICIC Express Letters, Part B: Applications*, 9(4), 339-346. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85042907768&partnerID=40&md5=a559235fd8580eb5c2040b505efafa31>
661. Haque, K. M. S., Uddin, M., Ampah, J. D., Haque, M. K., Hossen, M. S., Rokonzaman, M., Hossain, M. Y., Hossain, M. S., & Rahman, M. Z. (2023). Wildfires in Australia: a bibliometric analysis and a glimpse on 'Black Summer' (2019/2020) disaster [Review]. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 30(29), 73061-73086. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-023-27423-1>
662. Harju, V., Koskinen, A., & Pehkonen, L. (2019). An exploration of longitudinal studies of digital learning [Review]. *Educational Research*, 61(4), 388-407. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00131881.2019.1660586>
663. Haron, N. A., Hua, L. T., Hassim, S., Eftekhari, F., Muhammad, M. T., & Harun, A. N. (2019). Strategies to improve communication management within virtual project teams [Article]. *Pertanika Journal of Science and Technology*, 27(4), 2015-2030. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85074069244&partnerID=40&md5=bb4b66cc6b2e652a26a771ad53be4b34>
664. Harsh, D., Adnan, H. S., Raees, A. P., Manjul, T., & Anil, N. (2021). How Many Neurosurgeons Does It Take to Author an Article and What Are the Other Factors That Impact Citations? [Article]. *World Neurosurgery*, 146, e993-e1002. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wneu.2020.11.058>
665. Hassanpoor, A., Jafarina, S., Vakili, Y., & Marashi, S. J. (2023). Organisational forgetting in organisations: identifying the causes and contexts using thematic analysis method [Article]. *International Journal of Services and Operations Management*, 44(4), 520-539. <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJSOM.2023.130176>
666. Hasumi, T., & Chiu, M. S. (2022). Online mathematics education as bio-eco-techno process: bibliometric analysis using co-authorship and bibliographic coupling [Article]. *Scientometrics*, 127(8), 4631-4654. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-022-04441-3>
667. Hasumi, T., & Chiu, M. S. (2023). Higher Education Intellectual Performance, Social Network, and Strategies During the Pandemic: A Bibliometric Approach to Online Mathematics Education. In *Higher Education in Asia* (Vol. Part F3, pp. 39-67): Springer Science and Business Media B.V.
668. He, C., Zhang, S., Liang, Y., Ahmad, W., Althoey, F., Alyami, S. H., Javed, M. F., & Deifalla, A. F. (2022). A Scientometric Review on Mapping Research Knowledge for 3D Printing Concrete [Review]. *Materials*, 15(14), Article 4796. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma15144796>
669. He, K., Zhan, M., Li, X., Wu, L., Liang, K., & Ma, R. (2022). A Bibliometric of Trends on Acupuncture Research About Migraine: Quantitative and Qualitative Analyses [Article]. *Journal of Pain Research*, 15, 1257-1269. <https://doi.org/10.2147/JPR.S361652>
670. He, S., Wei, W., Ding, S., Zheng, S., & Niu, T. (2023). Coevolution between science and policy: A systematic analysis on circular economy in China and worldwide [Article]. *Environmental Science and Policy*, 139, 104-117. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2022.10.020>
671. He, X., Amin, M. N., Khan, K., Ahmad, W., Althoey, F., & Vatin, N. I. (2022). Self-healing concrete: A scientometric analysis-based review of the research development and scientific mapping [Article]. *Case Studies in Construction Materials*, 17, Article e01521. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cscm.2022.e01521>

672. He, X., & Liu, Y. (2024). Knowledge evolutionary process of Artificial intelligence in E-commerce: Main path analysis and science mapping analysis [Article]. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 238, Article 121801. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2023.121801>
673. He, X., Singh, C. K. S., & Ebrahim, N. A. (2022). Quantitative and qualitative analysis of higher-order thinking skills in blended learning [Article]. *Perspektivy Nauki i Obrazovania*, 59(5), 397-414. <https://doi.org/10.32744/pse.2022.5.23>
674. Head, M. G., Fitchett, J. R., Derrick, G., Wurie, F. B., Meldrum, J., Kumari, N., Beattie, B., Counts, C. J., & Atun, R. (2015). Comparing research investment to United Kingdom institutions and published outputs for tuberculosis, HIV and malaria: A systematic analysis across 1997-2013 [Article]. *Health Research Policy and Systems*, 13(1), Article 63. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12961-015-0052-5>
675. Hebebcı, M. T., & Ozer, N. (2023). BLENDED LEARNING IN HIGHER EDUCATION: A BIBLIOMETRIC ANALYSIS [Article]. *Turkish Online Journal of Distance Education*, 24(3), 93-116. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85165353049&partnerID=40&md5=1cbf042ee74fbd71c3bc79f1b360f217>
676. Hedayat, M., Jahangiri, P., Torkamani, A., Mashayekhi, M., Sabzali, M. K., & Ebrahim, N. A. (2015). The scientific articles on art criticism [Article]. *Asian Social Science*, 11(13), 130-138. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ass.v11n13p130>
677. Heena, C., & Nidhi, B. (2022). Barriers Affecting the Effectiveness of Digital Literacy Training Programs (DLTPs) for Marginalised Populations: A Systematic Literature Review [Article]. *Journal of Technical Education and Training*, 14(1), 110-127. <https://doi.org/10.30880/jtet.2022.14.01.010>
678. Heidari, A., & Olivieri, F. (2023). Qualitative and Quantitative Scientometric Analysis of Bioclimatic Retrofitting in Commercial Buildings from 2008 to 2022 [Review]. *Buildings*, 13(9), Article 2177. <https://doi.org/10.3390/buildings13092177>
679. Heidary, S., Hashemi, Z., Jamali, S. M., & Ebrahim, N. A. (2023). Quantitative and qualitative analysis of executive functions: a bibliometric approach [Article]. *Current Psychology*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12144-023-05033-x>
680. Heizmann, H. (2013). Promoting critical thinking in virtual teams: A dialogic approach. In *Collaborative Communication Processes and Decision Making in Organizations* (pp. 201-215). IGI Global. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-4666-4478-6.ch011>
681. Herawan, T., Arsyad, S., Widodo, W. I., Adiyanti, A. S., Damiasih, D., Ashartono, R., & Sari, E. N. (2023). A Decade Bibliometric Analysis of Decision Making in Tourism and Hospitality. In O. Gervasi, B. Murgante, F. Scorza, A. M. A. C. Rocha, C. Garau, Y. Karaca, & C. M. Torre (Eds.), (Vol. 14111 LNCS, pp. 17-36): Springer Science and Business Media Deutschland GmbH.
682. Heredia, J., Castillo-Vergara, M., Geldes, C., Carbajal Gamarra, F. M., Flores, A., & Heredia, W. (2022). How do digital capabilities affect firm performance? The mediating role of technological capabilities in the “new normal” [Article]. *Journal of Innovation and Knowledge*, 7(2), Article 100171. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jik.2022.100171>
683. Herman, A., & Manzerolle, V. (2014). The Rise, Fall and Future of BlackBerry™ Capitalism. In *Theories of the Mobile Internet: Materialities and Imaginaries* (pp. 100-124). Taylor and Francis Inc. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315849850>
684. Hermiatin, F. R., Handayati, Y., Perdana, T., & Wardhana, D. (2022). Creating Food Value Chain Transformations through Regional Food Hubs: A Review Article [Review]. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 14(13), Article 8196. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14138196>
685. Herrada, R. I., Baños, R., & Alcayde, A. (2020). Student response systems: A multidisciplinary analysis using visual analytics [Review]. *Education Sciences*, 10(12), 1-23, Article 348. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci10120348>

686. Herrmann, H. (2023). What's next for responsible artificial intelligence: a way forward through responsible innovation [Article]. *Heliyon*, 9(3), Article e14379.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e14379>
687. Herteliu, C., Ausloos, M., Ileanu, B. V., Rotundo, G., & Andrei, T. (2017). Quantitative and qualitative analysis of editor behavior through potentially coercive citations [Article]. *Publications*, 5(2), Article 15. <https://doi.org/10.3390/publications5020015>
688. Hertig, H. P. (2016). *Universities, rankings and the dynamics of global higher education: Perspectives from Asia, Europe and North America* [Book]. Palgrave Macmillan.
<https://doi.org/10.1057/978-1-137-46999-1>
689. Heßler, N., & Ziegler, A. (2022). Evidence-based recommendations for increasing the citation frequency of original articles [Article]. *Scientometrics*, 127(6), 3367-3381.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-022-04378-7>
690. Heßler, N., & Ziegler, A. (2023). Content and form of original research articles in general major medical journals [Article]. *PLoS ONE*, 18(6 JUNE), Article e0287677.
<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0287677>
691. Hidalgo-Fuente, S., & Martínez-Álvarez, I. (2023). Academic Procrastination Scale-Short Form: a reliability generalization metaanalysis [Article]. *Revista Fuentes*, 25(1), 71-81.
<https://doi.org/10.12795/revistafuentes.2023.21581>
692. Hisyam, & Lin, S. W. (2023). Bibliometric analysis of social enterprise literature: Revisit to regroup [Article]. *Journal of Innovation and Knowledge*, 8(3), Article 100411.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jik.2023.100411>
693. Hodge, D. R., Turner, P. R., & Huang, C. K. (2023). The 100 Leading Contributors to English-Language Gerontological Journals: An International Study of Scholarly Impact [Article]. *Journal of Gerontological Social Work*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01634372.2023.2236670>
694. Hodge, D. R., Turner, P. R., & Huang, C. K. (2023). Identifying the Leading Global Contributors to Scholarship in Religion Journals: A Bibliometric Study [Article]. *Journal of Religion and Health*, 62(5), 3501-3519. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10943-023-01815-6>
695. Hodges, G. W., Flanagan, K., Lee, J., Cohen, A., Krishnan, S., & Ward, C. (2020). A quasi-experimental study comparing learning gains associated with serious educational gameplay and hands-on science in elementary classrooms [Article]. *Journal of Research in Science Teaching*, 57(9), 1460-1489. <https://doi.org/10.1002/tea.21661>
696. Hodonu-Wusu, J. O., & Lazarus, G. N. (2018). Major trends in lis research: A bibliometric analysis [Article]. *Library Philosophy and Practice*, 2018, Article 1873.
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85057446973&partnerID=40&md5=677a3ce77edafb701d71aeb6ea6017a>
697. Hoppenstedt, B., Pryss, R., Stelzer, B., Meyer-Brötz, F., Kammerer, K., Treß, A., & Reichert, M. (2018). Techniques and emerging trends for state of the art equipment maintenance systems-A bibliometric analysis [Article]. *Applied Sciences (Switzerland)*, 8(6), Article 916.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/app8060916>
698. Horvat, N., Kunnen, S., Štorga, M., Nagarajah, A., & Škec, S. (2022). Immersive virtual reality applications for design reviews: Systematic literature review and classification scheme for functionalities [Review]. *Advanced Engineering Informatics*, 54, Article 101760.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aei.2022.101760>
699. Horvath, S. M., Muhr, M. M., Kirchner, M., Toth, W., Germann, V., Hundscheid, L., Vacik, H., Scherz, M., Kreiner, H., Fehr, F., Borgwardt, F., Günemann, A., Becsi, B., Schneeberger, A., & Gratzner, G. (2022). Handling a complex agenda: A review and assessment of methods to analyse

SDG entity interactions [Review]. *Environmental Science and Policy*, 131, 160-176.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2022.01.021>

700. Hossain, M. B., Dewan, N., Senin, A. A., & Illes, C. B. (2023). Evaluating the utilization of technological factors to promote e-commerce adoption in small and medium enterprises [Article]. *Electronic Commerce Research*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10660-023-09692-7>
701. Hosseini, M. R., & Chileshe, N. (2013). Global virtual engineering teams (GVETs): A fertile ground for research in Australian construction projects context [Article]. *International Journal of Project Management*, 31(8), 1101-1117. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijproman.2013.01.001>
702. Hosseini, M. R., & Chileshe, N. (2013). Towards an integrated approach for leading and managing transcultural virtual teams. In *Cultural and Technological Influences on Global Business* (pp. 220-241). IGI Global. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-4666-3966-9.ch012>
703. Hosseini, M. R., Zuo, J., Chileshe, N., & Baroudi, B. (2013). A conceptual meta-framework for managing multicultural global virtual teams [Article]. *International Journal of Networking and Virtual Organisations*, 12(4), 310-330. <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJNVO.2013.057280>
704. Howe, S., Ory, E., Carroll, D., Chu, S., Clarke, K., Dalton, B., Dudek, C., Horne, A., Howe, N., Kazi, S., Landeau, A., Lin, D., Degroot, P., Dixon, E., Sabry, F., & Widstrand, A. (2022). The SmithVent Experience and a Framework for Collaborative Distributed Design and Fabrication [Article]. *International Journal of Engineering Education*, 38(6), 1904-1922. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85171566556&partnerID=40&md5=c3dfe650e8cab9ba884b7f41a139c4de>
705. Hsu, A. L., Konner, M., Muttreja, A., Lee, C. H., Chien, J. L., & Irish, R. D. (2021). A comprehensive analysis of authorship trends in Skeletal Radiology since inception from 1976 to 2020 [Article]. *Skeletal Radiology*, 50(12), 2519-2523. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00256-021-03810-y>
706. Hu, S. W., Yang, J. J., & Lin, Y. Y. (2023). Mapping the Scientific Landscape of Bacterial Influence on Oral Cancer: A Bibliometric Analysis of the Last Decade's Medical Progress [Review]. *Current Oncology*, 30(10), 9004-9018. <https://doi.org/10.3390/curroncol30100650>
707. Hu, Y., Yu, Z., Cheng, X., Luo, Y., Wen, C., & Carrera, P. (2020). A bibliometric analysis and visualization of medical data mining research [Review]. *Medicine (United States)*, 99(22), Article 00018. <https://doi.org/10.1097/MD.00000000000020338>
708. Hu, Z., Tariq, S., & Zayed, T. (2021). A comprehensive review of acoustic based leak localization method in pressurized pipelines [Review]. *Mechanical Systems and Signal Processing*, 161, Article 107994. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ymsp.2021.107994>
709. Huang, C., Ye, Y., Jin, Y., & Liang, B. (2023). Research Progress, Hotspots, and Evolution of Nighttime Light Pollution: Analysis Based on WOS Database and Remote Sensing Data [Review]. *Remote Sensing*, 15(9), Article 2305. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs15092305>
710. Huang, L., Zhou, M., Lv, J., & Chen, K. (2020). Trends in global research in forest carbon sequestration: A bibliometric analysis [Article]. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 252, Article 119908. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.119908>
711. Huang, P. C. C. (2018). Citation Indexes: Uses and Misuses [Article]. *Modern China*, 44(6), 559-590. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0097700418796778>
712. Huang, Q., Söbke, H., & Lahmer, T. (2022). Ecosystem Simulator: A Learning Game About Genetic Algorithms. In H. Sobke, P. Spangenberg, P. Muller, & S. Gobel (Eds.), (Vol. 13476 LNCS, pp. 182-197): Springer Science and Business Media Deutschland GmbH.
713. Huang, R., Tang, J., Wang, S., Liu, Y., Zhang, M., Jin, M., Qin, H., Qian, W., Lu, Y., Yang, Y., Lu, B., Yao, Y., Yan, P., Huang, J., Zhang, W., Lu, J., Gu, M., Zhu, Y., Guo, X., . . . Huang, Z. (2023). Sequencing technology as a major impetus in the advancement of studies into rheumatism: A

bibliometric study [Article]. *Frontiers in Immunology*, 14, Article 1067830.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fimmu.2023.1067830>

714. Huang, S., Wang, H., Ahmad, W., Ahmad, A., Vatin, N. I., Mohamed, A. M., Deifalla, A. F., & Mehmood, I. (2022). Plastic Waste Management Strategies and Their Environmental Aspects: A Scientometric Analysis and Comprehensive Review [Review]. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(8), Article 4556. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph19084556>
715. Huang, W. H. D., & Andrade, J. (2014). Design and evaluation of mobile learning from the perspective of cognitive load management. In *Handbook of Research on Education and Technology in a Changing Society* (pp. 291-306). IGI Global. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-4666-6046-5.ch022>
716. Hudson, O., Hudson, D., Brahmstedt, C., & Brawner, J. (2023). The Ear Unwrapper: A Maize Ear Image Acquisition Pipeline for Disease Severity Phenotyping [Article]. *AgriEngineering*, 5(3), 1216-1225. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agriengineering5030077>
717. Hultgren, U., Palmer, S., & O'Riordan, S. (2022). Can cognitive behavioural team coaching increase well-being? In *Coaching Practiced* (pp. 169-182). wiley.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/9781119835714.ch15>
718. Humble, N., & Mozelius, P. (2022). Refurbishing the Educational Escape Room for Programming: Lowering the Threshold and Raising the Ceiling.
719. Hunt, J., Taub, M., Duarte, A., Bentley, B., Womack-Adams, K., Marino, M., Holman, K., & Kuhlman, A. (2023). Elementary Teachers' Perceptions and Enactment of Supplemental, Game-Enhanced Fraction Intervention [Article]. *Education Sciences*, 13(11), Article 1071.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci13111071>
720. Hunt, J. H., Taub, M., Marino, M., Duarte, A., Bentley, B., Holman, K., & Kuhlman, A. (2023). Effects of Game-Enhanced Supplemental Fraction Curriculum on Student Engagement, Fraction Knowledge, and STEM Interest [Article]. *Education Sciences*, 13(7), Article 646.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci13070646>
721. Hurley, C. O. (2018). MSME competitiveness in small island economies: a comparative systematic review of the literature from the past 24 years [Article]. *Entrepreneurship and Regional Development*, 30(9-10), 1027-1068. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08985626.2018.1515822>
722. Hussain, A., & Manoharan, S. (2020). Bibliometric analysis of published literature on spotify music application [Article]. *Journal of Advanced Research in Dynamical and Control Systems*, 12(6), 1700-1708. <https://doi.org/10.5373/JARDCS/V12I2/S20201369>
723. Hussain, A., & Subramanian, G. (2020). A bibliometric research analysis for online booking [Article]. *Journal of Advanced Research in Dynamical and Control Systems*, 12(6), 1671-1679.
<https://doi.org/10.5373/JARDCS/V12I2/S20201365>
724. Hussain, S. M., Jamshed, W., Safdar, R., Shahzad, F., Mohd Nasir, N. A. A., & Ullah, I. (2023). Chemical reaction and thermal characteristics of Maxwell nanofluid flow-through solar collector as a potential solar energy cooling application: A modified Buongiorno's model [Article]. *Energy and Environment*, 34(5), 1409-1432. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0958305X221088113>
725. Hussein, M. H., Ow, S. H., Cheong, L. S., & Thong, M. K. (2019). A Digital Game-Based Learning Method to Improve Students' Critical Thinking Skills in Elementary Science [Article]. *IEEE Access*, 7, 96309-96318, Article 8764331. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2929089>
726. Hussein, M. H., Ow, S. H., Elaiash, M. M., & Jensen, E. O. (2022). Digital game-based learning in K-12 mathematics education: a systematic literature review [Article]. *Education and Information Technologies*, 27(2), 2859-2891. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-021-10721-x>
727. Hustad, E., Vassilakopoulou, P., Cirikovic, M., & Koekebakker, E. (2017). Knowledge management towards a digitalization era: Systematic review of past research and future directions.

728. Hwang, K. E., & Kim, I. (2022). Post-COVID-19 modular building review on problem-seeking framework: function, form, economy, and time [Review]. *Journal of Computational Design and Engineering*, 9(4), 1369-1387. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jcde/qwac057>
729. Ibrahim, S. M., Ansari, S. S., & Hasan, S. D. (2023). Towards white box modeling of compressive strength of sustainable ternary cement concrete using explainable artificial intelligence (XAI) [Article]. *Applied Soft Computing*, 149, Article 110997. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asoc.2023.110997>
730. Idrees, H., Xu, J., Haider, S. A., & Tehseen, S. (2023). A systematic review of knowledge management and new product development projects: Trends, issues, and challenges [Article]. *Journal of Innovation and Knowledge*, 8(2), Article 100350. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jik.2023.100350>
731. Iezzi, D. F., & Celardo, L. (2020). Text Analytics: Present, Past and Future.
732. Iftikhar, B., Alih, S. C., Vafaei, M., Alrowais, R., Bashir, M. T., Khalil, A., Rizwan, M., Javed, M. F., Rehman, M. F., & Mohamed, A. (2023). A scientometric analysis approach on the plastic sand [Review]. *Heliyon*, 9(3), Article e14457. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e14457>
733. Iftikhar, S., Jahanzeb, N., Saleem, M., ur Rehman, S., Matinlinna, J. P., & Khan, A. S. (2021). The trends of dental biomaterials research and future directions: A mapping review [Review]. *Saudi Dental Journal*, 33(5), 229-238. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sdentj.2021.01.002>
734. Igwe, C., Nasiri, F., & Hammad, A. (2022). Construction workspace management: critical review and roadmap [Article]. *International Journal of Construction Management*, 22(10), 1960-1973. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15623599.2020.1756028>
735. Ilango, V., & Mohan Kumar, S. (2017). Factors for improving the research publications and quality metrics [Article]. *International Journal of Civil Engineering and Technology*, 8(4), 477-496. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85019093384&partnerID=40&md5=418e3767203273b1c862062ef61b88a7>
736. Ilas, M. (2010). University role in the development of future high-tech engineers.
737. Imani, M., Donn, M., & Balador, Z. (2019). Bio-inspired materials: Contribution of biology to energy efficiency of buildings. In *Handbook of Ecomaterials* (Vol. 3, pp. 2213-2236). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-68255-6_136
738. İnce, M. (2021). BiLSTM and dynamic fuzzy AHP-GA method for procedural game level generation [Article]. *Neural Computing and Applications*, 33(15), 9761-9773. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00521-021-06180-7>
739. Ingvarsson, C., Hallin, A., & Kier, C. (2023). Project stakeholder engagement through gamification: what do we know and where do we go from here? [Review]. *International Journal of Managing Projects in Business*, 16(8), 152-181. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJMPB-07-2022-0170>
740. Iocca, L., & Fidélis, T. (2022). Traditional communities, territories and climate change in the literature—case studies and the role of law [Article]. *Climate and Development*, 14(6), 537-556. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17565529.2021.1949573>
741. Ion, D., Niculescu, A. G., Păduraru, D. N., Andronic, O., Muşat, F., Grumezescu, A. M., & Bolocan, A. (2022). An up-to-date review of natural nanoparticles for cancer management [Review]. *Pharmaceutics*, 14(1), Article 18. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pharmaceutics14010018>
742. Iqbal, M., & Suzianti, A. (2021). New product development process design for small and medium enterprises: A systematic literature review from the perspective of open innovation [Review]. *Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity*, 7(2), Article 153. <https://doi.org/10.3390/joitmc7020153>
743. Iqbal, M. S., Mohd Isa, M. F., & Abd Aziz, F. S. (2022). Bibliometric Analysis of High-performance Organization Literature Review: 1984 till 2020 [Article]. *Journal of Scientometric Research*, 11(2), 199-204. <https://doi.org/10.5530/jscires.11.2.22>

744. Irwanto, I., Saputro, A. D., Widiyanti, W., & Laksana, S. D. (2023). Global Trends on Mobile Learning in Higher Education: A Bibliometric Analysis (2002–2022) [Article]. *International Journal of Information and Education Technology*, 13(2), 373-383. <https://doi.org/10.18178/ijiet.2023.13.2.1816>
745. Irwin, P. M. (2022). Physical Activity Among Older Women Living in Rural Areas in Canada: A Scoping Review [Review]. *Journal of Population Ageing*, 15(3), 755-801. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12062-022-09380-8>
746. Isabella, G., de Melo, A. F., & Gonzalez, M. C. (2023). Going Viral on Advertising YouTube Video: Detecting the Influences [Article]. *Revista de Administracao Contemporanea*, 27(4 Special Issue), Article e220300. <https://doi.org/10.1590/1982-7849rac2023220300.en>
747. Ishak, S. A., Din, R., & Hasran, U. A. (2021). Beyond play: Conceptualising the capability of a good digital game to stimulate interest in STEM [Article]. *International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research*, 20(10), 232-255. <https://doi.org/10.26803/ijlter.20.10.13>
748. Islam, A., Howlader, A. I., & Roy, P. (2022). Google Scholar Metrics: Assessing LIS Researchers' Scholarship in a Developing Country [Article]. *Proceedings of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, 59(1), 712-714. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pra2.699>
749. Islam, M. A., & Agarwal, N. K. (2021). What is the impact of library and information science on knowledge management research? [Article]. *VINE Journal of Information and Knowledge Management Systems*, 51(1), 1-26. <https://doi.org/10.1108/VJIKMS-11-2018-0098>
750. Islam, M. N., & Hu, G. (2023). An Insight into the State of Big Data Research: A Bibliometric Study of Scientific Publications [Review]. *Science and Technology Libraries*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0194262X.2023.2185919>
751. Islam, R., Jones, S., & Hudnall, M. (2023). Transportation system functions during hurricane Response: A systematic review of modes and methods [Review]. *Transportation Research Interdisciplinary Perspectives*, 18, Article 100786. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trip.2023.100786>
752. Işljamović, S., Jeremić, V., Petrović, N., & Radojičić, Z. (2014). Colouring the socio-economic development into green: I-distance framework for countries' welfare evaluation [Article]. *Quality and Quantity*, 49(2), 617-629. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11135-014-0012-0>
753. Ismail, I., & Hartati, S. (2023). TREND ON PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION RESEARCH: BIBLIOMETRIC ANALYSIS [Article]. *Journal of Governance and Regulation*, 12(1 Special Issue), 401-410. <https://doi.org/10.22495/jgrv12i1siart18>
754. Itayi, C. L., Mohan, G., & Saito, O. (2021). Understanding the conceptual frameworks and methods of the food-energy-water nexus at the household level for development-oriented policy support: A systematic review [Review]. *Environmental Research Letters*, 16(3), Article 033006. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/abd660>
755. Ivanaj, S., & Bozon, C. (2016). *Managing Virtual Teams* [Book]. Edward Elgar Publishing Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.4337/9781785369278>
756. Jabalbarezisarbijan, A., Golhosseini, S., & Marangi, F. (2015). The conceptual role of cyber systems in virtual R&D.
757. Jafari, M. M., Ahmed, S., Md Dawal, S. Z., & Zayandehroodi, H. (2010). The effects of electronic collaboration in reducing production time: Product design process in SMEs.
758. Jafarzadeh-Ghoushchi, S., Dorosti, S., & Asgari-Tehrani, S. (2017). Characteristics of the research on value engineering (2000-2015) [Article]. *World Review of Science, Technology and Sustainable Development*, 13(2), 101-116. <https://doi.org/10.1504/WRSTSD.2017.084171>
759. Jahanbin, P., & Wingreen, S. (2018). The effect of the social media tools on virtual team performance: The mediating role of transactive memory system mapping with the feature richness.

760. Jain, M., Sharma, G. D., & Mahendru, M. (2019). Can i sustain my happiness? A review, critique and research agenda for economics of happiness [Review]. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 11(22), Article 6375. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11226375>
761. Jain, P., & Gupta, A. K. (2023). Digital procurement towards new performance frontiers: a systematic literature review and future research fronts [Review]. *Journal of Global Operations and Strategic Sourcing*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JGOSS-03-2023-0017>
762. Jain, R., Jain, K., Behl, A., Pereira, V., Del Giudice, M., & Vrontis, D. (2022). Mainstreaming fashion rental consumption: A systematic and thematic review of literature [Article]. *Journal of Business Research*, 139, 1525-1539. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2021.10.071>
763. Jain, S., Bajaj, B., & Singh, A. (2023). Linking Metacognition, Workplace Cognitive Competencies and Performance: An Integrative Review-Based Conceptual Framework [Article]. *Primenjena Psihologija*, 16(1), 107-147. <https://doi.org/10.19090/pp.v16i1.2427>
764. Jaiswal, A., Manoj, M., & Tiwari, G. (2022). A review of studies on service quality of intermediate public transport [Review]. *IATSS Research*, 46(4), 537-546. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iatssr.2022.09.002>
765. Jalil, N. F. A., Hasran, U. A., Noor, S. F. M., & Norman, M. H. (2023). The Usability of Digital Game-based Learning for Low Carbon Awareness: Heuristic Evaluation [Article]. *International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications*, 14(5), 334-340. <https://doi.org/10.14569/IJACSA.2023.0140535>
766. Jamali, H., Krylova, K., & Dozois, C. M. (2019). The 100 Top-Cited Scientific Papers Focused on the Topic of Bacteriocins [Review]. *International Journal of Peptide Research and Therapeutics*, 25(3), 933-939. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10989-018-9741-6>
767. Jamali, S. M., Ale Ebrahim, N., & Jamali, F. (2023). The role of STEM Education in improving the quality of education: a bibliometric study [Article]. *International Journal of Technology and Design Education*, 33(3), 819-840. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10798-022-09762-1>
768. Janavi, E., Nadi-Ravandi, S., & Batooli, Z. (2020). Impact of researchgate on increasing citations and usage counts of hot papers in clinical medicine indexed in web of science [Article]. *Webology*, 17(1), 130-139, Article A212. <https://doi.org/10.14704/WEB/V17I1/A212>
769. Jang, O., Jo, S., & Kim, S. (2023). Deriving Controllable Local Optimal Solutions through an Environment Parameter Fixed Algorithm [Article]. *Applied Sciences (Switzerland)*, 13(12), Article 7110. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app13127110>
770. Javora, O., Hannemann, T., Volná, K., Děchtěrenko, F., Tetourová, T., Stárková, T., & Brom, C. (2021). Is contextual animation needed in multimedia learning games for children? An eye tracker study [Article]. *Journal of Computer Assisted Learning*, 37(2), 305-318. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jcal.12489>
771. Jelonek, D., Stepniak, C., Turek, T., & Ziora, L. (2013). The influence of virtualization of resources acquisition processes on the enterprises competitiveness.
772. Jelonek, D., Stepniak, C., Turek, T., & Ziora, L. (2015). The influence of virtualization of resources acquisition processes on the enterprises competitiveness.
773. Jiang, F., Sun, T., Cheng, P., Wang, J., & Gong, W. (2023). A Summary on Tuberculosis Vaccine Development—Where to Go? [Article]. *Journal of Personalized Medicine*, 13(3), Article 408. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jpm13030408>
774. Jiang, P., Dieckmann, E., Han, J., & Childs, P. R. N. (2021). A bibliometric review of sustainable product design [Article]. *Energies*, 14(21), Article 6867. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en14216867>
775. Jiang, S., Liu, Y., Xu, Y., Sang, X., & Lu, X. (2023). Research on liquid biopsy for cancer: A bibliometric analysis [Article]. *Heliyon*, 9(3), Article e14145. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e14145>

776. Jiang, T., Hou, Y., & Yang, J. (2023). Literature Review on the Development of Visualization Studies (2012–2022) † [Article]. *Engineering Proceedings*, 38(1), Article 89. <https://doi.org/10.3390/engproc2023038089>
777. Jiang, Z., Wu, J., Huang, F., Lv, Y., & Wan, L. (2021). A novel adaptive Kriging method: Time-dependent reliability-based robust design optimization and case study [Article]. *Computers and Industrial Engineering*, 162, Article 107692. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cie.2021.107692>
778. Jiménez-Olivencia, Y., Ibáñez-Jiménez, Á., Porcel-Rodríguez, L., & Zimmerer, K. (2021). Land use change dynamics in Euro-mediterranean mountain regions: Driving forces and consequences for the landscape [Article]. *Land Use Policy*, 109, Article 105721. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2021.105721>
779. Jin, R., Gao, S., Cheshmehzangi, A., & Aboagye-Nimo, E. (2018). A holistic review of off-site construction literature published between 2008 and 2018 [Review]. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 202, 1202-1219. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.08.195>
780. Jin, R., Yuan, H., & Chen, Q. (2019). Science mapping approach to assisting the review of construction and demolition waste management research published between 2009 and 2018 [Review]. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 140, 175-188. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2018.09.029>
781. Jin, R., Zhong, B., Ma, L., Hashemi, A., & Ding, L. (2019). Integrating BIM with building performance analysis in project life-cycle [Review]. *Automation in Construction*, 106, Article 102861. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2019.102861>
782. Jin, R., Zou, P. X. W., Piroozfar, P., Wood, H., Yang, Y., Yan, L., & Han, Y. (2019). A science mapping approach based review of construction safety research [Review]. *Safety Science*, 113, 285-297. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssci.2018.12.006>
783. Jin, R., Zou, Y., Gidado, K., Ashton, P., & Painting, N. (2019). Scientometric analysis of BIM-based research in construction engineering and management [Review]. *Engineering, Construction and Architectural Management*, 26(8), 1750-1776. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ECAM-08-2018-0350>
784. Jindal, N., & Singh, K. (2019). Digital image forensics-gateway to authenticity: Crafted with observations, trends and forecasts. In *Handbook of Multimedia Information Security: Techniques and Applications* (pp. 681-701). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-15887-3_33
785. Jing, L., & Feng, C. (2016). Knowledge management practice in the national nuclear safety administration of China.
786. Johnsson, M. (2022). *How to create high-performing innovation teams* [Book]. De Gruyter. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110731934>
787. Johnsson, M. (2023). *Creating Global High-Performing Innovation Teams – Insights and Guidelines* [Article]. *Journal of Innovation Management*, 11(2), 71-117. https://doi.org/10.24840/2183-0606_011.002_0004
788. Joshi, S., Rhoads, B., Jaeger-Helton, K., & Rivera-Jiménez, S. M. (2021). *Making it Work in the Virtual Capstone Climate and Beyond: Project-based Perspectives Across a Variety of Programs and Universities*.
789. Joshi, S., Sharma, M., Ekren, B. Y., Kazancoglu, Y., Luthra, S., & Prasad, M. (2023). *Assessing Supply Chain Innovations for Building Resilient Food Supply Chains: An Emerging Economy Perspective* [Article]. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 15(6), Article 4924. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15064924>
790. Jukić, T., Pevcin, P., Benčina, J., Dečman, M., & Vrbek, S. (2019). Collaborative innovation in public administration: Theoretical background and research trends of co-production and co-creation [Article]. *Administrative Sciences*, 9(4), Article 90. <https://doi.org/10.3390/admsci9040090>

791. Junior, A. J. G., & Mattedi, A. P. (2023). The perception of team leadership when using collaborative systems [Article]. *AtoZ*, 12. <https://doi.org/10.5380/atoz.v12i0.88006>
792. Junior, E. C., Andrade, R. M. C., Venceslau, A. D. P., Oliveira, P. A. M., Santos, I. S., & Oliveira, B. S. (2022). Where Is the Internet of Health Things Data?
793. Junjia, Y., Alias, A. H., Haron, N. A., & Abu Bakar, N. (2023). A Bibliometrics-Based Systematic Review of Safety Risk Assessment for IBS Hoisting Construction [Review]. *Buildings*, 13(7), Article 1853. <https://doi.org/10.3390/buildings13071853>
794. Kaba, A., & Ramaiah, C. K. (2020). Global Research Productivity in Knowledge Management: an Analysis of Scopus Database [Article]. *Library Philosophy and Practice*, 2020, 1-19. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85088315895&partnerID=40&md5=5d8c120fcdf828838f9e8f19a7bfc8d>
795. Kabagwira, J., Gonda, A., Vallejos, P., Babcock, B., Langridge, W. H. R., Senthil, M., & Wall, N. R. (2021). Optimization of blood handling for plasma extracellular vesicle isolation [Article]. *Journal of Nanoparticle Research*, 23(3), Article 65. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11051-021-05169-6>
796. Kabak, K., & Korucu, A. T. (2021). The effect of students' developing their own digital games on their academic achievement and attitudes towards for english lessons [Article]. *Participatory Educational Research*, 8(2), 74-93. <https://doi.org/10.17275/per.21.30.8.2>
797. Kabirifar, K., Mojtahedi, M., & Wang, C. C. (2021). A systematic review of construction and demolition waste management in Australia: Current practices and challenges [Review]. *Recycling*, 6(2), Article 34. <https://doi.org/10.3390/recycling6020034>
798. Kaczam, F., Siluk, J. C. M., Guimaraes, G. E., de Moura, G. L., da Silva, W. V., & da Veiga, C. P. (2022). Establishment of a typology for startups 4.0 [Review]. *Review of Managerial Science*, 16(3), 649-680. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11846-021-00463-y>
799. Kahn, M. (2018). Co-authorship as a proxy for collaboration: A cautionary tale [Article]. *Science and Public Policy*, 45(1), 117-123. <https://doi.org/10.1093/scipol/scx052>
800. Kahn, M., & Puri, A. (2017). La collaboration des brics dans les domaines de la science, de la technologie et de l'innovation [Article]. *HERMES (France)*, 79(3), 124-131. <https://doi.org/10.3917/herm.079.0124>
801. Kaisara, G., & Bwalya, K. J. (2023). Mobile Learning in Higher Education: Insights from a Bibliometric Analysis of the Body of Knowledge [Article]. *International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research*, 22(6), 152-174. <https://doi.org/10.26803/ijlter.22.6.9>
802. Kaiser, M., & Kuckertz, A. (2023). Bibliometrically mapping the research field of entrepreneurial communication: where we stand and where we need to go [Article]. *Management Review Quarterly*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11301-023-00355-3>
803. Kala, H. K., Mehta, R., Sen, K. K., Tandey, R., & Mandal, V. (2016). Critical analysis of research trends and issues in microwave assisted extraction of phenolics: Have we really done enough [Review]. *TrAC - Trends in Analytical Chemistry*, 85, 140-152. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trac.2016.09.007>
804. Kalantari, A., Kamsin, A., Kamaruddin, H. S., Ale Ebrahim, N., Gani, A., Ebrahimi, A., & Shamshirband, S. (2017). A bibliometric approach to tracking big data research trends [Article]. *Journal of Big Data*, 4(1), Article 30. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40537-017-0088-1>
805. Kamalulil, E. N., & Panatik, S. A. (2021). Socioeconomic status and mental health among low-income employees: A systematic literature review [Review]. *Pertanika Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*, 29(3), 1853-1874. <https://doi.org/10.47836/pjssh.29.3.20>
806. Kamarrudin, H., Talib, O., Kamarudin, N., Ismail, N., & Zamin, A. A. M. (2022). Examining the Trend of Research on Active Engagement in Science Education: Bibliometric Analysis [Article]. *Journal of Turkish Science Education*, 19(3), 937-957. <https://doi.org/10.36681/tused.2022.157>

807. Kamaruzzaman, W. M. I. W. M., Nasir, N. A. M., Hamidi, N. A. S. M., Yusof, N., Shaifudin, M. S., Suhaimi, A. M. A. A. M., Badruddin, M. A., Adnan, A., Nik, W. M. N. W., & Ghazali, M. S. M. (2022). 25 years of progress on plants as corrosion inhibitors through a bibliometric analysis using the Scopus database (1995–2020) [Article]. *Arabian Journal of Chemistry*, 15(4), Article 103655. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.arabjc.2021.103655>
808. Kamble, S. S., & Gunasekaran, A. (2020). Big data-driven supply chain performance measurement system: a review and framework for implementation [Review]. *International Journal of Production Research*, 58(1), 65-86. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00207543.2019.1630770>
809. Kamble, S. S., Gunasekaran, A., & Gawankar, S. A. (2020). Achieving sustainable performance in a data-driven agriculture supply chain: A review for research and applications [Review]. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 219, 179-194. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpe.2019.05.022>
810. Kamble, S. S., Gunasekaran, A., Goswami, M., & Manda, J. (2019). A systematic perspective on the applications of big data analytics in healthcare management [Review]. *International Journal of Healthcare Management*, 12(3), 226-240. <https://doi.org/10.1080/20479700.2018.1531606>
811. Kamyabi, Y., & Devi, S. (2012). The impact of advisory services on Iranian SME performance: An empirical investigation of the role of professional accountants [Review]. *South African Journal of Business Management*, 43(2), 61-72. <https://doi.org/10.4102/sajbm.v43i2.184>
812. Kang, C. M., Shin, H., & Lee, C. (2017). High-frequency organic rectifiers through interface engineering [Article]. *MRS Communications*, 7(4), 755-769. <https://doi.org/10.1557/mrc.2017.100>
813. Karakaya, E., & Nuur, C. (2018). Social sciences and the mining sector: Some insights into recent research trends [Article]. *Resources Policy*, 58, 257-267. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resourpol.2018.05.014>
814. Karakaya, Y. E., Dikmen, M., & Şahin, A. (2023). Bibliometric mapping of research trends in education, physical education, and sports for the disabled [Article]. *Life Span and Disability*, 26(1), 53-92. https://doi.org/10.57643/ljadj.2023.26.1_03
815. Karaman Aksentijević, N., Ježić, Z., & Zaninović, P. A. (2021). The effects of information and communication technology (ICT) use on human development—A macroeconomic approach [Article]. *Economies*, 9(3), Article 128. <https://doi.org/10.3390/economies9030128>
816. Kargar, S., Shahri, M. H., Ghorbani, Z., Saberi, A., Jamali, S. M., & Alebrahim, N. (2022). Patterns of publications in social media-based co-creation: a bibliometric analysis [Article]. *VINE Journal of Information and Knowledge Management Systems*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/VJIKMS-09-2021-0222>
817. Karl, A. A., & Scholz Karl, J. (2022). Human rights for refugees: enhancing sustainable humanitarian supply chain to guarantee a health environment in refugee settlements [Article]. *Journal of Humanitarian Logistics and Supply Chain Management*, 12(3), 382-403. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JHLSCM-11-2020-0104>
818. Karol, D. L., Sheriff, L., Jalal, S., Ding, J., Larson, A. R., Trister, R., & Khosa, F. (2021). Gender disparity in dermatologic society leadership: A global perspective [Article]. *International Journal of Women's Dermatology*, 7(4), 445-450. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijwd.2020.10.003>
819. Kassa, A., Kitaw, D., Stache, U., Beshah, B., & Degefu, G. (2023). Artificial intelligence techniques for enhancing supply chain resilience: A systematic literature review, holistic framework, and future research [Article]. *Computers and Industrial Engineering*, 186, Article 109714. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cie.2023.109714>
820. Kauffmann, D., & Carmi, G. (2017). A Comparative Study of E-Collaboration on Temporary vs. Ongoing Teams.

821. Kauffmann, D., & Carmi, G. (2017). E-collaboration of virtual teams: The mediating effect of interpersonal trust.
822. Kauffmann, D., & Carmi, G. (2018). Knowledge sharing of virtual teams: The mediating effect of trust on relationship communication.
823. Kauffmann, D., & Carmi, G. (2019). Communication and trust as facilitators for collaborative innovation development in virtual teams.
824. Kauffmann, D., & Carmi, G. (2019). A comparative study of temporary and ongoing teams on e-environment [Article]. *IEEE Transactions on Professional Communication*, 62(2), 148-164, Article 8667024. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TPC.2019.2900909>
825. Kauffmann, D., & Carmi, G. (2020). E-Collaboration in virtual teams: Trust as a facilitator of development. In *Knowledge Management, Innovation, and Entrepreneurship in a Changing World* (pp. 210-242). IGI Global. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-7998-2355-1.ch009>
826. Kaur, S., Arif, M., & Akre, V. (2016). Effect of social media on trust in virtual project teams of construction sector in Middle East. In Y. K. Dwivedi, M. Clement, E. L. Slade, N. P. Rana, M. N. Ravishankar, M. Mantymaki, M. Janssen, S. Al-Sharhan, & A. C. Simintiras (Eds.), (Vol. 9844 LNCS, pp. 419-429): Springer Verlag.
827. Kaushik, V., Tewari, S., Sahasranamam, S., & Hota, P. K. (2023). Towards a precise understanding of social entrepreneurship: An integrated bibliometric-machine learning based review and research agenda [Article]. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 191, Article 122516. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2023.122516>
828. Kazak, A. N., Dorofeeva, A. A., & Nyurenberger, L. B. (2019). Problems and prospects of digitalization of education for industry 4.0 in Russian Federation.
829. Kazak, A. N., Oleinikov, N. N., & Samokhvalov, D. V. (2021). Merging Roles in the Production of Massive Online Electric Drive Courses.
830. Kazemi, N., Modak, N. M., & Govindan, K. (2019). A review of reverse logistics and closed loop supply chain management studies published in IJPR: a bibliometric and content analysis [Review]. *International Journal of Production Research*, 57(15-16), 4937-4960. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00207543.2018.1471244>
831. Kearl, M., Noteboom, C. B., & Tech, D. (2017). A proposed improvement to google scholar algorithms through broad topic search.
832. Kehinde, T. O., Chan, F. T. S., & Chung, S. H. (2023). Scientometric review and analysis of recent approaches to stock market forecasting: Two decades survey [Review]. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 213, Article 119299. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2022.119299>
833. Kennedy, D. (2012). Supporting traditional management principles in a virtual work group setting.
834. Keong, L. B., Ramakrishnan, S., & Hishan, S. S. (2017). The review of corporate social responsibility (CSR) literature in the new millennium [Review]. *Advanced Science Letters*, 23(9), 9271-9274. <https://doi.org/10.1166/asl.2017.10068>
835. Kesavan, P. (2020). Enablers of Organisational Learning, Knowledge Management, and Innovation: Principles, Process, and Practice of Qualitative Data [Book]. Springer Singapore. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-15-9793-0>
836. Kesiena, O., & Olokunlade, T. (2022). The top 50 most cited articles on cardiac tumors: a bibliometric analysis [Article]. *Future Cardiology*, 18(7), 539-546. <https://doi.org/10.2217/fca-2022-0011>
837. Khalilia, W. M., Abuowda, A., Mystakidis, S., & Fragkaki, M. (2023). A Mediation Model of the Usability and Intergroup Relation for Online Project Management Community Effectiveness with Microsoft Teams [Article]. *Societies*, 13(12), Article 255. <https://doi.org/10.3390/soc13120255>

838. Khan, A., Sepasgozar, S., Liu, T., & Yu, R. (2021). Integration of bim and immersive technologies for aec: A scientometric-swot analysis and critical content review [Review]. *Buildings*, 11(3), Article 126. <https://doi.org/10.3390/buildings11030126>
839. Khan, A., Yu, R., Liu, T., Guan, H., & Oh, E. (2022). Drivers towards Adopting Modular Integrated Construction for Affordable Sustainable Housing: A Total Interpretive Structural Modelling (TISM) Method [Article]. *Buildings*, 12(5), Article 637. <https://doi.org/10.3390/buildings12050637>
840. Khan, F. M., & Gupta, Y. (2022). A bibliometric analysis of mobile learning in the education sector [Review]. *Interactive Technology and Smart Education*, 19(3), 338-359. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ITSE-03-2021-0048>
841. Khan, K., Ahmad, W., Amin, M. N., & Ahmad, A. (2022). A Systematic Review of the Research Development on the Application of Machine Learning for Concrete [Review]. *Materials*, 15(13), Article 4512. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma15134512>
842. Khan, K., Ahmad, W., Amin, M. N., Khan, S. A., Deifalla, A. F., & Younes, M. Y. M. (2023). Research evolution on self-healing asphalt: A scientometric review for knowledge mapping [Review]. *Reviews on Advanced Materials Science*, 62(1), Article 20220331. <https://doi.org/10.1515/rams-2022-0331>
843. Khan, K., Ahmad, W., Amin, M. N., & Nazar, S. (2022). Nano-Silica-Modified Concrete: A Bibliographic Analysis and Comprehensive Review of Material Properties [Review]. *Nanomaterials*, 12(12), Article 1989. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nano12121989>
844. Khan, M. A., Mittal, S., West, S., & Wuest, T. (2018). Review on upgradability – A product lifetime extension strategy in the context of product service systems [Article]. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 204, 1154-1168. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.08.329>
845. Khatun, M., Wagner, F., Jung, R., & Glaß, M. (2023). An application of DEMATEL and fuzzy DEMATEL to evaluate the interaction of safety management system and cybersecurity management system in automated vehicles [Short Survey]. *Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence*, 124, Article 106566. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engappai.2023.106566>
846. Kheilkordi, Z., Ziarani, G. M., & Mohajer, F. (2022). Application of Multi-component Reaction in the Synthesis of Heterocyclic [3.3.3] Propellane Derivatives [Article]. *Current Organic Chemistry*, 26(3), 287-298. <https://doi.org/10.2174/1385272826666220112161201>
847. Khumalo, M., & van der Lingen, E. (2017). The open business model in a dynamic business environment: A literature review [Review]. *South African Journal of Industrial Engineering*, 28(3SpecialEdition), 147-160. <https://doi.org/10.7166/28-3-1851>
848. Khurana, P., & Sharma, K. (2022). Impact of h-index on author's rankings: an improvement to the h-index for lower-ranked authors [Article]. *Scientometrics*, 127(8), 4483-4498. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-022-04464-w>
849. Ki, C. W., Chong, S. M., & Ha-Brookshire, J. E. (2020). How fashion can achieve sustainable development through a circular economy and stakeholder engagement: A systematic literature review [Review]. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, 27(6), 2401-2424. <https://doi.org/10.1002/csr.1970>
850. Kiely, G., Butler, T., & Finnegan, P. (2022). Global virtual teams coordination mechanisms: building theory from research in software development [Article]. *Behaviour and Information Technology*, 41(9), 1952-1972. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0144929X.2021.1909141>
851. Kiflee, A. K. R., Hasbullah, N. N., Ahmad, S. N., & Mastor, S. H. (2023). Research Progress of Digital Technology and Emerging Themes During Covid 19 in Malaysia: Bibliometric Analysis Approach [Article]. *International Journal of Interactive Mobile Technologies*, 17(6), 98-115. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijim.v17i06.35551>

852. Kiguchi, M., Saeed, W., & Medi, I. (2022). Churn prediction in digital game-based learning using data mining techniques: Logistic regression, decision tree, and random forest [Article]. *Applied Soft Computing*, 118, Article 108491. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asoc.2022.108491>
853. Kihlström, V., & Elbe, J. (2021). Constructing markets for solar energy—a review of literature about market barriers and government responses [Review]. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 13(6), Article 3273. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13063273>
854. Kilcullen, M., Feitosa, J., & Salas, E. (2022). Insights From the Virtual Team Science: Rapid Deployment During COVID-19 [Article]. *Human Factors*, 64(8), 1429-1440. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0018720821991678>
855. Kim, G., Choi, J. G., Ku, M., Cho, H., & Lim, S. (2021). A Multimodal Deep Learning-Based Fault Detection Model for a Plastic Injection Molding Process [Article]. *IEEE Access*, 9, 132455-132467. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3115665>
856. Kim, J., Lee, D., & Park, E. (2021). Authors ⇌ reply to: Bibliometric studies and the discipline of social media mental health research. comment on “machine learning for mental health in social media: Bibliometric study” [Letter]. *Journal of Medical Internet Research*, 23(6), Article e29549. <https://doi.org/10.2196/29549>
857. Kim, M. J., & Lim, J. H. (2019). A comprehensive review on logo literature: research topics, findings, and future directions [Article]. *Journal of Marketing Management*, 35(13-14), 1291-1365. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0267257X.2019.1604563>
858. Kiss, A., Lakner, Z., Soós, S., & Petróczy, A. (2022). Women's Footprint in Anti-Doping Sciences: A Bibliometric Approach to Research Impact [Article]. *Frontiers in Sports and Active Living*, 4, Article 866648. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fspor.2022.866648>
859. Kiss, A., Temesi, Á., Tompa, O., Lakner, Z., & Soós, S. (2021). Structure and trends of international sport nutrition research between 2000 and 2018: bibliometric mapping of sport nutrition science [Article]. *Journal of the International Society of Sports Nutrition*, 18(1), Article 12. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12970-021-00409-5>
860. Kizilcik, H. Ş. (2023). A Bibliometric Analysis of Articles on Physics Education in Turkey Between 2010 and 2020 [Article]. *Hacettepe Egitim Dergisi*, 38(3), 347-366. <https://doi.org/10.16986/HUJE.2023.493>
861. Koç, T., Kurt, K., & Akbiyik, A. (2019). A Brief Summary of Knowledge Management Domain: 10-Year History of the Journal of Knowledge Management.
862. Kodandarama, Manjesh, M., & Chandrashekar, M. D. (2020). Techniques Used by Post Graduate Students to reduce the rate of Similarity: a study [Article]. *Library Philosophy and Practice*, 2020, 1-6. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85098513411&partnerID=40&md5=c3aafedb4d7dced617b2fe979675b06d>
863. Kohlbeck, E., Beuren, F. H., & Santos, V. M. (2023). Analysis of the application of recycled polypropylene: a case study in the refrigeration segment in south of Brazil [Article]. *Brazilian Journal of Operations and Production Management*, 20(4), Article e20231560. <https://doi.org/10.14488/BJOPM.1560.2023>
864. Kohlbeck, E., Cauchick-Miguel, P. A., Mendes, G. H. D. S., & Zomer, T. T. D. S. (2023). A Longitudinal History-Based Review of the Product-Service System: Past, Present, and Future [Review]. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 15(15), Article 11922. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su151511922>
865. Koles, B., & Nagy, P. (2014). Individual and professional development in the digital age: Towards a conceptual model of virtual worlds for organizations [Article]. *Management Research Review*, 37(3), 288-307. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MRR-10-2012-0225>

866. Koles, B., & Nagy, P. (2014). Virtual worlds as digital workplaces: Conceptualizing the affordances of virtual worlds to expand the social and professional spheres in organizations [Article]. *Organizational Psychology Review*, 4(2), 175-195. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2041386613507074>
867. Kolle, S. R., Rabindranath, M., & Shankarappa, T. H. (2019). Characteristics of highly cited articles in communication (1989 to 2018): A web of science-based analysis [Article]. *Media Watch*, 10(3), 645-663. <https://doi.org/10.15655/mw/2019/v10i3/49700>
868. Kombe, G. G. (2023). An Overview of Algae for Biodiesel Production Using Bibliometric Indicators [Review]. *International Journal of Energy Research*, 2023, Article 9596398. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2023/9596398>
869. Kondraganti, A., Narayanamurthy, G., & Sharifi, H. (2022). A systematic literature review on the use of big data analytics in humanitarian and disaster operations [Article]. *Annals of Operations Research*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10479-022-04904-z>
870. Kör, B., Mutlutürk, M., & Caniels, M. C. J. (2022). Analysing and visualising the trends in knowledge management: Towards a normative knowledge management framework [Article]. *International Journal of Knowledge Management Studies*, 13(1), 1-32. <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJKMS.2022.119253>
871. Korner, M. E. H., Lambán, M. P., Albajez, J. A., Santolaria, J., Corrales, L. C. N., & Royo, J. (2020). Systematic literature review: Integration of additive manufacturing and industry 4.0 [Review]. *Metals*, 10(8), 1-24, Article 1061. <https://doi.org/10.3390/met10081061>
872. Kotur, A. S. (2023). A bibliometric review of research in wine tourism experiences: insights and future research directions [Article]. *International Journal of Wine Business Research*, 35(2), 278-297. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJWBR-07-2022-0024>
873. Koutantou, M., & Rangoussi, M. (2022). Digital Game-based Learning in Primary School: What Issues Does/Does Not Recent Research Focus on?
874. Krainer, J. A., Krainer, C. W. M., Vidolin, A. C., & Romano, C. A. (2020). Supplier in the Supply Chain: A Bibliometric Analysis.
875. Krath, J., Schürmann, L., & von Korfflesch, H. F. O. (2021). Revealing the theoretical basis of gamification: A systematic review and analysis of theory in research on gamification, serious games and game-based learning [Article]. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 125, Article 106963. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2021.106963>
876. Krayter, S., & Reibling, N. (2020). Medicalisation and psychologisation of poverty? An analysis of the scientific poverty discourse from 1956 to 2017 [Review]. *Journal of Poverty and Social Justice*, 28(3), 361-381. <https://doi.org/10.1332/175982720X15979441697421>
877. Kreutzer, J., & Staar, H. (2018). "I lead - so I am?" - Perception and assessment of the legitimacy of leadership positions in virtual collaborations.
878. Krueger, T. M., & Megits, N. (2021). The impact of economics and finance research published in central and eastern Europe [Article]. *Journal of Eastern European and Central Asian Research*, 8(1), 1-17. <https://doi.org/10.15549/jeecar.v8i1.647>
879. Krumm, S., & Hertel, G. (2013). Knowledge, skills, abilities and other characteristics (KSAOs) for virtual teamwork. In *The Psychology of Digital Media at Work* (pp. 80-100). Taylor and Francis. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203074145>
880. Krumm, S., Kanthak, J., Hartmann, K., & Hertel, G. (2016). What does it take to be a virtual team player? The knowledge, skills, abilities, and other characteristics required in virtual teams [Article]. *Human Performance*, 29(2), 123-142. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08959285.2016.1154061>
881. Krusch, A. L. C., Uphaus, P. O., & Rau, H. (2020). Only Location: A Systematic Literature Review on Context Marketing.

882. Kuciapski, M., & Weichbroth, P. (2021). Evaluating the internal and external usability of mobile technologies in facilitating knowledge transfer.
883. Kudroli, K. R., Sandhya Rao, K. P., Samartha, V., & Sushma, V. (2020). Systematic literature review of blood supply chain using bibliometric visualization techniques [Review]. *International Journal of Scientific and Technology Research*, 9(2), 3056-3058. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85079500063&partnerID=40&md5=154a498cadfc3997af0a4b8ac063123a>
884. Kulkanjanapiban, P., & Silwattananusarn, T. (2022). Comparative analysis of Dimensions and Scopus bibliographic data sources: An approach to university research productivity [Article]. *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering*, 12(1), 706-720. <https://doi.org/10.11591/ijece.v12i1.pp706-720>
885. Kumar, A., Dhingra, S., & Falwadiya, H. (2023). Adoption of Internet of Things: A systematic literature review and future research agenda [Review]. *International Journal of Consumer Studies*, 47(6), 2553-2582. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ijcs.12964>
886. Kumari, R., Jeong, J. Y., Lee, B. H., Choi, K. N., & Choi, K. (2021). Topic modelling and social network analysis of publications and patents in humanoid robot technology [Article]. *Journal of Information Science*, 47(5), 658-676. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0165551519887878>
887. Kuntolaksono, S., Joelianingsih, Yoshi, L. A., & Christwardana, M. (2022). Bibliometric Analysis of Global Research Trends on Electrochemical Nitrite Sensing using Scopus Database [Article]. *Analytical and Bioanalytical Electrochemistry*, 14(7), 680-695. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85135178183&partnerID=40&md5=33e3c850996817262510a5c81db00c2a>
888. Kurniawan, Subowo, H., & Firmansyah, I. (2022). Bibliometric Analysis of Carbon Accounting Research [Article]. *International Journal of Energy Economics and Policy*, 12(3), 482-489. <https://doi.org/10.32479/ijeep.12992>
889. Kurniawan, E., Dallyono, R., & Cahyowati, A. (2019). Exploring logical connectors in journals with different indexing levels: A comparison between international and national indexed journals [Article]. *Indonesian Journal of Applied Linguistics*, 9(1), 76-84. <https://doi.org/10.17509/ijal.v9i1.16088>
890. Kurniawan, E., & Sabila, N. A. A. (2021). Another look at the rhetorical moves and linguistic realizations in international and Indonesian journal articles: A case of tourism research article abstracts [Article]. *Indonesian Journal of Applied Linguistics*, 11(2), 318-329. <https://doi.org/10.17509/ijal.v11i2.32055>
891. Kurt, S., Assefa, F. Z., Tuzlukaya, S. E., & Karatepe, O. M. (2023). A 30-year journey of hospitality and tourism research: a comprehensive topic modeling analysis [Article]. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJCHM-01-2023-0109>
892. Kwanya, T., Kogos, A. C., Kibe, L. W., Ogolla, E. O., & Onsare, C. (2022). Cyber-bullying research in Kenya: a meta-analysis [Article]. *Global Knowledge, Memory and Communication*, 71(4-5), 208-229. <https://doi.org/10.1108/GKMC-08-2020-0124>
893. Kwary, D. A., Ratri, D., & Artha, A. F. (2017). Lexical bundles in journal articles across academic disciplines [Article]. *Indonesian Journal of Applied Linguistics*, 7(1), 132-140. <https://doi.org/10.17509/ijal.v7i1.6866>
894. Lah, N. H. C., Jumaat, N. F., & Wong, Y. S. (2022). The practice of gamification in higher education: A systematic review. In *Perspectives and Practices of Gamification* (pp. 279-300). Nova Science Publishers, Inc. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85152748744&partnerID=40&md5=28aca96218980b81c66b4c869b6544ec>

895. Lai, K. A., Saxena, G., & Allen, P. J. (2022). Research performance of academic psychologists in the United Kingdom [Article]. *Scientometrics*, 127(7), 4139-4166. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-022-04424-4>
896. Lamba, Y. S., Sood, S. K., Rawat, K. S., Chopra, M., & Singh, A. K. (2022). Knowledge mapping of 4D printing technologies in computer engineering [Review]. *Computer Applications in Engineering Education*, 30(6), 1959-1978. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cae.22561>
897. Lamerias, P., Arnab, S., de Freitas, S., Petridis, P., & Dunwell, I. (2021). Science teachers' experiences of inquiry-based learning through a serious game: a phenomenographic perspective [Article]. *Smart Learning Environments*, 8(1), Article 7. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40561-021-00152-z>
898. Lange-Küttner, C., & Sykorova, E. (2015). MOJIBAKE - The rehearsal of word fragments in verbal recall [Article]. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 6(MAR), Article 350. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2015.00350>
899. Langthorne, D., Beard, J., & Waller, G. (2023). Therapist factors associated with intent to use exposure therapy: a systematic review and meta-analysis [Review]. *Cognitive Behaviour Therapy*, 52(4), 347-379. <https://doi.org/10.1080/16506073.2023.2191824>
900. Lanzilotti, C. O., Pinto, L. F. R., Facchini, F., & Digiesi, S. (2022). Embedding Product-Service System of Cutting Tools into the Machining Process: An Eco-Efficiency Approach toward Sustainable Development [Article]. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 14(3), Article 1100. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14031100>
901. Lardo, A., Corsi, K., Varma, A., & Mancini, D. (2022). Exploring blockchain in the accounting domain: a bibliometric analysis [Article]. *Accounting, Auditing and Accountability Journal*, 35(9), 204-233. <https://doi.org/10.1108/AAAJ-10-2020-4995>
902. Lardón-López, M. E., Martín-Rojas, R., & García-Morales, V. J. (2022). "Social media technologies: a waste of time or a good way to learn and improve technological competences?" [Article]. *Journal of Knowledge Management*, 26(11), 348-377. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JKM-02-2022-0130>
903. Larocca, A., Borsato, M., Kubo, P., & Estorilio, C. (2022). Data management within new product development and collaborative engineering: a bibliometric and systemic analysis [Review]. *VINE Journal of Information and Knowledge Management Systems*, 52(5), 701-717. <https://doi.org/10.1108/VJIKMS-07-2020-0131>
904. Lastella, M., Memon, A. R., & Vincent, G. E. (2020). Global Research Output on Sleep Research in Athletes from 1966 to 2019: A Bibliometric Analysis [Review]. *Clocks and Sleep*, 2(2), 99-119. <https://doi.org/10.3390/clockssleep2020010>
905. Laughter, M. R., Maymone, M. B. C., Presley, C. L., Nodine, S., Szeto, M. D., Jones, J. D., Robertson, K., Wilkey, M., Yang, R., Anand, P., Dellavalle, R. P., Hugh, J., & Dunnick, C. A. (2021). Advanced Practice Providers and the Dermatology Literature: A Bibliometric Analysis of Trends 1973-2018 [Article]. *Journal of the Dermatology Nurses' Association*, 13(5), 258-264. <https://doi.org/10.1097/JDN.0000000000000632>
906. Launer, M., Çetin, F., & Paliszkievicz, J. (2022). Digital trust in the workplace: Testing a new instrument on a multicultural sample [Article]. *Forum Scientiae Oeconomia*, 10(1), 29-47. https://doi.org/10.23762/FSO_VOL10_NO1_2
907. Launer, M., Svenson, F., Çetin, F., & Pietrzak, P. (2022). Intuition and digital trust in virtual organizations: Toward digital intuition. In *Trust and Digital Business: Theory and Practice* (pp. 34-46). Taylor and Francis Inc. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003266525-5>
908. Lazar, N., & Chithra, K. (2022). Role of culture in sustainable development and sustainable built environment: a review [Review]. *Environment, Development and Sustainability*, 24(5), 5991-6031. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10668-021-01691-8>

909. Lazure, C., Dumont, L., El Mouderrib, S., Delisle, J. F., Sénécal, S., & Léger, P. M. (2020). Certified Flight Instructors' Performance—Review of the Literature and Exploration of Future Steps [Review]. *International Journal of Aerospace Psychology*, 30(3-4), 152-170. <https://doi.org/10.1080/24721840.2020.1796487>
910. Lazzarini, B., & Pérez-Foguet, A. (2018). Profiling research of the engineering academics who successfully promote education in Sustainable Human Development [Article]. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 172, 4239-4253. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2017.08.234>
911. Lazzarini, B., Pérez-Foguet, A., & Boni, A. (2018). Key characteristics of academics promoting Sustainable Human Development within engineering studies [Article]. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 188, 237-252. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.03.270>
912. Le, H. T. T., Dao, Q. T. M., Pham, V. C., & Tran, D. T. (2019). Global trend of open innovation research: A bibliometric analysis [Article]. *Cogent Business and Management*, 6(1), Article 1633808. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311975.2019.1633808>
913. Le, P. T., Kirytopoulos, K., Chileshe, N., & Rameezdeen, R. (2022). Taxonomy of risks in PPP transportation projects: a systematic literature review [Article]. *International Journal of Construction Management*, 22(2), 166-181. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15623599.2019.1615756>
914. Leal, C., Marques, C. S., Gaspar, P., & Fermento, A. (2022). Knowledge Sharing in Private Social Solidarity Institutions during Pandemics.
915. Leal, C., Meirinhos, G., Loureiro, M., & Marques, C. S. (2017). Cybersecurity management, intellectual capital and trust: A new management dilemma.
916. Leal, C., Meirinhos, G., Loureiro, M., & Silva, R. (2017). Knowledge sharing and (in)security: Towards a comprehensive view of managerial aspects.
917. Lechuga-Sancho, M. P., Martínez-Fierro, S., & Ramos-Rodríguez, A. R. (2023). Thirty years of research on high-growth entrepreneurship: bibliometric overview of its H-Classics [Article]. *Profesional de la Informacion*, 32(3), Article e320320. <https://doi.org/10.3145/epi.2023.may.20>
918. Lecourt, M., Chietera, G., Jullien, F., Blerot, B., & Antoniotti, S. (2023). From biosynthesis in plants to post-biosynthetic enzymatic conversion. Generation of odor-impact rose oxides from citronellol-rich essential oils [Article]. *Botany Letters*, 170(1), 15-27. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23818107.2022.2100476>
919. Lee, D. (2023). Bibliometric analysis of Asian 'language and linguistics' research: A case of 13 countries [Article]. *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications*, 10(1), Article 379. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-023-01840-6>
920. Lee, D., & Kim, K. (2021). Research and development investment and collaboration framework for the hydrogen economy in South Korea [Article]. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 13(19), Article 10686. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su131910686>
921. Lee, D., Ng, P. M. L., & Wut, T. M. (2022). Virtual Reality in Festivals: A Systematic Literature Review and Implications for Consumer Research [Article]. *Emerging Science Journal*, 6(5), 1153-1166. <https://doi.org/10.28991/ESJ-2022-06-05-016>
922. Lee, H., Son, J., Min, S., Lee, H., & Park, M. S. (2023). Natural Resources Conflicts on Borderlands by the Five Spheres of Earth System [Review]. *Land*, 12(2), Article 389. <https://doi.org/10.3390/land12020389>
923. Lee, M. B., Lee, C. T., Mong, G. R., Chong, W. W. F., & Sanip, S. M. (2024). A bibliometric analysis on the development trend of graphene-based transparent conductive electrodes (2009–2022) [Article]. *Materials Today Sustainability*, 25, Article 100650. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mtsust.2023.100650>

924. Lee, M. C. M., Scheepers, H., Lui, A. K. H., & Ngai, E. W. T. (2023). The implementation of artificial intelligence in organizations: A systematic literature review [Article]. *Information and Management*, 60(5), Article 103816. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.im.2023.103816>
925. Lee, S., Mott, B., Vandenberg, J., Spires, H. A., & Lester, J. (2023). Examining the Relationship of Gameplay and Learning in a Narrative-Centered Digital Game for Science Education.
926. Lee, S. H., Lee, J. H., Oh, K. S., Yoon, J. P., Seo, A., Jeong, Y. J., & Chung, S. W. (2023). Automated 3-dimensional MRI segmentation for the posterosuperior rotator cuff tear lesion using deep learning algorithm [Article]. *PLoS ONE*, 18(5 May), Article e0284111. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0284111>
927. Lera-López, F., Irisarri, M. A. G., & Fernández, M. J. S. (2017). The correlates of physical activity among the population aged 50-70 years [Article]. *Retos*, 31, 181-187. <https://doi.org/10.47197/RETOS.V0I31.50018>
928. Li, B., Tan, W., Wang, Z., Zhou, H., Zou, J., Li, Y., Yoshida, S., & Zhou, Y. (2023). Progress and prospects of gene therapy in ophthalmology from 2000 to 2022: A bibliometric analysis [Article]. *Heliyon*, 9(7), Article e18228. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e18228>
929. Li, C., Ashraf, S. F., Shahzad, F., Bashir, I., Murad, M., Syed, N., & Riaz, M. (2020). Influence of Knowledge Management Practices on Entrepreneurial and Organizational Performance: A Mediated-Moderation Model [Article]. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 11, Article 577106. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.577106>
930. Li, C., Chen, Z., Yu, T., & Song, X. (2022). Contact Tracking Development Trend Using Bibliometric Analysis [Article]. *Journal of Information Processing Systems*, 18(3), 359-373. <https://doi.org/10.3745/JIPS.01.0087>
931. Li, C., Liu, Z., & Shi, R. (2023). A comprehensive overview of cellular senescence from 1990 to 2021: A machine learning-based bibliometric analysis [Article]. *Frontiers in Medicine*, 10, Article 1072359. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmed.2023.1072359>
932. Li, G., Lin, J., Jiang, C., Feng, Q., & Wen, L. (2019). Trends in chronic hepatitis B treatment-related research from 1973 to 2018: a bibliometric and visual analysis [Review]. *Journal of International Medical Research*, 48(4). <https://doi.org/10.1177/0300060519893234>
933. Li, G., Wang, Y., Xu, X., Li, W., & Dong, G. (2021). Intelligent Cable Joint Quality Management System Based on RFID Technology.
934. Li, L., Wang, S., Zhang, S., Liu, D., & Ma, S. (2023). The Hydrogen Energy Infrastructure Location Selection Model: A Hybrid Fuzzy Decision-Making Approach [Article]. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 15(13), Article 10195. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su151310195>
935. Li, L., Zuo, J., Duan, X., Wang, S., Hu, K., & Chang, R. (2021). Impacts and mitigation measures of plastic waste: A critical review [Review]. *Environmental Impact Assessment Review*, 90, Article 106642. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eiar.2021.106642>
936. Li, M. (2020). A Systematic Review of the Research on Chinese Character Teaching and Learning [Review]. *Frontiers of Education in China*, 15(1), 39-72. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11516-020-0003-y>
937. Li, M., Gao, N., Wang, S., Ding, Y., Guo, Y. F., & Liu, Z. (2023). A bibliometric analysis of Barrett's esophagus [Article]. *European Review for Medical and Pharmacological Sciences*, 27(17), 8055-8073. https://doi.org/10.26355/eurev_202309_33566
938. Li, M., Gao, N., Wang, S., Guo, Y., & Liu, Z. (2023). A global bibliometric and visualized analysis of the status and trends of gastroparesis research [Review]. *European Journal of Medical Research*, 28(1), Article 543. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40001-023-01537-1>
939. Li, M., Luo, N., & Lu, Y. (2017). Biomass energy technological paradigm (BETP): Trends in this sector [Review]. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 9(4), Article 567. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su9040567>

940. Li, M., Zhang, K., He, J., Zhang, W., Lv, T., Wang, L., Xing, W., & Yu, H. (2023). Hepatic arterial infusion chemotherapy in hepatocellular carcinoma: A bibliometric and knowledge-map analysis [Article]. *Frontiers in Oncology*, 12, Article 1071860. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fonc.2022.1071860>
941. Li, P., Zhao, Y., Sufian, M., & Deifalla, A. F. (2023). Scientometric analysis of flood forecasting for Asia region and discussion on machine learning methods [Review]. *Open Geosciences*, 15(1), Article 20220475. <https://doi.org/10.1515/geo-2022-0475>
942. Li, R., Cheng, P., Lan, H., Li, W., Gerada, D., & Hong, Y. (2021). Stator non-uniform radial ventilation design methodology for a 15 mw turbo-synchronous generator based on single ventilation duct subsystem [Article]. *Energies*, 14(10), Article 2760. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en14102760>
943. Li, S., Liu, Y., & Su, Y. S. (2022). Differential Analysis of Teachers' Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) Abilities according to Teaching Stages and Educational Levels [Article]. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 14(12), Article 7176. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14127176>
944. Li, W., Aste, T., Caccioli, F., & Livan, G. (2019). Early coauthorship with top scientists predicts success in academic careers [Article]. *Nature Communications*, 10(1), Article 5170. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-019-13130-4>
945. Li, X. (2015). Work in progress - Students and engineers collaborating in global virtual context.
946. Li, X., & Lei, L. (2021). A bibliometric analysis of topic modelling studies (2000–2017) [Article]. *Journal of Information Science*, 47(2), 161-175. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0165551519877049>
947. Li, X., & Love, P. E. D. (2020). State-of-the-Art Review of Urban Rail Transit Public-Private Partnerships [Review]. *Journal of Infrastructure Systems*, 26(3), Article 03120002. [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)IS.1943-555X.0000552](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)IS.1943-555X.0000552)
948. Li, X., Qin, D., Hu, Y., Ahmad, W., Ahmad, A., Aslam, F., & Joyklad, P. (2022). A systematic review of waste materials in cement-based composites for construction applications [Review]. *Journal of Building Engineering*, 45, Article 103447. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jobbe.2021.103447>
949. Li, X., Yuan, J., Liu, X., Ke, Y., & Jia, S. (2022). Identifying Critical Influencing Factors of the Value Creation of Urban Rail Transit PPP Projects in China [Article]. *Buildings*, 12(8), Article 1080. <https://doi.org/10.3390/buildings12081080>
950. Li, Y., He, M., Zou, Z., Bian, X., Huang, X., Yang, C., Wei, S., & Dai, S. (2019). Artificial liver research output and citations from 2004 to 2017: A bibliometric analysis [Review]. *PeerJ*, 2019(1), Article e6178. <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.6178>
951. Li, Z., Liang, W., & Zhao, G. (2023). Rockburst Hazard Evaluation Using an Extended COPRAS Method with Interval-Valued Fuzzy Information [Article]. *Applied Sciences (Switzerland)*, 13(17), Article 9941. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app13179941>
952. Liao, N. L., Wu, C. Z., Jiang, Z., Huang, Y. Z., Ding, H. R., Li, R. H., & Li, Y. (2022). Research trends and hotspots related to exosomes in head and neck tumors based on bibliometric analysis [Article]. *Chinese Journal of Cancer Prevention and Treatment*, 29(16), 1229-1235. <https://doi.org/10.16073/j.cnki.cjcpt.2022.16.12>
953. Lihua, Y. (2023). Research on image segmentation methods based on optimization theory [Article]. *International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00170-023-12671-9>
954. Lima, F. R. P., Da Silva, A. L., Godinho Filho, M., & Dias, E. M. (2018). Systematic review: resilience enablers to combat counterfeit medicines [Review]. *Supply Chain Management*, 23(2), 117-135. <https://doi.org/10.1108/SCM-04-2017-0155>
955. Lin, C. N., & Roan, J. (2011). An exploration study of virtual project team development stages [Article]. *Advances in Information Sciences and Service Sciences*, 3(5), 63-71. <https://doi.org/10.4156/aiss.vol3.issue5.8>

956. Lin, C. N., & Roan, J. (2022). Identifying the development stages of virtual teams – An application of social network analysis [Article]. *Information Technology and People*, 35(7), 2368-2392. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ITP-04-2020-0251>
957. Lin, X. F., Hwang, G. J., Wang, J., Zhou, Y., Li, W., Liu, J., & Liang, Z. M. (2023). Effects of a contextualised reflective mechanism-based augmented reality learning model on students' scientific inquiry learning performances, behavioural patterns, and higher order thinking [Article]. *Interactive Learning Environments*, 31(10), 6931-6951. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10494820.2022.2057546>
958. Lin, X. F., Wang, Z., Zhou, W., Luo, G., Hwang, G. J., Zhou, Y., Wang, J., Hu, Q., Li, W., & Liang, Z. M. (2023). Technological support to foster students' artificial intelligence ethics: An augmented reality-based contextualized dilemma discussion approach [Article]. *Computers and Education*, 201, Article 104813. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2023.104813>
959. Lippert, H., & Dulewicz, V. (2018). A profile of high-performing global virtual teams [Article]. *Team Performance Management*, 24(3-4), 169-185. <https://doi.org/10.1108/TPM-09-2016-0040>
960. Lis, A. (2020). Sport management: Bibliometric study of key source titles in the research field [Article]. *Journal of Physical Education and Sport*, 20, 2423-2430, Article 331. <https://doi.org/10.7752/jpes.2020.s4331>
961. Lis, A., Sudolska, A., Pietryka, I., & Kozakiewicz, A. (2020). Cloud computing and energy efficiency: Mapping the thematic structure of research [Review]. *Energies*, 13(15), Article 4117. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en13164117>
962. Lis, A., Sudolska, A., & Tomanek, M. (2020). Mapping research on sustainable supply-chain management [Article]. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 12(10), Article 3987. <https://doi.org/10.3390/SU12103987>
963. Liu, C., & Li, K. (2020). Mapping the field: a bibliometric analysis of land use and carbon emissions (LUCE) research from 1987 to 2018 [Article]. *Library Hi Tech*, 39(2), 396-411. <https://doi.org/10.1108/LHT-12-2019-0252>
964. Liu, M., Wang, J., Wang, N., Xie, H., Zhang, H., Shen, H., & Gao, X. (2022). Design and optimization of sheller for ginkgo nut: A study about multifunctional ginkgo nut sheller [Article]. *PLoS ONE*, 17(10 October), Article e0276139. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0276139>
965. Liu, W., Wang, S., Dong, D., & Wang, J. (2020). Evaluation of the intelligent logistics eco-index: Evidence from China [Article]. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 274, Article 123127. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.123127>
966. Liu, W., Wang, S., & Wang, J. (2023). Evaluation method of path selection for smart supply chain innovation [Article]. *Annals of Operations Research*, 322(1), 167-193. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10479-021-04031-1>
967. Liu, W., Wei, S., Wang, S., & K. Lim, M. (2022). Theoretical framework of agricultural precision management based on the smart supply chain: evidence from China [Article]. *Production Planning and Control*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09537287.2022.2088424>
968. Liu, W., Ye, S., & Moultrie, J. (2019). Exploring traditional and new web-based methods to involve customers in new product development [Conference Paper]. *International Journal of Product Development*, 23(1), 42-64. <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJPD.2019.098398>
969. Liu, X., Sun, R., Wang, S., & Wu, Y. J. (2020). The research landscape of big data: a bibliometric analysis [Article]. *Library Hi Tech*, 38(2), 367-384. <https://doi.org/10.1108/LHT-01-2019-0024>
970. Liu, X., Zhu, W., & Seong, D. (2023). Exploring the Influence of Art Teachers' Core Quality Improvement on Students' Learning Motivation and Educational Policy: Empirical Evidence based on Chinese Universities [Article]. *Educational Administration: Theory and Practice*, 29(3), 48-68. <https://doi.org/10.52152/kuey.v29i3.702>

971. Liu, Y., Mai, F., & MacDonald, C. (2019). A Big-Data Approach to Understanding the Thematic Landscape of the Field of Business Ethics, 1982–2016 [Article]. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 160(1), 127-150. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-018-3806-5>
972. Liu, Y. G., Jiang, S. T., Zhang, L., Zheng, H., Zhang, T., Zhang, J. W., Zhao, H. T., Sang, X. T., Xu, Y. Y., & Lu, X. (2023). Worldwide productivity and research trend of publications concerning tumor immune microenvironment (TIME): a bibliometric study [Article]. *European Journal of Medical Research*, 28(1), Article 229. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40001-023-01195-3>
973. Liu, Z. (2022). Mapping the research trends of third language acquisition: A bibliometric analysis based on Scopus [Article]. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13, Article 1021517. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.1021517>
974. Liu, Z. Y., Shaikh, Z. A., & Gazizova, F. (2020). Using the concept of game-based learning in education [Article]. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning*, 15(14), 53-64. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijet.v15i14.14675>
975. Lodemann, S., Lechtenberg, S., Wesendrup, K., Hellingrath, B., Hoberg, K., & Kersten, W. (2022). Supply Chain Analytics: Investigating Literature-Practice Perspectives and Research Opportunities [Article]. *Logistics Research*, 15(1), Article 7. https://doi.org/10.23773/2022_7
976. Lopez-Fernandez, D., Gordillo, A., Alarcon, P. P., & Tovar, E. (2021). Comparing Traditional Teaching and Game-Based Learning Using Teacher-Authored Games on Computer Science Education [Article]. *IEEE Transactions on Education*, 64(4), 367-373. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TE.2021.3057849>
977. López-Fernández, D., Gordillo, A., Lara-Cabrera, R., & Alegre, J. (2023). Comparing effectiveness of educational video games of different genres in computer science education [Article]. *Entertainment Computing*, 47, Article 100588. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.entcom.2023.100588>
978. Lopez-Fernandez, D., Gordillo, A., Perez, J., & Tovar, E. (2023). Learning and Motivational Impact of Game-Based Learning: Comparing Face-to-Face and Online Formats on Computer Science Education [Article]. *IEEE Transactions on Education*, 66(4), 360-368. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TE.2023.3241099>
979. Lopez-Martinez, R. E., & Sierra, G. (2020). Research trends in the international literature on natural language processing, 2000-2019 - A bibliometric study [Article]. *Journal of Scientometric Research*, 9(3), 310-318. <https://doi.org/10.5530/JSCIRES.9.3.38>
980. Lopez-Morales, J. S. (2018). Multilatinas: a systematic literature review [Review]. *Review of International Business and Strategy*, 28(3-4), 331-357. <https://doi.org/10.1108/RIBS-05-2018-0041>
981. López-Robles, J. R., Otegi-Olaso, J. R., Porto-Gómez, I., Gamboa-Rosales, H., & Gamboa-Rosales, N. K. (2020). The relationship between Business Intelligence and Competitive Intelligence: A retrospective analysis and literature review from 1959 to 2017 [Article]. *Revista Espanola de Documentacion Cientifica*, 43(1), Article e256. <https://doi.org/10.3989/REDC.2020.1.1619>
982. Lorenzo, G., Lorenzo-Lledó, A., Lledó, A., & Pérez-Vázquez, E. (2020). Application of virtual reality in people with ASD from 1996 to 2019 [Review]. *Journal of Enabling Technologies*, 14(2), 99-114. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JET-01-2020-0005>
983. Lou, Y., Khan, K., Amin, M. N., Ahmad, W., Deifalla, A. F., & Ahmad, A. (2023). Performance characteristics of cementitious composites modified with silica fume: A systematic review [Article]. *Case Studies in Construction Materials*, 18, Article e01753. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cscm.2022.e01753>
984. Lowes, S. (2014). How much "Group" is there in online group work? [Article]. *Journal of Asynchronous Learning Network*, 18(1). <https://doi.org/10.24059/olj.v18i1.373>

985. Lu, L., Norder, K. A., Sawhney, A., & Emich, K. J. (2023). Setting the programmatic agenda: A comprehensive bibliometric overview of team mechanism research [Article]. *Journal of Business Research*, 154, Article 113297. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2022.09.002>
986. Lu, W., Tam, V. W. Y., Chen, H., & Du, L. (2020). A holistic review of research on carbon emissions of green building construction industry [Article]. *Engineering, Construction and Architectural Management*, 27(5), 1065-1092. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ECAM-06-2019-0283>
987. Lucas-González, R., Viuda-Martos, M., Pérez-Alvarez, J. A., & Fernández-López, J. (2018). In vitro digestion models suitable for foods: Opportunities for new fields of application and challenges [Review]. *Food Research International*, 107, 423-436. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodres.2018.02.055>
988. Lukyanova, Y. Y., & Shamaeva, N. P. (2019). Research on e-learning development trends as Russian federation economy digitalization direction.
989. Lumor, T., Pulkkinen, M., Hirvonen, A., & Neittaanmäki, P. (2021). Creating the Socio-Technical Context Needed to Derive Benefits from Big Data Initiatives in Healthcare [Article]. *Scandinavian Journal of Information Systems*, 33(2), 3-58, Article 1. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85127428011&partnerID=40&md5=a7a38136aaa743aa0c0dec409daaf4c5>
990. Lundberg, L. (2023). Bibliometric mining of research directions and trends for big data [Article]. *Journal of Big Data*, 10(1), Article 112. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40537-023-00793-6>
991. Luo, J., Wang, M., Chen, B., & Sun, M. (2022). Exposure to Nature Sounds through a Mobile Application in Daily Life: Effects on Learning Performance among University Students [Article]. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(21), Article 14583. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph192114583>
992. Lussak, A., & Darmawan, I. (2022). Examining the Impact of IT Experience, Training, Self-Efficacy and Anxiety on Remote Work Quality in Indonesia.
993. Lyu, X., & Costas, R. (2021). Studying the characteristics of scientific communities using individual-level bibliometrics: the case of Big Data research [Article]. *Scientometrics*, 126(8), 6965-6987. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-021-04034-6>
994. Ma, H., Ismail, L., Noordin, N., & Razali, A. B. (2023). Bibliometric analysis of willingness to communicate in the English as a second language (ESL) context [Review]. *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications*, 10(1), Article 702. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-023-02109-8>
995. Ma, L., Li, J., Jin, R., Ke, Y., & Yuan, J. (2019). A holistic review of public-private partnership literature published between 2008 and 2018 [Review]. *Advances in Civil Engineering*, 2019, Article 7094653. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2019/7094653>
996. Ma, X., Hao, Y., & Liu, L. (2021). Progress in nanomaterials-based optical and electrochemical methods for the assays of exosomes [Review]. *International Journal of Nanomedicine*, 16, 7575-7608. <https://doi.org/10.2147/IJN.S333969>
997. Machado, H. P. V., & Elias, M. L. G. G. R. (2020). Knowledge management: The field's constitution, themes, and research perspectives [Review]. *Transinformacao*, 32, Article e200037. <https://doi.org/10.1590/2318-0889202032E200037>
998. Maddodi, C. B., & Upadhyaya, P. (2023). In-app advertising: a systematic literature review and implications for future research [Review]. *Spanish Journal of Marketing - ESIC*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/SJME-05-2022-0120>
999. Madenoğlu, F. S. (2023). Industry 4.0: A bibliometric analysis. In *Organizational Behavior in the Digital World* (pp. 149-163). Nova Science Publishers, Inc. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85179561165&partnerID=40&md5=bc9034bc4738930c82f37940c183643c>

1000. Maduka, N. S., Edwards, H., Greenwood, D., Osborne, A., & Babatunde, S. O. (2018). Analysis of competencies for effective virtual team leadership in building successful organisations [Article]. *Benchmarking*, 25(2), 696-712. <https://doi.org/10.1108/BIJ-08-2016-0124>
1001. Maes, J. D., & Weldy, T. G. (2018). Building effective virtual teams: Expanding od research and practice [Article]. *Organization Development Journal*, 36(3), 83-90. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85055037560&partnerID=40&md5=202f82656ea858283a07c18809ff3391>
1002. Magana, A. J., Karabiyik, T., Thomas, P., Jaiswal, A., Perera, V., & Dworkin, J. (2022). Teamwork facilitation and conflict resolution training in a HyFlex course during the COVID-19 pandemic [Article]. *Journal of Engineering Education*, 111(2), 446-473. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jee.20450>
1003. Maganga, D. P., & Taifa, I. W. R. (2023). Quality 4.0 conceptualisation: an emerging quality management concept for manufacturing industries [Article]. *TQM Journal*, 35(2), 389-413. <https://doi.org/10.1108/TQM-11-2021-0328>
1004. Maghami, M. R., Hassani, R., Gomes, C., Hizam, H., Othman, M. L., & Behmanesh, M. (2020). Hybrid energy management with respect to a hydrogen energy system and demand response [Article]. *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, 45(3), 1499-1509. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2019.10.223>
1005. Maghami, M. R., Pasupuleti, J., & Ling, C. M. (2023). A Static and Dynamic Analysis of Photovoltaic Penetration into MV Distribution Network [Article]. *Processes*, 11(4), Article 1172. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pr11041172>
1006. Magni, D., Pezzi, A., & Vrontis, D. (2020). Towards a framework of students' co-creation behaviour in higher education institutions [Article]. *International Journal of Managerial and Financial Accounting*, 12(2), 119-148. <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJMFA.2020.109129>
1007. Magnone, E. (2014). An overview on the South Korean scientific production in the field of chemistry (1993-2012) [Review]. *Information (Switzerland)*, 5(2), 285-304. <https://doi.org/10.3390/info5020285>
1008. Magnone, E. (2015). Analysis of scholarly communication activities in Buddhism and Buddhist studies [Article]. *Information (Switzerland)*, 6(2), 162-182. <https://doi.org/10.3390/info6020162>
1009. Mahalakshmi, G. S., Muthu Selvi, G., & Sendhilkumar, S. (2019). Measuring authorial indices from the eye of co-author(s). In B. K. Panigrahi, S. Tiwari, P. K. Singh, M. C. Trivedi, & K. K. Mishra (Eds.), (Vol. 669, pp. 423-433): Springer Verlag.
1010. Mahesh, V., Gobinath, R., KIRGIZ, M. S., Shekar, R. P. V., & Shewale, M. (2022). Global Trends of Research Productivity in Natural Fibre Reinforced Composites: Comprehensive Scientometric Analysis [Article]. *Journal of Natural Fibers*, 19(16), 13088-13105. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15440478.2022.2085227>
1011. Mahi, M., Mobin, M. A., Habib, M., & Akter, S. (2021). A bibliometric analysis of pandemic and epidemic studies in economics: future agenda for COVID-19 research [Article]. *Social Sciences and Humanities Open*, 4(1), Article 100165. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssaho.2021.100165>
1012. Mahinkanda, M. M. M. P., Ochoa Paniagua, J. J., Rameezdeen, R., Chileshe, N., & Gu, N. (2023). Design Decision-Making for Construction Waste Minimisation: A Systematic Literature Review [Review]. *Buildings*, 13(11), Article 2763. <https://doi.org/10.3390/buildings13112763>
1013. Mahmood, M. N., & Dhakal, S. P. (2022). A Bibliometric Analysis of Ageing Literature: Global and Asia-Pacific Trends. In *Ageing in Asia and the Pacific in Changing Times: Implications for Sustainable Development* (pp. 33-47). Springer Nature. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-16-6663-6_3

1014. Mahmood, M. N., & Dhakal, S. P. (2023). Ageing population and society: a scientometric analysis [Article]. *Quality and Quantity*, 57(4), 3133-3150. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11135-022-01509-3>
1015. Mahmud, W., Fanani, A. Z., Santoso, H. A., & Budiman, F. (2023). Review of Time Series Classification Techniques and Methods.
1016. Maia, D. R. P., Lizarelli, F. L., & Gambi, L. D. N. (2023). Industry 4.0 and Six Sigma: a systematic review of the literature and research agenda proposal [Review]. *Benchmarking*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/BIJ-05-2022-0289>
1017. Maia, M. L. F., Pantoja, L. V. P. S., Da Conceição, B. C., Machado-Ferraro, K. M., Gonçalves, J. K. M., Dos Santos-Filho, P. M., Lima, R. R., Fontes-Junior, E. A., & Maia, C. S. F. (2023). Ketamine Clinical Use on the Pediatric Critically Ill Infant: A Global Bibliometric and Critical Review of Literature [Review]. *Journal of Clinical Medicine*, 12(14), Article 4643. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jcm12144643>
1018. Maisonobe, M. (2022). The future of urban models in the Big Data and AI era: a bibliometric analysis (2000–2019) [Article]. *AI and Society*, 37(1), 177-194. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00146-021-01166-4>
1019. Majerova, I., & Abdrazakova, A. (2021). A bibliometric mapping of cost-benefit analysis—Three decades of studies [Article]. *Economies*, 9(3), Article 110. <https://doi.org/10.3390/economies9030110>
1020. Majhi, S., Sahu, L., & Behera, K. (2023). Practices for enhancing research visibility, citations and impact: review of literature [Article]. *Aslib Journal of Information Management*, 75(6), 1280-1305. <https://doi.org/10.1108/AJIM-11-2023-532>
1021. Majid, M. A., Kasuan, N., Muhamad, N. A., Othman, N., Khairul Anuar, N. H., Dalila Khirul Ashar, N., Hairudin, M. A., & Kamarudin Hasan, K. (2022). A Bibliometrics Analysis of Research Trends on Pipeline Cathodic Protection(CP).
1022. Majid, N. A., Ramli, Z., Sum, S. M., & Awang, A. H. (2021). Sustainable palm oil certification scheme frameworks and impacts: A systematic literature review [Article]. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 13(6), Article 3263. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13063263>
1023. Makabate, C. T., Musonda, I., Okoro, C. S., & Chileshe, N. (2022). Scientometric analysis of BIM adoption by SMEs in the architecture, construction and engineering sector [Article]. *Engineering, Construction and Architectural Management*, 29(1), 179-203. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ECAM-02-2020-0139>
1024. Makovska, I., Dhaka, P., Chantziaras, I., Pessoa, J., & Dewulf, J. (2023). The Role of Wildlife and Pests in the Transmission of Pathogenic Agents to Domestic Pigs: A Systematic Review [Review]. *Animals*, 13(11), Article 1830. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ani13111830>
1025. Malacina, I., & Teplov, R. (2022). Supply chain innovation research: A bibliometric network analysis and literature review [Review]. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 251, Article 108540. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpe.2022.108540>
1026. Malek, E. J., & Abdul Rahim, A. R. (2022). A thematic review of forest certification publications from 2017 to 2021: Analysis of pattern and trends for future studies [Review]. *Trees, Forests and People*, 10, Article 100331. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tfp.2022.100331>
1027. Malik, B. A., & Mushtaq, M. (2020). Citations in chemical engineering research: Factors and their assessment [Article]. *Annals of Library and Information Studies*, 67(1), 36-44. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85090749923&partnerID=40&md5=6ad8d65c5c675fae7828f7e029245903>
1028. Malki, B., Uman, T., & Pittino, D. (2022). The entrepreneurial financing of the immigrant entrepreneurs: a literature review [Article]. *Small Business Economics*, 58(3), 1337-1365. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11187-020-00444-7>

1029. Mall, S., Panigrahi, T. R., & Verma, S. (2023). BIBLIOMETRIC ANALYSIS ON BIG DATA APPLICATIONS IN INSURANCE SECTOR: PAST, PRESENT, AND FUTURE RESEARCH DIRECTIONS [Review]. *Journal of Financial Management, Markets and Institutions*, 11(1), Article 2330001. <https://doi.org/10.1142/S2282717X23300015>
1030. Mallas, A., Samanta, M., & Xenos, M. (2022). Evaluating a Game-based and a Web-based User Interface Using Skin Conductivity Signals and Gamers and Non-Gamers Preferences.
1031. Mangas-Vega, A. (2022). Evolution of citation characteristics in monographies: the non-citation case [Article]. *Ibersid*, 16(1), 13-20. <https://doi.org/10.54886/IBERSID.V16I1.4737>
1032. Mangas-Vega, A. (2023). Evolution of citation characteristics in monographies: the non-citation case [Article]. *Endoxa*, 16(1), 13-20. <https://doi.org/10.54886/ibersid.v16i1.4737>
1033. Mannu, R., Karthikeyan, V., Velu, N., Arumugam, C., Roy, V. A. L., Gopalan, A. I., Saianand, G., Sonar, P., Lee, K. P., Kim, W. J., Lee, D. E., & Kannan, V. (2021). Polyethylene glycol coated magnetic nanoparticles: Hybrid nanofluid formulation, properties and drug delivery prospects [Article]. *Nanomaterials*, 11(2), 1-18, Article 440. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nano11020440>
1034. Mansoor, Z., Qadri, S., & Ikram, S. (2022). Functional Requirements Management in Virtual Team Environment. In D. N. A. Jawawi, I. S. Bajwa, & R. Kazmi (Eds.), (Vol. 1615 CCIS, pp. 125-133): Springer Science and Business Media Deutschland GmbH.
1035. Mansour, A. Z., Ahmi, A., Alkhuzaie, A. S. H., Alhmoode, M. A., Popoola, O. M. J., & Altarawneh, M. (2023). State of art in tax evasion research: A bibliometric review [Review]. *Review of Education*, 11(3), Article e3422. <https://doi.org/10.1002/rev3.3422>
1036. Mansour, A. Z., Ahmi, A., Popoola, O. M. J., & Znaimat, A. (2022). Discovering the global landscape of fraud detection studies: a bibliometric review [Article]. *Journal of Financial Crime*, 29(2), 701-720. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JFC-03-2021-0052>
1037. Mansour, K., Al-Daoud, E., & Al-Karaky, B. (2021). I. Predicting future citation counts using machine learning.
1038. Manzoor, A. (2017). Skill building for virtual teams. In *Remote Work and Collaboration: Breakthroughs in Research and Practice* (Vol. 1-2, pp. 214-225). IGI Global. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-5225-1918-8.ch012>
1039. Marinov, M. A., & Almor, T. (2023). Virtual teams across national borders: An overview. In *Virtual Teams Across National Borders* (pp. 1-13). Taylor and Francis. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003398745-1>
1040. Marques, A., & Da Luz, S. M. (2021). Use of biodegradable polymer for development of environmental tracers: A bibliometric review [Review]. *Polimeros*, 31(1), Article e2021012. <https://doi.org/10.1590/0104-1428.00221>
1041. Márquez-Hernández, V. V., Gutiérrez-Puertas, L., Garrido-Molina, J. M., García-Viola, A., Alcayde-García, A., & Aguilera-Manrique, G. (2021). Worldviews on evidence-based cardiopulmonary resuscitation using a novel method [Article]. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(18), Article 9536. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18189536>
1042. Martinez, E. S., Wu, A. S., & McMahan, R. P. (2022). Research Trends in Virtual Reality Locomotion Techniques.
1043. Martínez, I. D., & Signes, Á. P. (2021). Integration of Sustainable Practices in Firms: The Specifics of the Tourism, Leisure and Hospitality Sectors.
1044. Martínez, R. A., & Anderson, T. (2015). Are the most highly cited articles the ones that are the most downloaded? A bibliometric study of IRRODL [Article]. *International Review of Research in Open and Distance Learning*, 16(3), 18-40. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84933528849&partnerID=40&md5=54869adbf97b5065f79e45c501dccde4>

1045. Martínez-López, J. I., Barrón-González, S., & López, A. M. (2019). Which are the tools available for scholars? A review of assisting software for authors during peer reviewing process [Review]. *Publications*, 7(3), Article 59. <https://doi.org/10.3390/publications7030059>
1046. Martínez-Martínez, A., Cegarra-Navarro, J. G., Cobo, M. J., & de Valon, T. (2023). Impacts and Implications for Advancing in Environmental Knowledge in Hospitality Industry in COVID Society: a Bibliometric Analysis [Article]. *Journal of the Knowledge Economy*, 14(2), 2026-2053. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13132-022-00910-5>
1047. Martínez-Martínez, A., Cegarra-Navarro, J. G., & Garcia-Perez, A. (2023). Sustainability knowledge management and organisational learning in tourism: current approaches and areas for future development [Article]. *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 31(4), 895-907. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09669582.2022.2086560>
1048. Martínez-Navarro, J., Campayo-Sánchez, F., & Ostrovskaya Fedorova, L. (2023). Mapping the evolution of tourism research: the Spanish case [Review]. *Journal of Historical Research in Marketing*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JHRM-07-2023-0030>
1049. Martins, S., & Santos, C. (2023). The OH!BUG App: Learning to Identify Plants Through Their Characteristics. In L. Tomczyk (Ed.), (Vol. 1916 CCIS, pp. 115-124): Springer Science and Business Media Deutschland GmbH.
1050. Marusic, U., Kavcic, V., Pisot, R., & Goswami, N. (2019). The role of enhanced cognition to counteract detrimental effects of prolonged bed rest: Current evidence and perspectives [Review]. *Frontiers in Physiology*, 10(JAN), Article 1864. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphys.2018.01864>
1051. Masangcay, I. B., Tolentino, J. C. G., Miranda, J. P. P., Baltazar, M. A. N., Santos, E. B., & Custodio, S. I. (2023). Current research, emerging trends, gaps, and opportunities in physical education in the ASEAN context: A literature review and bibliometric analysis. In *Modern Perspectives and Current Trends in Asian Education, Psychology, and Sociology* (pp. 26-69). IGI Global. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-6684-7375-7.ch002>
1052. Masmuzidin, M. Z., Aziz, N. A. A., & Suhaimi, S. (2022). A Systematic Review of Augmented Reality Design for Young Children [Article]. *International Journal of Interactive Mobile Technologies*, 16(17), 60-71. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijim.v16i17.31837>
1053. Matsimbe, J., Dinka, M., Olukanni, D., & Musonda, I. (2022). A Bibliometric Analysis of Research Trends in Geopolymer [Review]. *Materials*, 15(19), Article 6979. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma15196979>
1054. Matsimbe, J., Dinka, M., Olukanni, D., & Musonda, I. (2022). Geopolymer: A Systematic Review of Methodologies [Review]. *Materials*, 15(19), Article 6852. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma15196852>
1055. Mattarelli, E., Tagliaventi, M. R., Carli, G., & Gupta, A. (2017). The Role of Brokers and Social Identities in the Development of Capabilities in Global Virtual Teams [Article]. *Journal of International Management*, 23(4), 382-398. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.intman.2017.01.003>
1056. Matthews, T., Chen, J., Whittaker, S., Pal, A., Zhu, H., Badenes, H., & Smith, B. A. (2014). Goals and perceived success of online enterprise communities: What is important to leaders & members?
1057. Matthews, T., Whittaker, S., Badenes, H., Smith, B. A., Muller, M., Ehrlich, K., Zhou, M. X., & Lau, T. (2013). Community Insights: Helping community leaders enhance the value of enterprise online communities.
1058. Matveeva, N., & Poldin, O. (2016). Citation of scholars in co-authorship network: Analysis of google scholar data [Article]. *Applied Econometrics*, 44, 100-118. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85028757817&partnerID=40&md5=03820dc24ecc7e2896e8010be04d608e>

1059. Maucuer, R., & Renaud, A. (2019). Business model research: A bibliometric analysis of origins and trends [Article]. *Management (France)*, 22(2), 176-215. <https://doi.org/10.3917/mana.222.0176>
1060. Mayowa, B., & Chinda, T. (2023). Environmental Assessment of Demolition Tools Used in Townhouse Demolition: System Dynamics Modeling [Article]. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 15(19), Article 14382. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su151914382>
1061. Mazón-Ortiz, G., Cerda-Mejía, G., Gutiérrez Morales, E., Diéguez-Santana, K., Ruso, J. M., & González-Díaz, H. (2023). Trends in Nanoparticles for Leishmania Treatment: A Bibliometric and Network Analysis [Review]. *Diseases*, 11(4), Article 153. <https://doi.org/10.3390/diseases11040153>
1062. Mazumder, G. C., Ibrahim, A. S. M., Rahman, M. H., & Huque, S. (2021). Solar PV and Wind Powered Green Hydrogen Production Cost for Selected Locations [Article]. *International Journal of Renewable Energy Research*, 11(4), 1748-1759. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85123899142&partnerID=40&md5=8e2075cfab9a7409d1c06b6faff29781>
1063. Md Khudzari, J., Kurian, J., Tartakovsky, B., & Raghavan, G. S. V. (2018). Bibliometric analysis of global research trends on microbial fuel cells using Scopus database [Article]. *Biochemical Engineering Journal*, 136, 51-60. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bej.2018.05.002>
1064. Md Osman, S. Z., & Md Napeah, R. (2021). A visual pattern of two decades of literature on mobile learning: A bibliometric analysis [Article]. *International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research*, 20(10), 291-312. <https://doi.org/10.26803/ijlter.20.10.16>
1065. Medina, E., Mazaira, A., & Alén, E. (2022). Innovation in the broadcasters' business model: A bibliometric and review approach [Article]. *European Research on Management and Business Economics*, 28(3), Article 100202. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iedeen.2022.100202>
1066. Mehmood, A., Ahmed, S., Viza, E., Bogush, A., & Ayyub, R. M. (2021). Drivers and barriers towards circular economy in agri-food supply chain: A review [Article]. *Business Strategy and Development*, 4(4), 465-481. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bsd2.171>
1067. Mehmood, K., Bao, Y., Saifullah, Bibi, S., Dahlawi, S., Yaseen, M., Abrar, M. M., Srivastava, P., Fahad, S., & Faraj, T. K. (2022). Contributions of Open Biomass Burning and Crop Straw Burning to Air Quality: Current Research Paradigm and Future Outlooks [Article]. *Frontiers in Environmental Science*, 10, Article 852492. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fenvs.2022.852492>
1068. Mehrollahia, T., Nora, M. M., Danaeab, M., & Trenamanc, B. (2019). How scientific production positively affect social psychology intervention? A bibliometric analysis on the science of well-being [Article]. *Humanities and Social Sciences Reviews*, 7(5), 327-339. <https://doi.org/10.18510/hssr.2019.7538>
1069. Mei, J., Xu, G., Ahmad, W., Khan, K., Amin, M. N., Aslam, F., & Alaskar, A. (2022). Promoting sustainable materials using recycled rubber in concrete: A review [Review]. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 373, Article 133927. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.133927>
1070. Meishar-Tal, H., & Kesler, A. (2023). "If I create a game I'll learn": online game creation as a tool to promote learning skills of students with learning difficulties [Article]. *Interactive Learning Environments*, 31(5), 3071-3082. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10494820.2021.1919146>
1071. Memisevic, H., Ajnadzic, N., & Memisevic, M. (2022). Measuring Scholarly Impact in Bosnia and Herzegovina: The Picture Beyond the Numbers [Article]. *Journal of Scientometric Research*, 11(1), 112-117. <https://doi.org/10.5530/jscires.11.1.11>
1072. Memon, A. R., To, Q. G., & Vandelanotte, C. (2021). Vigorously cited: A bibliometric analysis of the 500 most cited physical activity articles [Article]. *Journal of Physical Activity and Health*, 18(8), 904-919. <https://doi.org/10.1123/jpah.2020-0744>
1073. Memon, A. R., Vandelanotte, C., Olds, T., Duncan, M. J., & Vincent, G. E. (2020). Research Combining Physical Activity and Sleep: A Bibliometric Analysis [Review]. *Perceptual and Motor Skills*, 127(1), 154-181. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0031512519889780>

1074. Mendiratta, A., Singh, S., Yadav, S. S., & Mahajan, A. (2023). Bibliometric and Topic Modeling Analysis of Corporate Social Irresponsibility [Review]. *Global Journal of Flexible Systems Management*, 24(3), 319-339. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40171-023-00343-2>
1075. Mendoza-Muñoz, M., Vega-Muñoz, A., Carlos-Vivas, J., Denche-Zamorano, Á., Adsuar, J. C., Raimundo, A., Salazar-Sepúlveda, G., Contreras-Barraza, N., & Muñoz-Urtubia, N. (2022). The Bibliometric Analysis of Studies on Physical Literacy for a Healthy Life [Article]. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(22), Article 15211. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph192215211>
1076. Menezes, M. B. C., Ruiz-Hernández, D., & Guimaraes, R. (2016). The component commonality problem in a real multidimensional space: An algorithmic approach [Article]. *European Journal of Operational Research*, 249(1), 105-116. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejor.2015.08.021>
1077. Mengis, H. (2020). The role of individuals, incumbents, and failure in catch-up processes: a systematic literature review [Article]. *Technology Analysis and Strategic Management*, 1-25. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09537325.2020.1790515>
1078. Meriton, R., Bhandal, R., Graham, G., & Brown, A. (2021). An examination of the generative mechanisms of value in big data-enabled supply chain management research [Review]. *International Journal of Production Research*, 59(23), 7283-7310. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00207543.2020.1832273>
1079. Merli, R., Preziosi, M., & Acampora, A. (2018). How do scholars approach the circular economy? A systematic literature review [Review]. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 178, 703-722. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2017.12.112>
1080. Merli, R., Preziosi, M., Acampora, A., Lucchetti, M. C., & Petrucci, E. (2020). Recycled fibers in reinforced concrete: A systematic literature review [Article]. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 248, Article 119207. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.119207>
1081. Metelenko, N. G., Kovalenko, O. V., Makedon, V., Merzhynskyi, Y., & Rudych, A. I. (2019). Infrastructure security of formation and development of sectoral corporate clusters [Article]. *Journal of Security and Sustainability Issues*, 9(1), 77-89. [https://doi.org/10.9770/jssi.2019.9.1\(7\)](https://doi.org/10.9770/jssi.2019.9.1(7))
1082. Meyer, I. P., Bond-Barnard, T. J., Steyn, H., & Jordaan, J. (2016). Exploring the use of computer-mediated video communication in engineering projects in South Africa [Article]. *South African Journal of Industrial Engineering*, 27(2), 60-71. <https://doi.org/10.7166/27-2-1298>
1083. Meyer, N., Ben Said, F., Alkathiri, N. A., & Soliman, M. (2023). A scientometric analysis of entrepreneurial and the digital economy scholarship: state of the art and an agenda for future research [Review]. *Journal of Innovation and Entrepreneurship*, 12(1), Article 70. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13731-023-00340-w>
1084. Miao, S., & Yang, J. M. (2018). Bibliometrics-based evaluation of the Blockchain research trend: 2008–March 2017 [Article]. *Technology Analysis and Strategic Management*, 30(9), 1029-1045. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09537325.2018.1434138>
1085. Mikolajewska, E., Komendzinski, T., & Mikolajewski, D. (2018). Social context: Visualisation of cooperation - evidence-based medicine in neurorehabilitation. In *Information Visualization Techniques in the Social Sciences and Humanities* (pp. 274-293). IGI Global. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-5225-4990-1.ch015>
1086. Mikołajewska, E., Komendziński, T., & Mikołajewski, D. (2020). Social Context: Visualisation of Cooperation – Evidence- Based Medicine in Neurorehabilitation. In *Research Anthology on Rehabilitation Practices and Therapy* (pp. 845-865). IGI Global. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-7998-3432-8.ch041>
1087. Milkoreit, M., Hodbod, J., Baggio, J., Benessaiah, K., Calderón-Contreras, R., Donges, J. F., Mathias, J. D., Rocha, J. C., Schoon, M., & Werners, S. E. (2018). Defining tipping points for social-

- ecological systems scholarship - An interdisciplinary literature review [Review]. *Environmental Research Letters*, 13(3), Article 033005. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/aaaa75>
1088. Minas, R., Potter, R., Dennis, A., Bartelt, V., & Bae, S. (2014). Putting on the thinking cap: Using NeuroIS to understand information processing biases in virtual teams [Article]. *Journal of Management Information Systems*, 30(4), 49-82. <https://doi.org/10.2753/MIS0742-1222300403>
1089. Mir, A. A., Salma, S., Rashid, S., Shah, S. I., & Majeed, S. (2019). Mapping life sciences & Biomedicine research [Article]. *Library Philosophy and Practice*, 2019, Article 2782. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85072855418&partnerID=40&md5=3c6ca889bf04f7c3d3d105f1a544fc5e>
1090. Miranda, R., & Garcia-Carpintero, E. (2018). Overcitation and overrepresentation of review papers in the most cited papers [Article]. *Journal of Informetrics*, 12(4), 1015-1030. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joi.2018.08.006>
1091. Mirnezami, S. R., Beaudry, C., & Larivière, V. (2016). What determines researchers' scientific impact? A case study of Quebec researchers [Article]. *Science and Public Policy*, 43(2), 262-274. <https://doi.org/10.1093/scipol/scv038>
1092. Mishra, M., Acharyya, T., Chand, P., Santos, C. A. G., Silva, R. M. D., Santos, C. A. C. D., Pradhan, S., & Kar, D. (2022). Response of long- to short-term tidal inlet morphodynamics on the ecological ramification of Chilika lake, the tropical Ramsar wetland in India [Article]. *Science of the Total Environment*, 807, Article 150769. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.150769>
1093. Mittal, A., Krejci, C. C., & Craven, T. J. (2018). Logistics best practices for regional food systems: A review [Review]. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 10(1), Article 168. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su10010168>
1094. Moakizh, A. A. B., Nour, A. H., Alara, O. R., & Baarimah, A. O. (2022). Bioactive Components of Commiphora Gileadensis Plant for Various Medicinal Applications: A Bibliometric Analysis.
1095. Mohamed, M., Rasid, N. S. M., Ibrahim, N., & Seshaiyer, P. (2023). Engaging responsive and responsible learning through collaborative teaching in the STEM classroom. In *Cases on Responsive and Responsible Learning in Higher Education* (pp. 120-133). IGI Global. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-6684-6076-4.ch008>
1096. Mohammadi, E., & Karami, A. (2022). Exploring research trends in big data across disciplines: A text mining analysis [Article]. *Journal of Information Science*, 48(1), 44-56. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0165551520932855>
1097. Mohammadi Ziarani, G., Jamasbi, N., & Mohajer, F. (2022). Recent advances on the synthesis of natural pyrrolizidine alkaloids: alexine, and its stereoisomers [Review]. *Natural Products and Bioprospecting*, 12(1), Article 3. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13659-022-00324-5>
1098. Mohammadjafari, M., Ahmed, S., Dawal, S. Z. M., & Zayandehroodi, H. (2010). The importance of E-collaboration in SMEs by project management approach a review.
1099. Mohammadjafari, M., Ahmed, S., Md Dawal, S. Z., & Zayandehroodi, H. (2011). Reducing time and cost of new product development in SMEs by E-Collaboration through project management approach [Review]. *Advanced Science Letters*, 4(6-7), 2513-2516. <https://doi.org/10.1166/asl.2011.1540>
1100. Mohammadjafari, M., Ahmed, S., Md Dawal, S. Z., & Zayandehroodi, H. (2012). The role of project manager in SMEs for developing new product by E-collaboration. In (Vol. 433-440, pp. 1637-1645).
1101. Mohammadjafari, M., Dawal, S. Z. M., Ahmed, S., & Zayandehroodi, H. (2011). Toward a theoretical concept of E-collaboration through project management in SMEs for reducing time and cost in new product: A review [Article]. *Journal of Applied Sciences*, 11(1), 174-182. <https://doi.org/10.3923/jas.2011.174.182>

1102. Mohammed, H. A., Abd-Elraouf, M., Sulaiman, G. M., Almahmoud, S. A., Hamada, F. A., Khan, R. A., Hegazy, M. M., Abd-El-Wahab, M. F., Kedra, T. A., & Ismail, A. (2023). Variability in the volatile constituents and biological activities of *Achillea millefolium* L. essential oils obtained from different plant parts and by different solvents [Article]. *Arabian Journal of Chemistry*, 16(9), Article 105103. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.arabjc.2023.105103>
1103. Mohammed, M., Zainal, H., Ong, S. C., Aziz, F. A., Sha'aban, A., Mustapha, S., Looi, I., & Tangiisuran, B. (2021). Trends in Clinical Prediction Models of Stroke Outcomes Research: A Bibliometric Analysis [Article]. *ASM Science Journal*, 16. <https://doi.org/10.32802/ASMSCJ.2021.870>
1104. Mohd Razali, S., Radzi, M. A., Marin, A., & Samdin, Z. (2022). A bibliometric analysis of tropical mangrove forest land use change from 2010 to 2020 [Review]. *Environment, Development and Sustainability*, 24(10), 11530-11547. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10668-021-01935-7>
1105. Mohd Salleh, K., Musa, M. Y., & Sulaiman, N. L. (2017). The use of information and communication technology (ICT) and its effects on office technology and management practitioner's performance in Malaysia [Article]. *Man in India*, 97(10), 233-245. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85024376806&partnerID=40&md5=ad781ef8e5033f36f6e5b20d616639f6>
1106. Mohd Salleh, N. S., & Hussain, A. (2021). Bibliometric Analysis of Public Literature on Google Drive [Article]. *Webology*, 18(SpecialIssue), 107-124. <https://doi.org/10.14704/WEB/V18SI02/WEB18015>
1107. Mohsin, M., Nasir, N., Abid, M. A., Mubeen, A., & Ahmed, W. (2023). Future time perspective: a review and bibliometric analysis [Article]. *Quality and Quantity*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11135-023-01703-x>
1108. Moisescu, O. I. (2017). The moderating effects of demographics on the relationship between perceived csr and brand loyalty in the mobile telecom sector [Article]. *Society and Economy*, 39(1), 109-124. <https://doi.org/10.1556/204.2017.39.1.6>
1109. Mombini, H., & Tulu, B. (2020). A systematic review of decision-making theories used in decision support systems research.
1110. Moncada-Paternò-Castello, P., Vivarelli, M., & Voigt, P. (2011). Drivers and impacts in the globalization of corporate R&D: An introduction based on the European experience [Article]. *Industrial and Corporate Change*, 20(2), 585-603. <https://doi.org/10.1093/icc/dtr005>
1111. Monteiro, A. P., Aibar-Guzmán, B., Garrido-Ruso, M., & Aibar-Guzmán, C. (2021). Employee-related disclosure: A bibliometric review [Article]. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 13(10), Article 5342. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13105342>
1112. Montes-Martínez, R., & Ramírez-Montoya, M. S. (2023). Pedagogical models and ICT integration in entrepreneurship education: Literature review [Review]. *Cogent Education*, 10(2), Article 2264026. <https://doi.org/10.1080/2331186X.2023.2264026>
1113. Montoya, F. G., Alcayde, A., Baños, R., & Manzano-Agugliaro, F. (2018). A fast method for identifying worldwide scientific collaborations using the Scopus database [Article]. *Telematics and Informatics*, 35(1), 168-185. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tele.2017.10.010>
1114. Montoya, F. G., Baños, R., Alcayde, A., Montoya, M. G., & Manzano-Agugliaro, F. (2018). Power quality: Scientific collaboration networks and research trends [Article]. *Energies*, 11(8), Article 2067. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en11082067>
1115. Moon, Y. J., Choi, E., & Hwang, Y. H. (2018). Design and implementation of the expert system for health and medical treatment using integration of big data [Article]. *Journal of Theoretical and Applied Information Technology*, 96(6), 1680-1689.

<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85044837865&partnerID=40&md5=c9341fb253c254283d31773f12d461bd>

1116. Moosavi, J., Fathollahi-Fard, A. M., & Dulebenets, M. A. (2022). Supply chain disruption during the COVID-19 pandemic: Recognizing potential disruption management strategies [Review]. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, 75, Article 102983. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdr.2022.102983>
1117. Moraes, A. T., Silva, L. F., & Oliveira, P. S. G. (2020). Systematization of absorptive capacity microprocesses for knowledge identification in project management [Article]. *Journal of Knowledge Management*, 24(9), 2195-2216. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JKM-05-2020-0332>
1118. Morante-Carballo, F., Montalván-Burbano, N., Quiñonez-Barzola, X., Jaya-Montalvo, M., & Carrión-Mero, P. (2022). What Do We Know about Water Scarcity in Semi-Arid Zones? A Global Analysis and Research Trends [Review]. *Water (Switzerland)*, 14(17), Article 2685. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w14172685>
1119. Moré, A. O., Tesser, C. D., Da Silva, J. B., & Min, L. S. (2016). Status and impact of acupuncture research: A bibliometric analysis of global and Brazilian scientific output from 2000 to 2014 [Article]. *Journal of Alternative and Complementary Medicine*, 22(6), 429-436. <https://doi.org/10.1089/acm.2015.0281>
1120. Moreno, E. M., Castellá, V. O., & Abad, A. Z. (2012). The role of self-guided training in the relationship between task conflict and innovation in virtual teams [Article]. *Psicothema*, 24(1), 29-34. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84856987259&partnerID=40&md5=65a6fdc8fd31b86b383699f2a7f95215>
1121. Moreno-Acosta, J., & Zabala-Vargas, S. A. (2022). Effect on motivation and academic performance when applying game-based learning in the teaching of software defined networks [Article]. *Formacion Universitaria*, 15(4), 81-94. <https://doi.org/10.4067/S0718-50062022000400081>
1122. Moresi, E. A. D., Pinho, I., & Costa, A. P. (2022). How to Operate Literature Review Through Qualitative and Quantitative Analysis Integration? In A. P. Costa, A. Moreira, M. C. Sanchez-Gomez, & S. Wa-Mbaleka (Eds.), (Vol. 466 LNNS, pp. 194-210): Springer Science and Business Media Deutschland GmbH.
1123. Moscoso-Zea, O., Paredes-Gualtor, J., & Luján-Mora, S. (2018). A Holistic View of Data Warehousing in Education [Article]. *IEEE Access*, 6, 64659-64673, Article 8501908. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2018.2876753>
1124. Mota, R. D. O., Godinho Filho, M., Osiro, L., Ganga, G. M. D., & Mendes, G. H. D. S. (2021). Unveiling the relationship between drivers and capabilities for reduced time-to-market in start-ups: A multi-method approach [Article]. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 233, Article 108018. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpe.2020.108018>
1125. Moulahoum, H., Ghorbanizamani, F., Zihnioglu, F., Goksel, T., Turhan, K., & Timur, S. (2022). Biosensing technologies applied in virus detection as rapid tools during pandemics: past lessons and recent trends. In *Biosensors for Emerging and Re-emerging Infectious Diseases* (pp. 335-364). Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-323-88464-8.00004-X>
1126. Moutik, B., Summerscales, J., Graham-Jones, J., & Pemberton, R. (2023). Life Cycle Assessment Research Trends and Implications: A Bibliometric Analysis [Review]. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 15(18), Article 13408. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su151813408>
1127. Mrazova, S., & Wojcak, E. (2019). Impediments while working within virtual teams.
1128. Mu, X., & Antwi-Afari, M. F. (2023). The applications of Internet of Things (IoT) in industrial management: a science mapping review [Review]. *International Journal of Production Research*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00207543.2023.2290229>

1129. Mubaroq, S. R., Abdullah, A. G., Setiawan, A., Widiaty, I., & Dhina, M. A. (2023). Technological perspective on innovation, development and change in response to Covid-19: A scientometric research.
1130. Muh. Asriadi, A. M., Hadi, S., & Istiyono, E. (2023). Trend research mapping of differentiated instruction: A bibliometric analysis [Article]. *Journal of Pedagogical Research*, 7(3), 194-210. <https://doi.org/10.33902/JPR.202320544>
1131. Muhammad, A., Ali, M. A. H., Shanono, I. H., & Abdullah, N. R. H. (2021). A systematic and bibliometric analysis on 3D printing published in scientific citation index-expanded indexed journals between 1999 and 2019.
1132. Muharam, R. S., Rusli, B., Nurasa, H., & Muhtar, E. A. (2023). Seven clusters of data visualization articles in Scopus using social network analysis [Article]. *International Journal of Data and Network Science*, 7(3), 1333-1340. <https://doi.org/10.5267/j.ijdns.2023.4.005>
1133. Muhtar, E. A., Rusli, B., Karlina, N., Candradewini, C., & Muharam, R. S. (2021). Bibliometric analysis and visualization of energy economics and policy in scopus from 2010 to 2021 [Article]. *International Journal of Energy Economics and Policy*, 11(6), 503-507. <https://doi.org/10.32479/ijeep.11848>
1134. Mukhlif, F., Maswadi, K., Bin Noordin, K. A., & Ale Ebrahim, N. (2019). Research Direction Based Green Communications for Next Era: A Bibliometric Analysis.
1135. Mukhtar, N. B., Meeus, M., Gursen, C., Mohammed, J., De Pauw, R., & Cagnie, B. (2022). Effectiveness of Hands-Off Therapy in the Management of Primary Headache: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis [Article]. *Evaluation and the Health Professions*, 45(2), 183-203. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0163278720983408>
1136. Müller, A. M., Maher, C. A., Vandelanotte, C., Hingle, M., Middelweerd, A., Lopez, M. L., DeSmet, A., Short, C. E., Nathan, N., Hutchesson, M. J., Poppe, L., Woods, C. B., Williams, S. L., & Wark, P. A. (2018). Physical activity, sedentary behavior, and diet-related ehealth and mhealth research: Bibliometric analysis [Review]. *Journal of Medical Internet Research*, 20(4), Article e122. <https://doi.org/10.2196/jmir.8954>
1137. Mulyani, & Aryanto, R. (2019). New meeting form in the digital working environment era [Article]. *International Journal of Innovative Technology and Exploring Engineering*, 9(1), 2700-2705. <https://doi.org/10.35940/ijitee.A4849.119119>
1138. Munialo, S., Onyango, C. M., Lukachi, J. A., Wasonga, O. V., Maina, J. G., Nzuma, J. M., Dawood, A., & Sibanda, L. M. (2023). Gaps and opportunities in research on food systems; a micro-institutional analysis of the University of Nairobi [Review]. *Frontiers in Sustainable Food Systems*, 7, Article 1125094. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fsufs.2023.1125094>
1139. Munoz, D. A., Queupil, J. P., & Fraser, P. (2016). Assessing collaboration networks in educational research: A co-authorship-based social network analysis approach [Article]. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 30(3), 416-436. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJEM-11-2014-0154>
1140. Muñoz-Urtubia, N., Vega-Muñoz, A., Estrada-Muñoz, C., Salazar-Sepúlveda, G., Contreras-Barraza, N., & Castillo, D. (2023). Healthy Behavior and Sports Drinks: A Systematic Review [Review]. *Nutrients*, 15(13), Article 2915. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nu15132915>
1141. Munro, A. J., & Swartzman, S. (2013). What is a virtual multidisciplinary team (vMDT)? [Article]. *British Journal of Cancer*, 108(12), 2433-2441. <https://doi.org/10.1038/bjc.2013.231>
1142. Mustafa, F. (2019). "I think it is not plagiarism": How little do Indonesian undergraduate efl students understand plagiarism? [Article]. *Asian EFL Journal*, 21(2), 74-91. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85063682640&partnerID=40&md5=537e7f4a48fe677f5c69a4cef21f73ea>

1143. Muszynska, K. (2021). A bibliometric review of research on communication in virtual project teams.
1144. Muszynska, K. (2022). Measuring communication management performance in virtual project teams.
1145. Mutalib, W. A., Md Zain, N. A., Hanafiah, M. H., Mohd Zahari, M. S., & Asyraff, M. A. (2023). Exploring medical tourism service challenges post-Covid-19: Insights and perspectives from immediate healthcare stakeholders for sustainable business continuity [Article]. *International Journal of Healthcare Management*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/20479700.2023.2261691>
1146. Myshbayeva, Z. T., Sokira, T. S., Belgibayeva, Z. Z., & Dzhulaeva, A. M. (2022). EMPLOYMENT POLICY FOR PERSONS WITH DISABILITIES: SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW WITH BIBLIOMETRIC ANALYSIS [Article]. *Monitoring Obshchestvenno Mneniya: Ekonomicheskie i Sotsial'nye Peremeny*(4), 150-171. <https://doi.org/10.14515/monitoring.2022.4.2157>
1147. Mytskan, B., Mytskan, T., Iermakov, S., & Yermakova, T. (2022). Physical culture in the context of modern philosophical anthropology [Article]. *Pedagogy of Physical Culture and Sports*, 26(3), 210-221. <https://doi.org/10.15561/26649837.2022.0309>
1148. Nabi, M. N. U., Misbaudhin, S. M., & Dornberger, U. (2022). Downgrading as a strategy from the suppliers' perspective in global value chain: towards a conceptual framework and directions for future research [Article]. *Transnational Corporations Review*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19186444.2021.2009299>
1149. Nachtigall, V., Shaffer, D. W., & Rummel, N. (2022). Stirring a Secret Sauce: A Literature Review on the Conditions and Effects of Authentic Learning [Review]. *Educational Psychology Review*, 34(3), 1479-1516. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10648-022-09676-3>
1150. Nadhim, M. H., Omar, S. S., Oleiwia, A. T., Gueme, G. M., & binti Mohd Farid Fernandez, D. F. (2019). Innovative characteristics among small and medium enterprises In (Johor) Malaysia [Article]. *International Journal of Engineering and Advanced Technology*, 8(5), 150-158. <https://doi.org/10.35940/ijeat.E1022.0585C19>
1151. Naeni, L. M., & Salehipour, A. (2021). Optimization for Project Cost Management. In *Application of Mathematics and Optimization in Construction Project Management* (pp. 79-118). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-81123-5_4
1152. Nagaratnam, S., Ebrahnr, N. A., & Habibullah, M. S. (2016). A bibliometric analysis on "fertility rate" research trends [Article]. *International Journal of Professional Business Review*, 1(1), 1-14. <https://doi.org/10.26668/businessreview/2016.v1i1.4>
1153. Nagi, K., & John, V. K. (2020). Plagiarism among Thai students: A study of attitudes and subjective norms.
1154. Nankap, L. H., Bouchard, B., Imbeau, G., Petrillo, F., & Francillette, Y. (2022). Adapting the Scrum Framework to the Needs of Virtual Teams of Game Developers with Multi-site Members.
1155. Narbaev, T. (2015). Project management knowledge discovery in Kazakhstan: Co-word analysis of the field.
1156. Nath, R. D., & Chowdhury, M. A. F. (2021). Shadow banking: a bibliometric and content analysis [Review]. *Financial Innovation*, 7(1), Article 68. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40854-021-00286-6>
1157. Navarro-Lopez, C., Linares-Mustaros, S., & Mulet-Forteza, C. (2022). "The Statistical Analysis of Compositional Data" by John Aitchison (1986): A Bibliometric Overview [Article]. *SAGE Open*, 12(2). <https://doi.org/10.1177/21582440221093366>
1158. Navnath, N. N., Chandrasekaran, K., Stateczny, A., Sundaram, V. M., & Panneer, P. (2022). Spatiotemporal Assessment of Satellite Image Time Series for Land Cover Classification Using Deep

- Learning Techniques: A Case Study of Reunion Island, France [Article]. *Remote Sensing*, 14(20), Article 5232. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs14205232>
1159. Nazari, M. (2020). Tips to Increase Citation to Scientific Papers [Letter]. *Journal of Midwifery and Reproductive Health*, 8(1), 2126-2128. <https://doi.org/10.22038/jmrh.2019.40691.1464>
1160. Nekoonam, A., Nasab, R. F., Jafari, S., Nikolaidis, T., Ale Ebrahim, N., & Miran Fashandi, S. A. (2023). A Scientometric Methodology Based on Co-Word Analysis in Gas Turbine Maintenance [Article]. *Tehnicki Vjesnik*, 30(1), 361-372. <https://doi.org/10.17559/TV-20220118165828>
1161. Nemiro, J. (2023). Virtual teams. In *Handbook of Organizational Creativity: Individual and Group Level Influences*, Second Edition (pp. 269-290). Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-323-91840-4.00007-4>
1162. Neto, L. S. S., Rosa, T. S., Freire, M. D., Correa, H. L., Pedreira, R. C., Dias, F. C. F., Oliveira, D. V., & Osório, N. B. (2023). Geriatric and Gerontology Research: A Scientometric Investigation of Open Access Journal Articles Indexed in the Scopus Database [Article]. *Annals of Geriatric Medicine and Research*, 27(3), 183-191. <https://doi.org/10.4235/agmr.23.0076>
1163. Nevzorova, T., & Karakaya, E. (2020). Explaining the drivers of technological innovation systems: The case of biogas technologies in mature markets [Review]. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 259, Article 120819. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.120819>
1164. Nevzorova, T., & Kutcherov, V. (2019). Barriers to the wider implementation of biogas as a source of energy: A state-of-the-art review [Review]. *Energy Strategy Reviews*, 26, Article 100414. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esr.2019.100414>
1165. Ng, P. K., & Tung, B. (2018). The importance of reward and recognition system in the leadership of virtual project teams: a qualitative research for the financial services sector [Article]. *Journal of Transnational Management*, 23(4), 198-214. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15475778.2018.1512827>
1166. Nguea, S. M. (2023). Does technology affect human development? Examining some important moderating factors [Article]. *Information Development*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/02666669231185778>
1167. Nguyen, D. T., & Le, P. L. (2022). Twenty-year application of logistics and supply chain management in the construction industry [Article]. *Construction Management and Economics*, 40(10), 796-834. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01446193.2022.2110273>
1168. Nguyen, D. T., Rameezdeen, R., Chileshe, N., & Coggins, J. (2021). Third-party reverse logistics service provider selection approaches and criteria: A literature review [Review]. *International Journal of Logistics Systems and Management*, 40(3), 396-422. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85123426806&partnerID=40&md5=6ad589d60b07799d142c649eb6bb92df>
1169. Nguyen, P. M. B., Pham, L. X., Tran, D. K., & Truong, G. N. T. (2023). A systematic literature review on travel planning through user-generated video [Review]. *Journal of Vacation Marketing*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/13567667231152935>
1170. Nguyen Quoc, A., Nguyen Van, D., & Nguyen, N. N. A. (2023). Entrepreneurship, family and migration: a systematic literature review on Vietnamese migrant entrepreneurship [Review]. *Journal of Enterprising Communities*, 17(1), 125-157. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JEC-03-2020-0042>
1171. Nguyen, T. D. H. N., Moon, H., & Ahn, Y. (2022). Critical Review of Trends in Modular Integrated Construction Research with a Focus on Sustainability [Review]. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 14(19), Article 12282. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su141912282>
1172. Nijnik, M., Kluvánková, T., Melnykovich, M., Nijnik, A., Kopyi, S., Brnkal'áková, S., Sarkki, S., Kopyi, L., Fyzik, I., Barlagne, C., & Miller, D. (2021). An institutional analysis and reconfiguration framework for sustainability research on post-transition forestry—a focus on Ukraine [Article]. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 13(8), Article 4360. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13084360>
1173. Niknam, M., & Karshenas, S. (2014). A social networking website for AEC projects.

1174. Nikoi, E., & Boateng, K. (2013). Preface [Editorial]. *Collaborative Communication Processes and Decision Making in Organizations*, xvi-xxiii. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-4666-4478-6>
1175. Nikolopoulou, K. (2020). Secondary education teachers' perceptions of mobile phone and tablet use in classrooms: benefits, constraints and concerns [Article]. *Journal of Computers in Education*, 7(2), 257-275. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40692-020-00156-7>
1176. Nimasari, E. P. (2016). How do undergraduate students avoid plagiarism? [Article]. *Asian EFL Journal*, 2, 86-94. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85041405874&partnerID=40&md5=2b0dc450557c8fd7d3dcf1a30ce491b2>
1177. Nimfa, D. T., Islam, A., Latiff, A. S. A., & Wahab, S. A. (2021). Role of Innovation Competitive Advantage on Strategic Orientation Dimensions and Sustainable Growth of SMEs in Nigeria. In A. Gerber & K. Hinkelmann (Eds.), (Vol. 1477 CCIS, pp. 46-62): Springer Science and Business Media Deutschland GmbH.
1178. Nindito, H., Prabowo, H., Leslie Hendric, S. W. H., & Sfenrianto. (2021). A bibliometric analysis on e-government and tourism.
1179. Niñerola, A., Hernández-Lara, A. B., & Sánchez-Rebull, M. V. (2021). Is time-driven activity-based costing coming out on top? A comparison with activity-based costing in the health field [Article]. *Healthcare (Switzerland)*, 9(9), Article 1113. <https://doi.org/10.3390/healthcare9091113>
1180. Nishchaya, K., Rai, V. K., & Bansode, H. (2023). Methacrylic acid as a potential monomer for molecular imprinting: A review of recent advances [Article]. *Results in Materials*, 18, Article 100379. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rinma.2023.100379>
1181. Nobanee, H., Dilshad, M. N., Al Dhanhani, M., Al Neyadi, M., Al Qubaisi, S., & Al Shamsi, S. (2021). Big Data Applications the Banking Sector: A Bibliometric Analysis Approach [Article]. *SAGE Open*, 11(4). <https://doi.org/10.1177/21582440211067234>
1182. Nogueira, M. A., Costa, L. C., Resende, D. M., Carvalho, V. R., Mendes, J. C., & Peixoto, R. A. F. (2024). Mitigating the socioeconomic impacts of the mining industry through Social Technologies: Guidelines for technology transfer between universities and communities [Review]. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, 31(1), 54-68. <https://doi.org/10.1002/csr.2593>
1183. Norder, K., Emich, K., Kanar, A., Sawhney, A., & Behrend, T. S. (2022). A house divided: A multilevel bibliometric review of the job search literature 1973–2020 [Article]. *Journal of Business Research*, 151, 100-117. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2022.06.036>
1184. Norouzi, M., Chàfer, M., Cabeza, L. F., Jiménez, L., & Boer, D. (2021). Circular economy in the building and construction sector: A scientific evolution analysis [Article]. *Journal of Building Engineering*, 44, Article 102704. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jobee.2021.102704>
1185. Noto, G., Marisca, C., & Barresi, G. (2023). Adapting management control to virtual teams: evidence from a natural experiment [Article]. *Qualitative Research in Accounting and Management*, 20(5), 621-646. <https://doi.org/10.1108/QRAM-04-2022-0066>
1186. Noviarti, D., Arliansyah, J., & Kadarsah, E. (2023). Systematic literature review: Financing system in railway transportation.
1187. Nowotarski, P., Dubas, S., & Milwicz, R. (2017). Review of the Air-Coupled Impact-Echo Method for Non-Destructive Testing.
1188. Nowotarski, P., & Paslawski, J. (2017). Industry 4.0 Concept Introduction into Construction SMEs.
1189. Nowotarski, P., Paślawski, J., & Mielcarek, D. (2017). Accuracy of BLE systems in the H&S improvement aspects in construction.
1190. Nowotarski, P., Paślawski, J., Skrzypczak, M., & Krygier, R. (2017). RTLS systems as a Lean Management tool for productivity improvement.

1191. Nunes, A. M. M., Coelho Junior, L. M., Abrahão, R., Santos Júnior, E. P., Simioni, F. J., Rotella Junior, P., & Rocha, L. C. S. (2023). Public Policies for Renewable Energy: A Review of the Perspectives for a Circular Economy [Review]. *Energies*, 16(1), Article 485. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en16010485>
1192. Nunhes, T. V., Bernardo, M., & José de Oliveira, O. (2020). Rethinking the way of doing business: A reframe of management structures for developing corporate sustainability [Review]. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 12(3). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12031177>
1193. Nurhidayah, I. J., Wibowo, F. C., & Astra, I. M. (2021). Project Based Learning (PjBL) learning model in science learning: Literature review.
1194. Nwaogu, J. M., Chan, A. P. C., Hon, C. K. H., & Darko, A. (2020). Review of global mental health research in the construction industry: A science mapping approach [Review]. *Engineering, Construction and Architectural Management*, 27(2), 385-410. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ECAM-02-2019-0114>
1195. O'Brien, L. M., Paratore, J. R., Salinas, A., & Blodgett, S. (2023). Using connected teaching and learning to deepen children's interdisciplinary learning [Article]. *Journal of Early Childhood Research*, 21(2), 181-197. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1476718X221145503>
1196. O'Grady-Jones, M., & Grant, M. M. (2023). Ready Coder One: Collaborative Game Design-Based Learning on Gifted Fourth Graders' 21st Century Skills [Article]. *Gifted Child Today*, 46(2), 84-107. <https://doi.org/10.1177/10762175221149259>
1197. Obaideen, K., Abu Shihab, K. H., Madkour, M. I., & Faris, M. E. (2022). Seven decades of Ramadan intermittent fasting research: Bibliometrics analysis, global trends, and future directions [Article]. *Diabetes and Metabolic Syndrome: Clinical Research and Reviews*, 16(8), Article 102566. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dsx.2022.102566>
1198. Ochoa Jiménez, S., García García, A. R., Valdez del Río, S., & Jacobo Hernández, C. A. (2022). Entrepreneurship in Tourism Studies in the 21st Century: A Bibliometric Study of Wos and Scopus [Article]. *SAGE Open*, 12(2). <https://doi.org/10.1177/21582440221102438>
1199. Odeyemi, O. A., Stratev, D., Oko, J. O., & Salisu, N. (2021). A BIBLIOMETRIC ANALYSIS OF GLOBAL RESEARCH OUTPUTS ON SEAFOOD AND ANTIBIOTICS (1999 - 2019) [Article]. *Bulletin of the Transilvania University of Brasov, Series II: Forestry, Wood Industry, Agricultural Food Engineering*, 14-63(1), 173-192. <https://doi.org/10.31926/BUT.FWIAFE.2021.14.63.1.16>
1200. Odubela, C. A., Yaacob, H., Warid, M. N. B. M., Karim, K. J. B. A., & Zakka, W. P. (2023). A bibliometric analysis of rejuvenators in reclaimed asphalt pavement [Review]. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 30(11), 28575-28596. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-023-25265-5>
1201. Ogundeji, A. A., & Okolie, C. C. (2022). Perception and Adaptation Strategies of Smallholder Farmers to Drought Risk: A Scientometric Analysis [Review]. *Agriculture (Switzerland)*, 12(8), Article 1129. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agriculture12081129>
1202. Oğuz, A., & Ertuğrul, Ö. F. (2023). A survey on applications of machine learning algorithms in water quality assessment and water supply and management [Article]. *Water Supply*, 23(2), 895-922. <https://doi.org/10.2166/ws.2023.033>
1203. Ogwu, S., Keogh, S., & Sice, P. (2016). Virtual collaborative research communication the impact of mindsight. *Proceedings of the European Conference on e-Learning, ECEL*,
1204. Ogwu, S., Sice, P., Keogh, S., & Goodlet, C. (2020). An exploratory study of the application of mindsight in email communication [Article]. *Heliyon*, 6(7), Article e04305. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2020.e04305>

1205. Oh, J., Chang, H., Kim, J. A., Choi, M., Park, Z., Cho, Y., & Lee, E. G. (2017). Citation analysis for biomedical and health sciences journals published in Korea [Article]. *Healthcare Informatics Research*, 23(3), 218-225. <https://doi.org/10.4258/hir.2017.23.3.218>
1206. Ojeda-Pereira, I., & Campos-Medina, F. (2021). International trends in mining tailings publications: A descriptive bibliometric study [Article]. *Resources Policy*, 74, Article 102272. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resourpol.2021.102272>
1207. Ojemaye, M. O., & Okoh, A. I. (2021). Global research direction on Pt and Pt based electro-catalysts for fuel cells application between 1990 and 2019: A bibliometric analysis [Review]. *International Journal of Energy Research*, 45(11), 15783-15796. <https://doi.org/10.1002/er.6907>
1208. Okampo, E. J., & Nwulu, N. (2021). Optimisation of renewable energy powered reverse osmosis desalination systems: A state-of-the-art review [Review]. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 140, Article 110712. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2021.110712>
1209. Okasha, A. A., Haq, F., Medhekar, A., & Yasin, N. (2023). Exploring the challenges for medical tourism in the United Arab Emirates during the Covid-19 pandemic era: a stakeholder perspective [Article]. *Worldwide Hospitality and Tourism Themes*, 15(2), 155-168. <https://doi.org/10.1108/WHATT-10-2022-0119>
1210. Okeji, C. C., Eze, M. E., & Chibueze, N. M. (2019). Awareness and use of self-archiving options among academic librarians in Nigerian universities [Article]. *Global Knowledge, Memory and Communication*, 68(1-2), 2-16. <https://doi.org/10.1108/GKMC-12-2017-0109>
1211. Okoro, C., Owojori, O. M., & Umeokafor, N. (2022). The Developmental Trajectory of a Decade of Research on Mental Health and Well-Being amongst Graduate Students: A Bibliometric Analysis [Review]. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(9), Article 4929. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph19094929>
1212. Oktari, R. S., Munadi, K., Idroes, R., & Sofyan, H. (2020). Knowledge management practices in disaster management: Systematic review [Review]. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, 51, Article 101881. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdrr.2020.101881>
1213. Oktariato, M. L., & Handayanto, S. K. (2021). Science learning tools with cooperative models of teams games tournament to improve students learning outcomes in primary schools.
1214. Oláh, J., Kasza, G., Szabó-Bódi, B., Szakos, D., Popp, J., & Lakner, Z. (2022). Household Food Waste Research: The Current State of the Art and a Guided Tour for Further Development [Review]. *Frontiers in Environmental Science*, 10, Article 916601. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fenvs.2022.916601>
1215. Olaleye, S. A., Mogaji, E., Agbo, F. J., Ukpabi, D., & Gyamerah Adusei, A. (2023). The composition of data economy: a bibliometric approach and TCCM framework of conceptual, intellectual and social structure [Review]. *Information Discovery and Delivery*, 51(2), 223-240. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IDD-02-2022-0014>
1216. Olanipekun, A. O., & Sutrisna, M. (2021). Facilitating Digital Transformation in Construction—A Systematic Review of the Current State of the Art [Review]. *Frontiers in Built Environment*, 7, Article 660758. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fbuil.2021.660758>
1217. Olawumi, O., Olaleye, S., Adusei-Mensah, F., Olawuni, A., & Agjei, R. O. (2022). Adoption and implementation of electronic healthcare management system - A bibliometric approach [Article]. *International Journal of Electronic Healthcare*, 12(1), 54-96. <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJEH.2022.119583>
1218. Olesen, A. P., Amin, L., & Mahadi, Z. (2018). In Their Own Words: Research Misconduct from the Perspective of Researchers in Malaysian Universities [Article]. *Science and Engineering Ethics*, 24(6), 1755-1776. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11948-017-9997-9>

1219. Olisah, C., & Adams, J. B. (2020). Systematic mapping of organophosphate contaminant (OPC) research trends between 1990 and 2018 [Review]. *Environmental Geochemistry and Health*, 42(11), 3481-3505. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10653-020-00594-3>
1220. Oliveira, L. L., da Silva, A. L., Pereira, C. R., & Chaudhuri, A. (2023). The stakeholder's roles in risk management related to food supply chain recalls: a systematic literature review [Review]. *International Journal of Logistics Management*, 34(1), 106-129. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJLM-05-2021-0261>
1221. Oliveira, V. T. D., Teixeira, D., Rocchi, L., & Boggia, A. (2022). Geographic Information System Applied to Sustainability Assessments: Conceptual Structure and Research Trends [Review]. *ISPRS International Journal of Geo-Information*, 11(11), Article 569. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijgi11110569>
1222. Olsen, O. K., Ågotnes, K. W., Hetland, J., Espevik, R., & Ravnanger, C. A. (2023). Virtual team-cooperation from home-office: a quantitative diary study of the impact of daily transformational- and passive-avoidant leadership – and the moderating role of task interdependence [Article]. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 14, Article 1188753. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2023.1188753>
1223. Olugbade, D., Oyelere, S. S., & Agbo, F. J. (2024). Enhancing junior secondary students' learning outcomes in basic science and technology through PhET: A study in Nigeria [Article]. *Education and Information Technologies*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-023-12391-3>
1224. Olukolajo, M. A., Oyetunji, A. K., & Amaechi, C. V. (2023). A Scientometric Review of Environmental Valuation Research with an Altmetric Pathway for the Future [Review]. *Environments - MDPI*, 10(4), Article 58. <https://doi.org/10.3390/environments10040058>
1225. Omar, M., Mehmood, A., Choi, G. S., & Park, H. W. (2017). Global mapping of artificial intelligence in Google and Google Scholar [Article]. *Scientometrics*, 113(3), 1269-1305. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-017-2534-4>
1226. Onyanacha, O. B. (2018). Forty-Five Years of LIS Research Evolution, 1971–2015: An Informetrics Study of the Author-Supplied Keywords [Article]. *Publishing Research Quarterly*, 34(3), 456-470. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12109-018-9590-3>
1227. Onyanacha, O. B. (2020). A meta-analysis study of the relationship between research and economic development in selected countries in sub-Saharan Africa [Article]. *Scientometrics*, 123(2), 655-675. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-020-03390-z>
1228. Onyanacha, O. B., & Ocholla, D. N. (2019). Can Bradford's law be applied to determine core subject terms in a subject domain?
1229. Oosthuizen, R., & Grobbelaar, S. (2021). IMPLEMENTING BIBLIOMETRIC ANALYSIS AND TOPIC MODELLING TO INFORM CURRICULUM DEVELOPMENT FOR ENGINEERING MANAGEMENT.
1230. Oosthuizen, R., & Grobbelaar, S. (2023). Machine Learning-Based Bibliometric Analysis of Systems Thinking Research.
1231. Oosthuizen, R., & Pretorius, L. (2020). Bibliometric analysis of technology management research topic trends.
1232. Oosthuizen, R., & Pretorius, L. (2021). Analysis of INCOSE Systems Engineering journal and international symposium research topics [Review]. *Systems Engineering*, 24(4), 203-220. <https://doi.org/10.1002/sys.21575>
1233. Oosthuizen, R., & Pretorius, L. (2022). Bibliometric analysis of information communication technology for sustainable development: a machine-learning-based approach [Article]. *International Journal of Learning and Change*, 14(5-6), 537-558. <https://doi.org/10.1504/ijlc.2022.126421>
1234. Oraee, M., Hosseini, M. R., Papadonikolaki, E., Palliyaguru, R., & Arashpour, M. (2017). Collaboration in BIM-based construction networks: A bibliometric-qualitative literature review

- [Article]. *International Journal of Project Management*, 35(7), 1288-1301.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijproman.2017.07.001>
1235. Orengo, V., Zornoza, A., & Peiró, J. M. (2011). Equipment management of virtual organizations labour: Some contributions from the research [Review]. *Papeles del Psicologo*, 32(1), 82-93.
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-79951564990&partnerID=40&md5=a5977cde80dcc614cda083776e3b9b4e>
1236. Orhan, M. A. (2017). The evolution of the virtuality phenomenon in organisations: A critical literature review [Article]. *Entrepreneurial Business and Economics Review*, 5(4), 171-188.
<https://doi.org/10.15678/EBER.2017.050408>
1237. Orimoloye, I. R., Ekundayo, T. C., Ololade, O. O., & Belle, J. A. (2021). Systematic mapping of disaster risk management research and the role of innovative technology [Article]. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 28(4), 4289-4306. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-020-10791-3>
1238. Ortega, J. L. (2016). To be or not to be on Twitter, and its relationship with the tweeting and citation of research papers [Article]. *Scientometrics*, 109(2), 1353-1364.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-016-2113-0>
1239. Ortiz-Núñez, R. (2020). Metric analysis of the scientific production about COVID-19 in scopus [Article]. *Revista Cubana de Informacion en Ciencias de la Salud*, 31(3), 1-20, Article e1587.
<https://doi.org/10.36512/rcics.v31i2.1587>
1240. Osmani, M. W., Haddadeh, R. E., Hindi, N., & Weerakkody, V. (2020). The role of Co-innovation platform and E-collaboration ICTs in facilitating entrepreneurial ventures [Article]. *International Journal of E-Entrepreneurship and Innovation*, 10(2), 62-75.
<https://doi.org/10.4018/IJEEI.2020070104>
1241. Osorio-Mancilla, J. (2023). *A Bibliometric Analysis of Experimental Philosophy of Language. In Logic, Argumentation and Reasoning (Vol. 33, pp. 13-29): Springer Science and Business Media B.V.*
1242. Ota, L., Herbohn, J., Harrison, S., Gregorio, N., & Engel, V. L. (2018). Smallholder reforestation and livelihoods in the humid tropics: a systematic mapping study [Article]. *Agroforestry Systems*, 92(6), 1597-1609. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10457-017-0107-4>
1243. Otitolaiye, V. O., & Abd Aziz, F. S. (2023). Bibliometric analysis of safety management system research (2001–2021) [Article]. *Journal of Safety Research*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsr.2023.10.014>
1244. Ouma-Mugabe, J., Chan, K. Y., & Marais, H. C. (2021). A critical review of policy instruments for promoting innovation in manufacturing small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in South Africa. In *Entrepreneurship, Technology Commercialisation, and Innovation Policy in Africa* (pp. 237-258). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-58240-1_11
1245. Ouriques, R. A. B., Wnuk, K., Gorschek, T., & Svensson, R. B. (2019). Knowledge Management Strategies and Processes in Agile Software Development: A Systematic Literature Review [Article]. *International Journal of Software Engineering and Knowledge Engineering*, 29(3), Article 00153.
<https://doi.org/10.1142/S0218194019500153>
1246. Oyebisi, S., & Alomayri, T. (2023). Potential application of artificial intelligence to the alpha and gamma radiation from agricultural byproducts used as building and construction materials [Review]. *Scientific African*, 21, Article e01792. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sciaf.2023.e01792>
1247. Oza, N., & Prajapati, M. S. (2020). Scientometric Assessment of Publications on Electronic Resource Management and Electronic Resource Management System during [Article]. *Library Philosophy and Practice*, 2020, 1-24. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85101768334&partnerID=40&md5=247c2d3fbb3ce12825b1ea8ea7476a83>
1248. Ozornina, N. Y., Lyubitskaya, K. A., & Bochaver, A. A. (2022). ON THE PROBLEMS OF THE CONCEPTUAL APPARATUS IN RESEARCH ON PARENTING IN EDUCATION [Review].

- Monitoring Obshchestvennogo Mneniya: Ekonomicheskie i Sotsial'nye Peremeny(2), 42-65.
<https://doi.org/10.14515/monitoring.2022.2.1997>
1249. Ozturk, G. B. (2020). Interoperability in building information modeling for AECO/FM industry [Article]. *Automation in Construction*, 113, Article 103122.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2020.103122>
1250. Ozturk, G. B. (2020). Trends in interoperability in building information modeling (BIM) research: A scientometric analysis of authors and articles [Article]. *A/Z ITU Journal of the Faculty of Architecture*, 17(3), 169-183. <https://doi.org/10.5505/itujfa.2020.79026>
1251. Ozturk, G. B. (2021). Digital Twin Research in the AECO-FM Industry [Article]. *Journal of Building Engineering*, 40, Article 102730. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jobe.2021.102730>
1252. Păduraru, O., Moroşanu, A., Păduraru, C. Ş., & Cărăuşu, E. M. (2022). Healthcare Management: A Bibliometric Analysis Based on the Citations of Research Articles Published between 1967 and 2020 [Article]. *Healthcare (Switzerland)*, 10(3), Article 555.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/healthcare10030555>
1253. Palmeira, J. D., Cunha, M. V., Carvalho, J., Ferreira, H., Fonseca, C., & Torres, R. T. (2021). Emergence and spread of cephalosporinases in wildlife: A review [Review]. *Animals*, 11(6), Article 1765. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ani11061765>
1254. Pamuk, D., Faezi, S. A., & Başıbüyük, G. O. (2022). Ergonomics and aging: A bibliometric analysis [Review]. *Work*, 72(3), 853-864. <https://doi.org/10.3233/WOR-210112>
1255. Pan, A. J., Lai, C. F., & Kuo, H. C. (2023). Investigating the impact of a possibility-thinking integrated project-based learning history course on high school students' creativity, learning motivation, and history knowledge [Article]. *Thinking Skills and Creativity*, 47, Article 101214.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tsc.2022.101214>
1256. Pan, J., Yan, J. X., & Zhang, J. (2022). From blended to virtual learning: insights from a language enhancement workshop programme [Article]. *International Journal of Mobile Learning and Organisation*, 16(3), 349-376. <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJMLO.2022.124179>
1257. Pan, L., Tlili, A., Li, J., Jiang, F., Shi, G., Yu, H., & Yang, J. (2021). How to Implement Game-Based Learning in a Smart Classroom? A Model Based on a Systematic Literature Review and Delphi Method [Article]. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12, Article 749837.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.749837>
1258. Pan, Q., Zhou, J., Yang, D., Shi, D., Wang, D., Chen, X., & Liu, J. (2023). Mapping Knowledge Domain Analysis in Deep Learning Research of Global Education [Article]. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 15(4), Article 3097. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15043097>
1259. Papanastassiou, M., Pearce, R., & Zanfei, A. (2020). Changing perspectives on the internationalization of R&D and innovation by multinational enterprises: A review of the literature [Review]. *Journal of International Business Studies*, 51(4), 623-664. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41267-019-00258-0>
1260. Park, I., & Jeon, J. (2023). Psychological Skills Training for Athletes in Sports: Web of Science Bibliometric Analysis [Article]. *Healthcare (Switzerland)*, 11(2), Article 259.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/healthcare11020259>
1261. Parlina, A., Ramli, K., & Murfi, H. (2020). Theme mapping and bibliometrics analysis of one decade of big data research in the scopus database [Article]. *Information (Switzerland)*, 11(2), Article 69. <https://doi.org/10.3390/info11020069>
1262. Parnianifard, A., & Azfanizam, A. S. (2020). Metamodel-based robust simulation-optimization assisted optimal design of multiloop integer and fractional-order PID controller [Article]. *International Journal of Numerical Modelling: Electronic Networks, Devices and Fields*, 33(1), Article e2679. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jnm.2679>

1263. Parnianifard, A., Azfanizam, A. S., Ariffin, M. K. A., & Ismail, M. I. S. (2020). Comparative study of metamodeling and sampling design for expensive and semi-expensive simulation models under uncertainty [Article]. *Simulation*, 96(1), 89-110. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0037549719846988>
1264. Parnianifard, A., Azfanizam, A. S., Ariffin, M. K. A., & Ismail, M. I. S. (2020). Crossing weighted uncertainty scenarios assisted distribution-free metamodel-based robust simulation optimization [Article]. *Engineering with Computers*, 36(1), 139-150. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00366-018-00690-0>
1265. Parnianifard, A., Azfanizam, A. S., Ariffin, M. K. A., Ismail, M. I. S., & Ale Ebrahim, N. (2019). Recent developments in metamodel based robust black-box simulation optimization: An overview [Article]. *Decision Science Letters*, 8(1), 17-44. <https://doi.org/10.5267/j.dsl.2018.5.004>
1266. Parnianifard, A., Azfanizam, A. S., Ariffin, M. K. A., Ismail, M. I. S., Maghami, M. R., & Gomes, C. (2018). Kriging and Latin hypercube sampling assisted simulation optimization in optimal design of PID controller for speed control of DC motor [Article]. *Journal of Computational and Theoretical Nanoscience*, 15(5), 1471-1479. <https://doi.org/10.1166/jctn.2018.7379>
1267. Parnianifard, A., Chanchaen, R., Phanomchoeng, G., & Wuttisittikulkij, L. (2020). A new approach for low-dimensional constrained engineering design optimization using design and analysis of simulation experiments [Article]. *International Journal of Computational Intelligence Systems*, 13(1), 1663-1678. <https://doi.org/10.2991/ijcis.d.201014.001>
1268. Parnianifard, A., Chaudhary, S., Mumtaz, S., Wuttisittikulkij, L., & Imran, M. A. (2023). Expedited surrogate-based quantification of engineering tolerances using a modified polynomial regression [Article]. *Structural and Multidisciplinary Optimization*, 66(3), Article 61. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00158-023-03493-0>
1269. Parnianifard, A., Fakhfakh, M., Kotti, M., Zemouche, A., & Wuttisittikulkij, L. (2021). Robust tuning and sensitivity analysis of stochastic integer and fractional-order PID control systems: application of surrogate-based robust simulation-optimization [Article]. *International Journal of Numerical Modelling: Electronic Networks, Devices and Fields*, 34(2), Article e2835. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jnm.2835>
1270. Parnianifard, A., Jearavongtakul, S., Sasithong, P., Sinpan, N., Poomrittigul, S., Bajpai, A., Vanichchanunt, P., & Wuttisittikulkij, L. (2022). Digital-Twins towards Cyber-Physical Systems: A Brief Survey [Article]. *Engineering Journal*, 26(9), 47-61. <https://doi.org/10.4186/ej.2022.26.9.47>
1271. Parnianifard, A., Mumtaz, S., Chaudhary, S., Imran, M. A., & Wuttisittikulkij, L. (2022). A data driven approach in less expensive robust transmitting coverage and power optimization [Article]. *Scientific Reports*, 12(1), Article 17725. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-21490-z>
1272. Parnianifard, A., Zemouche, A., Chanchaen, R., Imran, M. A., & Wuttisittikulkij, L. (2020). Robust optimal design of FOPID controller for five bar linkage robot in a Cyber-Physical System: A new simulation-optimization approach [Article]. *PLoS ONE*, 15(11 November), Article e0242613. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0242613>
1273. Parnianifard, A., Zemouche, A., Imran, M. A., & Wuttisittikulkij, L. (2020). Robust simulation-optimization of dynamic-stochastic production/inventory control system under uncertainty using computational intelligence [Article]. *Uncertain Supply Chain Management*, 8(4), 633-648. <https://doi.org/10.5267/j.uscm.2020.9.002>
1274. Parra-Rizo, M. A. (2017). Most valued components of the quality of life in older people than 60 years physically active [Article]. *European Journal of Investigation in Health, Psychology and Education*, 7(3), 135-144. <https://doi.org/10.30552/ejihpe.v7i3.202>
1275. Parwita, W. G. S., Indradewi, I. G. A. A. D., & Wijaya, I. N. S. W. (2019). String matching based plagiarism detection for document in Bahasa Indonesia.

1276. Passavanti, C., Ponsiglione, C., Primario, S., & Rippa, P. (2023). The evolution of student entrepreneurship: State of the art and emerging research direction [Article]. *International Journal of Management Education*, 21(2), Article 100820. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijme.2023.100820>
1277. Patil, R. Y., Patil, Y. H., & Bannore, A. (2023). Security of Medical Internet of Things (MIoT)- A Bibliometric Analysis [Article]. *Journal of Engineering Science and Technology Review*, 16(3), 181-190. <https://doi.org/10.25103/jestr.163.22>
1278. Patra, S., Sahoo, J., & Mohanty, B. (2021). Research on Digital Preservation: An empirical analysis [Article]. *Library Philosophy and Practice*, 2021, 1-16. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85101259797&partnerID=40&md5=0b76beab313fb14667441bd92e8a4baf>
1279. Patton, R. M., Stahl, C. G., & Wells, J. C. (2016). Measuring scientific impact beyond citation counts [Article]. *D-Lib Magazine*, 22(9-10). <https://doi.org/10.1045/september2016-patton>
1280. Patyal, V., Jaspal, D., & Khare, K. (2020). Wastewater Treatment Technologies: A Bibliometric Analysis [Article]. *Science and Technology Libraries*, 39(4), 383-394. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0194262X.2020.1775164>
1281. Pauline-Graf, D., Mandel, S. E., Allen, H. W., & Devnew, L. E. (2021). Assumption validation process for the assessment of technology-enhanced learning [Article]. *Contemporary Educational Technology*, 13(4), Article ep316. <https://doi.org/10.30935/cedtech/11071>
1282. Pavlic, D. (2021). BUSINESS PROCESS MANAGEMENT AND CUSTOMER EXPERIENCE MANAGEMENT CONVERGENCE – A LITERATURE REVIEW.
1283. Pearson, L. (2011). Virtual teams and their leaders: A paradigm on achieving learning agility [Article]. *Academic Leadership*, 9(1). <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-79953796719&partnerID=40&md5=f8aefb240499659459057995f8de2b53>
1284. Pedro, A., Hussain, R., Pham-Hang, A. T., & Pham, H. C. (2019). Visualization technologies in construction education: A comprehensive review of recent advances. In *Engineering Education for Sustainability* (pp. 67-101). River Publishers. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85104162095&partnerID=40&md5=93f4ae4aad4b3fcfb4462545c83bb8f>
1285. Peifer, C., Pollak, A., Flak, O., Pyszka, A., Nisar, M. A., Irshad, M. T., Grzegorzek, M., Kordyaka, B., & Kożusznik, B. (2021). The Symphony of Team Flow in Virtual Teams. Using Artificial Intelligence for Its Recognition and Promotion [Article]. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12, Article 697093. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.697093>
1286. Peiris, S., Lai, J., & Kumaraswamy, M. M. (2022). Smart retrofitting of buildings: A bibliometric study.
1287. Peiris, S., Lai, J. H. K., Kumaraswamy, M. M., & Hou, H. C. (2023). Smart retrofitting for existing buildings: State of the art and future research directions [Review]. *Journal of Building Engineering*, 76, Article 107354. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jobbe.2023.107354>
1288. Pejić Bach, M., Bosilj Vukšić, V., Suša Vugec, D., & Stjepić, A. M. (2019). BPM and BI in SMEs: The role of BPM/BI alignment in organizational performance [Article]. *International Journal of Engineering Business Management*, 11. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1847979019874182>
1289. Pellegrini, M. M., Rialti, R., Marzi, G., & Caputo, A. (2020). Sport entrepreneurship: A synthesis of existing literature and future perspectives [Article]. *International Entrepreneurship and Management Journal*, 16(3), 795-826. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11365-020-00650-5>
1290. Penado Abilleira, M., Ríos-de-Deus, M. P., Tomé-Lourido, D., Rodicio-García, M. L., Mosquera-González, M. J., López-López, D., & Gómez-Salgado, J. (2023). Relationship between Sports Practice, Physical and Mental Health and Anxiety–Depressive Symptomatology in the Spanish Prison Population [Article]. *Healthcare (Switzerland)*, 11(6), Article 789. <https://doi.org/10.3390/healthcare11060789>

1291. Peñaranda-Ortega, M., González-Sala, F., & Osca-Lluch, J. (2021). Estimate costs for publishing in JCR-indexed scientific journals in 2017 and 2018: The case of Psychology [Article]. *Revista Espanola de Documentacion Cientifica*, 44(4), Article e311. <https://doi.org/10.3989/redc.2021.4.1819>
1292. Pereira, A. B. M., Montevechi, J. A. B., Pinto, W. G. M., & Santos, C. H. (2023). SIMULATION AND DIGITAL TWINS TO SUPPORT REVERSE LOGISTICS DECISIONS: A REVIEW [Article]. *International Journal of Simulation Modelling*, 22(3), 381-391. <https://doi.org/10.2507/IJSIMM22-3-640>
1293. Pereira, L., Tenera, A., Bispo, J., & Wemans, J. (2013). A risk diagnosing methodology web-based tool for SME's and start-up enterprises.
1294. Pereira, L., Tenera, A., Bispo, J., & Wemans, J. (2015). A risk diagnosing methodology web-based platform for micro, small and medium businesses: Remarks and enhancements. In J. L. G. Dietz, A. Fred, K. Liu, & J. Filipe (Eds.), (Vol. 454, pp. 340-356): Springer Verlag.
1295. Pereira, R., & Franco, M. (2020). Library as a consortium perspective: A systematic literature review [Article]. *Journal of Librarianship and Information Science*, 52(4), 1126-1136. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0961000620904754>
1296. Pérez, F. O. M., & Hincapié, J. M. M. (2023). Intangible Cultural Heritage and Creative Ecosystems: A Literature Review [Review]. *Revista Finanzas y Politica Economica*, 15(2), 517-535. <https://doi.org/10.14718/revfinanzpolitecon.v15.n2.2023.9>
1297. Peri, D. (2023). Machine learning algorithms in ship design optimization [Article]. *Ship Technology Research*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09377255.2023.2250160>
1298. Peroni, S., Dutton, A., Gray, T., & Shotton, D. (2015). Setting our bibliographic references free: Towards open citation data [Article]. *Journal of Documentation*, 71(2), 253-277. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JD-12-2013-0166>
1299. Persaud, A., & Thaffe, W. (2023). The state of financial inclusion research on developing countries [Article]. *Transnational Corporations Review*, 15(4), 22-34. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tncr.2023.08.002>
1300. Peter, A., Majid, R. B. A., & Tukiman, N. I. B. (2023). Bibliometric and Scientometric Review of Architectural Flood Resilience for Housing [Article]. *Civil Engineering and Architecture*, 11(1), 248-267. <https://doi.org/10.13189/cea.2023.110121>
1301. Peters, M., Elasri-Ejjaberi, A., Martínez-Argüelles, M. J., & Fàbregues, S. (2022). Teacher digital competence development in higher education: Overview of systematic reviews [Article]. *Australasian Journal of Educational Technology*, 38(3), 122-139. <https://doi.org/10.14742/ajet.7543>
1302. Peters, M., Perez-Navarro, A., & Fabregues, S. (2022). A Systematic Mapping of E-Learning Research: An Interdisciplinary and Multi-paradigmatic Perspective from the Universitat Oberta de Catalunya [Article]. *Electronic Journal of e-Learning*, 20(4), 451-466. <https://doi.org/10.34190/ejel.20.4.2327>
1303. Petrescu, M., & Krishen, A. S. (2023). Mapping 2022 in Journal of Marketing Analytics: what lies ahead? [Editorial]. *Journal of Marketing Analytics*, 11(1), 1-4. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41270-023-00214-w>
1304. Pevcin, P. (2019). Smart city label: Past, present, and future [Article]. *Zbornik radova Ekonomskog fakulteta u Rijeci / Proceedings of Rijeka Faculty of Economics*, 37(2), 801-822. <https://doi.org/10.18045/zbefri.2019.2.801>
1305. Pham, H., Kim, S. Y., & Luu, T. V. (2020). Managerial perceptions on barriers to sustainable construction in developing countries: Vietnam case [Article]. *Environment, Development and Sustainability*, 22(4), 2979-3003. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10668-019-00331-6>
1306. Phan, H. T., Vu, G. V., Vu, G. T., Ha, G. H., Pham, H. Q., Latkin, C. A., Tran, B. X., Ho, C. S. H., & Ho, R. C. M. (2020). Global mapping of research trends on interventions to improve health-

- related quality of life in asthma patients [Article]. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(10), Article 3540. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17103540>
1307. Phan, T. N., & Kappas, M. (2018). Application of MODIS land surface temperature data: A systematic literature review and analysis [Review]. *Journal of Applied Remote Sensing*, 12(4), Article 041501. <https://doi.org/10.1117/1.JRS.12.041501>
1308. Philsoophian, M., Akhavan, P., & Abbasi, M. (2021). Strategic alliance for resilience in supply chain: A bibliometric analysis [Article]. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 13(22), Article 12715. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su132212715>
1309. Phuong, N. L., Hien, L. T. T., Linh, N. Q., Thao, T. T. P., Pham, H. H. T., Giang, N. T., & Thuy, V. T. (2023). Implementation of STEM education: A bibliometrics analysis from case study research in Scopus database [Article]. *Eurasia Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology Education*, 19(6), Article em2278. <https://doi.org/10.29333/ejmste/13216>
1310. Piazzzi, M. A., Feng, H., & Kassem, M. (2022). AN INVESTIGATION OF CONCEPTS FOR THE SPECIFICATION OF GRAPHICAL EXCHANGE INFORMATION REQUIREMENTS IN BUILDING INFORMATION MODELLING [Article]. *Journal of Information Technology in Construction*, 27, 662-684. <https://doi.org/10.36680/j.itcon.2022.033>
1311. Pike, S., Dam, L., & Beatson, A. (2019). Social media gratifications in the context of international travel planning: The use of the repertory test method [Article]. *Acta Turistica*, 31(2), 153-178. <https://doi.org/10.22598/AT/2019.31.2.153>
1312. Pinto, D., Lopes, A., & Mouraz, A. (2019). Perspectives on the transition to higher education in Europe: an approach focused on literature [Article]. *Research in Post-Compulsory Education*, 24(4), 356-374. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13596748.2019.1584429>
1313. Pires, A. L. G., Junior, P. R., Morioka, S. N., Rocha, L. C. S., & Bolis, I. (2022). Main trends and criteria adopted in economic feasibility studies of offshore wind energy: A systematic literature review [Review]. *Energies*, 15(1), Article 12. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en15010012>
1314. Pires, S. M., Polido, A., Teles, F., Silva, P., & Rodrigues, C. (2020). Territorial innovation models in less developed regions in Europe: the quest for a new research agenda? [Article]. *European Planning Studies*, 28(8), 1639-1666. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09654313.2019.1697211>
1315. Pirola, F., Boucher, X., Wiesner, S., & Pezzotta, G. (2020). Digital technologies in product-service systems: a literature review and a research agenda [Review]. *Computers in Industry*, 123, Article 103301. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compind.2020.103301>
1316. Pishedda, G., Marinò, L., & Corsi, K. (2023). Defensive medicine through the lens of the managerial perspective: a literature review [Article]. *BMC Health Services Research*, 23(1), Article 1104. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12913-023-10089-3>
1317. Pisoschi, A. M., Pop, A., Predoi, G., & Purdoi, L. (2020). An analysis of the influence of some incentives on bibliometric performances [Review]. *Journal of Scientometric Research*, 9(3), 344-351. <https://doi.org/10.5530/JSCIRES.9.3.42>
1318. Plavin-Masterman, M. L. (2015). Are walls just walls? Organizational culture emergence in a virtual firm [Article]. *Journal of Organizational Culture, Communications and Conflict*, 19(2), 43-68. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84959337289&partnerID=40&md5=f92f3235ec3dc5488cf09d65a5ef77d0>
1319. Polat, E., & Koseoglu, M. A. (2023). Wellness tourism scholarship: a research agenda [Review]. *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Insights*, 6(5), 1860-1889. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JHTI-05-2022-0186>
1320. Poltronieri, E., Bravo, E., Curti, M., Ferri, M., & Mancini, C. (2016). Open access publishing trend analysis: Statistics beyond the perception [Article]. *Information Research*, 21(2).

<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85000454220&partnerID=40&md5=812a409a1d882284308c57a2e694943a>

1321. Pongolini, M., Lundin, J., & Svensson, L. (2011). Global online meetings in virtual teams -from media choice to interaction negotiation.
1322. Pontieri, P., Mennini, F. S., Magni, D., Fiano, F., Scuotto, V., Papa, A., Aletta, M., & Del Giudice, L. (2022). Sustainable open innovation for the agri-food system: sorghum as healthy food to deal with environmental challenges [Article]. *British Food Journal*, 124(9), 2649-2672. <https://doi.org/10.1108/BFJ-07-2021-0732>
1323. Popescu, F., & Warmenhoven, R. (2019). Use of technology and virtual communication via global virtual teams at Arnhem business school. In J. I. Kantola, S. Nazir, & T. Barath (Eds.), (Vol. 783, pp. 239-248): Springer Verlag.
1324. Pozin, M. A. A., & Nawi, M. N. M. (2016). Effective factor of virtual team: Resolving communication breakdown in IBS construction project.
1325. Pozin, M. A. A., Nawi, M. N. M., Ahmi, A., Harun, A. N., & Lapwong, T. (2019). Virtual team literature: A bibliometric evaluation [Article]. *Test Engineering and Management*, 81(11-12), 3935-3943. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85081064831&partnerID=40&md5=da13d177538415268c894112b1bbe397>
1326. Pozin, M. A. A., Nawi, M. N. M., & Romle, A. R. (2016). Effectiveness of virtual team for improving communication breakdown in IBS project delivery process [Article]. *International Journal of Supply Chain Management*, 5(4), 121-130. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85009431569&partnerID=40&md5=31df8761f94fb6eb37b76d479069924d>
1327. Prabakusuma, A. S., Wardono, B., Fahlevi, M., Zulham, A., Djoko Sunarno, M. T., Syukur, M., Aljuaid, M., Saniuk, S., Apriliani, T., & Pramoda, R. (2023). A bibliometric approach to understanding the recent development of self-sufficient fish feed production utilizing agri-food wastes and by-products towards sustainable aquaculture [Article]. *Heliyon*, 9(7), Article e17573. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e17573>
1328. Prahani, B. K., Dawana, I. R., Jatmiko, B., & Amelia, T. (2023). Research Trend of Big Data in Education During the Last 10 Years [Article]. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning*, 18(10), 39-64. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijet.v18i10.38453>
1329. Prancutè, R. (2021). Web of Science (WoS) and Scopus: the titans of bibliographic information in today's academic world [Review]. *Publications*, 9(1), Article 12. <https://doi.org/10.3390/publications9010012>
1330. Prexl, K. M., & Gonera, A. (2021). Understanding new corporate innovation strategies: Hybrid high-involvement approaches and the increasing importance of individual absorptive capacity [Article]. *International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Innovation Management*, 25(4-5), 363-390. <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJEIM.2021.119199>
1331. Punj, N., Ahmi, A., Tanwar, A., & Abdul Rahim, S. (2023). Mapping the field of green manufacturing: A bibliometric review of the literature and research frontiers [Review]. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 423, Article 138729. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2023.138729>
1332. Purba, L. D. A., Md Khudzari, J., Iwamoto, K., Mohamad, S. E., Yuzir, A., Abdullah, N., Shimizu, K., & Hermana, J. (2022). Discovering future research trends of aerobic granular sludge using bibliometric approach [Review]. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 303, Article 114150. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2021.114150>
1333. Purnama, C., & Subroto, W. T. (2016). Competition intensity, uncertainty environmental on the use of information technology and its impact on business performance small and medium enterprises [Article]. *International Review of Management and Marketing*, 6(4), 984-992.

<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84992549228&partnerID=40&md5=576870cf5874ad42287daf75f6eb4039>

1334. Purwanto, E., & Irawan, A. P. (2023). Bibliometric Analysis of Electric Vehicle Adoption Research: Trends, Implications, and Future Directions [Article]. *International Journal of Safety and Security Engineering*, 13(5), 789-800. <https://doi.org/10.18280/ijss.130503>
1335. Putera, P. B., & Gustina, A. (2021). Discourse on digital government and regulation: A bibliometric analysis [Article]. *Library Philosophy and Practice*, 2021, 1-11. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85109932480&partnerID=40&md5=a148326f4f489b3c93066a33d6cb102f>
1336. Putikadyanto, A. P. A., Zamahsari, G. K., & Thoha, M. (2022). A Bibliometric Analysis of Digital Game-Based Language Learning to Support Future Language Learning.
1337. Putri, A. S., & Hisjam, M. (2019). Research development of sustainable supply chain management: A comparative study.
1338. Qin, D., Hu, Y., & Li, X. (2021). Waste glass utilization in cement-based materials for sustainable construction: A review [Article]. *Crystals*, 11(6), Article 710. <https://doi.org/10.3390/cryst11060710>
1339. Qiu, F., & Dauth, T. (2022). Virtual work intensity, job satisfaction, and the mediating role of work-family balance: A study of employees in Germany and China [Article]. *German Journal of Human Resource Management*, 36(1), 77-111. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2397002221998227>
1340. Qiu, R. G. (2010). A collaborative model of engineering education for complex global environments.
1341. Qiu, R. G. (2014). *Service Science: The Foundations of Service Engineering and Management* (Vol. 9781118108239) [Book]. Wiley Blackwell. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118551820>
1342. Qiu, R. G. (2019). A systemic approach to leveraging student engagement in collaborative learning to improve online engineering education [Article]. *International Journal of Technology Enhanced Learning*, 11(1), 1-19. <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJTEL.2019.096734>
1343. Queiroz, G. A., Alves Junior, P. N., & Costa Melo, I. (2022). Digitalization as an Enabler to SMEs Implementing Lean-Green? A Systematic Review through the Topic Modelling Approach [Review]. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 14(21), Article 14089. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su142114089>
1344. Radević, L., & Milovanović, I. (2023). Current Trends in Math Anxiety Research: a Bibliometric Approach [Article]. *International Journal of Science and Mathematics Education*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10763-023-10424-4>
1345. Radulescu, C. Z., Radulescu, M., & Boncea, R. (2023). A New Revised Group DEMATEL method with application on facility location problem.
1346. Rafael, C. (2022). Virtual Tourism: Bibliometric Analysis [Note]. *RISTI - Revista Iberica de Sistemas e Tecnologias de Informacao*(Special Issue 47), 239-250. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85127604971&partnerID=40&md5=eef254609adbce4bc1b6432b93db38e>
1347. Raghav, A., & Jeong, G. B. (2021). A systematic review on the modifications of extracellular vesicles: a revolutionized tool of nano-biotechnology [Review]. *Journal of Nanobiotechnology*, 19(1), Article 459. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12951-021-01219-2>
1348. Rahaman, S., Govil, P., Khan, D., & Jevremov, T. D. (2023). A 30-year bibliometric assessment and visualisation of emotion regulation research: applying network analysis and cluster analysis [Review]. *Information Discovery and Delivery*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IDD-11-2022-0110>
1349. Rahardja, U., Harahap, E. P., & Dewi, S. R. (2019). The strategy of enhancing article citation and H-index on SINTA to improve tertiary reputation [Article]. *Telkomnika (Telecommunication*

- Computing Electronics and Control), 17(2), 683-692.
<https://doi.org/10.12928/TELKOMNIKA.V17I2.9761>
1350. Rahimkhani, P., Ordokhani, Y., & Sabermahani, S. (2023). Bernoulli wavelet least squares support vector regression: Robust numerical method for systems of fractional differential equations [Article]. *Mathematical Methods in the Applied Sciences*, 46(17), 17641-17659.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/mma.9522>
1351. Rahimkhani, P., Ordokhani, Y., & Sabermahani, S. (2023). Hahn hybrid functions for solving distributed order fractional Black–Scholes European option pricing problem arising in financial market [Article]. *Mathematical Methods in the Applied Sciences*, 46(6), 6558-6577.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/mma.8924>
1352. Rahman, R. A., Sadik, K., & Fitrianto, A. (2022). Simulation for Time Series Classification Using Feature Covariance Matrices with K-Nearest Neighbor.
1353. Raman, A., Thannimalai, R., Don, Y., & Rathakrishnan, M. (2021). A bibliometric analysis of blended learning in higher education: perception, achievement and engagement [Review]. *International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research*, 20(6), 126-151.
<https://doi.org/10.26803/IJLTER.20.6.7>
1354. Raman, R., Nair, V. K., Prakash, V., Patwardhan, A., & Nedungadi, P. (2022). Green-hydrogen research: What have we achieved, and where are we going? Bibliometrics analysis [Review]. *Energy Reports*, 8, 9242-9260. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egy.2022.07.058>
1355. Ramezani, A., Shahmoradi, L., Azadeh, F., Sheikshoaei, F., Atlasi, R., Namazi, N., & Larijani, B. (2021). VISUALIZATION OF KNOWLEDGE FLOW IN INTERPERSONAL SCIENTIFIC COLLABORATION NETWORK ENDOCRINOLOGY AND METABOLISM RESEARCH INSTITUTE [Article]. *Iranian Journal of Diabetes and Metabolism*, 20(1), 71-82.
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85147877660&partnerID=40&md5=cbaadfa2d310cbfaf1543ee7082ac79c>
1356. Ramirez, M. A. N., Rivero, R. A. B., Flores, C. L. V., Garcia, I. G. E., Del Rio, S. V., Banuelos, M. N. S., & Beltran, A. G. O. (2020). Organizational culture and knowledge management: Evidence from Bolivia and Mexico [Article]. *Asian Economic and Financial Review*, 10(3), 249-265.
<https://doi.org/10.18488/JOURNAL.AEFR.2020.103.249.265>
1357. Ramirez-Peña, M., Fraga, F. J. A., Salguero, J., & Batista, M. (2020). Assessing sustainability in the shipbuilding supply chain 4.0: A systematic review [Review]. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 12(16), Article 6373. <https://doi.org/10.3390/SU12166373>
1358. Ramy, A., Floody, J., Ragab, M. A. F., & Arisha, A. (2018). A scientometric analysis of Knowledge Management Research and Practice literature: 2003-2015 [Article]. *Knowledge Management Research and Practice*, 16(1), 66-77. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14778238.2017.1405776>
1359. Ramzy, M., & Ibrahim, B. (2022). The evolution of e-government research over two decades: applying bibliometrics and science mapping analysis [Article]. *Library Hi Tech*.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/LHT-02-2022-0100>
1360. Rana, S. K., Dangwal, B., Negi, V. S., & Bhatt, I. D. (2022). Scientific research in the Himalaya: Current state of knowledge, funding paradigm and policy implications [Review]. *Environmental Science and Policy*, 136, 685-695. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2022.07.030>
1361. Rana, S. K., Rawal, R. S., Dangwal, B., Bhatt, I. D., & Price, T. D. (2021). 200 Years of Research on Himalayan Biodiversity: Trends, Gaps, and Policy Implications [Review]. *Frontiers in Ecology and Evolution*, 8, Article 603422. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fevo.2020.603422>
1362. Rañeses, M. K., Chang-Richards, A., Wang, K. I. K., & Dirks, K. N. (2021). Housing for now and the future: A systematic review of climate-adaptive measures [Review]. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 13(12), Article 6744. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13126744>

1363. Rashid, L. (2019). Entrepreneurship education and sustainable development goals: A literature review and a closer look at fragile states and technology-enabled approaches [Review]. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 11(19), Article 5343. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11195343>
1364. Rathnasiri, N., De Silva, N., & Wijesundara, J. (2024). State of the art in work zone safety: A systematic review [Review]. *International Journal of Transportation Science and Technology*, 13, 14-28. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijst.2023.11.006>
1365. Rawat, D. S., Singh, K., Singh, M., Patel, A. K., & Patel, A. K. (2021). Research Productivity of Wadia Institute of Himalayan Geology [Article]. *Library Philosophy and Practice*, 2021, 1-22. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85110747168&partnerID=40&md5=ab424b2917272289f429a91e9dca8ace>
1366. Rawat, K. S., & Sood, S. K. (2021). Emerging trends and global scope of big data analytics: a scientometric analysis [Article]. *Quality and Quantity*, 55(4), 1371-1396. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11135-020-01061-y>
1367. Rawat, K. S., & Sood, S. K. (2021). Knowledge mapping of computer applications in education using CiteSpace [Article]. *Computer Applications in Engineering Education*, 29(5), 1324-1339. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cae.22388>
1368. Razak, M. F. A., Anuar, N. B., Salleh, R., & Firdaus, A. (2016). The rise of “malware”: Bibliometric analysis of malware study [Review]. *Journal of Network and Computer Applications*, 75, 58-76. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jnca.2016.08.022>
1369. Reeb, S., Clauss, A., Lenk, F., & Altmann, M. (2021). Success factors of intra-organisational online collaboration: A systematic literature review [Review]. *International Journal of Management and Enterprise Development*, 20(3), 200-233. <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJMED.2021.118405>
1370. Rehman, Z. U., Baharun, R., & Salleh, N. Z. M. (2020). Antecedents, consequences, and reducers of perceived risk in social media: A systematic literature review and directions for further research [Review]. *Psychology and Marketing*, 37(1), 74-86. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mar.21281>
1371. Reinhardt, H., Bergmann, J. P., Münnich, M., Rein, D., & Putz, M. (2020). A survey on modeling and forecasting the energy consumption in discrete manufacturing.
1372. Rejeb, A., Rejeb, K., Simske, S. J., & Treiblmaier, H. (2023). Drones for supply chain management and logistics: a review and research agenda [Article]. *International Journal of Logistics Research and Applications*, 26(6), 708-731. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13675567.2021.1981273>
1373. Renjith, V. R., Vijayan, S. S., & Arunkumar, V. R. (2021). Web of Science (WoS) Indexed Library and Information Science (LIS) Journals in Scopus: An Analysis [Article]. *Library Philosophy and Practice*, 2021, Article 6348. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85120963777&partnerID=40&md5=f1ad6893ebf762c9e6279a6087eaacab>
1374. Repiso, R., Moreno-Delgado, A., & Aguaded, I. (2021). Factors affecting the frequency of citation of an article [Article]. *Iberoamerican Journal of Science Measurement and Communication*, 1(1). <https://doi.org/10.47909/ijsmc.08>
1375. Reuß, F., Greimeister-Pfeil, I., Vreugdenhil, M., & Wagner, W. (2021). Comparison of long short-term memory networks and random forest for sentinel-1 time series based large scale crop classification [Article]. *Remote Sensing*, 13(24), Article 5000. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs13245000>
1376. Reyes, R. L. (2023). Article Citation Tracking Exercise: An Activity in Assessing Research Impact and the Interdisciplinary Nature of Chemistry [Article]. *Journal of Chemical Education*, 100(11), 4369-4377. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jchemed.3c00717>
1377. Reyes-Belmonte, M. A. (2021). Quo vadis solar energy research? [Review]. *Applied Sciences (Switzerland)*, 11(7), Article 3015. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app11073015>

1378. Reyes-Belmonte, M. A., Guédez, R., & Montes, M. J. (2021). Bibliometric analysis on supercritical CO₂ power cycles for concentrating solar power applications [Article]. *Entropy*, 23(10), Article 1289. <https://doi.org/10.3390/e23101289>
1379. Reza Hosseini, M., Chileshe, N., Zuo, J., & Baroudi, B. (2013). A conceptual framework for member selection in Global Virtual Teams (GVTs).
1380. Rezvani, S. M. H. S., Falcão, M. J., Komljenovic, D., & de Almeida, N. M. (2023). A Systematic Literature Review on Urban Resilience Enabled with Asset and Disaster Risk Management Approaches and GIS-Based Decision Support Tools [Review]. *Applied Sciences (Switzerland)*, 13(4), Article 2223. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app13042223>
1381. Riazi, S. A., Baghestan, A. G., Ideris, A., Khaniki, H., Akhtari-Zavare, M., & Farahmand, E. (2019). Science and technology diplomacy and the power of students: the case of Iranian student in Malaysia [Article]. *Pertanika Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*, 27(1), 649-662. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85064380191&partnerID=40&md5=80e2a5be6060bd1c79126e620c928138>
1382. Ribeiro, D. P., De Oliveira, U. R., Da Silva César, A., & Aprigliano Fernandes, V. (2021). Evaluation of medicine reverse logistics practices in hospitals [Article]. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 13(6), Article 3496. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13063496>
1383. Ribeiro, P. C. C., Amaral, P. R. B., Gomes, C. F. S., & dos Santos, M. (2022). The Triple Bottom Line in Sustainable Supply Chain Management Frameworks and Their Gaps in the Period 2014–2022.
1384. Ricart, S., Castelletti, A., & Gandolfi, C. (2022). On farmers' perceptions of climate change and its nexus with climate data and adaptive capacity. A comprehensive review [Review]. *Environmental Research Letters*, 17(8), Article 083002. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/ac810f>
1385. Rico-Pére, H., Arenas-Parr, M., & Quiroga-Garci, R. (2022). Scientific Development of Robo-Advisor: A Bibliometric Analysis [Article]. *Review of Economics and Finance*, 20, 776-786. <https://doi.org/10.55365/1923.X2022.20.87>
1386. Rimbau-Gilabert, E., Martínez-Argüelles, M. J., & Ruiz-Dotras, E. (2013). Managing Matrixed, Dispersed Advisors in Virtual Universities. In *Communications in Computer and Information Science* (Vol. 278, pp. 669-676): Springer Verlag.
1387. Rispens, S. (2021). Cooperation and conflict in academia. In *Becoming an Organizational Scholar: Navigating the Academic Odyssey* (pp. 158-171). Edward Elgar Publishing Ltd. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85130663451&partnerID=40&md5=6f22a520824e8cf35aa7ddbec1bc7f38>
1388. Riswantini, D., & Nugraheni, E. (2022). Machine learning in handling disease outbreaks: a comprehensive review [Article]. *Bulletin of Electrical Engineering and Informatics*, 11(4), 2169-2186. <https://doi.org/10.11591/eei.v11i4.3612>
1389. Rivero-Villar, A., & Vieyra Medrano, A. (2022). Governance for urban resilience in popular settlements in developing countries: a case-study review [Review]. *Climate and Development*, 14(3), 208-221. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17565529.2021.1906203>
1390. Robinson, J., Dusenberry, L., & Lawrence, H. M. (2016). Collaborative strategies for distributed teams: Innovation through interlaced collaborative writing.
1391. Robinson, S. A. (2020). Climate change adaptation in SIDS: A systematic review of the literature pre and post the IPCC Fifth Assessment Report [Review]. *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Climate Change*, 11(4), Article e653. <https://doi.org/10.1002/wcc.653>
1392. Robson, B. J., & Mousquès, A. (2014). Predicting citation counts of environmental modelling papers.

1393. Robson, B. J., & Mousquès, A. (2016). Can we predict citation counts of environmental modelling papers? Fourteen bibliographic and categorical variables predict less than 30% of the variability in citation counts [Article]. *Environmental Modelling and Software*, 75, 94-104. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsoft.2015.10.007>
1394. Rocha, I. F., & Kissimoto, K. O. (2022). Artificial intelligence and internet of things adoption in operations management: Barriers and benefits [Article]. *Revista de Administracao Mackenzie*, 23(4), Article eRAMR220119. <https://doi.org/10.1590/1678-6971/eRAMR220119.en>
1395. Rocha, I. F., & Kissimoto, K. O. (2022). Barreiras e benefícios na adoção de inteligência artificial e IoT na gestão de operação [Article]. *Revista de Administracao Mackenzie*, 23(4), Article eRAMR220119. <https://doi.org/10.1590/1678-6971/ERAMR220119.PT>
1396. Rochman, C., Mulhayatiah, D., Sari, I., Suhendi, H. Y., & Nasrudin, D. (2022). Science Process Skills through PjBL-STEM on Global Warming Concept.
1397. Rodrigues, C., Ferreira, F. A., Costa, V., Alves, M. J., Vaz, M., Fernandes, P. O., & Nunes, A. (2022). Health and Wellness Activities: Contemporary Market of Thermalism. In J. V. Carvalho, P. Liberato, & A. Pena (Eds.), (Vol. 284, pp. 361-371): Springer Science and Business Media Deutschland GmbH.
1398. Rodrigues, C., Ferreira, F. A., Costa, V., Alves, M. J., Vaz, M., Fernandes, P. O., & Nunes, A. (2023). Understanding Behavioral Intentions in a Spa Experience: Insights from Contemporary Literature.
1399. Rodrigues, C., Liberato, D., Esteves, E., & Liberato, P. (2023). Scientific Narratives on Creative Tourism: A Theoretical Framework.
1400. Rodrigues, S., Correia, R., Gonçalves, R., & Martins, J. (2021). Innovative Marketing Approaches as Triggers to Rural Tourism Sustainability: An In-Depth Analysis to Existing Literature. In T. Guarda, F. Portela, & M. F. Santos (Eds.), (Vol. 1485 CCIS, pp. 653-663): Springer Science and Business Media Deutschland GmbH.
1401. Rodrigues-Santana, L., Adsuar, J. C., Denche-Zamorano, A., Vega-Muñoz, A., Salazar-Sepúlveda, G., Contreras-Barraza, N., Galán-Arroyo, C., & Louro, H. (2022). Bibliometric Analysis of Studies on Whole Body Electromyostimulation [Article]. *Biology*, 11(8), Article 1205. <https://doi.org/10.3390/biology11081205>
1402. Rodrigues-Silva, J., & Alsina, Á. (2023). STEM/STEAM in Early Childhood Education for Sustainability (ECEfS): A Systematic Review [Review]. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 15(4), Article 3721. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15043721>
1403. Rodríguez, Á. M. C., Ardila, H. E. M., Gutierrez, D. A. R., & Castro, J. F. G. (2020). Reference practices associated with university spin-off creation.
1404. Rodríguez Rubio, M. J., Nuñez Ramírez, M. A., & Esparza García, I. G. (2018). Empirical test of the Nonaka and Takeuchi's knowledge management model in the university context [Article]. *Espacios*, 39(49). <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85058243233&partnerID=40&md5=ab30faf419aaaedc809395b6126f5583>
1405. Rodríguez-Antón, J. M., Rubio-Andrada, L., Celemín-Pedroche, M. S., & Ruíz-Peñalver, S. M. (2022). From the circular economy to the sustainable development goals in the European Union: an empirical comparison [Article]. *International Environmental Agreements: Politics, Law and Economics*, 22(1), 67-95. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10784-021-09553-4>
1406. Rodríguez-Insuasti, H., Montalván-Burbano, N., Suárez-Rodríguez, O., Yonfá-Medranda, M., & Parrales-Guerrero, K. (2022). Creative Economy: A Worldwide Research in Business, Management and Accounting [Article]. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 14(23), Article 16010. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su142316010>

1407. Rojo, J. R., Njororai Simiyu, W. W., & Starepravo, F. A. (2020). Research on sports migration: An analysis of methodological procedures [Article]. *Journal of Physical Education and Sport*, 20(2), 546-553, Article 81. <https://doi.org/10.7752/jpes.2020.02081>
1408. Rojo, J. R., Ribeiro, C. H. V., & Starepravo, F. A. (2021). The process of formation and development of an academic field: The example of sport migration [Review]. *International Sports Studies*, 43(2), 52-67. <https://doi.org/10.30819/iss.43-2.05>
1409. Romanowski, M. H. (2022). Preservice Teachers' Perception of Plagiarism: A Case from a College of Education [Article]. *Journal of Academic Ethics*, 20(3), 289-309. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10805-021-09395-4>
1410. Roncagliolo, E., Di Fabio, C., Avallone, F., & Ramassa, P. (2017). The effects of XBRL adoption: A literature review.
1411. Ronen, I., Guy, I., Kravi, E., & Barnea, M. (2014). Recommending social media content to community owners.
1412. Ross, M. B., Glennon, B. M., Murciano-Goroff, R., Berkes, E. G., Weinberg, B. A., & Lane, J. I. (2022). Women are credited less in science than men [Article]. *Nature*, 608(7921), 135-145. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-022-04966-w>
1413. Rossella, C., Pierpaolo, M., Angelo, B., & Paola, C. (2022). Going on a Quest for Social and Humane Intentions Within Strategic Entrepreneurship: A Systematic Literature Review Approach. In *Contributions to Management Science* (pp. 121-142): Springer Science and Business Media Deutschland GmbH.
1414. Rosu, S. M., & Dragoi, G. (2011). Virtual enterprise network solutions and monitoring as support for geographically dispersed business. In *Handbook of Research on Business Social Networking: Organizational, Managerial, and Technological Dimensions* (pp. 34-62). IGI Global. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-61350-168-9.ch003>
1415. Roşu, S. M., & Drăgoi, G. (2011). VPN solutions and network monitoring to support virtual teams work in virtual enterprises [Article]. *Computer Science and Information Systems*, 8(1), 1-26. <https://doi.org/10.2298/CSIS100127033R>
1416. Rotar, D. Z., Jokić, M., & Mateljan, S. (2018). The visibility of papers written by authors from European post-socialist countries as an indicator of integration into the EU legal system [Article]. *Croatian Yearbook of European Law and Policy*, 14(1), 136-160. <https://doi.org/10.3935/cyelp.14.2018.304>
1417. Rozario, S. D., Venkatraman, S., Marimuthu, M., Khaksar, S. M. S., & Subramani, G. (2021). Creating smart cities: A review for holistic approach [Review]. *Applied System Innovation*, 4(4), Article 70. <https://doi.org/10.3390/asi4040070>
1418. Rozman, T., Stjepanovic, T. K., & Raspor, A. (2017). An analysis of web-based document management and communication tools usage among project managers [Article]. *International Journal of Human Capital and Information Technology Professionals*, 8(1), 1-24. <https://doi.org/10.4018/IJHCITP.2017010101>
1419. Ruales Guzmán, B. V., Brun, A., & Castellanos Domínguez, O. F. (2019). Quality management as a determinant factor of productivity: A systematic literature review [Review]. *International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management*, 68(4), 675-698. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJPPM-07-2018-0251>
1420. Ruban, I., Khudov, H., Makoveichuk, O., Butko, I., Glukhov, S., Khizhnyak, I., Shamrai, N., & Kalimulin, T. (2023). Application of the Particle Swarm Algorithm to the Task of Image Segmentation for Remote Sensing of the Earth. In P. P. Joby, V. E. Balas, & R. Palanisamy (Eds.), (Vol. 528, pp. 573-585): Springer Science and Business Media Deutschland GmbH.

1421. Ruiz-Real, J. L., Uribe-Toril, J., Torres, J. A., & Pablo, J. D. E. (2021). Artificial intelligence in business and economics research: Trends and future [Article]. *Journal of Business Economics and Management*, 22(1), 98-117. <https://doi.org/10.3846/jbem.2020.13641>
1422. Russell, M. B., & Liggans, G. (2022). *Fired up!: A guide to transforming your team from burnout to engagement* [Book]. De Gruyter. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110741728>
1423. Saad, A., Ajayi, S. O., & Alaka, H. A. (2023). Trends in BIM-based plugins development for construction activities: a systematic review [Article]. *International Journal of Construction Management*, 23(16), 2756-2768. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15623599.2022.2093815>
1424. Saad, A. M., Dulaimi, M., & Zulu, S. L. (2023). A Systematic Review of the Business Contingencies Influencing Broader Adoption: Modern Methods of Construction (MMC) [Article]. *Buildings*, 13(4), Article 878. <https://doi.org/10.3390/buildings13040878>
1425. Saad, H. B. (2020). La tunisie medicale: Bibliometric analysis of the articles cites 10 times or more in the scopus database [Article]. *Tunisie Medicale*, 98(10), 527-536. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85093094236&partnerID=40&md5=d8d0b345c990f50dea8bfdd6b2d00cb6>
1426. Sabermahani, S., & Ordokhani, Y. (2021). Fibonacci wavelets and Galerkin method to investigate fractional optimal control problems with bibliometric analysis [Article]. *JVC/Journal of Vibration and Control*, 27(15-16), 1778-1792. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1077546320948346>
1427. Sabermahani, S., & Ordokhani, Y. (2021). General Lagrange-hybrid functions and numerical solution of differential equations containing piecewise constant delays with bibliometric analysis [Article]. *Applied Mathematics and Computation*, 395, Article 125847. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.amc.2020.125847>
1428. Sabermahani, S., & Ordokhani, Y. (2022). Numerical solution of a fractional epidemic model via general Lagrange scaling functions with bibliometric analysis. In *Mathematical Analysis of Infectious Diseases* (pp. 305-320). Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-32-390504-6.00022-X>
1429. Sabermahani, S., & Ordokhani, Y. (2022). A numerical technique for solving fractional Benjamin-Bona-Mahony-Burgers equations with bibliometric analysis. In *Fractional Order Systems and Applications in Engineering* (pp. 93-108). Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-32-390953-2.00013-X>
1430. Sachini, E., Sioumalas-Christodoulou, K., Chrysomallidis, C., Siganos, G., & Karampekios, N. (2022). Identifying the Intellectual Capital of Greek Defence Firms. *Science Outputs and Industrial Considerations* [Article]. *Defence and Peace Economics*, 33(3), 366-385. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10242694.2020.1849972>
1431. Sadeghi, M. T., Sobhani, F. M., & Ghatari, A. R. (2017). Representing a model to measure absorbency of information technology in small and medium sized enterprises [Article]. *Journal of Information Systems and Telecommunication*, 5(4), 242-251. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85041794035&partnerID=40&md5=b0124da5dfd8ba6e7534e5595afbbd0d>
1432. Sadeghi, S., Soltanmohammadlou, N., & Rahnamayiezekavat, P. (2021). A systematic review of scholarly works addressing crane safety requirements [Article]. *Safety Science*, 133, Article 105002. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssci.2020.105002>
1433. Sáez-Ortuño, L., Forgas-Coll, S., Huertas-García, R., & Sánchez-García, J. (2023). What's on the horizon? A bibliometric analysis of personal data collection methods on social networks [Article]. *Journal of Business Research*, 158, Article 113702. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2023.113702>
1434. Şahin, A., Karakaya, Y. E., & Dikmen, M. (2023). Mapping Tendencies in Curriculum Research on Physical Education and Sports: A Bibliometric Analysis [Article]. *Participatory Educational Research*, 10(3), 106-129. <https://doi.org/10.17275/per.23.47.10.3>

1435. Şahin, A., & Yılmaz, G. (2022). Local food research: a bibliometric review using Citespace II (1970–2020) [Article]. *Library Hi Tech*, 40(3), 848-870. <https://doi.org/10.1108/LHT-07-2021-0227>
1436. Şahin, K., & Candan, G. (2018). Scientific productivity and cooperation in Turkic world: a bibliometric analysis [Article]. *Scientometrics*, 115(3), 1199-1229. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-018-2730-x>
1437. Saif, A. N. M., Rahman, A. A., & Mostafa, R. (2021). Post-implementation challenges of erp adoption in apparel industry of developing country [Article]. *Logforum*, 17(4), 519-529. <https://doi.org/10.17270/J.LOG.2021.624>
1438. Saik, P., Petlovanyi, M., Lozynskyi, V., Sai, K., & Merzlikin, A. (2018). Innovative approach to the integrated use of energy resources of underground coal gasification. In *Solid State Phenomena* (Vol. 277, pp. 221-231): Trans Tech Publications Ltd.
1439. Sajadian, S. H., Akhavan, P., & Mohammadi-Fateh, A. (2022). Knowledge Strategy Research Fronts and Intellectual Bases: Based on Information Visualization Methodology [Article]. *International Journal of Information Science and Management*, 20(4), 275-295. <https://doi.org/10.22034/ijism.2022.698431>
1440. Sajdakova, J., Carey, E., Dhokia, V., Newnes, L., & Parry, G. (2022). Proposal of a Self-Assessment Competency Framework for Transdisciplinary Engineering [Article]. *Journal of Industrial Integration and Management*, Article 2250022. <https://doi.org/10.1142/S2424862222500221>
1441. Sajdakova, J., Newnes, L., Carey, E., & Dhokia, V. (2020). Mapping the competencies of design engineers against the jantsch's hierarchical system.
1442. Sakaguchi, K., Varughese, A., & Auld, G. (2017). Climate wars? A Systematic review of empirical analyses on the links between climate change and violent conflict [Article]. *International Studies Review*, 19(4), 622-645. <https://doi.org/10.1093/isr/vix022>
1443. Salam, S., & Senin, A. A. (2022). A Bibliometric Study on Innovative Behavior Literature (1961–2019) [Article]. *SAGE Open*, 12(3). <https://doi.org/10.1177/21582440221109589>
1444. Salder, J., Gilman, M., Raby, S., & Gkikas, A. (2020). Beyond linearity and resource-based perspectives of SME growth [Article]. *Journal of Small Business Strategy*, 30(1), 1-17. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85079858527&partnerID=40&md5=3987f63a56c83b0bea3dc2dcbc0492a0>
1445. Saleh, R. H., Durugbo, C. M., & Almahamid, S. M. (2023). What makes innovation ambidexterity manageable: a systematic review, multi-level model and future challenges [Review]. *Review of Managerial Science*, 17(8), 3013-3056. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11846-023-00659-4>
1446. Salikha, U. A., Sholihin, H., & Winarno, N. (2021). The influence of STEM project-based learning on students' motivation in heat transfer learning.
1447. Salleh, S. Z., & Bushroa, A. R. (2022). Bibliometric and content analysis on publications in digitization technology implementation in cultural heritage for recent five years (2016–2021) [Review]. *Digital Applications in Archaeology and Cultural Heritage*, 25, Article e00225. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.daach.2022.e00225>
1448. Salmerón-Manzano, E., & Manzano-Agugliaro, F. (2023). Worldwide research trends on land tenure [Article]. *Land Use Policy*, 131, Article 106727. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2023.106727>
1449. Samanta, A. K., Varaprasad, G., & Gurumurthy, A. (2023). Implementing Lean Six Sigma in health care: a review of case studies [Review]. *International Journal of Lean Six Sigma*, 14(1), 158-189. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJLSS-08-2021-0133>

1450. Samanta, S., Rautaray, B., & Swain, D. K. (2023). Intellectual structure and pattern of publication in the International Journal of Innovation Science: a bibliometric study [Article]. *International Journal of Innovation Science*, 15(2), 279-301. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJIS-06-2021-0103>
1451. Samanta, S., Rautaray, B. D., & Swain, D. K. D. (2021). Intellectual Structure and Publication Pattern in Journal of Money Laundering Control from 2014 to 2020: A Bibliometric Study [Article]. *Library Philosophy and Practice*, 2021, 1-15. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85111282156&partnerID=40&md5=5e4ab0777c3be8f596ad940d35b7431d>
1452. Sampaio, G. G., Behr, A., de Medeiros, M. M., & Bandeira, M. V. (2021). Bibliometric and cluster mapping of scientific research on knowledge management and social media [Article]. *REDES*, 32(1), 28-44. <https://doi.org/10.5565/REV/REDES.897>
1453. Samsudin, M. A., Jamali, S. M., Zain, A. N. M., & Ebrahim, N. A. (2020). The effect of STEM project based learning on self-efficacy among high-school physics students [Article]. *Journal of Turkish Science Education*, 17(1), 94-108. <https://doi.org/10.36681/tused.2020.15>
1454. Sanchez Cordero, A., Gomez Melgar, S., & Andujar Marquez, J. M. (2020). Incoming strategies for energy performance requirements at most frequently adopted green building rating systems from a refurbishment perspective.
1455. Sánchez-Garrido, A. J., Navarro, I. J., García, J., & Yepes, V. (2023). A systematic literature review on modern methods of construction in building: An integrated approach using machine learning [Review]. *Journal of Building Engineering*, 73, Article 106725. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.job.2023.106725>
1456. Sánchez-González, D., Rojo-Pérez, F., Rodríguez-Rodríguez, V., & Fernández-Mayoralas, G. (2020). Environmental and psychosocial interventions in age-friendly communities and active ageing: A systematic review [Review]. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(22), 1-35, Article 8305. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17228305>
1457. Sanchez-Roger, M., Oliver-Alfonso, M. D., & Sanchís-Pedregosa, C. (2019). Fuzzy logic and its uses in finance: A systematic review exploring its potential to deal with banking crises [Review]. *Mathematics*, 7(11), Article 1091. <https://doi.org/10.3390/math7111091>
1458. Sánchez-Ruiz, L. M., López-Alfonso, S., Moll-López, S., Morano-Fernández, J. A., & Vega-Fleitas, E. (2022). Educational Digital Escape Rooms Footprint on Students' Feelings: A Case Study within Aerospace Engineering [Article]. *Information (Switzerland)*, 13(10), Article 478. <https://doi.org/10.3390/info13100478>
1459. Sánchez-Suárez, J., Díaz, L., Coy-Barrera, E., & Villamil, L. (2022). Specialized Metabolism of *Gordonia* Genus: An Integrated Survey on Chemodiversity Combined with a Comparative Genomics-Based Analysis [Review]. *BioTech*, 11(4), Article 53. <https://doi.org/10.3390/biotech11040053>
1460. Sandanayake, M., Yang, W., Chhibba, N., & Vrcelj, Z. (2022). Residential building defects investigation and mitigation – a comparative review in Victoria, Australia, for understanding the way forward [Article]. *Engineering, Construction and Architectural Management*, 29(9), 3689-3711. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ECAM-03-2021-0232>
1461. Sandoval Hamón, L. A., Ruiz Peñalver, S. M., Thomas, E., & Fitjar, R. D. (2022). From high-tech clusters to open innovation ecosystems: a systematic literature review of the relationship between science and technology parks and universities [Article]. *Journal of Technology Transfer*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10961-022-09990-6>
1462. Sangwan, V., Harshita, Prakash, P., & Singh, S. (2020). Financial technology: a review of extant literature [Review]. *Studies in Economics and Finance*, 37(1), 71-88. <https://doi.org/10.1108/SEF-07-2019-0270>

1463. Sangwan, V., Kushwaha, S., Prakash, P., & Singh, A. (2023). Life cycle stage as determinant of operational efficiency with implications for benchmarking [Article]. *Applied Economics*.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/00036846.2023.2277688>
1464. Santa Rita, L. P., da Silva, L. S. C. V., Kaczam, F., Guedes Macêdo, M. J. F., Macêdo, Á. F. P. D., Silva, W. V. D., & da Veiga, C. P. (2023). Relationship between industry 4.0 and patents [Review]. *World Patent Information*, 74, Article 102221. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wpi.2023.102221>
1465. Santa Soriano, A., Lorenzo Álvarez, C., & Torres Valdés, R. M. (2018). Bibliometric analysis to identify an emerging research area: Public Relations Intelligence—a challenge to strengthen technological observatories in the network society [Article]. *Scientometrics*, 115(3), 1591-1614.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-018-2651-8>
1466. Santana, R., Rossi, G., Méndez, G. G., Rodríguez, A., & Cajas, V. (2021). Smart Glasses User Experience in STEM Students: A Systematic Mapping Study. In A. Rocha, H. Adeli, G. Dzemyda, F. Moreira, & A. M. R. Correia (Eds.), (Vol. 1365 AIST, pp. 455-467): Springer Science and Business Media Deutschland GmbH.
1467. Santisteban-Espejo, A., Campos, F., Martin-Piedra, L., Durand-Herrera, D., Moral-Munoz, J. A., Campos, A., & Martin-Piedra, M. A. (2018). Global Tissue Engineering Trends: A Scientometric and Evolutive Study [Article]. *Tissue Engineering - Part A*, 24(19-20), 1504-1517.
<https://doi.org/10.1089/ten.tea.2018.0007>
1468. Santos, A. C. O., da Silva, C. E. S., Braga, R. A. D. S., Corrêa, J. É., & de Almeida, F. A. (2020). Customer value in lean product development: Conceptual model for incremental innovations [Article]. *Systems Engineering*, 23(3), 281-293. <https://doi.org/10.1002/sys.21514>
1469. Santos, I. D. S., Andrade, R. M. D. C., Rocha, L. S., Matalonga, S., de Oliveira, K. M., & Travassos, G. H. (2017). Test case design for context-aware applications: Are we there yet? [Review]. *Information and Software Technology*, 88, 1-16. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.infsof.2017.03.008>
1470. Santos, S. R., & Vianna, M. (2018). Scientometric Analysis of Fisheries Science Studies of Western Atlantic Species of Paralichthys (Paralichthyidae: Pleuronectiformes) [Review]. *Reviews in Fisheries Science and Aquaculture*, 26(4), 443-459. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23308249.2018.1452896>
1471. Santos, S. R., & Vianna, M. (2018). Scientometric Analysis of the Fisheries Science for the Species of Cynoscion (Sciaenidae: Perciformes) from the Western Atlantic, with Emphasis in the Comparison of the North American and Brazilian Fisheries Catch Data [Review]. *Reviews in Fisheries Science and Aquaculture*, 26(1), 55-69. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23308249.2017.1337078>
1472. Santos, T., Santos, L., & Angelo, A. C. (2021). Socioeconomic pathways toward the sustainable development goals (SDGs) in Brazil during and post-COVID-19 pandemic. In *World Sustainability Series* (pp. 125-141): Springer Science and Business Media Deutschland GmbH.
1473. Santoso, M. A., Wijayanti, Y., Prasetyo, R. B., Setyandito, O., Nizam, Aprijanto, Subandriya, A., Kurniawan, A. T., Sudaryanto, A., & Sutejo, B. (2023). A Mini Review: Wave Energy Converters Technology, Potential Applications and Current Research in Indonesia [Article]. *Evergreen*, 10(3), 1642-1650. <https://doi.org/10.5109/7151712>
1474. Saraff, S., Singh, T., Kaur, H., & Biswal, R. (2022). Stigma and Health of Indian LGBT Population: A Systematic Review [Article]. *Stigma and Health*, 7(2), 178-195.
<https://doi.org/10.1037/sah0000361>
1475. Sarkar, S., & Maiti, J. (2020). Machine learning in occupational accident analysis: A review using science mapping approach with citation network analysis [Article]. *Safety Science*, 131, Article 104900. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssci.2020.104900>
1476. Sarwar, R., Urailetrprasert, N., Vannaboot, N., Yu, C., Rakthanmanon, T., Chuangsuwanich, E., & Nutanong, S. (2020). CAG : Stylometric Authorship Attribution of Multi-Author Documents Using

- a Co-Authorship Graph [Article]. *IEEE Access*, 8, 18374-18393, Article 8962080.
<https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2020.2967449>
1477. Sarwar, R., Yu, C., Nutanong, S., Uraileertprasert, N., Vannaboot, N., & Rakthanmanon, T. (2018). A scalable framework for stylometric analysis of multi-author documents. In Y. Manolopoulos, J. Li, S. Sadiq, & J. Pei (Eds.), (Vol. 10827 LNCS, pp. 813-829): Springer Verlag.
1478. Sater, Z. A., Farhat, T., Elsayed, M. N., Youssef, Y., Husain, M., Kaddoura, M., Jaber, L., Mukherji, D., & Taher, A. (2023). The state of cancer research in fragile and conflict-affected settings in the Middle East and North Africa Region: A bibliometric analysis [Article]. *Frontiers in Oncology*, 13, Article 1083836. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fonc.2023.1083836>
1479. Saura, J. R., Palacios-Marqués, D., & Ribeiro-Soriano, D. (2023). Digital marketing in SMEs via data-driven strategies: Reviewing the current state of research [Article]. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 61(3), 1278-1313. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00472778.2021.1955127>
1480. Sawka, A. M., Carty, S. E., Haugen, B. R., Hennessey, J. V., Kopp, P. A., Pearce, E. N., Sosa, J. A., Tufano, R. P., & Jonklaas, J. (2018). American thyroid association guidelines and statements: Past, present, and future [Article]. *Thyroid*, 28(6), 692-706. <https://doi.org/10.1089/thy.2018.0070>
1481. Saxena, G., Lai, K. A., & Allen, P. J. (2023). Clustering of UK universities based on the research productivity of psychology departments [Article]. *Power and Education*, 15(3), 385-393. <https://doi.org/10.1177/17577438221130983>
1482. Saygılı, M., Yıkkılmaz, D., & Tokdemir, O. B. (2022). Research review summary of the san fernando earthquake.
1483. Scarabottolo, C. C., Cyrino, E. S., Nakamura, P. M., Tebar, W. R., Canhin, D. D. S., Gobbo, L. A., & Christofaro, D. G. D. (2019). Relationship of different domains of physical activity practice with health-related quality of life among community-dwelling older people: A cross-sectional study [Article]. *BMJ Open*, 9(6), Article e027751. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2018-027751>
1484. Scarano, A., Aria, M., Mauriello, F., Riccardi, M. R., & Montella, A. (2023). Systematic literature review of 10 years of cyclist safety research [Article]. *Accident Analysis and Prevention*, 184, Article 106996. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aap.2023.106996>
1485. Schlichter, B. R., & Buchynska, T. (2021). Soft skills of delivery managers in a co-sourced software project.
1486. Schröter, I., Krüger, J., Ludwig, P., Thiel, M., Nürnberger, A., & Leich, T. (2017). Identifying innovative documents: Quo vadis?
1487. Schulze, F., & Dallasega, P. (2023). Barriers to lean implementation in engineer-to-order manufacturing with subsequent assembly on-site: state of the art and future directions [Article]. *Production Planning and Control*, 34(1), 91-115. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09537287.2021.1888159>
1488. Schulze, F., & Dallasega, P. (2023). Lean and Industry 4.0 mitigating common losses in Engineer-to-Order theory and practice: an exploratory study [Article]. *Flexible Services and Manufacturing Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10696-023-09503-z>
1489. Schulze, J., & Krumm, S. (2017). The “virtual team player”: A review and initial model of knowledge, skills, abilities, and other characteristics for virtual collaboration [Article]. *Organizational Psychology Review*, 7(1), 66-95. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2041386616675522>
1490. Scott, D. J., Broyd, T., & Ma, L. (2021). Exploratory literature review of blockchain in the construction industry [Review]. *Automation in Construction*, 132, Article 103914. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2021.103914>
1491. Scussel, F., Demo, G., de Souza Odaguiri Enes, Y., & Caneppele, N. R. (2022). Consumption experience: state of the art review and agenda proposition [Article]. *Tourism and Management Studies*, 18(2), 39-49. <https://doi.org/10.18089/tms.2022.180203>

1492. Sedhom, I., Khodeir, L. M., & Fathy, F. (2023). Investigating current practices for achieving effective participation of stakeholders in Facilities Management [Article]. *Ain Shams Engineering Journal*, 14(6), Article 102099. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asej.2022.102099>
1493. Sedighi, M. (2021). Assessing research impact based on altmetrics case study: Iranian scientific products in social sciences and computer science indexed in scopus [Review]. *Iranian Journal of Information Processing and Management*, 36(3), 679-708. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85107480352&partnerID=40&md5=7b1dcb9a1b9a6f861c41242ceb3e1d16>
1494. Sedighi, M. (2023). Altmetrics analysis of selected articles in the field of social sciences [Article]. *Global Knowledge, Memory and Communication*, 72(4-5), 452-463. <https://doi.org/10.1108/GKMC-07-2021-0124>
1495. Seitz, J., Benke, I., Heinzl, A., & Maedche, A. (2024). The Impact of Video Meeting Systems on Psychological User States: a State-of-the-Art Review [Conference Paper]. *International Journal of Human Computer Studies*, 182, Article 103178. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhcs.2023.103178>
1496. Semerjian, L., Okaiyeto, K., Ojemaye, M. O., Ekundayo, T. C., Igwaran, A., & Okoh, A. I. (2021). Global systematic mapping of road dust research from 1906 to 2020: Research gaps and future direction [Review]. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 13(20), Article 11516. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su132011516>
1497. Sendhil, R., Nyika, J., Yadav, S., Mackolil, J., Rama Prashat, G., Workie, E., Ragupathy, R., & Ramasundaram, P. (2022). Genetically modified foods: bibliometric analysis on consumer perception and preference [Review]. *GM Crops and Food*, 13(1), 65-85. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21645698.2022.2038525>
1498. Senna, P., Guimarães Marujo, L., Santos, A. C. S. G., Freitag, A. E. B., & França, S. L. B. (2023). Supply chain risk management to achieve healthcare supply chain operational excellence: a fsQCA and PLS-SEM approach [Article]. *International Journal of Lean Six Sigma*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJLSS-05-2023-0091>
1499. Senna, P., Marujo, L. G., Santos, A. C. S. G., Ferreira, A. C., & da Silva, L. A. A. (2023). E-waste supply chain risk management: a framework considering omnichannel and circular economy [Article]. *Benchmarking*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/BIJ-05-2023-0341>
1500. Senna, P., Reis, A., Dias, A., Coelho, O., Guimarães, J., & Eliana, S. (2023). Healthcare supply chain resilience framework: antecedents, mediators, consequents [Article]. *Production Planning and Control*, 34(3), 295-309. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09537287.2021.1913525>
1501. Sénquiz-Díaz, C., & Ortiz-Soto, M. (2019). A multifold perspective of knowledge sharing and virtual teams: The development of an IMOI model [Article]. *Journal of Technology Management and Innovation*, 14(2), 88-96. <https://doi.org/10.4067/s0718-27242019000200088>
1502. Sensuse, D. I., Gandhi, A., & Suchayo, Y. G. (2019). Exploring the soft system methodology in development of knowledge management conceptual model: A systematic literature review [Review]. *DESIDOC Journal of Library and Information Technology*, 39(5), 259-266. <https://doi.org/10.14429/djlit.39.5.14698>
1503. Seprum, P., & Wongwatkit, C. (2022). Trends and issues of immersive learning environments in higher education from 2001 to 2020: Perspectives on adaptive ubiquitous learning experiences [Article]. *International Journal of Mobile Learning and Organisation*, 16(1), 95-122. <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJMLO.2022.119966>
1504. Sepúlveda-Oviedo, E. H., Travé-Massuyès, L., Subias, A., Pavlov, M., & Alonso, C. (2023). Fault diagnosis of photovoltaic systems using artificial intelligence: A bibliometric approach [Article]. *Heliyon*, 9(11), Article e21491. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e21491>

1505. Sequeira, T. N., & Santos, M. S. (2018). Renewable energy and politics: A systematic review and new evidence [Article]. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 192, 553-568.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.04.190>
1506. Serenko, A. (2021). A structured literature review of scientometric research of the knowledge management discipline: a 2021 update [Article]. *Journal of Knowledge Management*, 25(8), 1889-1925. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JKM-09-2020-0730>
1507. Serpa, S., Sá, M. J., Santos, A. I., & Ferreira, C. M. (2020). Challenges for the academic editor in the scientific publication [Article]. *Academic Journal of Interdisciplinary Studies*, 9(3), 12-16.
<https://doi.org/10.36941/ajis-2020-0037>
1508. Setiawan, R., Wibisono, D., & Purwanegara, M. S. (2022). Defining Event Marketing as Engagement-Driven Marketing Communication [Article]. *Gadjah Mada International Journal of Business*, 24(2), 151-177. <https://doi.org/10.22146/gamaijb.63788>
1509. Seyman Guray, T., & Kismet, B. (2023). VR and AR in construction management research: bibliometric and descriptive analyses [Article]. *Smart and Sustainable Built Environment*, 12(3), 635-659. <https://doi.org/10.1108/SASBE-01-2022-0015>
1510. Shaffiee Haghshenas, S., Careddu, N., Jafarzadeh Ghouschi, S., Mikaeil, R., Kim, T. H., & Geem, Z. W. (2022). Quantitative and Qualitative Analysis of Harmony Search Algorithm in Geomechanics and Its Applications. In *Lecture Notes on Data Engineering and Communications Technologies* (Vol. 140, pp. 13-23): Springer Science and Business Media Deutschland GmbH.
1511. Shah, S. H. H., Noor, S., Butt, A. S., & Halepoto, H. (2021). Twitter research synthesis for health promotion: A bibliometric analysis [Article]. *Iranian Journal of Public Health*, 50(11), 2283-2291.
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85117271471&partnerID=40&md5=6fd50ffb5cdef9bf2698bdd1b1b31859>
1512. Shah, S. M., Lütjen, M., & Freitag, M. (2021). Text mining for supply chain risk management in the apparel industry [Review]. *Applied Sciences* (Switzerland), 11(5), 1-20, Article 2323.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/app11052323>
1513. Shahbazi-Moghadam, M., Salehi, H., Ale Ebrahim, N., Mohammadjafari, M., & Gholizadeh, H. (2015). Effective factors for increasing university publication and citation rate [Article]. *Asian Social Science*, 11(16), 338-348. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ass.v11n16p338>
1514. Shahidan, N. H., Latiff, A. S. A., & Wahab, S. A. (2021). Moving Towards Society 5.0: A Bibliometric and Visualization Analysis. In A. Gerber & K. Hinkelmann (Eds.), (Vol. 1477 CCIS, pp. 93-104): Springer Science and Business Media Deutschland GmbH.
1515. Shahrudin, S., & Zairul, M. (2020). BIM requirements across a construction project lifecycle: A PRISMA-compliant systematic review and meta-analysis [Article]. *International Journal of Innovation, Creativity and Change*, 12(5), 569-590.
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85084397412&partnerID=40&md5=fa3de46b8fe2eb40472ba99949db64c9>
1516. Shamsuzzoha, A., & Helo, P. (2018). Virtual supply chain for networked business: perspective of collaborative bill-of-materials, scheduling and process monitoring for developing innovative product [Article]. *International Journal of Computer Integrated Manufacturing*, 31(6), 595-610.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/0951192X.2017.1407444>
1517. Shamsuzzoha, A., Toscano, C., Carneiro, L. M., Kumar, V., & Helo, P. (2016). ICT-based solution approach for collaborative delivery of customised products [Article]. *Production Planning and Control*, 27(4), 280-298. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09537287.2015.1123322>
1518. Sharif, K. I. M., Omar, M., Noor, M. D. M., Ismail, M. A., Hassan, M. G., & Gilal, A. R. (2023). A Bibliometric Analysis of Research on Risks in the Poultry Farming Industry: Trends, Themes,

- Collaborations, and Technology Utilization [Article]. *International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications*, 14(7), 92-99. <https://doi.org/10.14569/IJACSA.2023.0140710>
1519. Sharma, A., & Kumar, P. (2023). Mapping pilgrimage tourism research through systematic literature review and bibliometric analysis. In *Prospects and Challenges of Global Pilgrimage Tourism and Hospitality* (pp. 18-32). IGI Global. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-6684-4817-5.ch002>
1520. Sharma, G., & Kulshreshtha, K. (2023). Exploring research trends of procrastination: a bibliometric analysis during 2010 to 2020 [Article]. *Benchmarking*, 30(10), 4487-4513. <https://doi.org/10.1108/BIJ-10-2021-0578>
1521. Sharma, H., Krishnakumar, B., Dickens, T. J., Yun, G. J., Kumar, A., & Rana, S. (2023). A bibliometric survey of research trends in vitrimer [Review]. *Heliyon*, 9(6), Article e17350. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e17350>
1522. Sharma, P., Gupta, V., & Sood, S. K. (2023). Post-Quantum Cryptography Research Landscape: A Scientometric Perspective [Review]. *Journal of Computer Information Systems*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08874417.2023.2260333>
1523. Sharma, R. R. K., Rahman, A., & Drave, V. (2018). Identifying factors that facilitates functioning of Virtual Teams in supply chain with differing strategy orientation.
1524. Sharma, V., Anand, S., Kumar, M., & Pattnaik, M. (2023). Bibliometric – thematic analysis and a technology-enabler-barrier-based framework for digital supply chain [Article]. *International Journal of Value Chain Management*, 14(1), 34-61. <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJVC.2023.129268>
1525. Sharma, V., & Nimawat, D. (2023). Cellular manufacturing system: a descriptive bibliometric analysis, framework, implementation steps and future research direction [Review]. *Benchmarking*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/BIJ-11-2021-0703>
1526. Sheeraz, M. I., Ungku Ahmad, U. N., Ishaq, M. I., Sarfraz, M., & Md. Nor, K. (2021). The Research on Organizational Justice in Scopus Indexed Journals: A Bibliometric Analysis of Seven Decades [Article]. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12, Article 647845. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.647845>
1527. Sheikh, A., & Richardson, J. (2023). Open access movement in the scholarly world: Pathways for libraries in developing countries [Article]. *Journal of Information Science*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/01655515231202758>
1528. Shen, C. W., & Ho, J. T. (2020). Technology-enhanced learning in higher education: A bibliometric analysis with latent semantic approach [Article]. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 104, Article 106177. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2019.106177>
1529. Shen, C. W., Nguyen, D. T., & Hsu, P. Y. (2019). Bibliometric networks and analytics on gerontology research [Article]. *Library Hi Tech*, 37(1), 88-100. <https://doi.org/10.1108/LHT-11-2017-0247>
1530. Shen, H., Xie, J., Li, J., & Cheng, Y. (2021). The correlation between scientific collaboration and citation count at the paper level: a meta-analysis [Article]. *Scientometrics*, 126(4), 3443-3470. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-021-03888-0>
1531. Sheng, S., Song, W., Lian, H., & Ning, L. (2022). Review of Urban Land Management Based on Bibliometrics [Review]. *Land*, 11(11), Article 1968. <https://doi.org/10.3390/land11111968>
1532. Shettar, I. M., & Hadagali, G. S. (2020). COLLABORATION TRENDS IN NATIONAL INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY KARNATAKA (NITK), SURATHKAL, INDIA: AN ANALYSIS BASED ON NETWORK MAPPING [Article]. *Library Philosophy and Practice*, 2020, 1-19. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85098570942&partnerID=40&md5=9c2d1fa4a2dd52a289107fd1c8f8d666>

1533. Shi, J., & Antwi-Afari, M. F. (2023). Organizational leadership and employee well-being in the construction industry: a bibliometric and scientometric review [Review]. *Journal of Engineering, Design and Technology*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JEDT-05-2023-0174>
1534. Shikoh, A. S., & Polyakov, A. (2020). A Quantitative Analysis of the Research Trends in Perovskite Solar Cells in 2009–2019 [Article]. *Physica Status Solidi (A) Applications and Materials Science*, 217(23), Article 2000441. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pssa.202000441>
1535. Shinde, S. V., Gawali, S. Z., & Thakore, D. M. (2015). MAS a scalable framework for research effort evaluation by unsupervised machine learning-Hybrid plagiarism model.
1536. Shipilova, A., & Mkrtychiev, S. (2020). Management system for publication activity of academic and teaching personnel at Russian Flagship University. In D. B. Solovev, V. V. Savaley, A. T. Bekker, V. I. Petukhov, & D. B. Solovev (Eds.), (Vol. 172, pp. 793-803): Springer.
1537. Shongwe, M. M. (2019). Knowledge management research: A South African perspective.
1538. Shonhe, L. (2020). Continuous Professional Development (CPD) of librarians: A bibliometric analysis of research productivity viewed through WoS [Article]. *Journal of Academic Librarianship*, 46(2), Article 102106. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.acalib.2019.102106>
1539. Shpak, N., Rębilas, R., Kulyniak, I., Shulyar, R., & Horbal, N. (2023). Trends in Digital Marketing Research: Bibliometric Analysis.
1540. Si, H., Shi, J. G., Tang, D., Wen, S., Miao, W., & Duan, K. (2019). Application of the theory of planned behavior in environmental science: a comprehensive bibliometric analysis [Article]. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 16(15), Article 2788. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph16152788>
1541. Siewerdt, F. L., Carvalho, R. M., & Andrade, R. M. C. (2016). Recommendations for usability testing in ubiquitous applications.
1542. Silke, A., & Schmidt-Petersen, J. (2017). The Golden Age? What the 100 Most Cited Articles in Terrorism Studies Tell Us [Article]. *Terrorism and Political Violence*, 29(4), 692-712. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09546553.2015.1064397>
1543. Silva, A., Jorge, S., & Rodrigues, L. L. (2021). Enforcement and accounting quality in the context of IFRS: is there a gap in the literature? [Review]. *International Journal of Accounting and Information Management*, 29(3), 345-367. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJAIM-08-2020-0126>
1544. Silva, L. A., Garrot, T. G., Pereira, A. M., & Correia, J. C. G. (2021). Historical perspective and bibliometric analysis of molecular modeling applied in mineral flotation systems [Review]. *Minerals Engineering*, 170, Article 107062. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mineng.2021.107062>
1545. Silva, R., Leal, C., Marques, C. S., & Ferreira, J. (2017). The strategic knowledge management, innovation and competitiveness: a bibliometric analysis.
1546. Silvestri, C., Silvestri, L., Forcina, A., Di Bona, G., & Falcone, D. (2021). Green chemistry contribution towards more equitable global sustainability and greater circular economy: A systematic literature review [Article]. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 294, Article 126137. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.126137>
1547. Silvestri, C., Silvestri, L., Piccarozzi, M., & Ruggieri, A. (2022). Toward a framework for selecting indicators of measuring sustainability and circular economy in the agri-food sector: a systematic literature review [Review]. *International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-022-02032-1>
1548. Silvestri, C., Silvestri, L., Piccarozzi, M., & Ruggieri, A. (2023). TQM and sustainability: a study of the methods and CSFs of TQM for achieving sustainability [Review]. *Total Quality Management and Business Excellence*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14783363.2023.2289938>
1549. Silvestri, L., Silvestri, C., Forcina, A., & De Luca, C. (2022). A review of energy-based indicators for assessing sustainability and circular economy in the agri-food production.

1550. Šímová, T., & Zychová, K. (2023). Who and What is Driving Remote Working Research? A Bibliometric Study [Article]. *Vision*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/09722629221139064>
1551. Simpeh, F., & Akinlolu, M. (2021). A Scientometric Review of Student Housing Research Trends.
1552. Sindhvani, R., Behl, A., Sharma, A., & Gaur, J. (2022). What makes micro, small, and medium enterprises not adopt Logistics 4.0? A systematic and structured approach using modified-total interpretive structural modelling [Article]. *International Journal of Logistics Research and Applications*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13675567.2022.2081672>
1553. Sindhvani, R., Chakraborty, S., Behl, A., & Pereira, V. (2022). Building resilience to handle disruptions in critical environmental and energy sectors: Implications for cleaner production in the oil and gas industry [Article]. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 365, Article 132692. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.132692>
1554. Sindhvani, R., Hasteeer, N., Behl, A., Chatterjee, C., & Hamzi, L. (2023). Analysis of sustainable supply chain and industry 4.0 enablers: a step towards decarbonization of supply chains [Article]. *Annals of Operations Research*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10479-023-05598-7>
1555. Singh, N. (2019). Big data technology: developments in current research and emerging landscape [Article]. *Enterprise Information Systems*, 13(6), 801-831. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17517575.2019.1612098>
1556. Singh, P., Singh, V. K., & Piryani, R. (2023). Scholarly article retrieval from Web of Science, Scopus and Dimensions: A comparative analysis of retrieval quality [Article]. *Journal of Information Science*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/01655515231191351>
1557. Singh, R., Khan, S., & Centobelli, P. (2022). Investigating the Interplay between Social Performance and Organisational Factors Supporting Circular Economy Practices [Article]. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 14(24), Article 16781. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su142416781>
1558. Singh, V. K., Singh, P., Karmakar, M., Leta, J., & Mayr, P. (2021). The journal coverage of Web of Science, Scopus and Dimensions: A comparative analysis [Article]. *Scientometrics*, 126(6), 5113-5142. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-021-03948-5>
1559. Singhania, O., Swain, S. K., & George, B. (2022). Interdependence and complementarity between rural development and rural tourism: a bibliometric analysis [Article]. *Rural Society*, 31(1), 15-32. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10371656.2022.2062198>
1560. Sivashanmugam, S., Rodriguez, S., Pour Rahimian, F., Elghaish, F., & Dawood, N. (2023). Enhancing information standards for automated construction waste quantification and classification [Review]. *Automation in Construction*, 152, Article 104898. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2023.104898>
1561. Sjøvold, E., Olsen, T. R., & Heldal, F. (2022). Use of Technology in the Study of Team-Interaction and Performance [Article]. *Small Group Research*, 53(4), 596-630. <https://doi.org/10.1177/10464964211069328>
1562. Skaar, C., Labonnote, N., & Gradeci, K. (2018). From zero emission buildings (ZEB) to Zero emission neighbourhoods (ZEN): A mapping review of algorithm-based LCA [Article]. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 10(7), Article 2405. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su10072405>
1563. Šmite, D., Kuhrmann, M., & Keil, P. (2014). Virtual teams [Guest editors' introduction] [Review]. *IEEE Software*, 31(6), 38-40, Article 6949534. <https://doi.org/10.1109/MS.2014.149>
1564. Smolina, S. G., Khafizov, D. M., & Erlikh, V. V. (2020). Bibliometric analysis of the publication activity of russian scientific institutions in sports science for 2008-2018 [Article]. *Journal of Physical Education and Sport*, 20(2), 783-790, Article 112. <https://doi.org/10.7752/jpes.2020.02112>

1565. Soares do Amaral, J. V., Montevechi, J. A. B., Miranda, R. D. C., & Junior, W. T. D. S. (2022). Metamodel-based simulation optimization: A systematic literature review [Article]. *Simulation Modelling Practice and Theory*, 114, Article 102403. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.simpat.2021.102403>
1566. Sofyantoro, F., Kusuma, H. I., Vento, S., Rademaker, M., & Frediansyah, A. (2022). Global research profile on monkeypox-related literature (1962—2022): A bibliometric analysis [Article]. *Narra J*, 2(3), Article e96. <https://doi.org/10.52225/narra.v2i3.96>
1567. Soga, L. R., Bolade-Ogunfodun, Y., Mariani, M., Nasr, R., & Laker, B. (2022). Unmasking the other face of flexible working practices: A systematic literature review [Article]. *Journal of Business Research*, 142, 648-662. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2022.01.024>
1568. Soheili, F., Khasseh, A. A., Mokhtari, H., & Sadeghi, M. (2022). Factors Affecting the Number of Citations: A Mixed Method Study [Article]. *Journal of Scientometric Research*, 11(1), 1-14. <https://doi.org/10.5530/jscires.11.1.1>
1569. Sohrabi, B., & Iraj, H. (2017). The effect of keyword repetition in abstract and keyword frequency per journal in predicting citation counts [Article]. *Scientometrics*, 110(1), 243-251. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-016-2161-5>
1570. Sohrabi, B., Vanani, I. R., Jalali, S. M. J., & Abedin, E. (2019). Evaluation of Research Trends in Knowledge Management: A Hybrid Analysis through Burst Detection and Text Clustering [Article]. *Journal of Information and Knowledge Management*, 18(4), Article 1950043. <https://doi.org/10.1142/S0219649219500436>
1571. Sohrabi, N., Alihosseini, A., Pirouzfard, V., & Pedram, M. Z. (2020). Analysis of dynamics targeting CNT-based drug delivery through lung cancer cells: Design, simulation, and computational approach [Article]. *Membranes*, 10(10), 1-16, Article 283. <https://doi.org/10.3390/membranes10100283>
1572. Solis, B. P., Argüello, J. C. C., Barba, L. G., Gurrola, M. P., Zarhri, Z., & TrejoArroyo, D. L. (2019). Bibliometric analysis of the mass transport in a gas diffusion layer in PEM fuel cells [Review]. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 11(23), Article 6682. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11236682>
1573. Soltani, M., Kythreotis, A., & Roshanpoor, A. (2023). Two decades of financial statement fraud detection literature review; combination of bibliometric analysis and topic modeling approach [Article]. *Journal of Financial Crime*, 30(5), 1367-1388. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JFC-09-2022-0227>
1574. Somlai, R. (2022). Integrating decision support tools into businesses for sustainable development: A paradoxical approach to address the food waste challenge [Article]. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 31(4), 1607-1622. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.2972>
1575. Song, S., Wu, H., Wang, F., Jiao, J., Xu, L., Wang, H., Tong, X., & Yan, H. (2022). Global research trends and hotspots on glioma stem cells [Article]. *Frontiers in Oncology*, 12, Article 926025. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fonc.2022.926025>
1576. Sönmez, Ö. F. (2020). Bibliometric analysis of educational research articles published in the field of social study education based on web of science database [Article]. *Participatory Educational Research*, 7(2), 216-229. <https://doi.org/10.17275/PER.20.30.7.2>
1577. Sonnenschein, S., Stites, M. L., Gursoy, H., & Khorsandian, J. (2023). Elementary-School Students' Use of Digital Devices at Home to Support Learning Pre- and Post-COVID-19 [Article]. *Education Sciences*, 13(2), Article 117. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci13020117>
1578. Sorooshian, S. (2023). Formulation of a Grey Sequence and an Optimization Solution to Present Multi-Layer Family Networks [Article]. *Mathematics*, 11(1), Article 144. <https://doi.org/10.3390/math11010144>
1579. Sorooshian, S., & Ebrahim, N. A. (2023). Journal editors can benefit from the archived data analysis: Two case studies. In *Handbook of Research on Driving Socioeconomic Development With Big Data* (pp. 341-349). IGI Global. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-6684-5959-1.ch016>

1580. Sorooshian, S., Jamali, S. M., & Ebrahim, N. A. (2023). Performance of the decision-making trial and evaluation laboratory [Review]. *AIMS Mathematics*, 8(3), 7490-7514. <https://doi.org/10.3934/math.2023376>
1581. Sorooshian, S., & Parsia, Y. (2018). Ahead of print: A strategy for faster communication with readers [Letter]. *European Science Editing*, 44(2), 48. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85047989785&partnerID=40&md5=8fb703ca6d31f661ca5481cc502f3d7c>
1582. Sorooshian, S., Tavana, M., & Ribeiro-Navarrete, S. (2023). From classical interpretive structural modeling to total interpretive structural modeling and beyond: A half-century of business research [Article]. *Journal of Business Research*, 157, Article 113642. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2022.113642>
1583. Soroya, S. H., Iqbal, S., Mahmood, K., Aljohani, N. R., Hassan, S. U., & Nawaz, R. (2022). Exploring the research landscape in a developing country: gauging the prospects of growth, research impact and innovation [Article]. *Transforming Government: People, Process and Policy*, 16(4), 567-581. <https://doi.org/10.1108/TG-05-2022-0071>
1584. Soto-Paz, J., Arroyo, O., Torres-Guevara, L. E., Parra-Orobio, B. A., & Casallas-Ojeda, M. (2023). The circular economy in the construction and demolition waste management: A comparative analysis in emerging and developed countries [Review]. *Journal of Building Engineering*, 78, Article 107724. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jobeb.2023.107724>
1585. Sousa, S. R. O., da Silva, W. V., Kaczam, F., Cruz, N. J. T., Veiga, C. P., & Zanini, R. R. (2022). The relationship between socioeconomic development, renewable energies and the innovative process [Review]. *International Journal of Energy Sector Management*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJESM-05-2021-0020>
1586. Souza, G. B. G., & Vianna, M. (2020). Fish-based indices for assessing ecological quality and biotic integrity in transitional waters: A systematic review [Article]. *Ecological Indicators*, 109, Article 105665. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2019.105665>
1587. Soyinka, O. A., Wadu, M. J., Lebunu Hewage, U. W. A., & Oladinrin, T. O. (2023). Scientometric review of construction demolition waste management: a global sustainability perspective [Review]. *Environment, Development and Sustainability*, 25(10), 10533-10565. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10668-022-02537-7>
1588. Spante, M., Hashemi, S. S., Lundin, M., & Algers, A. (2018). Digital competence and digital literacy in higher education research: Systematic review of concept use [Review]. *Cogent Education*, 5(1), 1-21. <https://doi.org/10.1080/2331186X.2018.1519143>
1589. Spinellis, D. (2023). Open reproducible scientometric research with Alexandria3k [Article]. *PLoS ONE*, 18(11 November), Article e0294946. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0294946>
1590. Srivastava, P., Singh, R. M., & Sonkar, S. K. (2021). Mapping of research output in the field of Big Data Analytics: Scientometrics study [Article]. *Library Philosophy and Practice*, 2021, 1-20. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85120360325&partnerID=40&md5=c9c863cf447afcb52adf931211114c84>
1591. Stanef-Puică, M. R., Badea, L., Șerban-Oprescu, G. L., Șerban-Oprescu, A. T., Frâncu, L. G., & Crețu, A. (2022). Green Jobs—A Literature Review [Review]. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(13), Article 7998. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph19137998>
1592. Steinhardt, I., Schneijderberg, C., Götze, N., Baumann, J., & Krücken, G. (2017). Mapping the quality assurance of teaching and learning in higher education: the emergence of a specialty? [Article]. *Higher Education*, 74(2), 221-237. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10734-016-0045-5>
1593. Stern, T., Wenger, J., Asada, R., Mair-Bauernfeind, C., Haas, V., Popowicz, M., Ranacher, L., Hesser, F., & Kriechbaum, M. (2021). Bioeconomy in the forest-based sector: Incremental or

- disruptive change? [Article]. *Schweizerische Zeitschrift für Forstwesen*, 172(1), 16-24.
<https://doi.org/10.3188/szf.2021.0016>
1594. Stone, D. L., Lukaszewski, K. M., Stone-Romero, E. F., & Johnson, T. L. (2013). Factors affecting the effectiveness and acceptance of electronic selection systems [Review]. *Human Resource Management Review*, 23(1), 50-70. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hrmr.2012.06.006>
1595. Storberg-Walker, J. (2015). Editor's Comment: Increasing the Impact of HRDR Through Principled Pluralism [Editorial]. *Human Resource Development Review*, 14(1), 3-7.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/1534484315572015>
1596. Stowell, F. (2021). Power in the 'Organisation': A Soft Systems Perspective [Article]. *Systemic Practice and Action Research*, 34(5), 515-535. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11213-020-09541-w>
1597. Subramaniam, R., & Nakkeeran, S. (2019). Impact of Corporate E-Learning Systems in Enhancing the Team Performance in Virtual Software Teams. In *Advances in Science, Technology and Innovation* (pp. 195-204): Springer Nature.
1598. Sullivan, B. P., Arias Nava, E., Rossi, M., & Terzi, S. (2023). A systematic literature review of changeability in engineering systems along the life cycle [Review]. *Journal of Engineering Design*, 34(12), 1046-1098. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09544828.2023.2273248>
1599. Sullivan, B. P., Rossi, M., & Terzi, S. (2018). A Review of Changeability in Complex Engineering Systems.
1600. Sultanova, G., Svyatov, S., & Ussenbayev, N. (2017). Transmitting competencies at universities: employability readiness of students [Article]. *VINE Journal of Information and Knowledge Management Systems*, 47(4), 522-537. <https://doi.org/10.1108/VJKMS-11-2016-0067>
1601. Sun, G., Li, L., & Zhang, X. (2022). A visualized and scientometric analysis of research trends of weight loss in overweight/obese children and adolescents (1958–2021) [Article]. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 10, Article 928720. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2022.928720>
1602. Sun, G., & Shen, J. (2014). Facilitating social collaboration in mobile cloud-based learning: A teamwork as a service (TaaS) approach [Article]. *IEEE Transactions on Learning Technologies*, 7(3), 207-220, Article 6860285. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TLT.2014.2340402>
1603. Sun, G., & Shen, J. (2016). Towards organizing smart collaboration and enhancing teamwork performance: a GA-supported system oriented to mobile learning through cloud-based online course [Article]. *International Journal of Machine Learning and Cybernetics*, 7(3), 391-409.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s13042-014-0269-6>
1604. Sun, Y., & Zhai, Y. (2018). Mapping the knowledge domain and the theme evolution of appropriability research between 1986 and 2016: a scientometric review [Article]. *Scientometrics*, 116(1), 203-230. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-018-2748-0>
1605. Sun, Z., Wang, Y., Zhou, H., Jiao, J., & Overstreet, R. E. (2021). Travel behaviours, user characteristics, and social-economic impacts of shared transportation: a comprehensive review [Article]. *International Journal of Logistics Research and Applications*, 24(1), 51-78.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/13675567.2019.1663162>
1606. Suprpto, N., & Hidayatullaah, H. N. (2023). University Students' Perspectives on Physics Education in Sustainable Development Goals.
1607. Susanin, A., Boyar, A., Costello, K., Fraiman, A., Misrok, A., Sears, M., & Hildebrandt, T. (2022). Rigor and reproducibility for data analysis and design in the study of eating disorders [Review]. *International Journal of Eating Disorders*, 55(10), 1267-1278.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/eat.23774>
1608. Susskind, A. M., & Odom-Reed, P. R. (2019). Team Member's Centrality, Cohesion, Conflict, and Performance in Multi-University Geographically Distributed Project Teams [Article]. *Communication Research*, 46(2), 151-178. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0093650215626972>

1609. Susur, E., Hidalgo, A., & Chiaroni, D. (2019). A strategic niche management perspective on transitions to eco-industrial park development: A systematic review of case studies [Article]. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 140, 338-359. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2018.06.002>
1610. Svejvig, P., & Commisso, T. H. (2012). Virtual projects: Building the bridge between best practices and practiced practices.
1611. Swarna Swetha, K., & Tezeswi, T. P. (2023). Emerging Research Topics and Major Waste-Generating Materials in Construction and Demolition Waste Management: A Scientometric and Beneficial Index Analysis. In *Lecture Notes in Civil Engineering* (Vol. 360, pp. 45-62): Springer Science and Business Media Deutschland GmbH.
1612. Sweileh, W. M. (2017). Bibliometric analysis of literature on toxic epidermal necrolysis and Stevens-Johnson syndrome: 1940 - 2015 [Article]. *Orphanet Journal of Rare Diseases*, 12(1), 1-15. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13023-017-0566-8>
1613. Sweileh, W. M. (2023). Visualized Analysis of Research Publications on Physical Activity among Higher Education Students [Article]. *American Journal of Health Education*, 54(5), 364-375. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19325037.2023.2232427>
1614. Sweileh, W. M., Al-Jabi, S. W., Zyoud, S. H., Sawalha, A. F., & Abu-Taha, A. S. (2018). Global research output in antimicrobial resistance among uropathogens: A bibliometric analysis (2002–2016) [Article]. *Journal of Global Antimicrobial Resistance*, 13, 104-114. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jgar.2017.11.017>
1615. Sweileh, W. M., Al-Jabi, S. W., Zyoud, S. H., Shraim, N. Y., Anayah, F. M. A., Sawalha, A. F., & AbuTaha, A. S. (2019). Bibliometric analysis of global publications in medication adherence (1900–2017) [Article]. *International Journal of Pharmacy Practice*, 27(2), 112-120. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ijpp.12471>
1616. Syawaludin, A., Prasetyo, Z. K., Jabar, C. S. A., & Retnawati, H. (2022). The Effect of Project-based Learning Model and Online Learning Settings on Analytical Skills of Discovery Learning, Interactive Demonstrations, and Inquiry Lessons [Article]. *Journal of Turkish Science Education*, 19(2), 608-621. <https://doi.org/10.36681/tused.2022.140>
1617. Sýkora, T., Stárková, T., & Brom, C. (2021). Can narrative cutscenes improve home learning from a math game? An experimental study with children [Article]. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 52(1), 42-56. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bjet.12939>
1618. Szomszor, M., & Adie, E. (2022). Overton: A bibliometric database of policy document citations [Article]. *Quantitative Science Studies*, 3(3), 624-650. https://doi.org/10.1162/qss_a_00204
1619. Tabatabaei-Malazy, O., Ramezani, A., Atlasi, R., Larijani, B., & Abdollahi, M. (2016). Scientometric study of academic publications on antioxidative herbal medicines in type 2 diabetes mellitus [Article]. *Journal of Diabetes and Metabolic Disorders*, 15(1), Article 48. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40200-016-0273-3>
1620. Tablatin, C. L. S., Casano, J. D. L., & Rodrigo, M. M. T. (2023). Using Minecraft to cultivate student interest in STEM [Article]. *Frontiers in Education*, 8, Article 1127984. <https://doi.org/10.3389/educ.2023.1127984>
1621. Tahamtan, I., Safipour Afshar, A., & Ahamdzadeh, K. (2016). Factors affecting number of citations: a comprehensive review of the literature [Article]. *Scientometrics*, 107(3), 1195-1225. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-016-1889-2>
1622. Taj, F., Klein, M. C. A., & Van Halteren, A. (2019). Digital health behavior change technology: Bibliometric and scoping review of two decades of research [Review]. *JMIR mHealth and uHealth*, 7(12), Article e13311. <https://doi.org/10.2196/13311>

1623. Takano, Y., & Kajikawa, Y. (2019). Extracting commercialization opportunities of the Internet of Things: Measuring text similarity between papers and patents [Article]. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 138, 45-68. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2018.08.008>
1624. Tan, C. K., Ramayah, T., Teoh, A. P., & Cheah, J. H. (2019). Factors influencing virtual team performance in Malaysia [Article]. *Kybernetes*, 48(9), 2065-2092. <https://doi.org/10.1108/K-01-2018-0031>
1625. Tang, R., Moon, J., Heo, G. R., & Lee, W. S. (2023). Exploring the knowledge structure and potential research areas of sustainable tourism in sustainable development: Based on text mining and semantic network analysis [Review]. *Sustainable Development*. <https://doi.org/10.1002/sd.2823>
1626. Tanko, B. L., Zakka, W. P., & Heng, W. N. (2022). BIM in the Malaysian construction industry: a scientometric review and case study [Article]. *Engineering, Construction and Architectural Management*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ECAM-04-2021-0324>
1627. Tao, X., Hanif, H., Ahmed, H. H., & Ebrahim, N. A. (2021). Bibliometric Analysis and Visualization of Academic Procrastination [Review]. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12, Article 722332. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.722332>
1628. Tao, X., Hanif, H., & Ebrahim, N. A. (2023). Emerging Trends of Self-regulated Learning: A Comprehensive Bibliometric Analysis [Article]. *World Journal of English Language*, 13(6), 252-269. <https://doi.org/10.5430/WJEL.V13N6P252>
1629. Tao, Y., Wang, X., Xu, X., & Chen, Y. (2017). Dynamic Resource Allocation Algorithm for Container-Based Service Computing.
1630. Tariq, S., Hussein, M., Wang, R. D., & Zayed, T. (2022). Trends and developments of on-site crane layout planning 1983–2020: bibliometric, scientometric and qualitative analyses [Review]. *Construction Innovation*, 22(4), 1011-1035. <https://doi.org/10.1108/CI-02-2021-0015>
1631. Tassinari, G., Drabik, D., Boccaletti, S., & Soregaroli, C. (2021). Case studies research in the bioeconomy: A systematic literature review [Review]. *Agricultural Economics (Czech Republic)*, 67(7), 286-303. <https://doi.org/10.17221/21/2021-AGRICECON>
1632. Tausch, A. (2023). *Bibliometry from a global perspective: Library and classroom outreach and the future ranking of political scientists and publishers* [Book]. Nova Science Publishers, Inc. <https://doi.org/10.52305/XICA3755>
1633. Tavana, M., & Sorooshian, S. (2024). A systematic review of the soft computing methods shaping the future of the metaverse [Article]. *Applied Soft Computing*, 150, Article 111098. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asoc.2023.111098>
1634. Tavares, M. C., Azevedo, G., Marques, R. P., & Bastos, M. A. (2023). Challenges of education in the accounting profession in the Era 5.0: A systematic review [Review]. *Cogent Business and Management*, 10(2), Article 2220198. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311975.2023.2220198>
1635. Tavares, M. C., Azevedo, G., Vale, J., & Bandeira, A. M. (2023). The Accountant in the New Era : Renewing the profession for Society 5.0.
1636. Tavares, T. M., Ganga, G. M. D., Godinho Filho, M., & Rodrigues, V. P. (2023). The benefits and barriers of additive manufacturing for circular economy: A framework proposal [Review]. *Sustainable Production and Consumption*, 37, 369-388. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spc.2023.03.006>
1637. Tavassoli, A., Soltani, S., Jamali, S. M., & Ebrahim, N. A. (2022). A Research on Violence Against Women: Are the Trends Growing? [Article]. *Iranian Rehabilitation Journal*, 20(3), 425-440. <https://doi.org/10.32598/irj.20.3.1664.1>
1638. Tay, J., Goh, Y. M., Safiena, S., & Bound, H. (2022). Designing digital game-based learning for professional upskilling: A systematic literature review [Article]. *Computers and Education*, 184, Article 104518. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2022.104518>

1639. Teixeira, A. A., Moraes, T. E. D. C., Stefanelli, N. O., de Oliveira, J. H. C., Teixeira, T. B., & de Souza Freitas, W. R. (2020). Green supply chain management in Latin America: Systematic literature review and future directions [Article]. *Environmental Quality Management*, 30(2), 47-73. <https://doi.org/10.1002/tqem.21712>
1640. Tennant, J. P., Crane, H., Crick, T., Davila, J., Enkhbayar, A., Havemann, J., Kramer, B., Martin, R., Masuzzo, P., Nobes, A., Rice, C., Rivera-López, B., Ross-Hellauer, T., Sattler, S., Thacker, P. D., & Vanholsbeeck, M. (2019). Ten hot topics around scholarly publishing [Review]. *Publications*, 7(2), Article 34. <https://doi.org/10.3390/publications7020034>
1641. Ter Haar, B., Kruger, J., & van Zijl, G. (2023). Off-site construction with 3D concrete printing [Review]. *Automation in Construction*, 152, Article 104906. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2023.104906>
1642. Tetourová, T., Hannemann, T., Javora, O., Volná, K., Šisler, V., & Brom, C. (2020). To solve or to observe? The case of problem-solving interactivity within child learning games [Article]. *Journal of Computer Assisted Learning*, 36(6), 981-996. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jcal.12454>
1643. Thavorn, J., Gowanit, C., Muangsin, V., & Muangsin, N. (2021). Collaboration Network and Trends of Global Coronavirus Disease Research: A Scientometric Analysis [Article]. *IEEE Access*, 9, 45001-45016, Article 9380131. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3066450>
1644. Thomas, B., Joseph, J., & Jose, J. (2023). Explorative Bibliometric Study of Medical Image Analysis: Unveiling Trends and Advancements [Article]. *Scientific Visualization*, 15(5), 35-49. <https://doi.org/10.26583/sv.15.5.04>
1645. Thomoglou, A. K., Jagadesh, P., & Voutetaki, M. E. (2023). Review of Out-of-Plane Strengthening Techniques of Unreinforced Masonry Walls [Review]. *Fibers*, 11(9), Article 78. <https://doi.org/10.3390/fib11090078>
1646. Ting, S. K., Lai, T. W., & Dollery, B. (2022). Empirical evidence on intellectual property copyright: student perspectives on learning outcomes and challenges [Article]. *International Journal of Education Economics and Development*, 13(3), 260-277. <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJEED.2022.123797>
1647. Ting, Y. S., & Yeh, Y. C. (2023). Growth-mindset intervention effects and the relationship of mindset, hope belief, and self-efficacy during creativity game-based learning [Article]. *Interactive Learning Environments*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10494820.2023.2170418>
1648. Tinga, A. M., de Back, T. T., & Louwerse, M. M. (2019). Non-invasive neurophysiological measures of learning: A meta-analysis [Review]. *Neuroscience and Biobehavioral Reviews*, 99, 59-89. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neubiorev.2019.02.001>
1649. Tisza, G., Zhu, S., & Markopoulos, P. (2021). Fun to Enhance Learning, Motivation, Self-efficacy, and Intention to Play in DGBL. In J. Baalsrud Hauge, J. Baalsrud Hauge, C. S. C. J, L. Roque, & P. A. Gonzalez-Calero (Eds.), (Vol. 13056 LNCS, pp. 28-45): Springer Science and Business Media Deutschland GmbH.
1650. Tjebane, M. M., Musonda, I., Okoro, C., & Onososen, A. (2023). Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Sustainable Construction Management: A Scientometric Review. In T. C. Haupt, M. Akinlolu, F. Simpeh, C. Amoah, & Z. Armoed (Eds.), (Vol. 245, pp. 137-150): Springer Science and Business Media Deutschland GmbH.
1651. Tokarz, B., Kohlbeck, E., Beuren, F. H., Fagundes, A. B., & Pereira, D. (2021). Systematic literature review: Opportunities and trends to the post-outbreak period of COVID-19 [Review]. *Brazilian Journal of Operations and Production Management*, 18(2), Article e20211146. <https://doi.org/10.14488/BJOPM.2021.030>
1652. Tokarz, B., Kohlbeck, E., Beuren, F. H., Fagundes, A. B., & Pereira, D. (2022). Methods and tools for the development of a Product-Service System: A holistic perspective [Article]. *Brazilian*

Journal of Operations and Production Management, 19(3), Article e20221227.
<https://doi.org/10.14488/BJOPM.2021.046>

1653. Tomar, R., Kundra, P., Sharma, J., Mohajer, F., Ziarani, G. M., & Yadav, S. (2024). An Overview: Synthesis of Menthol using Heterogeneous Catalysis [Short Survey]. *Letters in Organic Chemistry*, 21(1), 16-28. <https://doi.org/10.2174/157017862066230623114308>
1654. Tomas, V., Finlay, B., Gentles, S. J., Campbell, M., Gill-Badesha, D., Abel, C., Zwicker, J. D., & Lai, J. (2023). Development of Policy Recommendations to Support a National Autism Strategy: Case of a Virtual and Inclusive Stakeholder Engagement Process [Article]. *International Journal of Health Policy and Management*, 12(1), Article 7182. <https://doi.org/10.34172/ijhpm.2022.7182>
1655. Tomasiak, M. A., & Chamakiotis, P. (2017). Understanding diversity in virtual work environments: A comparative case study. In *Handbook of Research on Human Factors in Contemporary Workforce Development* (pp. 283-307). IGI Global. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-5225-2568-4.ch0013>
1656. Tonbuloglu, B., & Akbel, B. A. (2023). Research Trends in the Field of Emergency Remote Teaching: A Bibliometric Analysis of Open Access Literature [Article]. *Online Learning Journal*, 27(1), 485-517. <https://doi.org/10.24059/olj.v27i1.3241>
1657. Torqu, A., Chan, A. P. C., & Yung, E. H. K. (2020). Implementation of age-friendly initiatives in smart cities: probing the barriers through a systematic review [Article]. *Built Environment Project and Asset Management*, 11(3), 412-426. <https://doi.org/10.1108/BEPAM-01-2020-0008>
1658. Torqu, A., Chan, A. P. C., & Yung, E. H. K. (2021). Age-friendly cities and communities: A review and future directions [Review]. *Ageing and Society*, 41(10), 2242-2279. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0144686X20000239>
1659. Torres, R. T., Carvalho, J., Cunha, M. V., Serrano, E., Palmeira, J. D., & Fonseca, C. (2021). Temporal and geographical research trends of antimicrobial resistance in wildlife – A bibliometric analysis [Review]. *One Health*, 11, Article 100198. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.onehlt.2020.100198>
1660. Toyokawa, Y., Chen, M. R. A., Majumdar, R., Hwang, G. J., & Ogata, H. (2020). Trends of E-Book-based English language learning: A review of journal publications from 2010 to 2019.
1661. Tran, B. X., Dang, K. A., Le, H. T., Ha, G. H., Nguyen, L. H., Nguyen, T. H., Tran, T. H., Latkin, C. A., Ho, C. S. H., & Ho, R. C. M. (2019). Global evolution of obesity research in children and youths: Setting priorities for interventions and policies [Review]. *Obesity Facts*, 12(2), 137-149. <https://doi.org/10.1159/000497121>
1662. Tran, B. X., Nghiem, S., Afoakwah, C., Latkin, C. A., Ha, G. H., Nguyen, T. P., Doan, L. P., Pham, H. Q., Ho, C. S. H., & Ho, R. C. M. (2019). Characterizing obesity interventions and treatment for children and youths during 1991–2018 [Article]. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 16(21), Article 4227. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph16214227>
1663. Tran, B. X., Nghiem, S., Sahin, O., Vu, T. M., Ha, G. H., Vu, G. T., Pham, H. Q., Do, H. T., Latkin, C. A., Tam, W., Ho, C. S. H., & Ho, R. C. M. (2019). Modeling research topics for artificial intelligence applications in medicine: Latent dirichlet allocation application study [Article]. *Journal of Medical Internet Research*, 21(11), Article e15511. <https://doi.org/10.2196/15511>
1664. Tran, B. X., Wong, F. Y., Huy-Pham, K. T., Latkin, C. A., Hai-Ha, G., Thu-Vu, G., Ho, C. S. H., & Ho, R. C. M. (2019). Evolution of interdisciplinary landscapes of HIV/AIDS studies from 1983 to 2017: Results from the global analysis for policy in research (GAPresearch) [Article]. *AIDS Reviews*, 21(4), 184-194. <https://doi.org/10.24875/AIDSRev.19000083>
1665. Tran, T. B. H., Oh, C. H., & Choi, S. B. (2016). Effects of learning orientation and global mindset on virtual team members' willingness to cooperate in: The mediating role of self-efficacy [Review]. *Journal of Management and Organization*, 22(3), 311-327. <https://doi.org/10.1017/jmo.2015.37>

1666. Tran Thi Minh, T., & Duong Hong, N. (2022). The Role of Games in Online Courses at Vietnamese Public Universities.
1667. Traverso, J. V., Ortiz-Jaureguizar, E., Miguel, S., & Posadas, P. (2020). Similarity relationships and discriminatory value of the bibliometric indicators of the Scimago Journal and Country Rank. An analysis based on the generalist anthropology journals (2008-2017) [Article]. *Revista General de Informacion y Documentacion*, 30(1), 261-296. <https://doi.org/10.5209/RGID.70070>
1668. Traxler, J. (2021). A critical review of mobile learning: Phoenix, fossil, zombie or? [Article]. *Education Sciences*, 11(9), Article 525. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci11090525>
1669. Trisha, S., Vishnu Priya, V., & Gayathri, R. (2020). Awareness of cancer vaccines among college students – A survey [Review]. *Drug Invention Today*, 14(3), 345-347. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85095432721&partnerID=40&md5=4c0e4dd6eee4465385d4b427c1307878>
1670. Tsai, P. H., Berleant, D., Segall, R. S., Aboudja, H., Batthula, V. J. R., Duggirala, S., & Howell, M. (2023). Quantitative Technology Forecasting: A Review of Trend Extrapolation Methods [Review]. *International Journal of Innovation and Technology Management*, 20(4), Article 2330002. <https://doi.org/10.1142/S0219877023300021>
1671. Tsai, Y. L., & Tsai, C. C. (2020). A meta-analysis of research on digital game-based science learning [Review]. *Journal of Computer Assisted Learning*, 36(3), 280-294. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jcal.12430>
1672. Tsvetkova, M., Kukunin, S., Pitukhin, E., & Buymov, A. (2020). Identifying trends in artificial intelligence publications and their influence on the publication behavior of the scientific community members [Article]. *Journal of Advanced Research in Dynamical and Control Systems*, 12(2 Special Issue), 402-411. <https://doi.org/10.5373/JARDCS/V12SP2/SP20201087>
1673. Turalde, C. W. R., Espiritu, A. I., & Jamora, R. D. G. (2021). Associations of motor neuron disease research productivity and socioeconomic factors in Southeast Asia: A bibliometric analysis [Article]. *Arquivos de Neuro-Psiquiatria*, 79(11), 1002-1011. <https://doi.org/10.1590/0004-282X-ANP-2019-0464>
1674. Turbanti, S. (2014). Navigare nel mare di Scopus, Web of science e Google Scholar: L'avvio di una ricerca sulla vitalità delle discipline archivistiche e biblioteconomiche Italiane [Article]. *AIB Studi*, 54(2-3), 213-225. <https://doi.org/10.2426/aibstudi-10266>
1675. Turmuzi, M., Suharta, I. G. P., Astawa, I. W. P., & Suparta, I. N. (2023). Mapping of Mobile Learning Research Directions and Trends in Scopus-Indexed Journals: A Bibliometric Analysis [Article]. *International Journal of Interactive Mobile Technologies*, 17(3), 39-69. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijim.v17i03.36461>
1676. Turner, J. R. (2013). Multiagent systems as a team member [Article]. *International Journal of Technology, Knowledge and Society*, 9(1), 73-90. <https://doi.org/10.18848/1832-3669/CGP/v09i01/56355>
1677. Turner, J. R. (2016). Team Cognition Conflict: A Conceptual Review Identifying Cognition Conflict as a New Team Conflict Construct [Article]. *Performance Improvement Quarterly*, 29(2), 145-167. <https://doi.org/10.1002/piq.21219>
1678. Turner, J. R., Zimmerman, T., & Allen, J. M. (2012). Teams as a sub-process for knowledge management [Review]. *Journal of Knowledge Management*, 16(6), 963-977. <https://doi.org/10.1108/13673271211276227>
1679. Turner, M., & Hodis, F. A. (2023). A Systematic Review of Interventions to Reduce Academic Procrastination and Implications for Instructor-based Classroom Interventions [Review]. *Educational Psychology Review*, 35(4), Article 118. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10648-023-09838-x>

1680. Twetwa-Dube, S., & Oki, O. A. (2023). Technology Adoption for Precision Agriculture in Africa: a bibliometric analysis.
1681. Tyurin, A., & Shamshurin, V. (2023). Computerized evaluation of publication effectiveness using application programming interfaces of citation databases.
1682. Uc-Castillo, J. L., Marín-Celestino, A. E., Martínez-Cruz, D. A., Tuxpan-Vargas, J., & Ramos-Leal, J. A. (2023). A systematic review and meta-analysis of groundwater level forecasting with machine learning techniques: Current status and future directions [Review]. *Environmental Modelling and Software*, 168, Article 105788. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsoft.2023.105788>
1683. Ukwoma, S. C., & Dike, V. W. (2017). Academics' attitudes toward the utilization of institutional repositories in Nigerian universities [Article]. *Portal*, 17(1), 17-32. <https://doi.org/10.1353/pla.2017.0002>
1684. Ukwoma, S. C., & Mole, A. J. C. (2017). Utilisation of institutional repositories for searching information sources, self-archiving and preservation of research publications in selected nigerian universities [Article]. *African Journal of Library Archives and Information Science*, 27(2), 117-130. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85039041605&partnerID=40&md5=d69fea8d110cc1923c15619400ecea6e>
1685. Uleanya, C. (2023). Persistent African School Leadership Problems: A Scoping Review for Sustainability [Article]. *International Journal of Educational Organization and Leadership*, 30(2), 87-102. <https://doi.org/10.18848/2329-1656/CGP/v30i02/87-102>
1686. Uleanya, C. (2023). Postdigital leadership in education: scoping review of the case of Africa [Article]. *International Journal of Leadership in Education*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13603124.2023.2272141>
1687. Ülker, P., Ülker, M., & Karamustafa, K. (2023). Bibliometric analysis of bibliometric studies in the field of tourism and hospitality [Article]. *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Insights*, 6(2), 797-818. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JHTI-10-2021-0291>
1688. Ullah, F., & Al-Turjman, F. (2023). A conceptual framework for blockchain smart contract adoption to manage real estate deals in smart cities [Article]. *Neural Computing and Applications*, 35(7), 5033-5054. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00521-021-05800-6>
1689. Umejiaku, A., & Dang, T. (2021). Visualising Developing Nations Health Records: Opportunities, Challenges and Research Agenda.
1690. Umeokafor, N., Umar, T., & Evangelinos, K. (2022). Bibliometric and scientometric analysis-based review of construction safety and health research in developing countries from 1990 to 2021 [Article]. *Safety Science*, 156, Article 105897. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssci.2022.105897>
1691. Ungureanu, E. L., Mocanu, A. L., Stroe, C. A., Duță, D. E., & Mustățea, G. (2023). Assessing Health Risks Associated with Heavy Metals in Food: A Bibliometric Analysis [Review]. *Foods*, 12(21), Article 3974. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods12213974>
1692. Ur Rehman, M. A., Chaabane, A., & Khan, S. A. (2021). REVIEW OF CONSTRUCTION SUPPLY CHAIN OPTIMIZATION PAPERS FOR PERFORMANCE IMPROVEMENT.
1693. Urain, I., Eguren, J. A., & Justel, D. (2022). Development and validation of a tool for the integration of the circular economy in industrial companies: Case study of 30 companies [Article]. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 370, Article 133318. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.133318>
1694. Urbano-Mairena, J., Castillo-Paredes, A., Muñoz-Bermejo, L., Denche-Zamorano, Á., Rojo-Ramos, J., Pastor-Cisneros, R., & Mendoza-Muñoz, M. (2023). A Bibliometric Analysis of Physical Literacy Studies in Relation to Health of Children and Adolescents [Article]. *Children*, 10(4), Article 660. <https://doi.org/10.3390/children10040660>

1695. Urs, S. R., & Minhaj, M. (2023). Evolution of data science and its education in iSchools: An impressionistic study using curriculum analysis [Article]. *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, 74(6), 606-622. <https://doi.org/10.1002/asi.24649>
1696. Usman, G. B. T., Ali, M. N., & Ahmad, M. Z. (2023). Effectiveness of STEM problem-based learning on the achievement of biology among secondary school students in Nigeria [Article]. *Journal of Turkish Science Education*, 20(3), 453-467. <https://doi.org/10.36681/tused.2023.026>
1697. Utama, W. P., Chan, A., Zahoor, H., & Gao, R. (2016). Review of research trend in international construction projects: A bibliometric analysis [Review]. *Construction Economics and Building*, 16(2), 71-82. <https://doi.org/10.5130/AJCEB.v16i2.4866>
1698. Utama, W. P., Chan, A. P. C., Gao, R., & Zahoor, H. (2018). Making international expansion decision for construction enterprises with multiple criteria: a literature review approach [Review]. *International Journal of Construction Management*, 18(3), 221-231. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15623599.2017.1315527>
1699. Uzunboylyu, H., & Altay, O. (2021). State of affairs in multicultural education research: a content analysis [Article]. *Compare*, 51(2), 278-297. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03057925.2019.1622408>
1700. Uzunboylyu, H., & Özmen, S. (2021). Research orientations related to guidance and counselling programmes: A content analysis study [Article]. *Anales de Psicologia*, 37(1), 88-100. <https://doi.org/10.6018/analesps.422381>
1701. Vaicondam, Y., Sikandar, H., Irum, S., Khan, N., & Qureshi, M. I. (2022). Research Landscape of Digital Learning Over the Past 20 Years: A Bibliometric and Visualisation Analysis [Article]. *International journal of online and biomedical engineering*, 18(8), 4-22. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijoe.v18i08.31963>
1702. Valderrama-Zurián, J. C., Aguilar-Moya, R., Melero-Fuentes, D., & Aleixandre-Benavent, R. (2015). A systematic analysis of duplicate records in Scopus [Article]. *Journal of Informetrics*, 9(3), 570-576. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joi.2015.05.002>
1703. Valencia-Arias, A., Bermeo-Giraldo, M. C., Gallegos, A., Palacios-Moya, L., & Molina, S. G. (2023). Research trends in health information management [Review]. *Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmacognosy Research*, 11(3), 473-488. https://doi.org/10.56499/jppres22.1497_11.3.473
1704. Valencia-Galeano, Y. S., & Serrano-Sánchez, J. L. (2020). Learning a second language supported by digital technologies: A systematic review [Review]. *Education in the Knowledge Society*, 21. <https://doi.org/10.14201/eks.18734>
1705. Valente, A., Holanda, M., Mariano, A. M., Furuta, R., & Da Silva, D. (2022). Analysis of Academic Databases for Literature Review in the Computer Science Education Field.
1706. Valjak, F., & Lindwall, A. (2021). Review of design heuristics and design principles in design for additive manufacturing.
1707. Vallejos-Romero, A., Cordoves-Sánchez, M., Cisternas, C., Sáez-Ardura, F., Rodríguez, I., Aledo, A., Boso, Á., Prades, J., & Álvarez, B. (2023). Green Hydrogen and Social Sciences: Issues, Problems, and Future Challenges [Review]. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 15(1), Article 303. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15010303>
1708. Van Der Merwe, M. D., Grobbelaar, S. S., Schutte, C. S. L., & Von Leipzig, K. H. (2018). Toward an Enterprise Growth Framework for Entering the Base of the Pyramid Market: A Systematic Review [Article]. *International Journal of Innovation and Technology Management*, 15(4), Article 1850035. <https://doi.org/10.1142/S0219877018500359>
1709. Van Der Pol, C. B., McInnes, M. D. F., Petrcich, W., Tunis, A. S., & Hanna, R. (2015). Is quality and completeness of reporting of systematic reviews and meta-analyses published in high impact radiology journals associated with citation rates? [Article]. *PLoS ONE*, 10(3), Article e0119892. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0119892>

1710. van Deursen, A. J. A. M., & Mossberger, K. (2018). Any Thing for Anyone? A New Digital Divide in Internet-of-Things Skills [Article]. *Policy and Internet*, 10(2), 122-140. <https://doi.org/10.1002/poi3.171>
1711. van Deursen, A. J. A. M., van der Zeeuw, A., de Boer, P., Jansen, G., & van Rompay, T. (2021). Digital inequalities in the Internet of Things: differences in attitudes, material access, skills, and usage [Article]. *Information Communication and Society*, 24(2), 258-276. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1369118X.2019.1646777>
1712. van Geenhuizen, M., & Nijkamp, P. (2012). Knowledge virtualization and local connectedness among young globalized high-tech companies [Article]. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 79(7), 1179-1191. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2012.01.010>
1713. Van Waveren, C., Oerlemans, L., & Pretorius, T. (2017). Refining the classification of knowledge transfer mechanisms for project-to-project knowledge sharing [Article]. *South African Journal of Economic and Management Sciences*, 20(1), Article a1642. <https://doi.org/10.4102/sajems.v20i1.1642>
1714. Varela-Losada, M., Pérez-Rodríguez, U., Lorenzo-Rial, M. A., & Vega-Marcote, P. (2022). In Search of Transformative Learning for Sustainable Development: Bibliometric Analysis of Recent Scientific Production [Article]. *Frontiers in Education*, 7, Article 786560. <https://doi.org/10.3389/educ.2022.786560>
1715. Väyrynen, K., & Aalto, J. (2013). The organization's role in global virtual team leaders' possibilities to successfully lead the team across its lifecycle.
1716. Vázquez, M. Y. G., Sexto, C. F., Rocha, Á., & Aguilera, A. (2016). Mobile Phones and Psychosocial Therapies with Vulnerable People: a First State of the Art [Article]. *Journal of Medical Systems*, 40(6), Article 157. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10916-016-0500-y>
1717. Vázquez-Cano, E., Belando Montoro, M. R., & Bernal Bravo, C. (2017). Bibliometric and impact study of *Revista Complutense de Educación* (2005-2015) [Article]. *Revista Complutense de Educacion*, 28(4), 1227-1250. <https://doi.org/10.5209/RCED.51672>
1718. Vega-Muñoz, A., González-Gómez-del-miño, P., & Espinosa-Cristia, J. F. (2021). Recognizing new trends in brain drain studies in the framework of global sustainability [Article]. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 13(6), Article 3195. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13063195>
1719. Vega-Muñoz, A., Salazar-Sepúlveda, G., & Contreras-Barraza, N. (2021). Identifying the blue economy global epistemic community [Article]. *Water (Switzerland)*, 13(22), Article 3234. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w13223234>
1720. Vega-Muñoz, A., Salazar-Sepúlveda, G., Contreras-Barraza, N., & Araya-Silva, L. (2021). Port governance and cruise tourism [Article]. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 13(9), Article 4877. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13094877>
1721. Vega-Muñoz, A., Salazar-Sepúlveda, G., Espinosa-Cristia, J. F., & Sanhueza-Vergara, J. (2021). How to measure environmental performance in ports [Review]. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 13(7), Article 4035. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13074035>
1722. Velastegui-Montoya, A., Montalván-Burbano, N., Carrión-Mero, P., Rivera-Torres, H., Sadeck, L., & Adami, M. (2023). Google Earth Engine: A Global Analysis and Future Trends [Review]. *Remote Sensing*, 15(14), Article 3675. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs15143675>
1723. Verma, S., Yadav, S. K., & Raj, R. (2023). Trends in the Evaluation of Masstige Marketing: A Bibliometric Analysis Using R [Review]. *Vision*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/09722629231172046>
1724. Vetter, M. A., & McDowell, Z. J. (2023). A spectrum of surveillance: Charting functions of epistemic inequality across EdTech platforms in the post-COVID-19 era [Article]. *Journal of University Teaching and Learning Practice*, 20(2), Article 2. <https://doi.org/10.53761/1.20.02.02>

1725. Vial, N. A., Fraiz-Brea, J. A., Cardoso, L. A., & Pereira, A. M. (2020). Scopus analysis of the academic research performed by public Universities in Galicia and North of Portugal [Article]. *Information Resources Management Journal*, 33(1), 16-38. <https://doi.org/10.4018/IRMJ.2020010102>
1726. Vial-Gallardo, M., Acevedo-Duque, Á., Gomes, T., & Daza, D. A. (2022). From academic communication to political discourse around COVID-19, in political science [Article]. *Revista de Ciencias Sociales*, 28(ESPECIAL 5), 313-330. <https://doi.org/10.31876/rcs.v28i.38166>
1727. Videnovik, M., Madevska Bogdanova, A., & Trajkovik, V. (2024). Game-based learning approach in computer science in primary education: A systematic review [Review]. *Entertainment Computing*, 48, Article 100616. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.entcom.2023.100616>
1728. Viegas, C., Agapito, D., & Pinto, P. (2023). Sensory marketing: The purpose of sensory stimuli in consumer behaviour in the context of the retail environment. In *Measuring Consumer Behavior in Hospitality for Enhanced Decision Making* (pp. 161-189). IGI Global. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-6684-6607-0.ch008>
1729. Vieira, J., Martins, J. P., de Almeida, N. M., Patrício, H., & Morgado, J. G. (2022). Towards Resilient and Sustainable Rail and Road Networks: A Systematic Literature Review on Digital Twins [Review]. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 14(12), Article 7060. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14127060>
1730. Vigneshkumar, C., & Salve, U. R. (2020). A scientometric analysis and review of fall from height research in construction [Article]. *Construction Economics and Building*, 20(1), 17-35. <https://doi.org/10.5130/AJCEB.v20i1.6802>
1731. Vijayalekshmi, S., Twetwa-Dube, S., Vinoth-Kumar, D., & Gumbo, S. (2023). The Role of Higher Education Institutions in Enabling the Fourth Industrial Revolution: A Bibliometric Analysis.
1732. Vijayasarithi, A., Ding, J., Duszak, R., Jr., & Khosa, F. (2021). Business and publication models of radiology journals [Article]. *Clinical Imaging*, 76, 222-227. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clinimag.2021.04.005>
1733. Vila-López, N., Kuster-Boluda, I., Mora-Pérez, E., & Pascual-Riquelme, I. (2023). A bibliometric analysis of virtual influencers in the Web of Science [Article]. *Journal of Marketing Analytics*. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41270-023-00262-2>
1734. Vílchez-Román, C., Vara-Horna, A., & Vargas-Bianchi, L. (2023). Bringing managers closer to papers: Measuring the relevance of business and management research [Article]. *Journal of Education for Business*, 98(1), 17-24. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08832323.2021.2017251>
1735. Vitta, J. P., & Al-Hoorie, A. H. (2017). Scopus- and SSCI-indexed L2 journals: A list for the Asia TEFL community [Article]. *Journal of Asia TEFL*, 14(4), 784-792. <https://doi.org/10.18823/asiatefl.2017.14.4.14.784>
1736. Vizuete-Luciano, E., Güzel, O., & Merigó, J. M. (2023). Bibliometric research of the Pay-What-You-Want Topic [Article]. *Journal of Revenue and Pricing Management*, 22(5), 413-426. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41272-022-00414-6>
1737. Vojnovic, I., & Schintler, L. A. (2023). Over 40 years of shaping global urban research: The Journal of Urban Affairs, 1979–2021 [Article]. *Journal of Urban Affairs*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07352166.2023.2235036>
1738. Vong, C., Rita, P., & António, N. (2021). Health-related crises in tourism destination management: A systematic review [Review]. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 13(24), Article 13738. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su132413738>
1739. Vrcelj, A., Hoic-Bozic, N., & Dlab, M. H. (2021). Using Digital Tools for Gamification in Schools.
1740. Vrdoljak, I. (2023). Lifelong Education in Economics, Business and Management Research: Literature Review [Review]. *Business Systems Research*, 14(1), 153-172. <https://doi.org/10.2478/bsrj-2023-0008>

1741. Vu, G. T., Tran, B. X., McIntyre, R. S., Pham, H. Q., Phan, H. T., Ha, G. H., Gwee, K. K., Latkin, C. A., Ho, R. C. M., & Ho, C. S. H. (2020). Modeling the research landscapes of artificial intelligence applications in diabetes (GAPresearch) [Article]. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(6), Article 1982. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17061982>
1742. Vukašinić, N., & Pavković, N. (2017). Use of virtual mobility to facilitate modern project-based NPD education [Article]. *International Journal of Engineering Education*, 33(6), 2008-2019. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85037728934&partnerID=40&md5=ad8b71c35216edef15b7cb9ca2f97e08>
1743. Vuong, Q. H., La, V. P., Vuong, T. T., Ho, M. T., Nguyen, H. K. T., Nguyen, V. H., Pham, H. H., & Ho, M. T. (2018). Data descriptor: An open database of productivity in Vietnam's social sciences and humanities for public use [Article]. *Scientific Data*, 5, Article 180188. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2018.188>
1744. Wahlquist, A. E., Muhammad, L. N., Herbert, T. L., Ramakrishnan, V., & Nietert, P. J. (2018). Dissemination of novel biostatistics methods: Impact of programming code availability and other characteristics on article citations [Article]. *PLoS ONE*, 13(8), Article e0201590. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0201590>
1745. Walsh, I., & Rowe, F. (2023). BIBGT: combining bibliometrics and grounded theory to conduct a literature review [Article]. *European Journal of Information Systems*, 32(4), 653-674. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0960085X.2022.2039563>
1746. Walter, N., & Hinterberger, T. (2022). Self-organized criticality as a framework for consciousness: A review study [Article]. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13, Article 911620. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.911620>
1747. Walter, N., Orbenes, N., Rupp, M., & Alt, V. (2022). The State of Research in Fracture-Related Infection—A Bibliometric Analysis [Article]. *Medicina (Lithuania)*, 58(9), Article 1170. <https://doi.org/10.3390/medicina58091170>
1748. Walugembe, A., Ntayi, J., Olupot, C., & Elasu, J. (2022). Adaptive behaviors in education institutions before and after COVID-19: A systematic literature review [Review]. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13, Article 1017321. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.1017321>
1749. Wang, C., Xia, X., Li, G., Zhi, G., Wu, Y., Wang, L., & Ruan, L. (2020). Research Progress on CRISPR/Cas9: A Bibliometric Analysis Based on a SCI-Expanded Database [Article]. *Serials Review*, 46(4), 264-274. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00987913.2020.1851440>
1750. Wang, H., Kamal, E. M., Mahdiyar, A., & Ulang, N. M. (2023). CONSTRUCTION WORKER SAFETY BEHAVIOR AND THE THEORY OF PLANNED BEHAVIOR: A SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW [Review]. *Xinan Jiaotong Daxue Xuebao/Journal of Southwest Jiaotong University*, 58(5), 669-680. <https://doi.org/10.35741/issn.0258-2724.58.5.51>
1751. Wang, K., Duan, Y., Chen, H., Hu, J., & Liang, M. (2022). The rise of global research trends on cathinones during 1994-2018: lessons from a systematic bibliometric analysis [Article]. *Journal of Substance Use*, 27(2), 141-148. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14659891.2021.1916841>
1752. Wang, K., & Guo, F. (2022). Towards Sustainable Development through the Perspective of Construction 4.0: Systematic Literature Review and Bibliometric Analysis [Review]. *Buildings*, 12(10), Article 1708. <https://doi.org/10.3390/buildings12101708>
1753. Wang, L., Huang, M., Zhang, X., Jin, R., & Yang, T. (2020). Review of BIM Adoption in the Higher Education of AEC Disciplines [Review]. *Journal of Civil Engineering Education*, 146(3), Article 06020001. [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)EI.2643-9115.0000018](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)EI.2643-9115.0000018)
1754. Wang, L., Jia, H. X., Cheng, S. J., & Wong, P. P. W. (2024). Extending the theory of planned behaviour to foreign students' perceptions of traditional Chinese medical tourism [Article]. *Environment and Social Psychology*, 9(1), Article 1861. <https://doi.org/10.54517/esp.v9i1.1861>

1755. Wang, M., Wang, Z., & Chen, G. (2019). Which can better predict the future success of articles? Bibliometric indices or alternative metrics [Article]. *Scientometrics*, 119(3), 1575-1595. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-019-03052-9>
1756. Wang, P., Gurmani, S. H., Tao, Z., Liu, J., & Chen, H. (2023). Interval time series forecasting: A systematic literature review [Article]. *Journal of Forecasting*. <https://doi.org/10.1002/for.3024>
1757. Wang, P., Zhu, F. W., Song, H. Y., Hou, J. H., & Zhang, J. L. (2018). Visualizing the academic discipline of knowledge management [Article]. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 10(3), Article 682. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su10030682>
1758. Wang, S. Q., Wang, J. X., Zhang, C., Sun, F. H., Xie, Y. J., Jiang, W., Ou, X., Miyamoto, A., & Wang, L. (2020). What You Should Know About Osteoarthritis Rehabilitation: A Bibliometric Analysis of the 50 Most-Cited Articles [Article]. *Geriatric Orthopaedic Surgery and Rehabilitation*, 11. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2151459320973196>
1759. Wankmüller, C., & Reiner, G. (2020). Coordination, cooperation and collaboration in relief supply chain management [Article]. *Journal of Business Economics*, 90(2), 239-276. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11573-019-00945-2>
1760. Waris, I., Iqbal, A., Ahmed, R., Hashim, S., & Ahmed, A. (2023). Values and information publicity shape tourists' intentions to visit green hotels: an application of the extended value-belief norms theory [Article]. *Management of Environmental Quality: An International Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MEQ-04-2023-0130>
1761. Warsaw, J., Whittaker, S., Matthews, T., & Smith, B. A. (2016). When distance doesn't really matter: Effects of geographic dispersion on participation in online enterprise communities.
1762. Warsy, A. S., & Warsy, I. A. (2019). Publish ethically or perish [Review]. *Journal of Nature and Science of Medicine*, 2(4), 186-195. https://doi.org/10.4103/JNSM.JNSM_17_19
1763. Weber, M., Auch, M., Doblander, C., Mandl, P., & Jacobsen, H. A. (2021). Transfer Learning with Time Series Data: A Systematic Mapping Study [Article]. *IEEE Access*, 9, 165409-165432. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3134628>
1764. Wee, C., & Yap, K. M. (2021). Gender Diversity in Computing and Immersive Games for Computer Programming Education: A Review [Article]. *International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications*, 12(5), 477-487. <https://doi.org/10.14569/IJACSA.2021.0120559>
1765. Wei, Q., Shen, J., Wang, D., Han, X., Shi, J., Zhao, L., & Teng, Y. (2021). A bibliometric analysis of researches on flap endonuclease 1 from 2005 to 2019 [Article]. *BMC Cancer*, 21(1), Article 374. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12885-021-08101-2>
1766. Weichbroth, P., & Łysik, Ł. (2020). Mobile Security: Threats and Best Practices [Review]. *Mobile Information Systems*, 2020, Article 8828078. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2020/8828078>
1767. Weimann, P., Pollock, M., Scott, E., & Brown, I. (2013). Enhancing team performance through tool use: How critical technology-related issues influence the performance of virtual project teams [Article]. *IEEE Transactions on Professional Communication*, 56(4), 332-353, Article 6663247. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TPC.2013.2287571>
1768. Wenger, A. (2023). Shifting from academic air travel to sustainable research exchange: Examining networking efficacy during virtual conferences [Conference Paper]. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 414, Article 137577. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2023.137577>
1769. Wenger, J., & Stern, T. (2019). Reflection on the research on and implementation of biorefinery systems – a systematic literature review with a focus on feedstock [Review]. *Biofuels, Bioproducts and Biorefining*, 13(5), 1347-1364. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bbb.2021>
1770. White, E., & King, L. (2020). Shaping scholarly communication guidance channels to meet the research needs and skills of doctoral students at Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and

- Technology [Article]. *Journal of Academic Librarianship*, 46(1), Article 102081.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.acalib.2019.102081>
1771. Wicaksono, A. G., Sunarno, W., Ashadi, & Adi Prayitno, B. (2021). Research Trends of Discovery Learning from 2015 to 2019: A Bibliometric Analysis.
1772. Widyaningrum, R., Wicaksono, A. G., Jumanto, J., Prihastari, E. B., & Restuningsih, A. (2023). Research trends of online teaching and learning from 2016 to 2020: A bibliometrics analysis.
1773. Wiener, M., Saunders, C., & Marabelli, M. (2020). Big-data business models: A critical literature review and multiperspective research framework [Review]. *Journal of Information Technology*, 35(1), 66-91. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0268396219896811>
1774. Wiid, J. A., Cant, M. C., & Prinsloo, C. (2015). Customer expectations and service delivery: Are sme's aware of the service quality standards gap? [Article]. *Corporate Ownership and Control*, 12(4CONT1), 175-184. <https://doi.org/10.22495/cocv12i4c1p1>
1775. Wijewickrema, M. (2021). Authors' perception on abstracting and indexing databases in different subject domains [Article]. *Scientometrics*, 126(4), 3063-3089. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-021-03896-0>
1776. Wilke, C., Bensmann, A., Martin, S., Utz, A., & Hanke-Rauschenbach, R. (2018). Optimal design of a district energy system including supply for fuel cell electric vehicles [Article]. *Applied Energy*, 226, 129-144. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2018.05.102>
1777. Wu, D., Li, Y., Kong, H., Meng, T., Sun, Z., & Gao, H. (2021). Scientometric analysis-based review for drought modelling, indices, types, and forecasting especially in asia [Review]. *Water (Switzerland)*, 13(18), Article 2593. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w13182593>
1778. Wu, M., Kozanoglu, D. C., Min, C., & Zhang, Y. (2021). Unraveling the capabilities that enable digital transformation: A data-driven methodology and the case of artificial intelligence [Article]. *Advanced Engineering Informatics*, 50, Article 101368. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aei.2021.101368>
1779. Wu, Q., Sun, Y., Luo, Z., Li, X., Wen, Y., Shi, Y., Wu, X., Huang, X., Zhu, Y., & Huang, C. (2024). Application and development of zero-valent iron (ZVI)-based materials for environmental remediation: A scientometric and visualization analysis [Review]. *Environmental Research*, 241, Article 117659. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2023.117659>
1780. Wu, T. T., & Sung, T. W. (2023). Analysis of the effects of a game-based review system integrated with the hierarchy of learning on learning outcomes in an elementary social science course [Article]. *Interactive Learning Environments*, 31(6), 4000-4020.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/10494820.2021.1948870>
1781. Wu, Y. Y., & Chou, W. H. (2023). A Bibliometric Analysis to Identify Research Trends in Intervention Programs for Smartphone Addiction [Review]. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 20(5), Article 3840. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph20053840>
1782. Wu, Z., Yang, K., Lai, X., & Antwi-Afari, M. F. (2020). A scientometric review of system dynamics applications in construction management research [Review]. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 12(18), Article 7474. <https://doi.org/10.3390/SU12187474>
1783. Wyant, J. D., Keath, A., & Baek, J. H. (2022). A bibliometric analysis informed reading list for physical educators [Review]. *Journal of Pedagogical Research*, 6(3), 1-16.
<https://doi.org/10.33902/JPR.202214054>
1784. Wyss, R., Luthe, T., Pedoth, L., Schneiderbauer, S., Adler, C., Apple, M., Acosta, E. E., Fitzpatrick, H., Haider, J., Ikizer, G., Imperiale, A. J., Karanci, N., Posch, E., Saidmamatov, O., & Thaler, T. (2022). Mountain Resilience: A Systematic Literature Review and Paths to the Future [Article]. *Mountain Research and Development*, 42(2), A23-A36. <https://doi.org/10.1659/MRD-JOURNAL-D-21-00044.1>

1785. Xia, N., Xie, Q., Griffin, M. A., Ye, G., & Yuan, J. (2020). Antecedents of safety behavior in construction: A literature review and an integrated conceptual framework [Article]. *Accident Analysis and Prevention*, 148, Article 105834. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aap.2020.105834>
1786. Xiao, X., Skitmore, M., Li, H., & Xia, B. (2019). Mapping knowledge in the economic areas of green building using scientometric analysis [Review]. *Energies*, 14(15), Article 3011. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en12153011>
1787. Xie, J., Bian, Z., Wu, Q., Tao, L., Wu, F., & Lin, T. (2023). Global knowledge domain and prospects in tuna research: A bibliometric analysis [Article]. *Aquaculture and Fisheries*, 8(2), 202-210. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aaf.2021.09.005>
1788. Xiong, F., Shen, P., Li, Z., Huang, Z., Liang, Y., Chen, X., Li, Y., Chai, X., Feng, Z., & Li, M. (2023). Bibliometric Analysis of Post-Stroke Pain Research Published from 2012 to 2021 [Article]. *Journal of Pain Research*, 16, 1-20. <https://doi.org/10.2147/JPR.S375063>
1789. Xu, A., Chen, J., Matthews, T., Muller, M., & Badenes, H. (2013). CommunityCompare: Visually comparing communities for online community leaders in the enterprise.
1790. Xu, W., Lou, Y. F., Chen, H., & Shen, Z. Y. (2023). Exploring the interaction of cognition and emotion in small group collaborative discourse by Heuristic Mining Algorithm (HMA) and Inductive Miner Algorithm (IMA) [Article]. *Education and Information Technologies*, 28(10), 13153-13178. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-023-11722-8>
1791. Xu, Y., Piyatamrong, T., & Nyamapfene, A. (2023). Rethinking Evolution of Active Learning in the Hybrid/Online Engineering Education in the Post-COVID-19 Era: A quantitative keyword co-occurrence analysis.
1792. Xu, Y., Zeng, J., Chen, W., Jin, R., Li, B., & Pan, Z. (2018). A holistic review of cement composites reinforced with graphene oxide [Review]. *Construction and Building Materials*, 171, 291-302. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2018.03.147>
1793. Yadav, A., McHale, J., & O'Neill, S. (2023). How does co-authoring with a star affect scientists' productivity? Evidence from small open economies [Article]. *Research Policy*, 52(1), Article 104660. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2022.104660>
1794. Yadav, S., Luthra, S., & Garg, D. (2021). Modelling Internet of things (IoT)-driven global sustainability in multi-tier agri-food supply chain under natural epidemic outbreaks [Article]. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 28(13), 16633-16654. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-020-11676-1>
1795. Yadava, S. M., Patrick, H. S., Ananth, C. V., Rosen, T., & Brandt, J. S. (2019). Top-cited articles in the Journal: a bibliometric analysis [Article]. *American Journal of Obstetrics and Gynecology*, 220(1), 12-25. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajog.2018.11.1091>
1796. Yahia Meddah, R., Ghodbani, T., Senouci, R., Rabehi, W., Duarte, L., & Teodoro, A. C. (2023). Estimation of the Coastal Vulnerability Index Using Multi-Criteria Decision Making: The Coastal Social–Ecological System of Rachgoun, Western Algeria [Article]. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 15(17), Article 12838. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su151712838>
1797. Yahia, Y., Lopes, J. C., & Lopes, R. P. (2023). Computer Vision Algorithms for 3D Object Recognition and Orientation: A Bibliometric Study [Article]. *Electronics (Switzerland)*, 12(20), Article 4218. <https://doi.org/10.3390/electronics12204218>
1798. Yalcin, A. S., Kilic, H. S., & Delen, D. (2022). The use of multi-criteria decision-making methods in business analytics: A comprehensive literature review [Article]. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 174, Article 121193. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2021.121193>
1799. Yalçın, N., & Çapanoğlu, A. E. (2023). Detection of Violent Elements in Digital Games Using Deep Learning [Article]. *SN Computer Science*, 4(5), Article 639. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42979-023-02064-w>

1800. Yan, B., & Zhang, X. (2022). What Research Has Been Conducted on Procrastination? Evidence From a Systematical Bibliometric Analysis [Review]. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13, Article 809044. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.809044>
1801. Yan, S., Zhang, H., & Wang, J. (2022). Trends and hot topics in radiology, nuclear medicine and medical imaging from 2011–2021: a bibliometric analysis of highly cited papers [Article]. *Japanese Journal of Radiology*, 40(8), 847-856. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11604-022-01268-z>
1802. Yang, B., Huang, K., Sun, D., & Zhang, Y. (2017). Mapping the scientific research on non-point source pollution: a bibliometric analysis [Article]. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 24(5), 4352-4366. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-016-8130-y>
1803. Yang, C., Huang, C., Su, J., & Wang, S. (2021). Topic analysis of academic disciplines based on prolific and authoritative researchers [Article]. *Library Hi Tech*, 39(4), 1043-1062. <https://doi.org/10.1108/LHT-04-2020-0102>
1804. Yang, D., Zhou, J., Shi, D., Pan, Q., Wang, D., Chen, X., & Liu, J. (2022). Research Status, Hotspots, and Evolutionary Trends of Global Digital Education via Knowledge Graph Analysis [Article]. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 14(22), Article 15157. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su142215157>
1805. Yang, H., Liu, L., Yang, W., Liu, H., Ahmad, W., Ahmad, A., Aslam, F., & Joyklad, P. (2022). A comprehensive overview of geopolymer composites: A bibliometric analysis and literature review [Article]. *Case Studies in Construction Materials*, 16, Article e00830. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cscm.2021.e00830>
1806. Yang, N., Jo, J., Jeon, M., Kim, W., & Kang, J. (2022). Semantic and explainable research-related recommendation system based on semi-supervised methodology using BERT and LDA models [Article]. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 190, Article 116209. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2021.116209>
1807. Yang, X., Gebbing, P., Lankut, E., & Lattemann, C. (2023). Virtual Creativity–Bibliometric Literature Review on Measurements and Factors That Influence Creative Virtual Teamwork [Article]. *Creativity Research Journal*, 35(4), 568-582. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10400419.2023.2198300>
1808. Yang, X., Majid, A. Z. A., Guangyu, Z., & Tiantian, M. (2023). A Qualitative Study of the Sustainable-Oriented Modularity Methods Based on the Bibliometric Analysis [Article]. *Academic Journal of Interdisciplinary Studies*, 12(4), 277-292. <https://doi.org/10.36941/ajis-2023-0114>
1809. Yang, Z., Chen, S., Bao, R., Li, R., Bao, K., Feng, R., Zhong, Z., & Wang, X. (2022). Public Health Concern on Sedentary Behavior and Cardiovascular Disease: A Bibliometric Analysis of Literature from 1990 to 2022 [Article]. *Medicina (Lithuania)*, 58(12), Article 1764. <https://doi.org/10.3390/medicina58121764>
1810. Yazdani, M., Mojtahedi, M., Loosemore, M., Sanderson, D., & Dixit, V. (2021). Hospital evacuation modelling: A critical literature review on current knowledge and research gaps [Review]. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, 66, Article 102627. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdrr.2021.102627>
1811. Yeo, N. (2023). Managing Teams. In *Crisis Leadership: A Guide for Leaders* (pp. 127-145). World Scientific Publishing Co. https://doi.org/10.1142/9789811262456_0008
1812. Yesilbas, H., & Kantek, F. (2022). Trends and hot topics in nurse empowerment research: A bibliometric analysis [Article]. *Japan Journal of Nursing Science*, 19(2), Article e12458. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jjns.12458>
1813. Yheulon, C. G., Balla, F. M., Ernat, J. J., Lin, E., & Davis, S. S., Jr. (2019). Academic inertia: Examining changes of scholarly output over time among academic minimally invasive surgeons [Article]. *American Journal of Surgery*, 218(5), 813-817. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.amjsurg.2019.03.014>

1814. Yi, M. Z., & Lin, T. S. (2018). A Decade Development of Academic Research on Information Design: 2007-2017 [Article]. *Journal of Design*, 23(4), 45-68.
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85063150517&partnerID=40&md5=dfd8a667da08e60102fde2cdc18262cb>
1815. Yi, Z. (2019). Data center management technology based on RFID automatic radio frequency identification technology [Article]. *Journal of Intelligent and Fuzzy Systems*, 37(5), 6013-6020.
<https://doi.org/10.3233/JIFS-179183>
1816. Yildirim, G., Alim, M. A., & Rahman, A. (2022). Review of Rainwater Harvesting Research by a Bibliometric Analysis [Review]. *Water (Switzerland)*, 14(20), Article 3200.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/w14203200>
1817. Yin, X., Wang, H., Wang, W., & Zhu, K. (2020). Task recommendation in crowdsourcing systems: A bibliometric analysis [Article]. *Technology in Society*, 63, Article 101337.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techsoc.2020.101337>
1818. Yoganingrum, A. (2018). The biodiversity research outputs of the megadiverse ASEAN countries.
1819. Yoo, H., Jang, J., Oh, H., & Park, I. (2022). The potentials and trends of holography in education: A scoping review [Article]. *Computers and Education*, 186, Article 104533.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2022.104533>
1820. Yoo, K., Bacarreza, O., & Aliabadi, M. H. F. (2021). Multi-fidelity robust design optimisation for composite structures based on low-fidelity models using successive high-fidelity corrections [Article]. *Composite Structures*, 259, Article 113477. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2020.113477>
1821. Yordanova, Z. (2021). Innovation Process in Universities – A Bibliometric Analysis. In T. Guarda, F. Portela, & M. F. Santos (Eds.), (Vol. 1485 CCIS, pp. 197-208): Springer Science and Business Media Deutschland GmbH.
1822. You, Y., Min, L., Tang, M., Chen, Y., & Ma, X. (2021). Bibliometric evaluation of global tai chi research from 1980–2020 [Article]. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(11), Article 6150. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18116150>
1823. You, Y., Wang, D., Liu, J., Chen, Y., Ma, X., & Li, W. (2022). Physical Exercise in the Context of Air Pollution: An Emerging Research Topic [Review]. *Frontiers in Physiology*, 13, Article 784705. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphys.2022.784705>
1824. Yu, D. (2015). A scientometrics review on aggregation operator research [Article]. *Scientometrics*, 105(1), 115-133. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-015-1695-2>
1825. Yu, D., Xu, Z., & Wang, W. (2018). Bibliometric analysis of fuzzy theory research in China: A 30-year perspective [Article]. *Knowledge-Based Systems*, 141, 188-199.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.knosys.2017.11.018>
1826. Yu, H. Y., & Chang, Y. C. (2022). A Bibliometric Analysis of Platelet-Rich Fibrin in Dentistry [Article]. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(19), Article 12545.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph191912545>
1827. Yuan, Z., Shen, G. Q. P., Chung, K. H., & Ramly, Z. M. (2013). A study of virtual value management workshop: Identifying risks of its implementation.
1828. Yulineth Cardenas, E., Guillermo Valencia, O., & Eras, J. C. (2018). Trends in failure studies of generation engines based on statistical models from 2007 to 2017 [Article]. *Journal of Engineering Science and Technology Review*, 11(3), 163-167. <https://doi.org/10.25103/jestr.113.22>
1829. Yumitro, G., Febriani, R., Roziqin, A., & Indraningtyas, A. (2023). Bibliometric analysis of international publication trends on social media and terrorism by using the Scopus database [Article]. *Frontiers in Communication*, 8, Article 1140461. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fcomm.2023.1140461>

1830. Zachlod, C., Samuel, O., Ochsner, A., & Werthmüller, S. (2022). Analytics of social media data – State of characteristics and application [Article]. *Journal of Business Research*, 144, 1064-1076. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2022.02.016>
1831. Zahrae, R. F., Safae, A., Mohammed, L., & Naoufal, R. (2022). A Literature Systematic Review of Thermal Infrared Remote Sensing Satellites Land Surface Temperature.
1832. Zakaria, N., & Ab Rahman Muton, N. (2022). Cultural code-switching in high context global virtual team members: A qualitative study [Article]. *International Journal of Cross Cultural Management*, 22(3), 487-515. <https://doi.org/10.1177/14705958221137256>
1833. Zakka, W. P., Abdul Shukor Lim, N. H., & Chau Khun, M. (2021). A scientometric review of geopolymer concrete [Review]. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 280, Article 124353. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.124353>
1834. Žáková, K. (2016). Online support for tracking of publication resources.
1835. Zazyki, M. A., da Silva, W. V., de Moura, G. L., Kaczam, F., & da Veiga, C. P. (2022). Property rights in informal settlements [Article]. *Cities*, 122, Article 103540. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cities.2021.103540>
1836. Zelenkov, Y. (2019). The topics dynamics in knowledge management research. In L. Uden, I. H. Ting, & J. M. Corchado (Eds.), (Vol. 1027, pp. 324-335): Springer Verlag.
1837. Żemła, M. (2021). Winter sports resorts and natural environment—systematic literature review presenting interactions between them [Article]. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 13(2), 1-17, Article 636. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13020636>
1838. Zeng, L., & Peng, Q. (2022). Bibliometric Analysis and Science Mapping Approach in Digital Landscape Published in WoS and JoDLA from 2010 to 2021 [Article]. *Journal of Digital Landscape Architecture*, 2022(7), 570-591. <https://doi.org/10.14627/537724054>
1839. Zeng, L., & Tissenbaum, M. (2022). The Impact of Device Orientation on Small Group Collaboration During Whole Class Game-Based Simulations.
1840. Zeng, L., & Tissenbaum, M. (2022). The Impact of Device Orientation on Small Group Collaboration During Whole Class Game-Based Simulations.
1841. Zennaro, F., Furlan, E., Simeoni, C., Torresan, S., Aslan, S., Critto, A., & Marcomini, A. (2021). Exploring machine learning potential for climate change risk assessment [Review]. *Earth-Science Reviews*, 220, Article 103752. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.earscirev.2021.103752>
1842. Zerwas, D. (2014). Organizational culture and absorptive capacity: The meaning for SMEs [Book]. Springer Fachmedien. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-658-05552-3_1
1843. Zhang, B., Ahmad, W., Ahmad, A., Aslam, F., & Joyklad, P. (2022). A scientometric analysis approach to analyze the present research on recycled aggregate concrete [Review]. *Journal of Building Engineering*, 46, Article 103679. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jobe.2021.103679>
1844. Zhang, B., Rahmatullah, B., Wang, S. L., Zhang, G., Wang, H., & Ebrahim, N. A. (2021). A bibliometric of publication trends in medical image segmentation: Quantitative and qualitative analysis [Article]. *Journal of Applied Clinical Medical Physics*, 22(10), 45-65. <https://doi.org/10.1002/acm2.13394>
1845. Zhang, C., Su, B., Beckmann, M., & Volk, M. (2024). Emergy-based evaluation of ecosystem services: Progress and perspectives [Review]. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 192, Article 114201. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2023.114201>
1846. Zhang, D., Jia, N., Xiang, J., Zhong, Y., Chen, W., & Hu, Y. (2023). Future perspectives and trends in inflammation in cerebral ischemia-reperfusion injury: Based on bibliometric analysis [Article]. *Brain Disorders*, 11, Article 100087. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dscb.2023.100087>

1847. Zhang, F., Zhang, Y., Yu, Y., Lu, W., & Zhang, H. (2022). Bibliometric analysis of the top-50 cited articles on COVID-19 and physical activity [Article]. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 10, Article 926244. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2022.926244>
1848. Zhang, G., Liang, Y., & Wei, F. (2023). Combining Bibliometric and Social Network Analysis to Understand the Scholarly Publications on Artificial Intelligence [Article]. *Journal of Scholarly Publishing*, 54(4), 552-568. <https://doi.org/10.3138/jsp-2022-0070>
1849. Zhang, J. J., & Guan, J. (2017). Scientific relatedness and intellectual base: a citation analysis of un-cited and highly-cited papers in the solar energy field [Article]. *Scientometrics*, 110(1), 141-162. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-016-2155-3>
1850. Zhang, P., & Jin, Q. (2022). Evolution, status, and trends of exergy research: a systematic analysis during 1997–2020 [Review]. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 29(49), 73769-73794. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-022-22915-y>
1851. Zhang, Q., Oo, B. L., & Lim, B. T. H. (2019). Drivers, motivations, and barriers to the implementation of corporate social responsibility practices by construction enterprises : A review [Review]. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 210, 563-584. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.11.050>
1852. Zhang, Y., Ali, F., Wang, K., Nazir, S., & Leng, Z. (2021). Utilizing Virtual Crowd for Global Software Development [Article]. *Scientific Programming*, 2021, Article 2259594. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2021/2259594>
1853. Zhang, Y., & McGuire, S. J. J. (2023). A BIBLIOMETRIC ANALYSIS OF HRM SYSTEMS AND FIRM INNOVATION [Article]. *International Journal of Business and Society*, 24(1), 82-99. <https://doi.org/10.33736/ijbs.5604.2023>
1854. Zhang, Y., Porter, A. L., Cunningham, S., Chiavetta, D., & Newman, N. (2021). Parallel or intersecting lines? intelligent bibliometrics for investigating the involvement of data science in policy analysis [Conference Paper]. *IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management*, 68(5), 1259-1271, Article 09028088. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TEM.2020.2974761>
1855. Zhang, Y., Saberi, M., & Chang, E. (2018). A semantic-based knowledge fusion model for solution-oriented information network development: a case study in intrusion detection field [Article]. *Scientometrics*, 117(2), 857-886. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-018-2904-6>
1856. Zhang, Y., Zulkifli, N. N., & Mohd Ayub, A. F. (2022). Interactive Analysis of Children's Video Game Products.
1857. Zhang, Z., Guo, B. H. W., Chang-Richards, A., Feng, Z., Jin, R., Zou, Y., & Miang Goh, Y. (2023). Digital technology enhanced situation awareness for construction safety: Systematic review and future research directions [Article]. *Safety Science*, 167, Article 106280. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssci.2023.106280>
1858. Zhao, F., Fashola, O. I., Olarewaju, T. I., & Onwumere, I. (2021). Smart city research: A holistic and state-of-the-art literature review [Article]. *Cities*, 119, Article 103406. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cities.2021.103406>
1859. Zhao, G. (2021). Effect analysis of small-problem-based teaching method for improving students' problem-solving ability in the experiment of power electronics course [Article]. *IET Circuits, Devices and Systems*, 15(6), 560-570. <https://doi.org/10.1049/cds2.12051>
1860. Zhao, X., Webber, R., Kalutara, P., Browne, W., & Pienaar, J. (2022). Construction and demolition waste management in Australia: A mini-review [Review]. *Waste Management and Research*, 40(1), 34-46. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0734242X211029446>
1861. Zhao, Y., Meng, D., Ma, X., Guo, J., Zhu, L., Fu, Y., & Mu, L. (2022). Examining the relationship between bedtime procrastination and personality traits in Chinese college students: the mediating role of self-regulation skills [Article]. *Journal of American College Health*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07448481.2022.2038179>

1862. Zhao, Y., Pinto Llorente, A. M., & Sánchez Gómez, M. C. (2021). Digital competence in higher education research: A systematic literature review [Article]. *Computers and Education*, 168, Article 104212. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2021.104212>
1863. Zhou, J., Tam, V. W. Y., Qin, Y., & Illankoon, C. (2023). A critical review and comparative analysis of cost management on prefabricated construction research (2000–2022) [Article]. *International Journal of Construction Management*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15623599.2023.2193920>
1864. Zhou, L., Amadi, U., & Zhang, D. (2020). Is Self-Citation Biased? An Investigation via the Lens of Citation Polarity, Density, and Location [Article]. *Information Systems Frontiers*, 22(1), 77-90. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10796-018-9889-9>
1865. Zhou, S., & Bakhir, N. M. (2023). Application of Serious Games and Digital Game Based Learning (DGBl) in Higher Education: A Systematic Review [Article]. *Migration Letters*, 20, 823-841. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85176144515&partnerID=40&md5=d22875c613f7b65c0a845261368651bd>
1866. Zhou, Z. Q., Tse, T. H., & Witheridge, M. (2021). Metamorphic Robustness Testing: Exposing Hidden Defects in Citation Statistics and Journal Impact Factors [Article]. *IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering*, 47(6), 1164-1183, Article 8708940. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TSE.2019.2915065>
1867. Zhu, L., Ye, Q., Yuan, J., Hwang, B. G., & Cheng, Y. (2021). A scientometric analysis and overview of research on infrastructure externalities [Review]. *Buildings*, 11(12), Article 630. <https://doi.org/10.3390/buildings11120630>
1868. Zhu, W., & Wang, Z. (2018). The collaborative networks and thematic trends of research on purchasing and supply management for environmental sustainability: A bibliometric review [Review]. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 10(5), Article 1510. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su10051510>
1869. Zhu, Y., Yan, E., & Song, I. Y. (2017). A natural language interface to a graph-based bibliographic information retrieval system [Article]. *Data and Knowledge Engineering*, 111, 73-89. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.datak.2017.06.006>
1870. Zhu, Y., Yan, E., & Song, I. Y. (2017). The use of a graph-based system to improve bibliographic information retrieval: System design, implementation, and evaluation [Article]. *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, 68(2), 480-490. <https://doi.org/10.1002/asi.23677>
1871. Zhu, Y. P., Zhu, Y., & Fan, L. Z. (2022). Research on hotspots and evolution paths in the field of health information behavior: a comparison study of bibliometrics based on CNKI and WoS data [Article]. *Library Hi Tech*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/LHT-08-2022-0399>
1872. Ziarani, G. M., Jamasbi, N., & Mohajer, F. (2024). The Synthesis of Australine and its Stereoisomers as Naturally Pyrroliz-idine Alkaloids [Short Survey]. *Mini-Reviews in Organic Chemistry*, 21(1), 40-57. <https://doi.org/10.2174/1570193X19666220704115936>
1873. Ziarani, G. M., Javadi, F., & Mohajer, F. (2021). The molecular diversity scope of oxindole derivatives in organic synthesis [Review]. *Current Organic Chemistry*, 25(7), 779-818. <https://doi.org/10.2174/138527282566621011112814>
1874. Ziarani, G. M., Mohajer, F., Jamali, S. M., & Ebrahim, N. A. (2020). Quantitative and qualitative bibliometric scope toward the synthesis of rose oxide as a natural product in perfumery [Review]. *Current Organic Synthesis*, 17(8), 610-624. <https://doi.org/10.2174/1872208314666200722161044>
1875. Ziek, P., & Smulowitz, S. (2014). The impact of emergent virtual leadership competencies on team effectiveness [Article]. *Leadership and Organization Development Journal*, 35(2), 106-120. <https://doi.org/10.1108/LODJ-03-2012-0043>

1876. Zong, Q., Fan, L., Xie, Y., & Huang, J. (2020). The relationship of polarity of post-publication peer review to citation count: Evidence from Publons [Article]. *Online Information Review*, 44(3), 583-602. <https://doi.org/10.1108/OIR-01-2019-0027>
1877. Zong, Q., Xie, Y., & Liang, J. (2020). Does open peer review improve citation count? Evidence from a propensity score matching analysis of PeerJ [Article]. *Scientometrics*, 125(1), 607-623. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-020-03545-y>
1878. Zoo, H., de Vries, H. J., & Lee, H. (2017). Interplay of innovation and standardization: Exploring the relevance in developing countries [Article]. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 118, 334-348. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2017.02.033>
1879. Zulu, S. L., Saad, A. M., & Omotayo, T. (2023). The Mediators of the Relationship between Digitalisation and Construction Productivity: A Systematic Literature Review [Review]. *Buildings*, 13(4), Article 839. <https://doi.org/10.3390/buildings13040839>
1880. Zuofa, T., & Ochieng, E. G. (2017). Working separately but together: appraising virtual project team challenges [Article]. *Team Performance Management*, 23(5-6), 227-242. <https://doi.org/10.1108/TPM-06-2016-0030>
1881. Zychová, K., Šimová, T., & Fejfarová, M. (2023). A bibliometric analysis of team autonomy research [Article]. *Cogent Business and Management*, 10(1), Article 2195024. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311975.2023.2195024>
1882. Zyoud, S. H., Waring, W. S., Al-Jabi, S. W., & Sweileh, W. M. (2017). Global cocaine intoxication research trends during 1975-2015: A bibliometric analysis of Web of Science publications [Article]. *Substance Abuse: Treatment, Prevention, and Policy*, 12(1), Article 6. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13011-017-0090-9>
1883. Zyoud, S. H., Waring, W. S., Al-Jabi, S. W., & Sweileh, W. M. (2017). Global research production in glyphosate intoxication from 1978 to 2015: A bibliometric analysis [Article]. *Human and Experimental Toxicology*, 36(10), 997-1006. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0960327116678299>
1884. Zyoud, S. H., Waring, W. S., Sweileh, W. M., & Al-Jabi, S. W. (2017). Global Research Trends in Lithium Toxicity from 1913 to 2015: A Bibliometric Analysis [Article]. *Basic and Clinical Pharmacology and Toxicology*, 121(1), 67-73. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bcpt.12755>